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Non-Cooperative
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Lidar Navigation for Non-Cooperative Space Rendezvous

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Summary

To ensure a sustainable and ambitious future use of space, it is essential to maintain the growing satellite infrastructure, and reduce the number of space debris. This is achieved by in-orbit refueling, repair, and active debris removal missions. At the core of these missions is the capability to autonomously rendezvous with a non-cooperative spacecraft. The close range phase of a rendezvous, when the inter-satellite distance is below tens of meters, is the most critical. Precise relative navigation is required to perform a safe approach and potential robotic activities, and is enabled by electro-optical sensors embarked onboard the spacecraft. Lidar sensors offer particular advantages for this task, since they provide accurate 3D point cloud measurements of the target satellite, independently of the external lighting conditions. Relative navigation then consists in matching the lidar point clouds collected onboard with a pre-defined model of the target, to retrieve a relative pose estimate.

This dissertation presents the design and experimental validation of a lidar-based navigation system for non-cooperative space rendezvous. There exists precise methods for point cloud tracking, however, a major constraint is to perform pose estimation onboard and in real-time. Since space-qualified onboard computers have limited processing power, this imposes strong runtime requirements. Next to point cloud tracking, finding an initial pose estimate in real-time is also particularly challenging, since local matching methods are not applicable. Many spacecraft also present a symmetrical shape, making an unambiguous pose estimation impossible. Further, spacecraft are often composed of reflective materials, which lower the quality of the point cloud data. A navigation system should be able to cope with this noise, and to handle the fast relative dynamics of an uncontrolled satellite or space debris, which might tumble with several degrees per second.

Focusing on these core problems, the dissertation is organized in three blocks: The first is the development of a precise and onboard capable point cloud tracking method. A variant of the Normal Distribution Transform is developed, consisting in the application of a Gaussian smoothing to the probabilistic map representation, alongside with a relaxed formulation of the optimization problem. It is shown how this method leads to increased robustness, precision and efficiency compared to the state-of-the-art. The second block is the combination of this tracker with a filter to form a robust navigation system. A new formulation of a relative navigation filter is introduced, based on expanding the Invariant Extended Kalman Filter formalism. It is used in interplay with the tracking method to provide accurate pose estimates, and to compensate for motion blur when dealing with rapidly tumbling space objects. The third segment is the design of a framework for lidar-based pose initialization. The approach relies on training a neural network with synthetic point cloud data generated by a custom rendezvous lidar simulator, and optimizing the network to achieve real-time capability. An attitude classification logic is further introduced to handle the specificities of symmetrical spacecraft.

The findings of this research are supported by experiments conducted at the European Proximity Operations Simulator. The navigation system is precise and reliable when tested on real lidar data, under various scenarios and conditions. Runtime evaluations also demonstrate its real-time capability on onboard representative hardware. The lidar-based navigation system is flight-ready, laying the groundwork for the widespread use of lidar sensors in upcoming rendezvous missions.

Zusammenfassung

Durch Wartung der wachsenden Satelliten-Infrastruktur und Reduzierung von Weltraummüll kann eine nachhaltige und ehrgeizige Nutzung des Weltraums in Zukunft gewährleistet werden. Dies wird durch Betankungen in der Umlaufbahn, Reparaturen und aktive Trümmerbeseitigung erreicht. Ein Kernpunkt hierfür ist die Fähigkeit, ein Rendezvous mit einem unkooperativen Raumfahrzeug durchzuführen. Die kritischste Phase des Rendezvous ist im Nahbereich, wenn der Abstand zwischen den beiden Satelliten unter einigen zehn Metern liegt. Dort ist präzise Relativnavigation erforderlich, und wird durch elektro-optische Sensoren an Bord des Raumfahrzeugs gestützt. Lidar-Sensoren bieten hierfür besondere Vorteile, da sie unabhängig von den äußeren Lichtverhältnissen genaue 3D-Punktwolkenmessungen des Zielsatelliten liefern. Die Relativnavigation besteht dann darin, die Punktwolken mit einem vordefinierten Modell des Zielsatelliten abzugleichen, um eine relative Posenschätzung zu erhalten.

Diese Dissertation beschäftigt sich mit der Entwicklung und experimentellen Validierung eines Lidar-basierten Navigationssystems für unkooperative Weltraum-Rendezvous. Es gibt zwar präzise Methoden für Punktwolken-Tracking, aber eine wesentliche Einschränkung besteht darin, die Posenschätzung an Bord und in Echtzeit durchzuführen. Das gilt besonders, weil weltraumtaugliche Bordcomputer nur über eine begrenzte Rechenleistung verfügen. Neben dem Tracking ist auch die Ermittlung einer initialen Posenschätzung in Echtzeit eine starke Herausforderung. Viele Raumfahrzeuge weisen auch eine symmetrische Form auf, was eine eindeutige Posenschätzung erschwert. Hinzu kommt, dass Raumfahrzeuge in der Regel aus reflektierenden Materialien bestehen, wodurch es zu Fehlmessungen vom Lidar kommen kann. Außerdem sollte ein Navigationssystem in der Lage sein, mit der schnellen relativen Dynamik eines unkontrollierten Satelliten, der mit mehreren Grad pro Sekunde taumeln kann, umzugehen.

Die Dissertation konzentriert sich auf diese Kernprobleme, und ist in drei Blöcke gegliedert: Der erste ist die Entwicklung einer präzisen und bordtauglichen Methode für Punktwolken-Tracking. Eine Variante von Normal Distribution Transform ist eingeführt, bei der die Zufallsverteilungen geglättet werden, und das Optimierungsproblem umformuliert wird. Es wird gezeigt, wie diese Methode im Vergleich zum Stand der Technik zu mehr Robustheit, Präzision und Effizienz führt. Der zweite Block ist die Kombination dieses Trackers mit einem Filter, um ein robustes Navigationssystem zu bilden. Hierfür wird der Formalismus vom Invariant Extended Kalman Filter erweitert. Im Zusammenspiel mit der Tracking-Methode ermöglicht es der Filter, genaue Posenschätzungen zu liefern, und die Bewegungsunschärfe bei schnell taumelnden Objekten zu korrigieren. Das dritte Segment ist die Entwicklung eines Frameworks für die initiale Posenschätzung. Der Ansatz beruht auf dem Training eines neuronalen Netzwerks mit synthetischen Punktwolken, die mit einem eigenen Lidar-Simulator erzeugt werden. Das Netzwerk ist optimiert, um Echtzeitfähigkeit zu erreichen. Außerdem wird eine Lageklassifizierungs-Methode entwickelt, um Symmetrien des Zielsatelliten zu berücksichtigen.

Die Ergebnisse dieser Forschung werden durch Experimente am European Proximity Operations Simulator gestützt. Sie bestätigen die Präzision und Zuverlässigkeit des Navigationssystems, auch für unterschiedliche Szenarien und Bedingungen. Die Echtzeitfähigkeit der implementierten Methoden wird auf einem repräsentativen Bordrechner demonstriert. Das Lidar-basierte Navigationssystem ist flugbereit, und legt damit den Grundstein für den gängigen Einsatz von Lidar-Sensoren bei zukünftigen Rendezvous-Missionen.

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List of publications

Parts of the results of this dissertation have been published, or are under publication, as a main contributing author in:

- [1] Léo Renaut, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Smoothed normal distribution transform for efficient point cloud registration during space rendezvous. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications*, volume 5, pages 919–930, 2023.
- [2] Léo Renaut, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Lidar Pose Tracking of a Tumbling Spacecraft Using the Smoothed Normal Distribution Transform. *Remote Sensing*, 15(9):2286, 2023.
- [3] Léo Renaut, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. LiDAR based pose tracking of an uncooperative spacecraft using the smoothed normal distribution transform. In *12th International Conference on Guidance, Navigation & Control Systems (ESA GNC and ICATT 2023)*. 12.-16. Jun. 2023, Sopot, Poland., 2023.
- [4] Léo Renaut, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. CNN-based Pose Estimation of a Non-Cooperative Spacecraft with Symmetries from Lidar Point Clouds. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 2024. (in press).
- [5] Léo Renaut, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Deep Learning on 3D Point Clouds for Fast Pose Estimation during Satellite Rendezvous. *Acta Astronautica*, 232:231–243, 2025.
- [6] Léo Renaut, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Invariant Extended Kalman Filtering for Relative Pose Estimation during Spacecraft Rendezvous. (in preparation).

In particular, references [1–3] form the basis of the literature research of Section 1.5.1, and of Chapters 2 and 3. Reference [6] is a condensed version of the filtering logic presented in Chapter 3. The second part of the literature research (Section 1.5.1), and Chapter 4 draw from references [4, 5].

Acronyms

ADR	Active Debris Removal
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOCS	Attitude and Orbit Control System
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPD	Coherent Point Drift
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEOS	German Orbital Servicing Mission
DGCNN	Dynamic Graph CNN
DLR	German Aerospace Center
DOF	Degrees Of Freedom
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
EPOS	European Proximity Operations Simulator
ERO	Earth Return Orbiter
ESA	European Space Agency
FPFH	Fast Point Feature Histograms
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FPS	Farthest Point Sampling
GEO	Geostationary Orbit
GNC	Guidance, Navigation and Control
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GSOC	German Space Operations Center
ICP	Iterative Closest Point
IEKF	Invariant Extended Kalman Filter
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
MEKF	Multiplicative Extended Kalman Filter
MEV	Mission Extension Vehicle
MLI	Multi-Layer Insulation
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDT	Normal Distribution Transform
OOS	On-Orbit Servicing
PDF	Probability Density Function
PFH	Point Feature Histogram
PnP	Perspective- n -Point
PMD	Photonic Mixing Device
PSD	Power Spectral Density
RANSAC	Random Sample Consensus
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROI	Region Of Interest
RTN	Radial, Tangential, Normal
Sim2Real	Simulation To Reality

SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SLERP	Spherical Linear Interpolation
SoC	System-On-Chip
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
ToF	Time-of-Flight
UKF	Unscented Kalman Filter
4PCS	4-Points Congruent Sets

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 The need for space rendezvous technology

Rendezvous has been a central topic since the early days of spaceflight. In 1962, the Vostok 4 spacecraft embarking Soviet astronaut Pavel Popovich was inserted into a similar orbit to Vostok 3, with the aim of approaching it, but was unable to get closer than 6.5 km to it. Three years later, after a failed attempt with Gemini 4, US astronaut Walter Schirra succeeded in maneuvering Gemini 6 within 30 cm of Gemini 7, making it the first ever successful space rendezvous (Fig. 1.1). By *rendezvous* is meant the approach of two spacecraft towards one another until a very close distance, where the relative velocities are brought to zero and the position is held (station-keeping). It usually involves an active satellite which performs a set of orbital maneuvers to approach a passive satellite. The former is called the *chaser* spacecraft, and the latter the *target*.

Figure 1.1: Gemini 7 photographed from Gemini 6 on December 15th, 1965. *Image credit: National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), public domain.* Source link.

A rendezvous is said to be *cooperative* as soon as the target spacecraft facilitates the approach through communication, by performing orbital maneuvers, or through the presence of markers such as retro-reflectors or diodes helping the visual navigation. Typical examples are in-orbit assembly or docking to the International Space Station (ISS), or close-proximity satellite formation flying. On the contrary, when the target is fully passive, the rendezvous is *non-cooperative*. This case is more challenging, mainly due to the fact that the exact state of the target spacecraft is unknown. The parameters of the target, such as its position and velocity, have to be estimated by the chaser spacecraft or from the ground. In addition, if the target spacecraft is not attitude controlled, it might be spinning freely, also referred to as *tumbling*.

The last decade has seen a growing interest in space for commercial applications, and in particular in big satellite constellations. Combined with decreasing launch costs, this leads to a drastic increase in the number of active and inactive satellites orbiting the Earth. Between 2015 and 2023, the number of objects in Earth orbit cataloged by the European Space Agency (ESA) has doubled [7]. In order to maintain this expanding satellite infrastructure, multiple use cases involving non-cooperative rendezvous are gaining attention. One of them are *On-Orbit Servicing (OOS)* missions, which aim at extending the lifetime of a satellite by repairing or refueling it. From 1993 to 2009, five missions saw astronauts board on the Space Shuttle to repair the Hubble Space Telescope, constituting a famous example of human orbital repairs [8]. However, for reliability, costs and safety reasons, space missions are becoming less dependent on human intervention and increasingly autonomous.

To demonstrate the feasibility of autonomous satellite servicing, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) launched the Orbital Express mission in 2007. The chaser satellite ASTRO, also called servicer, performed autonomous rendezvous, docking and refueling of the target or client satellite NEXTSat [9]. The target was equipped with a docking plate and prepared specifically to be serviced. The first commercial OOS mission was only completed recently, in 2020, by the Mission Extension Vehicle (MEV) 1. [10]. MEV-1 rendezvoused with Intelsat 901 in Geostationary Orbit (GEO), and repositioned it on its orbit in order to extend its operational lifetime by five additional years. One year later, a second Intelsat (IS-10-02) was serviced by the next servicer, MEV-2. Fig. 1.2a shows a view of IS-10-02 while being approached for docking by MEV-2. OOS missions have been identified as a need in the commercial, civil and military domain, with multiple technology demonstrators planned to be developed in the next years [11]. Since 2014, the US Air Force has launched a network of four satellites as part of the Geosynchronous Space Situational Awareness Program (GSSAP) [12]. These satellites, operating in GEO orbit, have the capability to maneuver in order to perform rendezvous and inspection of other spacecraft. The objective of this program is to identify and surveil space objects in these orbits.

With more satellites in Earth orbit, the probability of collision between them also increases. Predictions see an exponential growth in the number of collisions [7] which could ultimately endanger future space activities, a phenomenon known as the Kessler syndrome [13]. With the Clean Space initiative [14], ESA identified several directions to address this issue and secure sustainable access to space. Solutions involve the study of space debris mitigation technologies to prevent the creation of additional space debris and manage the end-of-life of satellites, as well as the development of *Active Debris Removal (ADR)* missions, as illustrated in Fig. 1.2b. Such missions aim at removing inactive satellites or other types of space debris from orbit, by sending

Figure 1.2: Examples of OOS missions. **(a)** IntelSat seen from MEV-2. *Image credit: ©Northrop Grumman, used with permission.* Source link. **(b)** Illustration of possible grasping operations using a robotic arm. *Image credit: ©ESA-David Ducros, used under the ESA license for informational purposes.* Source link.

a servicer spacecraft to collect them and bring them back into the Earth atmosphere. The focus lies mostly on debris located in Low Earth Orbit (LEO), which is defined by altitudes lower than 2000 km. LEO orbits contain more than 70% of the currently active satellites, and represent the region with the highest danger of collisions [7]. Resulting from the Clean Space initiative, the possibly first ADR mission, ClearSpace-1, is planned to be launched 2028 [15]. The mission will attempt to capture and remove a derelict satellite from orbit. Several other public and private companies are researching in the field of OOS and ADR, such as Astroscale. In 2022, the company performed a first demonstration of its rendezvous technologies in the context of the ELSA-d mission, by re-approaching a target that had previously been released using a magnetic docking mechanism [16].

Outside Earth orbit, some science or exploration missions also involve challenging rendezvous phases. For Mars Sample Return, a mission led by NASA and ESA, a rendezvous between the Earth Return Orbiter (ERO) and a small capsule containing samples of the Mars surface is planned in Mars orbit [17]. In the course of this complex mission, a rover will collect samples on Mars, before a launcher sends them into Mars orbit. Once in there, the capsule has to be collected by the ERO autonomously, before being brought back to Earth.

1.2 Stages of a rendezvous mission

The course of a rendezvous depends on the type of mission, how autonomous the chaser satellite is, and whether the target is cooperative or not. Yet it is possible to make a general division in different phases which are common to most missions [18]. For non-cooperative cases with a high degree of autonomy for OOS and ADR missions, which will be in the focus of this dissertation, some adjustments are made, specifically concerning the last steps of the rendezvous [19].

The autonomous rendezvous truly begins after the initial launch and phasing are completed (Sections 1.2.1 and 1.2.2). From there on, the task of the onboard Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) system will first be to estimate the relative trajectory of the target (*navigation*). Based on this estimation, the rendezvous trajectory profile as well as the associated maneuvers are defined (*guidance*). This plan will be executed and followed by the chaser satellite to perform the approach (*control*).

For describing the relative motion between both satellites, the Radial, Tangential, Normal (RTN) frame attached to the target is commonly used [20–22]. It is defined as follows:

- R: The radial direction points from the Earth to the satellite;
- T: The tangential direction is defined such that the coordinate frame is orthonormal. For a circular orbit, it corresponds to the flight direction of the target;
- N: The normal direction is orthogonal to the target’s orbital plane.

While this convention will be used in the rest of this work, other conventions exist. The tangential direction is sometimes referred to as V-bar, and the normal direction as H-bar [18]. Also, the R-bar is sometimes defined in the opposite direction [23, 18]. A schematic overview of a rendezvous scenario, involving a representation of the RTN frame, is shown in Fig. 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Schematic representation of the possible trajectory and stages of a rendezvous mission.

1.2.1 Launch

A prerequisite to a rendezvous mission is to have an initial, possibly coarse estimation of the target satellite’s orbit. This initial orbit estimation is most often computed prior to the launch and obtained through ground stations observations. Having determined the target orbit, the goal of the launch will be to insert the chaser satellite in an orbit close to the target’s orbital plane with a dedicated launch vehicle. The insertion orbit of the chaser is typically lower than the target orbit [18].

1.2.2 Phasing

After insertion, the phasing stage begins. Due to different constraints on the launcher and the precision of the launching vehicle, the insertion orbit might not be exactly in the target's orbital plane. Maneuvers to correct the out-of-plane components are computed and commanded from the ground. In addition, different strategies are employed to reduce the distance between both satellites. Usually, the chaser being on a lower orbit, it is faster, and will progressively catch up with the target. Once the relative distance is sufficient, perigee and apogee raising maneuvers are performed to reduce the relative velocity between both satellites and initiate the rendezvous from a steady state. The maneuvers performed during the phasing stage are computed from the ground, by means of absolute navigation and orbit estimation of both satellites. The distance of the chaser to the target satellite at the end of the phasing is typically of 10 km to 100 km [18].

1.2.3 Far range rendezvous

The beginning of the far range rendezvous marks the transition from ground based commanding of the satellite to autonomous onboard operations. The computation of the maneuvers and all the required processing should be performed on board, with as little commanding from the ground as possible [24]. In a fully automated rendezvous mission, the role of ground operators is limited to a monitoring role, where the only commands to be sent are “go” and “no-go” decisions.

In addition, the GNC system switches from absolute to *relative navigation*. The rendezvous is not based on an absolute estimate of the target's orbit anymore, since in a non-cooperative rendezvous scenario, the absolute orbit of the target is only coarsely known. Additional measurements are gathered onboard to estimate the relative trajectory between the chaser and target, and continue the rendezvous [25, 26]. To monitor the target at these distances, the chaser is equipped with a narrow optic camera. Alternatively, it is possible to use for this purpose the camera head of star tracker units, which are already on board most satellite platforms and have similar characteristics [27]. At tens of kilometers, the target satellite seen from the chaser appears as a bright dot in the sky, similar to a star. It is only visible when it is not currently in the Earth's shadow, or when the chaser's cameras are not blinded by the sunlight [28]. The obtained images are processed on board to extract the target's position on the image. The processing usually consists in estimating the centroid of bright objects on the image, removing the detections which correspond to known stars by comparing with a star catalog, and performing refinements based on the found centroid's trajectory [27, 29].

The result of the image processing is a direction of the target without a distance information, which is represented by two angles. These angular measurements are accumulated over time in an *angles-only* navigation filter to estimate the target's trajectory [21, 30, 31]. A convenient and widespread parametrization of the relative state in far-range consists in using relative orbital elements [32, 33]. While the distance to the target is poorly observable, maneuvers performed by the chaser help to refine the estimated relative orbital elements by triangulation [34].

The objective of the far range rendezvous phase is to approach within a few hundred meters of the target, where the shape and details of the satellite become distinguishable. This is achieved by a set of impulsive maneuvers computed by the GNC system, under the constraint of minimizing propellant costs [28]. The approach trajectory usually has the shape of a spiral,

as schematically represented in Fig. 1.3. Such a spiraling trajectory ensures the passive safety of the rendezvous, so that in case of thruster failure, the chaser satellite will continue its course by circling towards, around and past the target without risking a collision [28, 35].

1.2.4 Mid range rendezvous

Once arrived at a relative distance in the order of 100 m to the target, the precision of angles-only navigation might not be sufficient to continue the approach. The target is too close to allow for important uncertainties on the navigation, but still too far for to precisely distinguish its shape using *electro-optical sensors*. In addition, a precise knowledge of the target's attitude might not be yet needed at this distance. To bridge the gap, it is often preferred to switch to a 3D estimation of the target's position using sensors such as a lidar [10], a radar [15] or a laser rangefinder [36]. These 3D sensors have the advantage of directly delivering a distance information without the need for complex processing methods, ensuring a possibly coarse, but direct and reliable position estimation of the target.

Based on this 3D estimation, the approach continues in a so-called *closing* trajectory. In cooperative rendezvous scenarios, for example for docking on the ISS, an approach corridor might be defined which the chaser should not leave [18]. In such a case, the closing trajectory takes the form of a straight line approach or a hopping trajectory, most often along the tangential or radial directions. If the chaser happens to leave the corridor because of control errors, it should perform a collision-avoidance maneuver to abort the rendezvous and enter a safe exit trajectory [26].

In non-cooperative cases, the target satellite is usually sufficiently small so that the safety of the approach is also achieved passively by a spiraling approach similar to the far range trajectory (Section 1.2.3). Such an approach in mid-range is illustrated in Fig. 1.3. In addition to being passively safe, a spiral approach is also more fuel efficient than a hopping or straight-line approach trajectory [37].

The target might be an unknown object or debris, or a satellite which has had some damage and requires to be inspected prior to the final approach. The inspection is carried out by flying around it on an inspection ellipsis in order to observe it from different angles [35], as represented in Fig. 1.3. The result of this phase is the generation, on ground or on board, of a 3D geometric model of the target which will enable its identification or the detection of possible changes [38, 39, 19, 40]. The inspection is also sometimes the main objective of the mission [12]. All activities in vicinity of the target spacecraft, such as inspection, close range rendezvous and any type of robotic operation are also referred to as *proximity operations*.

1.2.5 Close range rendezvous

At a distance of few tens of meters, once a 3D model of the target satellite is known following the inspection, the final approach starts. This approach requires a precise knowledge of the target's relative position and attitude (*pose*), even if it might be tumbling with an important angular rate. To meet these requirements, relative pose estimation is performed on board by means of image, point cloud or other types of data processing. Different types of close range rendezvous sensors are used, and will be detailed in Section 1.3.

The approach trajectory until the last meters to the target will often consist in a straight-line approach along the tangential ($\pm T$) or negative radial direction ($-R$) [23, 18]. The tangential direction is advantageous for a slow and fuel efficient approach, since hold points during the approach are dynamically stable. The approach from below, i.e., the negative radial direction, has interesting safety properties [23]: If no maneuver is performed, for example in case of a thruster failure, the chaser will safely drift away from the target since it is on a lower orbit.

The requirements on the precision of the GNC during the rendezvous depend on the type of mission. Fehse [18] states that typical requirements on the navigation accuracy for docking are of 1% of the range and 1 deg, but are loosened by a factor 5 for berthing operations. On the opposite, the velocity requirements are of 1 cm/s and 0.1 deg/s but should be more strict for berthing missions, since a robotic capture is a longer process. Likewise, Telaar et al. [41] define requirements for the study of a robotic OOS mission with a large acceptable position error in the initial phase (10 m) and a more restrictive precision for the final approach and capture (5 cm). The requirement on the angular precision is initially of 5 deg, before being restricted to 2 deg in the final capture phase. The acceptable velocity errors (1 cm/s and 0.5 deg/s in the capture phase) are larger than the ones defined by Fehse. From these two different sets of requirements, a trade-off leads to the definition of the requirements of Table 1.1 for OOS or ADR mission scenarios. From these requirements, the navigation type and appropriate sensors are chosen, such that a switch from angles-only and position-only estimation to full pose estimation in close range is performed.

Table 1.1: Typical GNC requirements on relative navigation accuracy for an OOS or ADR mission. The “-” indicates that requirements on this quantity are not relevant for this phase.

mission phase	navigation type	rel. position	rel. velocity	rel. attitude	rel. angular velocity
far range	angles-only	10% of distance	-	-	-
mid range	position only	5% of distance	-	-	-
close range	pose estimation	1% of distance	1 cm/s	5 deg	0.1 deg/s
robotic servicing	pose estimation	5 cm	1 cm/s	2 deg	0.1 deg/s

1.2.6 Servicing

The final step of the rendezvous is the establishment of physical contact between the chaser and the target. The type of interaction between both satellites is defined by the mission objective, which might involve docking, refueling, de-tumbling, de-orbiting or servicing of another sort. If the target is equipped for *docking*, the objective is to align and fit the docking mechanisms of both satellites in order to establish connection between them. In the case of *berthing*, the chaser (or sometimes the target in cooperative rendezvous scenarios [42]) is equipped with a robotic arm to grasp the target in a pre-defined way, as illustrated in Fig. 1.2b. Because the target is possibly free-tumbling, the chaser either has to synchronize its motion with the target, or to

wait for the appropriate moment to grasp it. Once connected, both satellites must be stabilized [19].

In case of an ADR mission in LEO, both satellites might re-enter the atmosphere together following the capture in order to complete the *de-orbiting*. For other servicing scenarios, the chaser will release or separate from the target before performing a retreat, and potentially going on to servicing other satellites.

1.3 Mid- and close range rendezvous sensors

The first type of sensors that are used for relative spacecraft navigation are imaging cameras, which have different operating ranges, such as visible or near infrared, and thermal [43]. Visible cameras have the advantage of relatively low power consumption and mass, which are two important requirements of satellite missions. They are common sensors, with many space qualified models on the market. Due to the simplicity of the sensors, relative navigation using monocular visible cameras is being widely studied, and multiple synthetic or hybrid datasets have been released as baseline for comparing relative navigation methods [44–46]. However, visual cameras are strongly affected by the harsh illumination conditions in orbit, such as frequent day/night eclipses, Sun blinding, high contrasts, solar reflections on the satellite and Earth albedo. During the Swedish-led PRISMA satellite experiment, images of the target “Tango” were collected in close range, and later processed on ground to assess relative navigation strategies [47]. Fig. 1.4 shows some images collected during the mission. While the satellite is clearly distinguishable on the first image (1.4a), it becomes less visible on image 1.4b and even less on image 1.4c. Because of the intrinsic limitations of visible cameras in space environment, it is questionable whether such sensors alone are adapted for the task of relative navigation in space.

Figure 1.4: Visual camera images of the Tango spacecraft taken during the PRISMA mission. *Image credit: ©OHB Sweden, used with permission.* Source links: (a), (b), (c).

Thermal cameras operate in the mid and far infrared spectrum. By measuring the thermal radiations of the observed spacecraft, they are less dependent on the external light conditions, hence more robust to reflections and blinding effects [43]. Amongst other sensors (visual cameras and lidar), a thermal camera was embarked onboard the sensor suite of the MEV to provide an

additional relative navigation solution [10]. Likewise, Neptec’s TriDAR navigation sensor, next to a lidar, comprises a thermal camera which was studied for developing relative pose estimation methods [48]. Yet compared to visual cameras, thermal cameras often have a lower resolution, deliver images which vary strongly depending on the surface material of the observed object, and might encounter highly variable temperature profiles in orbit [43]. In order to mitigate the limitations of both types of sensors, hybrid approaches fusing both visible and thermal images have been developed [49].

Recently, event cameras have also been assessed for spacecraft relative navigation [50]. These sensors, also known as neuromorphic cameras, detect local changes in brightness on a scene and produce according events on an image plane. Compared to traditional frame-base cameras, event cameras have a high dynamic range, so that they could be used to recognize shapes even in scenes with very high luminosity contrasts such as in space [51]. The research on event based vision is still at an early stage, and currently no space qualified event sensors exist.

Electro-optical sensors used for relative navigation in space are divided in two categories, passive sensors such as visual, thermal and event cameras, or active sensors such as lidar or Time-of-Flight (ToF) cameras. ToF cameras and scanning lidars rely on the same working principle of actively emitting light signals and measuring the reflected signal. The measurement is either a phase shift, or a time shift between the emission and reception of the signal [52]. Because of their active measurement principle, these sensors are relatively independent of the external illumination conditions, but the measurement ability depends on the target’s reflectivity properties [53]. These sensors provide a depth information which directly eliminates the possible distance ambiguity of 2D sensors, so that their use for relative navigation in space is being increasingly studied [54].

Figure 1.5: Measurement principle of a ToF sensor.

A ToF camera emits a pulse of light with LEDs or laser diodes, usually in the near infrared domain, and a receptor array measures a distance for each pixel. By the emission of a flash, these sensors provide an instantaneous depth image of the observed object with a potentially high resolution, in addition to an intensity information. There are two possible ways to measure the distance. When using a modulated light source, the distance is computed by measuring the phase shift between the emitted and reflected signal. For measuring this phase shift, the

receptor array is usually a Photonic Mixing Device (PMD), so that modulated ToF cameras are sometimes also directly referred to as PMD cameras. The advantage of phase shift measurement is that it is precise, yet intrinsically bounded in maximum range due to the periodic nature of the phase measurement [52]. Sensors under study for space applications currently have a maximum working distance of around 10 m [55–57], so that they have to be coupled with other rendezvous sensors in order to cover the whole close range domain.

On the opposite, non-modulated ToF cameras measure a distance directly through the time-of-flight principle, i.e., by measuring the time between the emission and reception of the signal. This principle is illustrated on Fig. 1.5. Such sensors are able to cover larger ranges [52]. Non-modulated ToF cameras are also referred to as *flash lidars*, due to their emission principle being to emit a flash of light covering the whole field-of-view. NASA has been developing a flash lidar for landing or proximity operations applications with achieves kilometer ranges [58]. Between 2020 and 2021, this sensor was flown as a test instrument in the OSIRIS-REx mission, aiming to collect a sample from the Bennu asteroid [59, 60]. It is now commercialized as ASC’s GSFL-16KS Space 3D Flash LIDAR™ [61], with maximum range specifications below 6 km.

Scanning lidars also rely on the time-of-flight measurement principle to measure distances. However, instead of emitting a flash, they emit a directional laser ray which covers large distances but only hits one point of the target satellite at a time. In order to get a full view of the target, these sensors periodically scan over the whole field of view. The resulting measurement is an unordered set of points, called a *point cloud*, where each point might have an amplitude or intensity information in addition to its 3D position coordinates. Lidar sensors have a wide operational range, which is of several hundred meters for the lidar integrated in Neptec’s TriDAR sensor [62] and even a few kilometers for Jena-Optronik’s RVS lidar flown on the MEV [10]. Fig. 1.6 shows a representation of a point cloud captured by the lidar during this mission. Scanning lidars for space currently have an important mass, size and power consumption, but miniaturized sensors are under qualification [63].

Figure 1.6: Sensor images of Intelsat 10-02 viewed by MEV-2 at a distance of 220 m [10]. **(a)** Lidar point cloud. **(b)** Camera image. *Image credit: ©Northrop Grumman, used with permission.*

Compared to a ToF camera which provides an instantaneous depth image, a scanning lidar has to scan the whole field of view with a certain repetition rate. If the scene moves during the

duration of the scan, which is for example the case for a tumbling target, the scan is distorted. This effect arising with scanning lidar is called *motion blur*. The quality of a lidar point cloud is determined by intrinsic characteristics of the sensor such as beam divergence, sensor noise or motion blur due to low scanning rates, but also by extrinsic factors such as potential reflections due to the target properties, or perturbations from the Sun when it is directly in the field of view.

A lidar (scanning or flash) is adapted for use over the whole mid and close range domain, for delivering a simple position estimation in mid range and a full pose estimation in close range. Because of the potentialities of lidars, the use of these sensors for relative navigation in space will be studied in this dissertation.

1.4 Lidar pose estimation for navigation

This work will focus on the processing of lidar point cloud data for navigation in non-cooperative rendezvous scenarios. Of course, the techniques developed in this work are also applicable to cooperative scenarios, but the non-cooperative case, in which the target might be tumbling or unknown, is more challenging. More specifically, the goal of lidar-based navigation is the relative pose determination of the target in close range. The *input* of the navigation is a point cloud captured by the lidar, while the *output* is an estimate of the relative pose, i.e., the relative position and attitude of the target satellite with respect to the chaser.

To perform pose estimation, it is assumed that a *geometric model* of the target is known. The pose determination is then based on matching the model with the lidar measurements. This matching is also referred to as *point cloud registration* [64]. The geometric model is gained in two ways: If the target which is to be approached is known in the beforehand, then a 3D model is usually available before the flight. On the other hand, when approaching an unknown or damaged object such as a space debris, an inspection of the satellite is performed before starting the final approach, see Section 1.2.4. The images or point clouds gathered during the inspection enable to construct a 3D model of the target satellite [38, 39, 19, 40]. After the inspection, the chaser satellite retreats. The final approach is resumed once the target model and the pose estimation methods have been updated. In all cases, performing an inspection phase before starting the close range approach enables to detect possible changes, and to refine on ground the type of robotic activities that are to be performed on the target satellite.

Model-free pose estimation is also possible [65, 57]. It consists in aggregating point clouds using a Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) approach to construct a model of the target and estimate its inertia and center of mass parameters [65]. From an operational perspective, it is unlikely that the inspection and subsequent proximity operations are all performed in one step during a mission [41, 19]. Therefore, we limit this research to the case where a 3D model of the target is already known to perform pose estimation.

A major constraint when designing a pose estimation method is that the processing has to happen onboard and in *real-time*. This means that the pose estimation has to be performed within a pre-defined time, which might vary depending on the mission scenario. An order of magnitude of the frequency with which new measurements should be processed by the GNC system in close range is 1 Hz [41]. If the relative dynamics is slow, for example for a slowly

tumbling target, lower frequency updates might also be sufficient.

The runtime of an algorithm is very dependent on the computing platform on which it is evaluated. Space-qualified hardware has to be resilient to vacuum, large thermal amplitudes and high levels of radiation [66]. At the same time, the onboard computer is required to have a low power consumption on the spacecraft. Because of the long development and qualification times of radiation-hardened processors, space computing hardware is typically more than a decade behind computing platforms being developed on ground [67]. Therefore, the available processing power in orbit is expected to be very limited compared to what is achieved on ground. Likewise, while Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) are currently being tested for in-orbit applications [68, 69], it cannot be expected for now that a GPU will be available on the satellite. Under these constraints, the real-time requirement becomes even more challenging.

When performing pose estimation for relative navigation, the estimation is usually split in two steps, *pose initialization* and *pose tracking*, as illustrated in Fig. 1.7. In the beginning, the relative pose of the target spacecraft is unknown, so that an initialization method is required to provide a first estimate. Once an estimate of the relative pose is known, the navigation goes into a tracking mode. During tracking, the previously found solution is refined in order to find the new relative pose. Therefore, when navigating towards a spacecraft, initialization only has to be performed once, and refinement or tracking is performed every time a new lidar point cloud is received.

Figure 1.7: Schematic representation of the pose initialization and tracking pipeline

While both initialization and tracking provide a relative navigation solution, they are inherently different in the used methods and algorithms, and in the conceptual problem to solve: At pose initialization, the full 6 Degrees Of Freedom (DOF) search space of position and attitude has to be explored to find the relative pose, it is a *global optimization* problem. On the other hand, tracking only performs a refinement of the previous estimate, and is a *local optimization* method, starting from an initial solution.

A pose initialization method provides a direct estimation of the relative pose, so that it might be asked why the initialization method is not used throughout the full navigation phase, and why a pose tracking method is needed at all. The reason is that the initialization usually only provides a coarse estimate of the solution, while the tracking is a refinement, and delivers a more precise solution [54]. Hence, both methods combined enable to converge towards a precise solution.

Raw results from the pose estimation are not used as such by the chaser's guidance and control systems. Indeed, the pose measurements are noised, and inputting this noise directly in a controller would lead to unnecessary corrections and propellant consumption. A complete

navigation system additionally comprises a navigation filter, which filters the measurements over time to provide a smooth estimate of the relative pose [70–72].

In the following section, we will first give an overview of pose tracking and filtering techniques, before providing a review of the state of the art for pose initialization. If pose initialization might come first in a mission scenario, discussing first pose tracking, and then pose initialization, enables to transition from local to global registration, which is an a priori more difficult problem.

1.5 State of the art

1.5.1 Pose tracking

Point cloud registration

Lidar point cloud registration consists in the alignment of two point clouds representing at least partially the same scene, but taken from different perspectives. The objective is to find the relative pose transformation (rotation and translation) of the sensor between the two views. These methods are widely applied to navigation problems in various fields of mobile robotics such as autonomous driving [64]. When an initial guess of the relative transformation is known, the transformation is refined using a fine registration method. A review of existing coarse and fine registration methods for terrestrial applications is found in [73]. Fine registration methods are often at the basis of lidar odometry, mapping or SLAM procedures [74] for pairwise or multiple scan alignment.

Figure 1.8: Example of fine registration on point clouds of the *Hanover 2* dataset [75]. **(a)** Source (red) and target (green) point cloud before registration. **(b)** After registration, both scans are aligned.

When matching two point clouds, the reference point cloud is referred to as target point cloud. In case the scene or object which is observed is known in the beforehand, for example for satellite pose estimation, the target point cloud is constructed from a 3D model [76, 54]. On the contrary, if the scene is unknown, the target point cloud is a previously captured point

cloud [76, 74]. It is then matched to the current point cloud registered by the lidar, which is referred to a source point cloud. Therefore, the objective of the registration method is to align the source with the target point cloud. Fig. 1.8 shows an example of the result of a registration algorithm applied to two consecutive point clouds of the *Hanover 2* dataset [75], which consists of scans taken by a Velodyne lidar sensor at the Hanover university campus.

ICP

The most widespread point cloud registration algorithm is the Iterative Closest Point (ICP), introduced by Besl and McKay [77]. The idea of ICP is to minimize the sum of squared distances between the points of the source and target point clouds. The steps of the algorithm are schematized in Fig. 1.9. First, the source point cloud is positioned relatively to the target point cloud according to the initial guess of the relative pose between both clouds. Each point of the source cloud is then associated with the corresponding closest point in the target cloud. The third step is to compute the rigid pose transformation which minimizes the sum of the squared distances between each pair of neighbors. To ensure that a valid rotation matrix is obtained, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is usually applied [78]. Finally, the source point cloud is transformed according to this optimal relative pose. Because the initial association of neighbors might not be exact if the initial pose estimate is not perfect, the pose found is not yet guaranteed to be the optimal pose. Therefore, these steps of the algorithm are iterated until the relative pose converges.

Figure 1.9: Schematic representation of the steps of the ICP algorithm in 2D. (1) Target point cloud. (2) Source point cloud. (3) Nearest neighbor computation. (4) Least squares transformation.

There exist numerous variants of ICP, one of them being point-to-plane ICP introduced by Chen and Medioni [79]. Instead of minimizing the distance between pair of points, in point-to-plane ICP, the surface normals of the target point cloud are computed, and the distance of each point of the source to the closest surface of the target is minimized. Alternatively, reciprocal ICP [80] aims at rejecting erroneous point-pairs associations by only keeping pairs which satisfy the closest point property in both ways. In order to increase the robustness of the algorithm against noisy point clouds, in trimmed ICP, Chetverikov et al. [81] suggest minimizing the trimmed sum of squared distances instead of the complete sum, so that a fraction of the most

important distances, which might be outliers, is left out. To represent the local neighborhood of each point, Segal et al. propose in generalized-ICP [82] to compute the covariance matrix of the surrounding of each point. This local description of covariance matrices is used to minimize the sum of the distances between the pair of points weighted by the covariance matrices: generalized-ICP is a general formulation of point-to-point, point-to-plane but also plane-to-plane ICP. To accelerate generalized-ICP, Koide et al. [83] suggest replacing the nearest neighbor search by a voxel search, where each point of the source is associated with every target point distribution of the voxel to which it belongs. Recently, Zhang et al. [84] suggested using a different error metric for ICP to reject outliers and increase the algorithm's robustness. This is coupled with an acceleration technique accounting for past iterations to improve the current iterate.

One step of ICP is the computation of the nearest neighbor pairs, and it has an important impact on the algorithm's speed. In order to accelerate this search, the original ICP implementation of Besl and McKay [77] suggests the use of a k-d tree structure to sort the points of the target cloud, and efficiently search for a closest neighbor. For faster search, Greenspan and Yurick [85] propose relaxing the nearest neighbor condition. This approximate closest point search leads to an increase of efficiency without a noticeable loss of precision. For further acceleration, Nüchter et al. [86] introduce a cached version of k-d trees exploiting the iterative structure of ICP. Alternatively, the use of different processing hardware such as a GPU enables a considerable speedup of the closest point search [87]. Instead of a nearest neighbor search and closest point pair association, Yew and Lee [88] propose the use of a soft correspondence function obtained by a deep learning network (RPM-Net). If ICP is a robust and precise point cloud registration method, it remains a local optimization method, and is sensitive on a good initial estimation to successfully converge.

NDT

A second algorithm that has gained attention next to ICP is the Normal Distribution Transform (NDT), introduced by Biber and Straßer [89]. NDT was initially developed for registration of 2D laser scans, and extended to 3D point cloud registration by Magnusson [90]. The idea of NDT is to prevent wrong point pair associations and accelerate registration by using a probabilistic representation of the target point cloud. The steps of NDT are schematically represented in the 2D case in Fig. 1.10. First, space is divided in a regular voxel grid, usually using an octree. For each voxel, the mean and covariance matrix of all points of the target cloud belonging to that voxel is computed, so that the target point cloud is represented by a probabilistic distribution in each voxel instead of individual points. NDT relies on the assumption that the distribution of points in each voxel follows a normal distribution. According to this probabilistic representation, the likelihood of the source point cloud is computed for the current pose, by assigning to each point of the source cloud a score corresponding to the normal distribution of the voxel to which it belongs. The objective of NDT is to maximize the likelihood of the source point cloud. Similarly to ICP, the optimization process is an iterative procedure, relying on gradient-based methods. NDT is also a highly precise registration method, and is found to be faster than ICP in the context of mine mapping [91] and autonomous driving [92].

An important parameter of NDT is the grid cell resolution. A higher grid size ensures that the optimization will converge even in the presence of initialization errors, while a smaller reso-

Figure 1.10: Schematic representation of the steps of NDT in 2D. (1) Target point cloud. (2) Computation of the distribution in each voxel (covariance ellipsis represented in green). (3) Likelihood heat map, and source point cloud. (4) Likelihood maximization of the source point cloud.

lution leads to a better precision of the registration. Therefore, coarse-to-fine strategies consist in progressively reducing the NDT grid resolution during the algorithm’s iterations [93, 94]. Because lidar sensors provide a better resolution for objects of the scene in the near surrounding than for objects further away, a strategy is to have multi-resolution voxel maps, where the close surroundings are described with a grid map with a finer resolution, while the background has a coarser resolution [95–97]. For terrestrial applications, Das and Waslander [98] suggest segmenting the scene to remove the points corresponding to the ground, and clustering the remaining objects of interest in order to compute a minimal number of Gaussian distributions. In this case, each distribution corresponds to a cluster of points.

ICP aligns points of the source with points of the target point cloud, while standard NDT aligns points of the source with distributions of the target point cloud. In distribution-to-distribution NDT, Stoyanov et al. [99] propose computing the distributions of both point clouds to align them, in order to achieve higher efficiency of the algorithm. The resulting algorithm is an iterative alignment of the two Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) formed by the sum of the normal distributions. Such methods belong to the family of the Coherent Point Drift (CPD) algorithm, introduced by Myronenko and Song [100]. This idea is also combined with a multi-resolution voxel map representation by Droschel et al [96]. Similarly, in probabilistic NDT Hong and Lee [101] assign a Probability Density Function (PDF) to each point of the target cloud to avoid degenerate distributions, before performing distribution-to-distribution NDT.

In the original 3D-NDT implementation [90], the cost function is the negative sum of probabilities, which is minimized following Newton’s method. In order to use a more efficient non-linear least squares solver, Schulz and Zell suggest instead minimizing the sum of squared probability residuals [102]. If the Mahalanobis distance [103] is used to express the distance between a point and a distribution, minimizing the sum of squared Mahalanobis distances becomes a standard linear least squares problem which is solved very efficiently [94].

In spite of its efficiency, NDT is also a local optimization method, and requires a good initialization in order to successfully converge [104]. Indeed, when a point of the source cloud is moved from one voxel to another during the algorithm’s iterations, the distribution of the target cloud that it is associated with changes, leading to discontinuities in the cost function. If the ICP cost function is also subject to discontinuities, these are more important for NDT because

of the coarser voxel representation, and affect the optimization process. To mitigate this effect, in their original 2D implementation, Biber and Straßer [89] suggest evaluating simultaneously four partially overlapping voxel grids. In 3D, the same strategy leads to the evaluation of eight overlapping voxel grids for each point [95, 105], leading to an increase in the computation time by eight times. A similar idea by Magnusson et al. [91] is to only compute one voxel grid for the distributions of the target point cloud, but to associate each point of the source with the eight closest voxel distributions, a strategy called tri-linear interpolation. Yet the authors also report an increase in computation time by four to eight times. Quenzel and Behnke [97] propose to directly associate each point of the source cloud with the 27 surrounding distributions to form a Gaussian mixture representation, yet to run in real-time the method relies on the use of a GPU. When using a GPU, Behley and Stachniss [106] use planar surface elements (surfels) instead of 3D distributions. The points of the target cloud are efficiently projected on the surfel map to minimize the point-to-plane error. However, with the objective of running point cloud registration methods on hardware with limited computing performance in real-time, there is a need for mitigating the NDT discontinuity issue without relying on the use of a GPU or increasing the algorithm’s runtime.

Continuous-time registration

Because scanning lidars continuously capture 3D points, when the device is attached to a moving object or the observed scene is changing rapidly, the lidar scan is distorted, an effect known as motion blur. To mitigate the effect of motion blur, one approach is to correct the scan distortion prior to performing the registration, using the individual timestamp of each point [107–110]. This is achieved with a linear motion model assuming a constant velocity and angular rate for the duration of the scan, with these parameters being approximated from the result of the previous registration steps [107–110]. In the work of Moosmann and Stiller [107] and Wang et al. [110], this estimation is then refined in a second step, where the result of the registration is used to update the estimated velocity before adding the undistorted scan to a global map.

Instead of performing motion compensation prior to the registration, elastic scan registration methods estimate the relative motion as part of the iterative optimization. Park et al. [111] use ellipsoid 3D surfels similar to NDT cells for jointly performing registration and undistortion of the point cloud, assuming a uniform movement during scan time. To represent non-linearities in the motion, the trajectory is interpolated by a cubic B-spline curve [112, 97]. For accounting for high-frequency motion without needing a complex trajectory interpolation, in continuous-time ICP, Dellenbach et al. [113] suggest keeping the assumption of uniform motion during a scan, but introduce a discontinuity between two consecutive scans. Alternatively, in Lidar Odometry and Mapping (LOAM), Zhang and Singh [114] propose a two stages strategy: Feature points are extracted and registered dynamically with 10 Hz, before this motion estimation is used to undistort and register the scan to a global map with a lower rate (1 Hz). Nüchter et al. [115] introduce a semi-rigid matching based on a division of the scan into several slices which are rigidly registered. The output of these piece-wise registrations is then used in a second elastic matching algorithm, but the method is not meant for real-time operations.

Pose tracking in space

For tracking a non-cooperative spacecraft using point clouds captured by a lidar or a ToF camera, ICP or one of its variants are most often used [55, 62, 54]. Opromolla et al. [76] use a combination of point-to-point and point-to-plane ICP: The first iteration of the algorithm uses a standard nearest neighbor search which is robust against bigger initial deviations, and the subsequent ones are based on normal shooting for faster convergence and better precision. The tracking is performed in real-time, but with relatively sparse simulated point clouds, with less than 500 points. Sun et al. [57] study the use of a high-resolution ToF camera providing around 300,000 points. For performing registration in real-time, the authors suggest downsampling the point cloud extracting salient points and performing registration using only these points, before incrementing a global map of the target, which is supposed to be unknown. The authors propose a comparison with other methods such as generalized-ICP and NDT, but these methods are compared when using the raw point cloud.

Using a PMD camera producing a dense point cloud, Klionovska and Burri [56] apply ICP with reverse calibration [116] in order to limit the nearest neighbor search to few candidates and accelerate the registration process. The authors additionally processes the amplitude image from the PMD camera separately, before fusing the estimates into one. Likewise, Li et al. [117] suggest a pose estimation method based on fusing two point clouds captured by two different sensors, a Kinect and a lidar. To robustly reject potential wrong associations in the point cloud data, Li et al. [65] combine RANSAC with ICP. The result of the registration is used in a SLAM scheme to perform model-free pose estimation. Satellites are often coated with golden Multi-Layer Insulation (MLI) sheets which are particularly reflective and become invisible to the sensor or produce multiple reflections. To robustly eliminate some artifacts arising from these reflections, Wang et al. [118] suggest the use of a trimmed ICP algorithm.

When tracking a rapidly tumbling satellite, a scanning lidar is affected by motion blur. However, due to their instantaneous flash measurement principle, ToF cameras are not subject to motion blur. Martinez et al. [119] consider the use case of a rocket upper stage spinning rapidly with 10 deg/s to be tracked with a ToF camera scanning at 1 Hz. The relative displacement between two consecutive scans is important, so that a feature tracking method is combined to ICP to accelerate the registration process. Motion blur is often neglected and not simulated when simulating scanning lidar scans [76, 120], but is observed when tracking a tumbling target with a scanning lidar at a robotic facility. Li et al. [65] perform a hardware-in-the-loop experiment with a target spinning with 1 deg/s and a scanning period of 1.65 s, yet motion blur is not compensated or taken into account. Indeed, motion blur is only significant when the tumbling velocity is high compared to the scanning frequency, i.e., when the observed target performs a significant motion during the duration of the scan. Likewise, Yin et al. [121] perform a field experiment on a robotic facility for tracking a target rotating with 10 deg/s using sparse point clouds, but the lidar scan acquisition frequency is also very high (10 Hz), so that the relative motion between two consecutive scans is not very important. Thus, the effects of motion blur when tracking tumbling space targets with a scanning lidar are relatively unstudied.

Relative navigation filter

For a smooth pose tracking over time, a navigation filter is used. A navigation filter is a state estimation method [122]: Given a series of measurements and a model of the environment, it estimates the most likely current state. Such states estimation methods are referred to as probabilistic methods or Bayes filters [123] since they involve a probability model of the environment. In mobile robotics, the Kalman filter [124] or one of its non-linear variants are commonly used [125, 126, 122]. Other types of filters include particle filters, which are useful for systems which are highly non-linear and difficult to model [123].

A widespread variant of the linear Kalman filter for non-linear systems is the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) [126]. However, both the linear and extended version of the Kalman filter assume that the state to estimate is in a vector space. While this is true for the relative position, the relative attitude is not strictly speaking a vector: It is an element of the rotation group. A standard for extension of the EKF to attitude estimation problems is the Multiplicative Extended Kalman Filter (MEKF) [127, 128]. The MEKF consists in representing the estimation error multiplicatively relative to the state, typically with quaternion multiplication. Through a linearization of the error state dynamics, the error state is estimated and re-injected in the absolute state. In the case of spacecraft absolute attitude estimation, the measurements from the gyroscope are angular velocity and acceleration. However, for pose estimation during rendezvous, the sensor processing directly provides a relative attitude measurement. Filipe et al. [70] suggested an extension of the MEKF to the case of relative spacecraft navigation. The MEKF and its different variants is currently a widespread choice for relative attitude estimation during rendezvous [43].

Instead of the multiplicative version, it is possible to apply modified versions of the additive EKF, treating all four components of the quaternion independently, and imposing some normalization constraints [71, 72]. However, the additive EKF is found to be less effective in practice than the multiplicative EKF [129]. A further alternative is the application of an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) for spacecraft relative navigation [130]. In addition to providing a filtered navigation estimate, Opromolla and Nocerino [120] use the UKF for lidar based pose tracking of fast tumbling targets: The filter prediction is used to initialize ICP from a better starting pose, leading to faster convergence.

To exploit the inherent properties of the rotation group, the Invariant Extended Kalman Filter (IEKF) [131, 132] is becoming increasingly popular for attitude estimation [133, 134]. It is designed specifically as an extension of the EKF on Lie groups, to which the rotation group belongs. The IEKF shows better convergence results and robustness to noise than the MEKF for attitude estimation problems [131, 133]. The MEKF and IEKF share similar properties, but the MEKF constitutes a special case of the IEKF, with additional first-order approximations [133]. Therefore, the IEKF is a more general and accurate formulation.

The IEKF was originally designed for cases where only the state vector is possibly an attitude, while the measurements are in a vector space. This is a standard case for attitude estimation problems, where the measurements typically come from a gyroscope and consist of an angular velocity and angular acceleration, which are both 3D vectors [133, 134]. However, for pose estimation during rendezvous, the measurement is directly an attitude and is also not in a vector space. To the best of our knowledge, an extension of the IEKF to the case where the

measurements are directly attitude measurements, and an application to the problem of relative attitude estimation for space rendezvous has never been proposed.

1.5.2 Pose initialization

Global optimization methods

The task of global point cloud registration consists in aligning two scans without having an initial estimate of the relative pose between them. It is a global optimization problem, where the search space consists of all possible translations and rotations. Therefore, one possibility is to apply deterministic methods for solving global optimization problems. Hess et al. [135] suggest a branch and bound approach combined with a depth-first search for recognizing loop closure in 2D lidar SLAM. The method is able to find the relative pose which globally minimizes the cost function between both 2D grid maps in real-time. In 3D, Yang et al. [136] also propose to apply a branch-and-bound method to find a global optimum to the ICP minimization problem. The authors introduce bounds to the ICP cost function, and combine ICP iterations with branch and bound operations to reach the global optimum. However, due to the size of the search space in 3D compared to 2D, the method is computationally intensive. It is applied to the problem of lidar pose tracking for space rendezvous by Liu et al. [55]. To do so, the authors first define a bounding box of the translation domain estimation with an eigenvalue decomposition of the point cloud's covariance matrix. Afterwards, the global branch and bound ICP searching method [136] is used to retrieve the full pose.

Another popular algorithm for pairwise global registration is the 4-Points Congruent Sets (4PCS) algorithm introduced by Aiger et al. [137]. In this framework, sets of 4 coplanar points are extracted from the target point cloud. For each set, all sets of 4 points of the source point cloud which are congruent to the first set (i.e., sets which respect a similar shape ratio) are extracted, and the best match is kept, as illustrated in Fig. 1.11. This match defines a pose transformation candidate, and Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) is applied to test the hypothesis, so that the iterations stop once a sufficiently good pose transformation is found. For testing the TriDAR system, which flew on the Discovery Shuttle in order to estimate the relative pose of the International Space Station (ISS), Ruel et al. [62] apply a polygonal aspect hashing technique belonging to the family of the 4PCS algorithm. Accelerations of 4PCS have been introduced by Mellado et al., with super-4PCS [138], which uses a voxel grid representation of the data for efficient point search and accelerates the 4-points set matching step. The runtime of the method is thereby reduced to linear complexity in the size of the point clouds. An alternative way to accelerate the algorithm is to only consider feature points as input to 4PCS, as proposed by Theiler et al. in keypoint-based 4PCS [139].

Using depth images from a PMD camera sensor, Klionovska and Benninghoff [141] initialize the pose of a non-cooperative satellite applying the approach of Drost et al. [142]. This object recognition algorithm is similar to 4PCS, but only uses two points to find a match. For a pair of oriented points, a geometric descriptor is built, before a hashing-technique is combined with a voting scheme to retrieve correspondences between both point clouds. Also similar to the 4PCS algorithm, Yin et al. [121] propose a “congruent tetrahedron align” algorithm for pose tracking in space. The method aims at finding similar tetrahedrons in the source and target point cloud.

Figure 1.11: Illustration of a pair of congruent 4-point sets matched between two point clouds. *Image credit: Fotsing et al. [140], licensed under CC-BY 4.0.*

For efficient retrieval of correspondences, a hash table is used. The pose candidates are tested and refined via ICP until a solution which minimizes the ICP cost function is found. For pose estimation with Jena-Optronik’s RVS lidar [143] flown on several space missions, Schmitt et al. [144] implement a neural network aided polygon matching algorithm. The principle is that a polygon is extracted from the source point cloud, and forwarded to a neural network to find a match with a polygon of the target point cloud. When a match is found, ICP refinement is performed to assess the quality of the match. This polygon matching procedure is iterated until the ICP cost function is below a pre-defined threshold, resulting in multiple ICP runs. To accelerate the method, parts of the algorithm are implemented on a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA).

With 3D lidar data of a spacecraft, an easy way to obtain a coarse estimate of the satellite’s center of mass is to compute the centroid of the point cloud. Opromolla et al. [145] suggest a two-step technique based on first estimating the position by computing the centroid, and then applying a template matching algorithm for attitude estimation, before performing an ICP refinement. The idea of template matching is to discretize the attitude space, and generate a point cloud template of the satellite for each discrete attitude. Afterwards, the source point cloud is compared with each template, and the best attitude is the one which minimizes the ICP cost function. Even though an acceleration method is proposed to avoid searching through all templates, the method is not adapted for real-time operations. In following work [76], the authors first retrieve the principal axis of the spacecraft, before estimating only the roll angle around this axis, thus reducing the number of templates to evaluate. Guo et al. [146] propose a further acceleration of the template matching strategy by using 2D binary images of the projected silhouettes as templates instead of 3D point clouds. Using a binary similarity metric, the authors achieve efficient pose initialization, but with a success rate on simulated point clouds from 60% to 90%, depending on the studied satellite’s shape.

Feature-based global registration

One way to achieve global registration is also by extracting local point cloud features and matching them between two point clouds [54]. In feature-based registration, the first step is to extract points of interest that will have to be matched. For this aim, several keypoint extractors exist such as Intrinsic Shape Signatures (ISS) [147], MeshDOG [148] or Harris3D [149]. Some are an extension of descriptors initially used in computer vision. Afterwards, keypoint descriptors

aim at providing a unique low-dimensional description of a point cloud region. They are invariant under rigid (and sometimes scale) transformation. Guo et al. [150] separate them in two categories: The first one are descriptors of the distribution of the surrounding points' coordinates such as spin images [151], Shape Context (SC) [152], and Rotational Projection Statistics (RoPS) [153]. The others are descriptors of the local geometric attributes (curvature or normals) such as Point Feature Histograms (PFHs) [154], Fast Point Feature Histograms (FPFH) [155] or Signature of Histogram of Orientations (SHOT) [156]. Once the correspondences between both point clouds are established as illustrated in Fig. 1.12, RANSAC [157] is usually applied in order to determine the pose transformation between the two point clouds while discarding wrong feature associations. Using the FPFH feature combined with a direct and robust optimization formulation, Zhou et al. [158] introduce a general method for fast global registration of point clouds. Yet feature-based methods struggle to achieve good results when being used with low resolution or noisy data [150]. In space, Woods and Christian [159] suggest using a point cloud descriptor belonging to the family of PFH descriptors. Pose refinement is then performed with ICP.

Figure 1.12: Feature correspondences between two point clouds. *Image credit: Brightman et al. [160], licensed under CC-BY 4.0.*

When using optical cameras for spacecraft pose estimation, feature-based methods are also popular [43]. D'Amico et al. [47] suggest the use of the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT), before retrieving the pose using the Perspective- n -Point (PnP) algorithm, which estimates the pose based on correspondences between the 2D points on the image and their corresponding 3D position on the satellite. To remove the background and especially the Earth, Sharma et al. [161] propose to apply a weak gradient elimination technique, and combine the use of multiple features. Likewise, Capuano et al. [162] introduce a robust feature extraction scheme by combining several visible features. Hybrid sensor systems are also used: Hu et al. [163] combine a stereo camera with a ToF camera. The feature points detected with the stereo camera are augmented by the depth information to perform feature matching, before the pose is refined with ICP.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for camera and lidar pose estimation

In recent years, the use of CNNs has become a standard in visual camera based pose estimation [164]. These methods are of interest for lidar pose estimation, because conceptually close. Chen et al. [165] suggest the use of a CNN to detect a spacecraft on a camera image, before cropping the image and applying a second CNN for landmark detection. Finally, an optimization scheme initialized with the result of the PnP algorithm delivers the estimated pose. The network is trained and tested on virtual and real images from the SPEED dataset [166]. To achieve real-time performance, Cosmas and Kenichi [167] embed a similar CNN-based landmark detection on an FPGA. Alternatively, Black et al. [168] suggest using MobileNetV2 [169] as a backbone, which is an efficient CNN designed for enabling vision on edge devices such as onboard computers. Jawaid et al. [50] propose a similar CNN-based keypoint regression approach followed by PnP, but based on images from an event camera, which is less sensitive to the harsh lightning conditions in space than visual cameras. Instead of cropping the region of interest, Hu et al. [45] apply a single-stage approach, where the image is processed by a single network to establish 2D to 3D correspondences before applying PnP combined with RANSAC. Rather than a discrete landmark detection, Ulmer et al. [170] suggest training a CNN to learn a dense estimation of 2D to 3D correspondences, before applying a multi-hypothesis PnP algorithm to retrieve the relative pose.

A major difficulty when training a CNN for space applications is the lack of representative data to train the model. Models are usually trained with synthetic data, but the performance gap once evaluated on real or laboratory data is sometimes important and known as *domain gap* [171]. This is the challenge of Simulation To Reality (Sim2Real) transfer [170, 50]. Extensive data augmentation is commonly used, but also randomization of the target satellite's texture [171, 172]. Many satellites present a symmetrical shape, which has to be accounted for when developing a pose estimation method [172]. Several synthetic or hybrid image datasets for non-cooperative pose estimation have been published [166, 173, 45, 174], relying on different rendering engines. To adapt the network to the actual space images with which it is confronted, Park and D'Amico [175] further propose an online domain refinement step. During this step, the weights of the batch normalization layers of the CNN are re-computed, and the entropy of the discrete classification output minimized.

Instead of finding 2D to 3D correspondences, a network is sometimes trained to directly provide an estimate of the relative position and attitude. Sharma et al. [176] suggest the use of a CNN with multiple prediction heads to simultaneously estimate a bounding box of the target, and classify its attitude into one of the discrete attitude categories created by dividing the attitude space. Similarly, Proença and Gao [173] perform direct pose estimation from camera images by using ResNet [177] as a backbone with two prediction heads, one for the position, and one for attitude classification using soft labels (with continuous values). For incorporating temporal information in the pose prediction, Rondao et al. [49] propose an end-to-end deep Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), a type of network which processes a sequence of inputs and maintains an internal memory. The method fuses visible and thermal images and delivers a direct relative pose output. Park and D'Amico [175] recently introduced a network with multiple prediction heads for background segmentation, pose estimation or feature detection on the target satellite using visible images. The network is based on the EfficientDet architecture [178], which is an

EfficientNet [179] backbone combined with a second network for feature detection.

For lidar-based pose estimation, Kechagias-Stamatis et al. [180] investigate coupling CNNs with a RNN in order to estimate the relative pose of a spacecraft over consecutive lidar scans. This enables a smooth trajectory prediction over the input sequence. The point cloud is initially transformed into three different depth images viewed from different perspectives (X , Y and Z axes). These images are then concatenated into a three-channel image before being passed to the recurrent CNN, yet this architecture requires a GPU to run in real-time. For spacecraft pose estimation using a lidar during lunar landing, Chekakta et al. [181] also combine a CNN with an RNN. While the CNN converts the input depth images into feature vectors, the RNN processes the sequence of feature vectors to estimate the current pose.

For lidar pose estimation during rendezvous, Pensado et al. [182] also project 3D point clouds to a 2D depth image, and process the image with a neural network to retrieve a pose estimation. However, instead of applying a CNN, the depth image is flattened and processed with a 1D neural network, also referred to as a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). The network first estimates the relative attitude, before a second network uses the attitude output to predict the relative position in the normalized depth image.

Neural networks for 3D point cloud understanding

Specific neural network architectures have also been developed to directly process 3D point clouds. An overview of deep learning based methods for point cloud processing is given by Guo et al. [183]. A first possibility is to represent a point cloud as a 3D voxel grid and process such data with a 3D CNN [184, 185]. When the resolution of the voxel grid increases, the complexity explodes, so that sparse convolutions based on octree [186] or k-d tree [187] representations have been suggested. An alternative is to use sparse tensors for 3D convolutions [188, 189].

A major evolution in the field was the introduction of PointNet by Qi et al. in 2017 [190]. It is a deep multipurpose neural network which takes as input an unordered set of 3D points. The simplified architecture of the classification model is presented in Fig. 1.13. A list of N points with c channels is transformed into N points with f channels by applying a shared MLP, i.e., each point is processed individually by the same MLP. In the last step, max pooling (selecting the maximum) is performed along the first dimension to obtain a feature vector of dimension 1024. This ensures that PointNet is order invariant, i.e., the order of the input points has no influence on the result. A set of matrix transformations learned by the network, called T-Net by the authors, also seeks at normalizing the input to make it rotation and translation invariant, but is not represented in Fig. 1.13. Finally, the global feature representing the point cloud serves as input to another MLP to provide classification or segmentation results.

In their following paper, the authors introduce PointNet++ [191], which uses multiple nested PointNet networks to capture smaller features in the point cloud. Similarly to classical CNNs, the first layers focus on local regions of the point cloud, before merging the results into larger regions until the whole point cloud is represented. Wang et al. introduced Dynamic Graph CNN (DGCNN) [192], which is also a multipurpose network. Its basic block, “EdgeConv” not only takes a set of points as input, but also the information of the k nearest neighbors of each point. Because the k nearest neighbors of each feature point are recomputed after each layer, the nearest neighbor graph is dynamically updated. Other efficient and learnable point-wise

Figure 1.13: Simplified representation of the PointNet [190] classification model, without the T-Net transform and top layers.

convolutions have been suggested to operate on point neighborhoods by applying grid weights [193] or kernel point weights [194]. A different approach is the PointTransformer architecture of Zhao et al. [195]. Similarly to text understanding, where words have to be correlated with other words of a sentence to make sense, this network applies a self-attention layer originating from Large Language Models (LLMs) to interpret correlations between points in each local neighborhood.

Next to these multi-purpose neural networks for point cloud understanding, specific architectures for 3D point cloud matching have been proposed. For example, Aoki et al. [196] suggest combining PointNet with the Lucas-Kanade [197] method in a single RNN to achieve global point cloud registration in an iterative way. To uniquely transform the neighborhood of each point into a high dimensional feature space, Wang and Solomon [198] compare the use of PointNet and DGCNN, and conclude that DGCNN is more adapted. Thereafter, an attention network merges the embeddings of both point clouds into a new feature space to compute soft correspondences between the points, before applying SVD to retrieve the optimal pose.

Few authors have studied the use of these neural network architectures for pose estimation during space rendezvous. Zhang et al. [199] suggest an iterative method similar to ICP, but based on a PointTransformer network to obtain point correspondences: At each iteration, the network is used to produce a correlation matrix between the source and target point clouds, before SVD is applied to retrieve the optimal pose. In their following work [200], the authors introduce another hybrid registration method. The point matching step of Coherent Point Drift (CPD) [100] is replaced with a learnable association. The neural network used for this aim contains layers from both DGCNN and PointTransformer. Due to their iterative nature, these methods involve several neural network evaluations for each point cloud, which increases the runtime. While point-based neural networks have been used in hybrid iterative methods, to the best of our knowledge, no single-stage frameworks have been suggested for neural network based lidar pose estimation during rendezvous.

1.6 Research questions

Figure 1.14: Components of the lidar navigation system developed in this research.

The objective of this dissertation is to design a complete lidar-based navigation system for non-cooperative space rendezvous scenarios. The focus lies hereby both on the theoretical investigation of lidar point cloud processing algorithms for this task, and on the experimental validation of the developed methods. The lidar navigation system studied in this work is schematically represented in Fig. 1.14. It is split into three components: A pose initialization method, a pose tracking method and a navigation filter. The study of these components and their interaction to provide a reliable pose estimate to the satellite's guidance and control will be at the core of this research, which is structured around following Research Questions (RQs):

- **RQ1: How are lidar-based tracking methods enhanced to achieve efficient, robust and precise pose tracking of a spacecraft in non-cooperative rendezvous scenarios ?**

The point cloud collected by a lidar sensor during rendezvous is to be matched with a 3D model of the target. Existing tracking methods, relying on an initial estimate of the relative pose, enable precise tracking. However, space computing hardware has limited processing power compared to what is achieved on ground. These tracking methods must be accelerated to ensure real-time capability for onboard implementation, while maintaining a high level of precision and reliability.

- **RQ2: How is the robustness and precision of a lidar-based navigation system ensured in the case of a rapidly tumbling target spacecraft ?**

Inactive satellites or space debris often present a tumbling motion. In case the tumbling rate of the target is high, the relative motion between two consecutive lidar scans becomes important. In addition, when using a scanning lidar, the faster the tumbling is, the more the point clouds are blurred. The interplay between the navigation filter and the tracker is

to be studied to guarantee a stable pose estimate, and correct motion blur even for rapidly tumbling spacecraft.

- **RQ3: How is a reliable pose initialization method designed for real-time on-board implementation, accounting for varying conditions, sensor noise, and potential symmetries in the shape of the target satellite ?**

A first estimate of the relative pose is needed to initialize the tracking. It has to be sufficiently precise to enable subsequent tracking. However, because the search space for such a pose initialization method is large, finding a solution in real-time is particularly challenging, especially on space-qualified computing hardware. Moreover, spacecraft often present symmetrical shapes, so that the initialization method has to be able to handle symmetrical objects.

To support this research, experimental validation is performed at a robotic rendezvous facility. This facility, the European Proximity Operations Simulator (EPOS), is located at the German Aerospace Center (DLR) in Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany, and will be presented in detail in Section 2.4.1. It enables to collect realistic lidar data to assess the performance of the navigation system.

The lidar navigation system described in this work was implemented and integrated in the autonomous GNC software developed by the OOS research group of DLR. It is developed with the purpose of being flown in future rendezvous or servicing missions.

1.7 Dissertation outline

This dissertation is structured in three chapters, each of them centered around one of the research questions presented in 1.6. The order of the chapters follows the order of the research questions. This is not necessarily the intuitive order, which could consist in first addressing the topic of pose initialization, before investigating pose refinement or tracking, and finally the navigation filter. However, the structure of this thesis corresponds to the order in which the subjects were chronologically covered. Coincidentally, this order also enables to gradually introduce the necessary concepts for this research, so that it was kept to ensure clarity and help orient the reader effectively.

Chapter 2 addresses RQ1. As such, it introduces a smoothed version of the NDT registration algorithm, aiming to mitigate the NDT discontinuity issue while maintaining the algorithm's efficiency. This method is applied to pose tracking of a non-cooperative spacecraft, and evaluated during hardware-in-the-loop experiments at EPOS. Chapter 3 details the design of the navigation filter implemented for this research, and in particular, how the IEKF formalism is extended to cover the problem of relative attitude estimation of a spacecraft. To answer RQ2, it is shown how the navigation filter is used in coordination with motion compensation strategies to correct motion blur. Experiments at EPOS demonstrate that the resulting system enables to precisely navigate towards a spacecraft, even if it tumbles with a high angular rate. In Chapter 4, the topic of pose initialization addressed in RQ3 is investigated. Two single-stage neural network based methods are proposed, either with a CNN to process a depth image, or with a point-based neural network to directly process the point cloud. The methods are optimized for

runtime and adapted to account for symmetries in the target spacecraft's shape. A high-fidelity lidar simulator is developed to generate synthetic training datasets, while the method is tested on real EPOS datasets. Finally, conclusions and outlooks are drawn in Chapter 5.

Chapter 2

Lidar pose tracking with the smoothed Normal Distribution Transform

Lidar sensors provide precise 3D point clouds, which are used for pose tracking during spacecraft rendezvous. However, for large point clouds, the runtime of methods such as ICP becomes critical to meet real-time requirements on space onboard computers with limited processing power. This leads to following research question:

RQ1: How are lidar-based tracking methods enhanced to achieve efficient, robust and precise pose tracking of a spacecraft in non-cooperative rendezvous scenarios ?

This chapter introduces a smoothed formulation of the NDT algorithm, aiming to take advantage of the NDT's efficiency while increasing its robustness in case the initial estimate lies further away from the solution. The tracking algorithm is validated experimentally on datasets collected at the EPOS rendezvous facility, where a lidar sensor is mounted. In particular, the experiments demonstrate the precision, efficiency and robustness of the method compared to ICP or classical NDT.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 2.1 provides an overview of the point cloud registration problem, and of ICP and NDT implementations. A smoothed version of the NDT registration algorithm is then introduced in 2.2. In 2.3, we show how its cost function is minimized efficiently by formulating it as an optimization problem on the manifold of a Lie group. To validate the tracking algorithm, data is collected by integrating a lidar sensor at the EPOS rendezvous facility: This setup is detailed in 2.4. The results of the experiments, and in particular the comparison of the proposed algorithm with ICP and classical NDT, are presented in Section 2.5. Finally, 2.6 concludes this chapter.

2.1 Point cloud registration formulation

The point cloud registration problem with fine registration algorithms, introduced in Section 1.5.1, consists in the alignment of two point clouds. For tracking the pose of a satellite, it is assumed in this chapter that a 3D model of the target satellite is known. From this 3D mesh, a point cloud is generated representing the target point cloud. This target point cloud is to be aligned with a source point cloud captured in flight by a lidar, as illustrated in Fig. 2.1. Fine registration methods are based on local optimization methods, they require a good initial guess to converge towards the optimum.

Figure 2.1: Point cloud alignment task: (a) Target point cloud generated from a mesh of the target satellite; (b) Source point cloud taken at the EPOS facility; (c) Result of the alignment, showing the superposition of both point clouds.

2.1.1 Point cloud structures

A 3D point cloud is an unstructured list of 3D points. Each point is sometimes additionally associated with a timestamp, and an amplitude or intensity of the returned light. Because point clouds sometimes contain millions of points, several representations exist to ease the processing of this data. The following is a list of the most common representations of lidar point clouds.

Voxel grids To represent how the space is occupied by the environment, the 3D space of interest is separated into multiple cubes of fixed size, called voxels [184, 185]. If at least one point from the point cloud falls back into a voxel, this one will contain binary information

stating that this voxel contains a point. Alternatively, a voxel sometimes holds a continuous probability representing the likeliness that this voxel is indeed occupied by the environment. Other compression approaches using voxel grids define, for each voxel, the centroid of all points that fall back into it.

Octrees One major inconvenience of voxel grids is that a lot of voxels are empty but take a lot of memory space. An octree data structure handles this sparsity [201]. Considering a cubic portion of the 3D space containing some points from the cloud, the basic idea of an octree is to split this cube into eight equal sub-cubes. Then, only the sub-cubes that also contain some data points are split again, and so on. In this way, large empty areas are not described with an unnecessarily high resolution. The data structure follows the one of a tree, where each node (the initial node being the whole cubic space) is split into eight child nodes that are further inspected or not depending on what they contain.

K-d trees Just like an octree, the idea of a k-d tree is to divide the space into multiple subspaces and repeat the operation [202]. However, a k-d tree is a binary tree, so that at each step, the original space is only divided into 2 subspaces. The first split is done along the first dimension of space x , at the next step it is made along y , then along z before it starts again along x and so on.

Range images It is also possible to represent a 3D scene in two dimensions [203]. A depth image is a conventional image where each pixel does not represent a light intensity, but a distance. Such depth images are obtained by projecting a point cloud on an image plane, and by assigning to each pixel the distance corresponding to the mean (or another function) of all points from the cloud that fall back into that pixel.

Constructing one of these data structures given the raw input data of a lidar sensor, which is a list of 3D points, requires some computation. Voxel grids and range images are constructed iteratively, by assigning each point to a voxel in 3D, or pixel in 2D. On the other hand, the tree structures (octree and k-d tree) are typically built recursively [201, 202].

2.1.2 Iterative Closest Point

An overview of the ICP algorithm and its different variants was presented in Section 1.5.1. This section details the formalization and equations of a standard version of ICP, because the main concepts of the algorithm will also be used for the NDT implementation. Moreover, the implementation detailed in this section will serve as a reference when later comparing different algorithms. In the rest of the dissertation, bold lowercase symbols (such as \mathbf{x}) will represent vectors.

The objective of a fine registration algorithm is to find the rigid 3D transformation that best aligns the source with the target point cloud. A rigid 3D transformation belongs to the 3D special Euclidean group $SE(3)$. A transformation $T \in SE(3)$ is viewed as a pair composed of a 3D rotation, and a 3D translation. Thus, T is decomposed in $(R, \boldsymbol{\rho}) \in SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3$, where R

is a rotation matrix of the 3D rotation group $SO(3)$, and $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ a translation vector. The action of the rigid transformation T on a point $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is

$$T \cdot \mathbf{x} = R\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\rho}. \quad (2.1)$$

We consider a target point cloud of size N_x , with points denoted by $(\mathbf{x}_i)_{1 \leq i \leq N_x}$. The source point cloud has size N_z and the coordinates of its points are $(\mathbf{z}_i)_{1 \leq i \leq N_z}$. The objective of ICP is to find the transformation which minimizes the distance between both point clouds in a least squares sense. The cost function is

$$s_{\text{ICP}}(T) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} \|(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \mathbf{x}_{\nu(i)}\|^2, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\nu(i)$ is the index of the point in $(\mathbf{x}_i)_{1 \leq i \leq N_x}$ nearest to $(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)$, defined by

$$\nu(i) = \arg \min_{1 \leq j \leq N_x} \|(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \mathbf{x}_j\|. \quad (2.3)$$

To minimize the cost function, ICP proceeds in an iterative fashion. Starting from the current guess of the optimal transformation T , the nearest neighbor function ν is computed. Based on this nearest neighbor association, the new optimal transformation T which minimizes s_{ICP} is directly computed. This process is repeated until convergence. ICP being a fine registration algorithm, it requires an initial guess not too far from the optimal solution in order to converge.

Nearest neighbors are usually computed making use of efficient data structures for searching through the source point cloud such as octrees or k-d trees. One possibility to obtain the optimal transformation given the neighbor association is given by Arun et al. [78]. The first step is to compute the centroid of both point clouds. For the target point cloud, only the points which are nearest to a point of the source are considered:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_x = \frac{1}{N_z} \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} \mathbf{x}_{\nu(i)}, \quad \boldsymbol{\mu}_z = \frac{1}{N_z} \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} \mathbf{z}_i. \quad (2.4)$$

The cross-correlation matrix is

$$W_{xz} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} (\mathbf{z}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_z)(\mathbf{x}_{\nu(i)} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_x)^T. \quad (2.5)$$

The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) decomposition of W_{xz} ,

$$W_{xz} = U\Lambda V^T, \quad (2.6)$$

enables to obtain the optimal rotation matrix defined by

$$R = VU^T. \quad (2.7)$$

This solution is not valid if $\det(VU^T) = -1$, but this only happens in degenerate cases (such as a point cloud consisting of only colinear points), which are not an issue in practice [78]. Finally, the optimal translation is

$$\boldsymbol{\rho} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_x - R\boldsymbol{\mu}_z. \quad (2.8)$$

2.1.3 Normal Distribution Transform

The NDT algorithm, and its possible variations found in literature, was also introduced in Section 1.5.1. The original formulation of the method [89, 93] is detailed in this section, to formalize the main concepts and serve as a reference implementation for later comparing different versions of the algorithm.

The specificity of NDT lies in the representation of the model point cloud. Instead of considering it point by point, the target scene is divided into N_v voxels of a certain size, usually with an octree or k-d tree. The voxels are denoted by $\mathcal{V}_1, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{N_v}$. The number of points of the target cloud $(\mathbf{x}_i)_{1 \leq i \leq N_x}$ that belong to voxel \mathcal{V}_k is denoted by n_k . Then, the mean and covariance matrix of the points' distribution within each voxel indexed by k is computed as

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_k = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{V}_k} \mathbf{x}_i, \quad (2.9)$$

$$C_k = \frac{1}{n_k - 1} \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{V}_k} (\mathbf{x}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)(\mathbf{x}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)^T, \quad (2.10)$$

with $C_k = 0_3$ if $n_k = 1$.

These parameters enable to define the estimated PDF of the distribution of the target points in each voxel. Assuming that they follow a normal distribution, the PDF of voxel k is defined for $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ by:

$$p_k(\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{c} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{z} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)^T C_k^{-1}(\mathbf{z} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)\right), \quad (2.11)$$

where c is a normalization constant which is left out ($c = 1$) for this problem.

The objective of NDT is to maximize the likelihood of the source point cloud $((T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i))_{1 \leq i \leq N_z}$ under these probability distributions. The cost to minimize is the inverse of the likelihood:

$$s_{\text{NDT}}(T) = -\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} p_{\eta(i)}(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i), \quad (2.12)$$

where $\eta(i) \in 1, \dots, N_v$ is the index of the voxel to which $(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)$ belongs. For each $1 \leq i \leq N_z$, $\eta(i)$ is defined such that

$$(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) \in \mathcal{V}_{\eta(i)}. \quad (2.13)$$

In the original implementations [89, 93], this cost is iteratively minimized by applying Newton's algorithm. To this aim, the gradient and Hessian of the cost function with respect to the parameters of the transformation T are computed. Similarly to ICP, after each iteration, the voxel to which each transformed point of the source cloud corresponds is recomputed, i.e., the assignment function η is recomputed. The correct association of each point with its corresponding voxel is unknown at the beginning of the iterations, and the optimization method is a gradient-based algorithm. Therefore, like ICP, NDT is a local registration algorithm, and requires a good initial estimate to converge to the correct transformation.

2.2 Smoothed Normal Distribution Transform

This Section introduces a modified version of the NDT algorithm developed in this work. The modifications aim at increasing the efficiency and robustness of the method, with the objective of integrating the method for onboard lidar pose tracking during a rendezvous mission.

2.2.1 Smoothing of the NDT map

Gaussian kernel smoothing

The discontinuity problem of the NDT representation was introduced in Section 1.5.1. After each iteration of the algorithm, a point from the source point cloud is assigned to a new voxel via the function η defined in (2.13). Therefore, the probability distribution to which each point is assigned to changes after each iteration, and the cost function is discontinuous. To mitigate the effects of these discontinuities, several approaches have been proposed and were presented in Section 1.5.1. However, all of them lead to an increase in the required computation time, as they involve the evaluation of more probability distributions for each point of the source cloud.

We propose a smoothing method to attenuate the discontinuities between adjacent probability distributions, while keeping the runtime of the algorithm's iterations equal. The main idea is to apply a Gaussian smoothing kernel to the voxel grid containing the normal distributions. The result of the convolution is obtained by deriving following general formula: We consider N independent random variables $\mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_N$, and weighting coefficients (probabilities) $w_1, \dots, w_N \geq 0$ such that $\sum_i w_i = 1$. The mixture of these random variables is the new random variable \mathcal{X} , defined such that with probability w_i , \mathcal{X} will follow the same law as \mathcal{X}_i . This is also written as

$$\mathcal{X} \sim \begin{cases} \mathcal{X}_1 & \text{with probability } w_1 \\ \dots & \\ \mathcal{X}_N & \text{with probability } w_N \end{cases}. \quad (2.14)$$

Let \mathcal{Y} be a random variable with realizations y_1, \dots, y_N , where y_i is the event: “ \mathcal{X} follows the law of \mathcal{X}_i ”. Applying the law of total expectation, the expected value of \mathcal{X} is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}) &= \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{P}(y_i) \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}|y_i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}_i). \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

From the law of total variance, the variance of \mathcal{X} is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(\mathcal{X}) &= \mathbb{E}(\text{Var}(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y})) + \text{Var}(\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y})) \\ &= \mathbb{E}(\text{Var}(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y})) + \mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y})\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y})^T) - \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X})\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X})^T \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{P}(y_i) \text{Var}(\mathcal{X}_i) \right) + \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{P}(y_i) \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}_i)\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}_i)^T \right) - \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X})\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X})^T \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_i \text{Var}(\mathcal{X}_i) \right) + \left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_i \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}_i)\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X}_i)^T \right) - \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X})\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{X})^T. \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

Therefore, a “smoothing” operation takes as input N distributions with mean and covariance parameters $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}_i}, C_{\mathcal{X}_i}$, and smoothing weights w_i . It produces a new distribution with mean and covariance parameters $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}}, C_{\mathcal{X}}$ such that:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}} = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}_i}, \quad (2.17)$$

$$C_{\mathcal{X}} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_i (C_{\mathcal{X}_i} + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}_i} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}_i}^T) \right) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathcal{X}}^T. \quad (2.18)$$

The weights are chosen as the ones from a Gaussian kernel because it applies a natural smoothing effect to the grid of distributions. The kernel is only applied to cells which contain a distribution, while empty cells are not convoluted with the kernel. The effect of such a smoothing kernel when applied on a regular 2D voxel grid is illustrated in Fig. 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Schematic representation of the smoothing step of the NDT voxel grid in the 2D case. The original blue point cloud (left) is stored in a regular voxel grid to compute the NDT distributions represented by their colored confidence ellipses (middle). After convolution with the smoothing kernel, the new distributions are obtained (right).

In 3D, the kernel is also 3-dimensional. One possibility is to apply a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ Gaussian kernel with weights similar to the 2D kernel illustrated in Fig. 2.2: If the 3D kernel is seen as a superposition of three 2D kernels, the first and last 2D kernels are identical to the one on the illustration, and the middle one has double the weights. Such a kernel is chosen in this work. To account for the varying point density of the target point cloud, each weight of the kernel is additionally multiplied by the number of points of the target cloud which are contained in the currently evaluated cell. Finally, the weights are normalized such that their sum equals one.

Formally, if \mathcal{V}_k is the voxel to be currently smoothed, the surrounding voxels including itself are denoted by $\mathcal{V}_{k_1}, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{k_N}$ (in case of a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ kernel, $N = 27$) and contain n_{k_1}, \dots, n_{k_N} points. If $g(k_1), \dots, g(k_N)$ are the weights of the Gaussian kernel, the smoothing weights are, for $i = 1, \dots, N$,

$$w_{k_i} = \frac{1}{S_k} g(k_i) n_{k_i}, \quad S_k = \sum_{i=1}^N g(k_i) n_{k_i}. \quad (2.19)$$

After the smoothing operation, a distribution not only represents the partitioning of the points contained in this cell, but also the distribution of the points contained in the surroundings

of this cell. In a sense, this operation enables to extend the receptive field of each cell, so that points outside the cell are also taken into account for computing the distribution. Therefore, when a point of the source cloud is moved from one cell to another during the iterations of the NDT algorithm, the change in the probability distribution against which it is evaluated is less important.

One observation is that the proposed method consists in obtaining the smoothed distributions by averaging surrounding distributions. This step is viewed as computing a “mean of means”. An alternative way could be to compute the smoothed distribution directly from the points, without the need for intermediate distributions. Mathematically, this is equivalent: Consider the random variable for which all the possible realizations are the points in voxels $\mathcal{V}_{k_1}, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{k_N}$, and a point in voxel \mathcal{V}_{k_i} has a probability of realization equal to w_{k_i}/n_{k_i} . Then, the mean and covariance of this random variable are identical to (2.17) and (2.18).

Covariance matrix regularization

Most scenes contain planar surfaces. Therefore, it is common in point clouds to have regions where points are all located on the same plane. Such neighborhoods lead to degenerate covariance matrices, where at least one of the eigenvalues of the covariance is close to zero. If the smoothing step enables to mitigate these cases, it is still not ensured that the covariance matrices will be non-singular after smoothing.

To avoid singular covariance matrices, Magnusson [90] suggests inflating small eigenvalues of the matrix. Likewise, Hong and Lee [101] associate a probability distribution to each individual point. This ensures that the distribution of a neighborhood of points, computed as the aggregation of individual point distributions, is non-singular.

The proposed approach is similar to the one of Magnusson [90] and consists in regularizing the matrix’ condition number. The condition number of a positive semi-definite matrix C with maximum and minimum eigenvalues $\lambda_{max} \geq \lambda_{min} \geq 0$ is defined as

$$\text{cond}(C) = \frac{\lambda_{max}}{\lambda_{min}} \in [1, +\infty]. \quad (2.20)$$

An ill-conditioned matrix has a high condition number. The regularization consists in modifying the matrix C such that its new condition number is below a defined threshold $\kappa > 1$ (typically, we use a value of $\kappa = 5$). This is achieved by adding a matrix proportional to the identity matrix I to the original matrix, so that the new matrix is $C + \delta_\kappa I$. The smallest value of δ_κ which enables to satisfy $\text{cond}(C + \delta_\kappa I) \leq \kappa$ is given by [204]

$$\delta_\kappa = \max\left(0, \frac{\lambda_{max} - \kappa\lambda_{min}}{\kappa - 1}\right). \quad (2.21)$$

Compared to the regularization method of Magnusson [90], the proposed approach not only modifies one eigenvalue, but all eigenvalues through the addition of a matrix proportional to identity. Thus the original shape of the covariance matrix is better preserved.

2.2.2 K-d tree adaptation

K-d tree construction

The NDT cells are usually constructed from a regular voxel grid. To avoid unnecessarily storing empty cells, an octree structure is often used. From the initial unordered list of point, the octree is built recursively to assign each point to a corresponding voxel. Afterwards, the parameters of the NDT distribution are computed for each voxel. For more flexibility and memory efficiency, the use of a k-d tree for storing the voxels initially constructed with a regular voxel grid is investigated by Schulz et al. [105]. However, since the authors first build a regular voxel grid before storing the cells in a k-d tree, the full potential of k-d trees is not exploited.

In this work, we investigate how to directly construct the NDT cells following the recursive construction logic of k-d trees. Contrarily to octree cells, k-d tree cells are not ensured to be cubic, which might be problematic when computing the distribution within each cell. Indeed, if each cell represents how the points are distributed in a different volume of space, the different distributions might not be comparable with one another. To alleviate this issue, we suggest in the following a k-d tree construction strategy which ensures that the cells have a good aspect ratio, i.e., that the longest side of a cell is at most two times the length of its shortest side. This corresponds to a maximum aspect ratio of 2:1, and avoids elongated cells.

The subdivision logic of the k-d tree is presented in Fig. 2.3. Given an initial point cloud, the first step is to compute the axis-aligned bounding box of these points. In the next step, the bounding box is split in two equal volumes along its longest edge. This ensures that the cells maintain a shape which is close to cubic. Then, these two steps are recursively applied to the two sub-clouds created by the subdivision. The subdivision of a cell stops once its longest edge is below a certain threshold, i.e., once the cell is small enough. Given a desired approximate cell size r , the threshold is set to $\frac{4}{3}r$ to ensure that after construction, the longest edge of each cell is within $[\frac{2}{3}r, \frac{4}{3}r]$.

This construction of the k-d tree is performed only once for the target point cloud. For implementation for a rendezvous mission, since the target point cloud is known prior to the mission, it is possible to construct the k-d tree offline. However, the creation of the k-d tree is relatively efficient, see the runtime evaluation presented later in Table 2.4.4. Therefore, from a runtime perspective, constructing the tree online would also be possible. The k-d tree construction is implemented recursively, following the steps presented previously.

Figure 2.3: Schematic representation of the k-d tree construction process in 2D, for the yellow point cloud. At each step, the bounding box of the points in each cell is computed, and the box is split along its longest axis to create two new cells.

Continuous Gaussian kernel

Once the cells are constructed via the k-d tree, the NDT distribution parameters of each cell are computed. However, the smoothing step (Section 2.2.1) needs to be adapted, since the neighboring cells are not regularly located as in the voxel grid case. Given a k-d tree cell indexed by k , the first step for smoothing the distribution of this cell is to define its neighboring distributions. The center of the cell's bounding box is denoted by \mathbf{c}_k . For a neighbor search radius d_r , the neighboring distributions indexed by k_i are the ones for which the mean value of the distribution $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k_i}$ satisfies the condition $\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k_i} - \mathbf{c}_k\| < d_r$.

To find the neighbors of each cell, it is not needed to iterate through all cells, since the k-d tree structure is used for efficient search. The complexity of a radius search to obtain the neighbors of a cell is in $O(\log(N_v))$, where N_v is the number of cells (voxels). Therefore, the smoothing operation, which is performed for each cell, has a complexity in $O(N_v \log(N_v))$. In terms of runtime, this step is negligible compared to the construction of the k-d tree, see later Table 2.4.4. Like the k-d tree construction, the smoothing step is only performed once for the target point cloud. Again, in the use case of a rendezvous mission where the target point cloud is known prior to the mission, the smoothing step is performed offline. During online registration, the algorithm uses the incoming source point cloud and the already built smoothed NDT tree of the target point cloud.

Instead of a discrete Gaussian kernel, in the k-d tree case, a continuous Gaussian kernel is applied to all neighboring cells. Specifically, for each cell k_i belonging to the list of neighbors of the cell k , the Gaussian kernel weight is

$$g(k_i) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_{k_i} - \mathbf{c}_k\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (2.22)$$

where σ is the standard deviation chosen for the kernel. Finally, the smoothing weights w_{k_i} are

obtained with the same normalization logic (2.19) as in the regular grid case. A schematized representation of the smoothing step in the k-d tree case is presented in Fig. 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Schematic representation of the smoothing step in case where the NDT map is stored in k-d tree cells. The initial distributions represented by their colored confidence ellipses (left) are convoluted with the continuous Gaussian kernel (middle) to obtain the smoothed distributions (right). For example, for smoothing the cell with the blue distribution, a radius search is performed to find the neighboring distributions (red dotted circle).

The standard deviation σ of the smoothing kernel depends on the approximate cell size r . In the experiments of this work, the standard deviation is chosen such that the half width at half maximum of the Gaussian kernel's distribution equals r , i.e., such that

$$\exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \iff \sigma = \frac{r}{\sqrt{2\ln(2)}}. \quad (2.23)$$

Finally, to select all the neighboring distributions which have a significant contribution to the smoothed distribution, the radius of the neighbor search is set to $d_r = 3\sigma$.

2.2.3 Relaxed cost function

In conventional NDT, the objective is to maximize the likelihood of the source point cloud under the distributions obtained with the NDT representation of the target cloud (2.12). One problem of this representation is that with the normal distribution PDF, the gradients of the cost function fade away if the initial estimate is far away from the optimal solution. This leads to slow convergence when using gradient-based algorithms to minimize the cost function in these cases. As discussed in Section 1.5.1, instead of maximizing the sum of probabilities, relaxed formulations of the cost function are possible to speed up the optimization process. In this work, we suggest getting rid of the normal distribution PDF to directly minimize the sum of Mahalanobis distances, similarly to [94]. The motivation for this change is twofold: First, the computation of gradients is simpler so that the computations are faster. Second, the cost function (2.24) takes the form of a weighted, non-linear least squares problem, which is solved efficiently by applying a Gauss-Newton method. The relaxed cost function of the smoothed NDT algorithm takes the form

$$s(T) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} ((T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)})^T C_{\eta(i)}^{-1} ((T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)}), \quad (2.24)$$

where $(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)}, C_{\eta(i)})$ are now the smoothed mean and covariance matrix of the cell to which the point $(T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)$ belongs. The smoothed parameters of the distribution are obtained through the process described in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2.

In the octree case, if a point of the source cloud does not fall into a cell, its contribution to the cost function is ignored. When a k-d tree is used to build the NDT map (Section 2.2.2), the association function η is modified to find the cell which is nearest to the query point. This enlarges the receptive field of each cell. An exact nearest cell search would require traversing multiple branches of the k-d tree. For efficiency, a simple approximate nearest cell search is performed instead. It consists in selecting the cell to which the query point leads when traversing the tree. In detail, at each split node of the tree, the space is divided in two by a plane, and the subtree to which the query point belongs is selected, until a leaf node is reached. This strategy is an approximation of the nearest cell search, but enables to traverse the tree only once. It is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Schematic representation of the approximate nearest cell search: The query point is associated with the cell in which it falls according to the k-d tree subdivisions (which is the cell with center c_1). This cell is not necessarily the exact closest cell (which would be the cell with center c_2).

For better precision in the approximate nearest cell search, a maximum point-to-cell threshold is defined, similarly to the maximum point-to-point distance parameter in ICP implementations. If the distance of a query point to the center of its (approximate) nearest cell is above the point-to-cell threshold, the nearest cell association is not considered as valid, and the contribution of this point to the cost function is ignored. The point-to-cell distance is represented in gray on Fig. 2.5.

To minimize the original NDT cost function (2.12), an iterative gradient descent algorithm is usually applied [93, 94]. This requires the computation of the gradients, and depending on

the algorithm also the Hessian of the cost function. For the relaxed cost function (2.24), we suggest applying the Gauss-Newton algorithm, which requires to compute the gradients. In the next section, we will introduce a formalism to compute gradients on the manifold of the rotation group $SO(3)$, enabling a minimal and singularity free formulation of the iterative solution to the minimization problem. To maintain an overview, Table 2.1 already lists the main changes of smoothed NDT compared to original NDT. Note that the last change (optimization on the $SO(3)$ manifold) will only be presented in the next Section, 2.3.

Table 2.1: Main changes of smoothed NDT compared to the original NDT algorithm.

change	goal
Gaussian kernel smoothing	increase robustness and convergence properties
k-d tree representation	implementation simplicity, flexibility and memory efficiency
relaxed cost function	faster convergence, simpler optimization
optimization on the $SO(3)$ manifold	singularity free optimization with a minimum set of parameters

2.3 Optimization on the $SO(3)$ manifold

The group of 3D rotations $SO(3)$ is represented by rotation matrices in $\mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$. Other representations of $SO(3)$ have lower dimensionality, such as quaternions with 4 parameters, or Euler angles with 3 parameters. The minimum of parameters needed for representing the rotation group is 3, and such minimal representations are interesting for optimization problems, as they imply that the number of parameters to optimize is also kept to a minimum. However, Euler angles come with singularities, the gimbal lock problem and convention setting [205]. We present here an alternative and convenient representation for optimization on the $SO(3)$ manifold. While still considering rotations as elements of $\mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$, increments are only performed in a three-dimensional space. This modeling, applied here to the optimization problem (2.24), is based on the work of Hertzberg et al. [206] and Sola et al. [207]. An overview of Lie Group and Algebra theory is provided in the book of Kirillov [208].

2.3.1 $SO(3)$ as a Lie group

$SO(3)$ is also a differentiable manifold of dimension 3, making it a matrix Lie group [207]. Formally, a Lie group is defined as follows:

Definition 1 (Lie group). *A Lie group \mathcal{F} is both a group, and a smooth manifold [207, 208]. Because it is a group, it is associated with a group operation such that the group is stable by this operation, the operation is associative, has an identity element, and each element has an inverse.*

The concept of smooth manifold implies that the group multiplication $\mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ and inversion $\mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ are both smooth maps, i.e., they are infinitely differentiable (C^∞) [208].

For our purposes, we will restrict ourselves to real matrix Lie groups when talking about a Lie group. This implies that the Lie group is a subgroup of a group of n -dimensional real matrices. A Lie group is interesting because it has an associated Lie algebra which is identified with a low-dimensional vector space. Let \mathcal{F} be a Lie group and $x(t)$ a trajectory on this Lie group, the velocity is

$$\dot{x}(t) = \frac{\partial x(t)}{\partial t} \in \mathcal{T}_{x(t)}\mathcal{F}, \quad (2.25)$$

where $\mathcal{T}_{x(t)}\mathcal{F}$ is the tangent space to the Lie group's manifold at this point $x(t)$.

Definition 2 (Lie algebra). *The Lie algebra \mathfrak{f} associated with the Lie group \mathcal{F} is the tangent space expressed at the identity element of the group [207]:*

$$\mathfrak{f} := \mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{1}}\mathcal{F}, \quad (2.26)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the identity element.

For example, for the rotation group $SO(3)$, the time derivative of a rotation matrix R is of the form

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = R\omega^\times, \quad (2.27)$$

with $\omega \in \mathbb{R}^3$, where the cross-product matrix of an element θ in \mathbb{R}^3 is defined by:

$$\theta^\times = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\theta_3 & \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 & 0 & -\theta_1 \\ -\theta_2 & \theta_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.28)$$

The Lie algebra of $SO(3)$ is the space to which $R\omega^\times$ belongs when $R = I_3$ is the identity matrix. Thus, the Lie algebra of $SO(3)$ is the space of skew-symmetric matrices. Following property of Lie algebras is particularly useful [207]:

Property 1. *A Lie algebra is a vector space, i.e., the elements of a Lie algebra \mathfrak{f} are identified with elements of \mathbb{R}^n , n being the dimension of this vector space.*

For $SO(3)$, again, this is seen very easily. Every element of the algebra is of the form θ^\times , and is identified with the vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The Lie algebra of $SO(3)$ is of dimension 3.

2.3.2 The exponential map for operations on rotations

To switch between elements of the Lie group and the algebra, the exponential map is defined. The general definition of the exponential map is found in [208]. Following is the definition for matrix Lie groups [207, 209]:

Definition 3 (Exponential map). *Let \mathcal{F} be a matrix Lie group and \mathfrak{f} its associated Lie algebra, the exponential map converts elements from the Lie algebra to the group*

$$\exp : \begin{cases} \mathfrak{f} & \rightarrow \mathcal{F} \\ x & \mapsto \mathbf{1} + x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots \end{cases}. \quad (2.29)$$

Its inverse is the logarithm map:

$$\log : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathfrak{f}. \quad (2.30)$$

A precise justification of why the exponential map has values in the Lie group \mathcal{F} is provided in [208]. Instead of using the Lie algebra \mathfrak{f} , it is more convenient to directly work in the associated vector space \mathbb{R}^n resulting from Property 1. Therefore, following the convention of Sola et al. [207] we define the capitalized exponential and logarithm maps:

Definition 4 (Capitalized exponential map). *Let \mathcal{F} be a Lie group and \mathfrak{f} which is identified to \mathbb{R}^n , the capitalized exponential map converts elements from the vector space to the group*

$$\text{Exp} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{F}. \quad (2.31)$$

Its inverse is the capitalized logarithm map:

$$\text{Log} : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n. \quad (2.32)$$

For $SO(3)$, this means that there is a mapping between elements of \mathbb{R}^3 and $SO(3)$. This mapping will be used as a low-dimensional representation of the rotation group. Similarly to Euler angles or the axis-angle representation, this mapping is minimal, i.e., it only consists of 3 parameters.

For $SO(3)$, the capital exponential map Exp is simply the matrix exponential of the associated cross-product matrix:

$$\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \exp(\boldsymbol{\theta}^\times), \quad (2.33)$$

In this case, there is a direct formula for the exponential [206, 207]. Writing $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \theta \mathbf{u}$ with $\theta = \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$, we have from Rodrigues' formula:

$$\text{Exp}(\theta \mathbf{u}) = I_3 + (\sin \theta) \mathbf{u}^\times + (1 - \cos \theta) (\mathbf{u}^\times)^2. \quad (2.34)$$

The inverse mapping is the logarithm map. For a rotation matrix $R \in SO(3)$, its logarithm is denoted by the capital logarithm function, Log , and obtained by [206]

$$\text{Log } R := \frac{\theta}{2 \sin \theta} \begin{pmatrix} R_{32} - R_{23} \\ R_{13} - R_{31} \\ R_{21} - R_{12} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.35)$$

where

$$\theta = \arccos \frac{\text{trace}(R) - 1}{2}. \quad (2.36)$$

If $\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = R$, then $\text{Log}(R) = \boldsymbol{\theta}$, and the definition of θ (2.36) coincides with the definition $\theta = \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$.

Like every 3D representation of the rotation group, the logarithm map also has singularities. The logarithm map is not defined for $\theta = \pi$. However, the exponential map and logarithm map will not be applied for absolute rotations, but to represent small rotation increments in the rotation group. It will be assumed that these increments are always with a magnitude such that $\theta < \pi$.

The exponential map is useful to represent increments in a Lie group. Following Sola et al. [207], we introduce following ‘‘round-plus’’ and ‘‘round-minus’’ operators:

Definition 5 (Left \oplus and \ominus operators). *Let (\mathcal{F}, \cdot) be a Lie group with its associated operation. Its Lie algebra is identified to \mathbb{R}^n . The \oplus operator defines an increment of an element of the group by an element of the tangent space*

$$\oplus : \begin{cases} \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathcal{F} & \rightarrow \mathcal{F} \\ \epsilon, x & \mapsto \epsilon \oplus x = \text{Exp}(\epsilon) \cdot x \end{cases} \quad (2.37)$$

The \ominus operator defines the difference in the vector space of two elements from the group:

$$\ominus : \begin{cases} \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{F} & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \\ x, y & \mapsto x \ominus y = \text{Log}(x \cdot y^{-1}) \end{cases} \quad (2.38)$$

Depending on in which order the previous matrix multiplication is made, we have a “right” or a “left” round-plus and round-minus operator [207]. In our case, we only use “left” operators, because they lead to a more simple formulation. Therefore, in the following, we will not always specify that the \oplus and \ominus operators are left operators.

For $R \in SO(3)$, the \oplus operator increments the rotation by an element $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^3$:

$$\theta \oplus R = \text{Exp}(\theta)R, \quad (2.39)$$

and \ominus expresses the difference between two rotations $R, Q \in SO(3)$ in a 3-dimensional space:

$$R \ominus Q = \text{Log}(RQ^T). \quad (2.40)$$

A particular case also of interest is the case where the Lie group \mathcal{F} is simply a vector space, for example $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{R}^n$. In this case, the group operation is the addition, the Exp and Log maps equal identity, and the \oplus and \ominus operators are the usual $+$ and $-$ operators.

2.3.3 Differentiation on the manifold of $SO(3)$

The previous section shows how to express increments in the rotation group with a minimal number of parameters using the \oplus and \ominus operators. This will be useful for defining an iterative optimization method to solve the smoothed NDT optimization problem (2.24).

To use a gradient based optimization method, it is necessary to compute the Jacobian matrix of the objective function. However, the standard definition of the Jacobian consists in computing the partial derivative of every output element by every input element. In the case where the rotation matrix is in Lie group $SO(3)$, it is not efficient to compute the partial derivative with respect to all 9 elements of the rotation matrix. Instead, it is sufficient to compute the 3 derivatives in the manifold to capture the necessary information for the Jacobian. We consider perturbations of the argument by 3-dimensional elements of its associated Lie algebra. The effect of this perturbation is also observed in the vector space of the result.

To do so, we define the general formula for differentiation on a Lie group. Because we are using left operators, this definition corresponds to the definition of left Jacobians on Lie groups, and is found in [207, 209].

Definition 6 (Differentiation on a Lie group). *Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} be two Lie groups, with associated Lie algebras identified to \mathbb{R}^n and \mathbb{R}^m . Consider a function $f : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$. Let $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be a perturbation of the input argument $x \in \mathcal{F}$. Then the result $f(x)$ is also perturbed. The Jacobian on Lie groups is the linear mapping between the perturbation in the Lie algebra of the argument space \mathbb{R}^n , and the perturbation in the Lie algebra of the result space \mathbb{R}^m :*

$$\frac{\partial^{\mathcal{G}} f(x)}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} x} := \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(\epsilon \oplus x) \ominus f(x)}{\epsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}. \quad (2.41)$$

Here, the division by the vector ϵ is a compact notation of the limit, also found in [207, 209], to avoid writing the limit for every component of the vector of the numerator and every component of the denominator. If writing out the Jacobian matrix for each component $(i, j) \in \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^n$, the definition is

$$\left(\frac{\partial^{\mathcal{G}} f(x)}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} x}\right)_{i,j} = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{f(\epsilon e_j \oplus x) \ominus f(x)}{\epsilon}\right)_i, \quad (2.42)$$

where e_j is the j -th element of the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^n .

In case \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are regular vector spaces, this corresponds to the standard definition of the Jacobian. Therefore, this notation is an extension of the Jacobian definition. The notation $\partial^{\mathcal{F}}$ (or $\partial^{\mathcal{G}}$) refers to the fact that the element after this operator is in a Lie group \mathcal{F} . We only specify \mathcal{F} or \mathcal{G} if they are not vector spaces. If for example \mathcal{G} is a vector space, to simplify the notation, we write $\frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} x}$.

The Taylor expansion is generalized to differentiation on a Lie group [207]:

Property 2 (Taylor expansion on a Lie group). *The Taylor expansion at the first order yields*

$$f(\epsilon \oplus x) = \left(\frac{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} f(x)}{\partial^{\mathcal{G}} x} \epsilon\right) \oplus f(x) + o(\|\epsilon\|). \quad (2.43)$$

Let's make this more concrete: If the argument of the function f is a rotation matrix, i.e., if $\mathcal{F} = SO(3)$, and the result is a 3D vector, i.e., $\mathcal{G} = \mathbb{R}^3$ then the Jacobian is only a 3×3 matrix. To minimize the cost function of the smoothed NDT formulation (2.24), we need to compute the differential of the rigid transformation function (2.1) with respect to the rotation matrix R . Consider $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and $T \in SE(3)$ which is decomposed in $(R, \boldsymbol{\rho}) \in SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3$. The Jacobian of the transformation $(T \cdot \mathbf{x})$ with respect to R is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(T \cdot \mathbf{x})}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} &= \frac{\partial(R\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\rho})}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} \\ &= \frac{\partial(R\mathbf{x})}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} \\ &= \lim_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \rightarrow 0} \frac{(\boldsymbol{\theta} \oplus R)\mathbf{x} \ominus R\mathbf{x}}{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \\ &= \lim_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta})R\mathbf{x} - R\mathbf{x}}{\boldsymbol{\theta}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

The last line is explained by the fact that \mathbb{R}^3 being at the same time a Lie group and a vector space, the \ominus operator in \mathbb{R}^3 is simply the $-$ operator.

The Taylor expansion at the first order of $\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ evaluated around $\boldsymbol{\theta} = 0$ yields

$$\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = I_3 + \boldsymbol{\theta}^\times + o(\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|). \quad (2.45)$$

Therefore, (2.44) re-writes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(T \cdot \boldsymbol{x})}{\partial^{SO(3)}R} &= \lim_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\boldsymbol{\theta}^\times R\boldsymbol{x}}{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \\ &= \lim_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \rightarrow 0} \frac{-(R\boldsymbol{x})^\times \boldsymbol{\theta}}{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \quad (\text{cross-product property}) \\ &= -(R\boldsymbol{x})^\times. \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

2.3.4 Iterative optimization of the NDT cost function

The cost function (2.24) of the smoothed NDT algorithm is not only minimized with respect to the relative attitude, but with respect to the full transformation $T \in SE(3)$. The group of rigid transformations $SE(3)$ is identified to $SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3$. Because both $SO(3)$ and \mathbb{R}^3 are Lie groups, $SE(3)$ is also a Lie group. The associated Lie algebra of $SE(3)$ is the concatenation of the Lie algebras of both groups, so that it is $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3$ which is identified to \mathbb{R}^6 .

Let's consider an element $(R, \boldsymbol{\rho}) \in SE(3)$, and an increment in its associated Lie algebra $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^6$. For convenience, we will decompose $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ in $\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\delta} \in \mathbb{R}^3$:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\theta} \\ \boldsymbol{\delta} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.47)$$

The \oplus and \ominus operators in $SE(3)$ are simply defined as the concatenation of these operators in $SO(3)$ and \mathbb{R}^3 :

$$\oplus : \begin{cases} \mathbb{R}^6 \times SE(3) & \rightarrow SE(3) \\ \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\theta} \\ \boldsymbol{\delta} \end{pmatrix}, (R, \boldsymbol{\rho}) & \mapsto (\boldsymbol{\theta} \oplus R, \boldsymbol{\delta} + \boldsymbol{\rho}) \end{cases}, \quad (2.48)$$

and

$$\ominus : \begin{cases} SE(3) \times SE(3) & \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^6 \\ (Q, \boldsymbol{\kappa}), (R, \boldsymbol{\rho}) & \mapsto \begin{pmatrix} Q \ominus R \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa} - \boldsymbol{\rho} \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}. \quad (2.49)$$

With this definition, the Jacobian of a transformation T applied on $\boldsymbol{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ with respect to the transformation parameters is defined by (see (2.41)):

$$\frac{\partial(T \cdot \boldsymbol{x})}{\partial^{SE(3)}T} = \lim_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \rightarrow 0} \frac{((\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T) \cdot \boldsymbol{x}) \ominus (T \cdot \boldsymbol{x})}{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}. \quad (2.50)$$

This Jacobian is an element of $\mathbb{R}^{3 \times 6}$. Because the increment $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is decomposed in the rotation increment $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and the translation increment $\boldsymbol{\delta}$, the Jacobian is directly:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(T \cdot \boldsymbol{x})}{\partial^{SE(3)}T} &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial(T \cdot \boldsymbol{x})}{\partial^{SO(3)}R} & \frac{\partial(T \cdot \boldsymbol{x})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} -(R\boldsymbol{x})^\times & I_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{from (2.46)}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.51)$$

We want to optimize (2.24). This cost function takes the form of a weighted least-squares problem

$$s(T) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} \mathbf{r}_i^T W_i \mathbf{r}_i, \quad (2.52)$$

where the residuals are $\mathbf{r}_i = ((T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)})$ and the weighting matrices $W_i = C_{\eta(i)}^{-1}$. The Jacobians of the residuals are

$$\begin{aligned} J_i &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_i}{\partial SE(3)T} \\ &= \frac{\partial (T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)}{\partial SE(3)T}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.53)$$

which are directly given by (2.51).

According to the Gauss-Newton algorithm, the increment to perform at each step to minimize the cost function is

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = -\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} J_i^T W_i J_i\right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} J_i^T W_i \mathbf{r}_i\right). \quad (2.54)$$

This increment is applied to the transformation T via:

$$T \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T, \quad (2.55)$$

and this procedure is repeated until convergence.

Proof of (2.54). Because (2.52) is not a standard formulation of a weighted least squares problem, which usually assumes scalar weights and residuals, we will provide here a justification of the formula (2.54), which determines the increment to apply at each step. We will prove the following:

- Under the assumption of linearization around the current value of the rigid transformation, i.e., assuming that $(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T) \cdot \mathbf{z}_i = (T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) + J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, the increment (2.54) defines $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ which minimizes $s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T)$.

We seek the increment $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ which minimizes $s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T)$. Under the linear approximation assumption, the residuals for the perturbed rigid transformation are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_i(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T) &= ((\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T) \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)} \\ &= (T \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) + J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)} \\ &= \mathbf{r}_i(T) + J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.56)$$

The minimum is defined by

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} (s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T)) &= \min_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} (\mathbf{r}_i(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T))^T W_i (\mathbf{r}_i(\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \oplus T)) \right) \\
&= \min_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} (\mathbf{r}_i(T) + J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon})^T W_i (\mathbf{r}_i(T) + J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \right) \\
&= \min_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} (J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon})^T W_i (J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} (J_i \boldsymbol{\epsilon})^T W_i \mathbf{r}_i(T) \right) \\
&= \min_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \left(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T A \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T \mathbf{b} \right),
\end{aligned} \tag{2.57}$$

where $A = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} J_i^T W_i J_i$ and $\mathbf{b} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} J_i^T W_i \mathbf{r}_i(T)$.

A is a positive definite, so it is symmetric and invertible. Due to A being symmetric, we have

$$\frac{\partial(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T A \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^T \mathbf{b})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = 2A \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \mathbf{b}. \tag{2.58}$$

Hence, the minimum is obtained for

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = -\frac{A^{-1} \mathbf{b}}{2}. \tag{2.59}$$

□

The gradient descent algorithm is an iterative procedure. To define the stopping criteria of the algorithm, a maximum number of iterations n_{iter}^{max} , an angular threshold θ_{min} and a translation threshold δ_{min} are defined. The iterations stop once one of the following two conditions is met:

- The number of iterations has exceeded n_{iter}^{max} ;
- The increment $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\theta} \\ \boldsymbol{\delta} \end{pmatrix}$ is such that $\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\| < \theta_{min}$ and $\|\boldsymbol{\delta}\| < \delta_{min}$.

Introducing the exponential map formalism enables to use a minimal, 3-dimensional and singularity free representation of the rotation increments. It is the natural way of computing differentials in a Lie group, and enables to compute the gradients for the weighted least squares problem. This problem is then solved using a Gauss-Newton procedure. It remains that the gradient descent methods are local optimization method, they require an initial guess to start with, and might be stuck in a local minimum if the initial guess is not close enough to the absolute minimum. Like ICP and classical NDT, the smoothed NDT is a local registration algorithm. However, both the smoothing step, and the formulation of the optimization as weighted least squares, enables to widen the convergence basin of the algorithm, as will be shown in the results, Section 2.5.4.

While the formalism to perform the optimization in the manifold of $SO(3)$ might seem complex, the final result is surprisingly simple. The expression of the gradients J_i , given by (2.51), is straightforward. To compute the increment at each iteration following (2.54), it is only necessary to invert a positive definite 6×6 matrix, which is easily done.

2.4 Experiment setup at EPOS

To evaluate and compare the different methods presented for pose tracking, hardware-in-the-loop experiments are performed at the EPOS facility. Different methods will be compared for lidar-based tracking of a spacecraft during a non-cooperative rendezvous mission scenario: ICP, classical NDT and the smoothed NDT method presented in this Chapter. The target satellite considered is the satellite mock-up illustrated in Fig. 2.6. It is made of real materials such as solar panels and golden MLI sheets covering the front part of the satellite.

Figure 2.6: Close view of the satellite mock-up installed at the EPOS facility.

2.4.1 European Proximity Operations Simulator

Validation is an important topic for space technology, because it is challenging to simulate or reproduce during tests on ground the exact conditions in which the system will operate in orbit. To validate the lidar navigation system developed in this work, the European Proximity Operations Simulator (EPOS) is used. It is located at the German Space Operations Center (GSOC) in Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany.

The EPOS facility [210] consists of two industrial robotic arms, as illustrated in Fig. 2.7. Both robots move with 6 DOF to reproduce different relative positions and orientations. Additionally, one robotic arm is mounted on a linear rail, so that it translates up to a relative distance of 25 m to the first robot. In the current setup, the robot mounted on the linear rail carries a plate on which the different rendezvous sensors of the chaser satellite are attached. It is referred to as “Robot 1”. The second robot, “Robot 2”, holds a 1:1 mock-up of the target spacecraft, which is a model of the past German Orbital Servicing Mission (DEOS) spacecraft in this case. Depending on the use-case, it is possible to install different mock-ups at the facility for test campaigns [211].

A space dynamics simulator propagates the trajectory of both satellites, and an optimization routine computes corresponding feasible configurations of both robots in real-time to reproduce their relative pose. The facility is used to produce trajectories either in open loop, based on pre-defined trajectories, or in closed loop. In closed loop, it is coupled to a GNC system for controlling the chaser satellite. The relative pose of the target satellite is estimated by a navigation filter which combines the result of the processing of the different sensors mounted on the sensor

Figure 2.7: EPOS facility. The left robotic arm (Robot 1) is mounted on a linear rail, and carries the rendezvous sensors of the chaser satellite. The right arm (Robot 2) holds a mock-up of the target spacecraft.

plate, such as a visual camera, a PMD camera and a lidar [72]. Based on this estimation, the controller commands maneuvers to be performed by the chaser satellite in order to follow the desired guidance trajectory. These maneuvers are then reproduced at the facility in real-time to close the loop. The results of the GNC system is compared to the ground truth given by the facility to assess its performance. The facility is regularly calibrated, and the latest calibration report concludes that the positioning and pointing accuracy of each robot is better than 1.74 mm and 0.2 deg.

2.4.2 Lidar sensor

Space qualified lidar sensors are relatively expensive, and no such sensor was available at EPOS at the time of this research. To perform representative tests for the use of a lidar during close range rendezvous, a lidar sensor coming from the automotive domain, a Livox[®] Mid-40, is used for testing at EPOS. The characteristics of this lidar are presented in Table 2.2. The Livox[®] Mid-40 is a scanning lidar. It has a non-repetitive rosette scanning pattern, so that more points are collected in the center of the field of view than on the outside. This scanning pattern is illustrated in Fig. 2.8a. The lidar is mounted on the sensor plate of Robot 1. An image of the mounted sensor is shown in Fig. 2.8b.

2.4.3 Lidar calibration

Figure 2.9 gives a schematic overview of the coordinate frames defined at the EPOS facility. In this configuration, the two robots are more distant from each other, since Robot 1 is translated on the linear rail away from Robot 2, which is fix. On the left of the illustration, Robot 2 carries the full-scale mock-up of the target spacecraft. On the right, the Robot 1 is equipped with a

Table 2.2: Characteristics of the Livox[®] Mid-40 [212].

parameter	value
detection range	90 m @ 10% reflectivity 130 m @ 20% reflectivity 260 m @ 80% reflectivity
field of view	38.4 deg
point rate	100 000 pts/s
range precision (1σ)	2 cm
angular precision	< 0.1 deg
beam divergence	0.28 deg

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.8: (a) Scanning pattern of the Livox[®] Mid-40. (b) View of the sensor mounted on the sensor plate of the “chaser robot” at EPOS.

sensor plate on which the Livox Mid-40 lidar is mounted.

The EPOS facility is precisely calibrated [210], so that the pose of both robots is logged and is known for every time step (with a frequency of 250 Hz). However, when the lidar is first installed on the sensor plate of Robot 1, its relative pose with respect to the coordinate frame of Robot 1 is unknown. This transformation must be known in order to acquire the ground truth value of the pose of the target satellite with respect to the sensor during the experiments.

To find this relative pose, the lidar must be calibrated. When calibrating a sensor, two types of parameters are calibrated: The extrinsic parameters, corresponding to the pose of the sensor in the experiment setup, and the intrinsic parameters, which correct the potential internal biases and distortion effects of the sensor. Calibrating the extrinsic parameters of a sensor is also referred to as the “hand-eye calibration” [213]. The intrinsic calibration method for a lidar is usually dependent on the exact type of lidar sensor [214–216]. While intrinsic

Figure 2.9: Definition of coordinate frames at the EPOS facility. The lidar sensor, attached to the sensor plate of Robot 1, scans in direction of the satellite mock-up held by Robot 2.

parameter calibration is common for some sensors such as visual cameras, it is less widespread for lidars: Calibration methods for multi-sensor systems often focus on the intrinsic and extrinsic calibration of the camera, and only on the extrinsic calibration of the lidar [217–219].

Likewise, in this work, we will only consider the extrinsic, “hand-eye calibration” of the lidar, and the intrinsic parameters will be considered to be calibrated precisely enough by the sensor manufacturer. To properly define coordinate frame transformations, we will denote by T_A^B the rigid transformation of $SE(3)$ which transforms a point expressed in frame A into a point expressed in frame B . Following coordinate frames are defined on Fig. 2.9:

- *Rob1*: The coordinate frame of the tool held by Robot 1;
- *Rob2*: The coordinate frame of the tool held by Robot 2;
- *Tar*: The coordinate frame of the target satellite;
- *Lid*: The coordinate frame of the lidar;
- *GLC*: The Global Lab Coordinate (GLC) frame, which is the fix coordinate frame of the EPOS facility.

The objective of the extrinsic lidar calibration is to determine the pose of the lidar in the Robot 1 coordinate frame, i.e., the transformation T_{Rob1}^{Lid} . Due to the facility being calibrated, the pose of the robots $T_{Rob1}^{GLC}, T_{Rob2}^{GLC}$ are known at every time step. The pose of the satellite with respect to the arm of Robot 2, T_{Rob2}^{Tar} , is also to be calibrated. However, this pose is already accurately known, due to the precise manufacturing of the satellite mock-up to fit on the robot plate in the context of the DEOS project [211]. Therefore, it is considered for this calibration that T_{Rob2}^{Tar} is fix and already known.

The calibration is performed by collecting a series of point clouds $P_1, \dots, P_{N_{calib}}$ at the facility. These point clouds are acquired for various poses of the two robots, and different relative distances. Afterward, a joint NDT-based optimization is performed on all point clouds to retrieve the hand-eye calibration of the lidar T_{Lid}^{Rob1} . This principle is explained in the following.

We consider a point cloud P with points $\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_N$. These points are usually expressed in the lidar coordinate frame. In the definition of the smoothed NDT (2.24), the mean and covariance matrices of the NDT distribution are on the contrary expressed in the target coordinate frame, so that the pose to optimize is the transformation from the lidar to the target:

$$s(T_{Lid}^{Tar}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} ((T_{Lid}^{Tar} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)})^T C_{\eta(i)}^{-1} ((T_{Lid}^{Tar} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)}). \quad (2.60)$$

The objective is to express this cost as a function of the unknown transformation T_{Lid}^{Rob1} . The transformation T_{Lid}^{Tar} is expressed as a function of this transformation by application of the chain rule:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{Lid}^{Tar} &= T_{Rob1}^{Tar} \circ T_{Lid}^{Rob1} \\ &= T_{Rob2}^{Tar} \circ T_{GLC}^{Rob2} \circ T_{Rob1}^{GLC} \circ T_{Lid}^{Rob1}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.61)$$

where “ \circ ” is the composition operator. The cost function (2.60) re-writes:

$$s(T_{Lid}^{Tar}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} (T_{Rob1}^{Tar} \cdot (T_{Lid}^{Rob1} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)})^T C_{\eta(i)}^{-1} (T_{Rob1}^{Tar} \cdot (T_{Lid}^{Rob1} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)}). \quad (2.62)$$

This cost function is minimized similarly to the optimization presented in Section 2.3. The only difference is that the residuals are now $\mathbf{r}_i = (T_{Rob1}^{Tar} \cdot (T_{Lid}^{Rob1} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)})$, so that when minimizing for T_{Lid}^{Rob1} , the Jacobian (2.53) is replaced with

$$\begin{aligned} J_i &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_i}{\partial SE(3) T_{Lid}^{Rob1}} \\ &= \frac{\partial (T_{Rob1}^{Tar} \cdot (T_{Lid}^{Rob1} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i))}{\partial SE(3) T_{Lid}^{Rob1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.63)$$

Writing out this expression separately for the derivative with respect to the rotation part, and the derivative with respect to the translation part, this Jacobian results in:

$$J_i = R_{Rob1}^{Tar} \frac{\partial (T_{Lid}^{Rob1} \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)}{\partial SE(3) T_{Lid}^{Rob1}}, \quad (2.64)$$

where R_{Rob1}^{Tar} is the rotational part of the transformation, and the right side is the known Jacobian (2.51). The derivation of (2.64) is immediate for the translation part. However, for the rotational part, it makes use of the non-trivial Property 4, which will only be proven in the next chapter, Section 3.3.2. For conciseness, this result is anticipated here.

Finally, with multiple point clouds $P_1, \dots, P_{N_{calib}}$ the hand-eye calibration parameters are the result of a joint optimization: If $s_1, \dots, s_{N_{calib}}$ are the cost functions of the different calibration point clouds given by (2.62), the calibrated transformation is

$$(T_{Lid}^{Rob1})^* = \min_{T_{Lid}^{Rob1}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{calib}} s_k(T_{Lid}^{Rob1}). \quad (2.65)$$

This minimization problem is solved in the same way presented in Section 2.3, with the difference that the Jacobians are provided by (2.64).

For the actual calibration of the Livox Mid-40 lidar at the EPOS facility, $N_{calib} = 13$ point clouds are recorded, corresponding to various configurations and distances between Robot 1 and Robot 2. More point clouds lead to a more precise calibration, and this number was found sufficient to obtain a hand-eye calibration of the lidar for the experiments. Following settings were chosen for the smoothed NDT algorithm: The cell size of the NDT grid, as well as the maximum point-to-cell distance, is set to 7.5 cm. The maximum number of iterations of the algorithm is set to 100, and the angular and translation thresholds for defining the convergence criteria of the algorithm are set to 0.1 mm and 0.01 deg.

The result of the calibration process is illustrated in Fig. 2.10. The initial calibration matrix is defined per hand, by measuring the position of the sensor on the robot tool plate, and estimating the rotation matrix corresponding to its orientation. Only few iterations, here 15, are needed for the smoothed NDT algorithm to converge towards a more accurate calibration solution. The value of the cost function (2.65) is presented in Fig. 2.10a. This cost function is additionally scaled by the number of points which have a matching cell in the NDT map. The cost effectively decreases over the iterations, and reaches a plateau which represents a local optimum. In Fig. 2.10b, the value of the position and rotation increment applied after each iteration to correct the rigid transformation is presented. Both values decrease rapidly until they fall below the termination threshold of 0.1 mm and 0.01 deg, where the optimization terminates.

Figure 2.10: Results of the calibration: (a) Value of the calibration cost function over the iterations; (b) Norm of the rotation (blue) and translation (orange) increment applied at each iteration.

2.4.4 Setup and integration in the GNC system

Background removal

For testing visual sensors under realistic illumination conditions imitating the sunlight exposure, a spotlight illuminates the target spacecraft at the facility. In addition, the robotic arm carrying the target mock-up as well as the background behind the target are covered with black molton,

so that only the target satellite and no background are visible on images captured by a passive visual sensor placed on the chaser sensor board. However, this is different for an active sensor such as a lidar.

From Table 2.2, it is seen that the Livox Mid-40 has an impressive scan rate of 100 000 points/s, spread over a circular field-of-view of 38.4 deg, and scanned in the rosette pattern shown in Fig. 2.8a. Most laser rays don't hit the target satellite, but other elements of the robotic facility: The walls, the floor, the ceiling, the curtains behind the robot carrying the mock-up, or the robotic arm carrying the mock-up. Such a point cloud, where not only the target satellite but an important part of the facility is seen, is shown in Fig. 2.11.

Figure 2.11: Raw point cloud captured by the Livox Mid-40 at the EPOS facility before background removal. All elements of the facility such as the curtains behind the robot, the floor, the linear rail and the robotic arm are seen. The rosette pattern of the Mid-40 lidar is clearly seen. The gap corresponds to the curtain's shadow, similarly to the shadow of Robot 2.

In space, these elements would not be seen. Therefore, a pre-processing logic is integrated in order to automatically remove these elements from the point cloud. Care is taken to avoid that this method removes from the point cloud interesting effects such as outliers, or double reflections. The logic of the background removal is therefore to remove all points which belong to known objects of the facility: The walls, curtains, robot arm etc. Due to the facility being calibrated, the position of these objects is known for each point cloud. The pre-processing computes the position of these objects, applies an additional tolerance of 10 cm to 60 cm depending on the object, and removes all points from the point cloud which are within these areas.

Sensor configuration

The Livox Mid-40 is integrated as one of the sensors of the chaser satellite. While the lidar scans continuously, the points are parsed in distinct point clouds. When setting the frame rate,

different settings are chosen: The first possibility is to set a constant frame rate (equal to 1 Hz in the experiments). This corresponds for example to the setting of ASC’s GSFL-16KS Space 3D Flash LIDARTM [61], which has a constant frame rate, a fix field-of-view and a 128×128 pixels array detector. If the frame rate is fix, for example at 1 Hz, then the number of points collected by the lidar (after background removal) increases quadratically when the distance decreases, see Fig. 2.12a.

Before being processed by the registration algorithms, the point clouds are downsampled using an octree compression with a voxel grid of 2 cm. This means that the scene is split in voxels of 2 cm side, and at most one point is kept per voxel. The first advantage is that the number of points in the scan becomes less variable of the distance between the sensor and target: While the original point clouds have sizes between 8000 and 70 000 points, after downsampling, the scans have sizes between 5000 and 15 000 points (Fig. 2.12a). Both ICP and NDT having a time complexity with a linear dependency in the number of points of the source point cloud, this enables to have a less variable runtime. In addition, the point clouds after downsampling have a more uniform density, so that using the downsampled point clouds increases the precision and robustness of the tracking algorithms.

Figure 2.12: Densities of the point clouds collected at EPOS, after background removal, as a function of the distance between the chaser and target. The number of points is shown before and after octree downsampling with a voxel grid of 2 cm for two different frame rate settings: **(a)** Fix lidar frame rate of 1 Hz. **(b)** Adaptive frame rate with a variable frequency between minimum 0.2 Hz and maximum 3 Hz. Below a distance of 5 m, the maximum frame rate of 3 Hz is reached, so that the point cloud density of the raw point clouds increases.

On the opposite, to avoid scanning mostly void space, some scanning lidars for space also have a dynamically adaptable field-of-view and repetition rate: This is for example the case of the Jena-Optronik RVS 3000TM scanning lidar [143]. If the lidar adapts its field-of-view to scan around the target, the number of points per lidar scan is approximately constant. While the field-of-view of the Livox Mid-40 cannot be adapted dynamically, to reproduce this behavior, a second possibility is to dynamically adapt the sensor frame rate, such that after the background removal step presented previously, the number of points contained in the point cloud is always

approximately the same. This number of points is set to 10 000.

With this setting, the frame rate of the lidar is set dynamically with a simple feedback loop, so that whenever the number of points exceed a threshold (here of 11 000 points), the frame rate is increased, and vice-versa to decrease the frame rate for point clouds with less than 9000 points. In addition, maximum and minimum values are set for the frame rate: The minimum frame rate is of 0.2 Hz, and the maximum of 3 Hz. The density of point clouds as a function of the distance to the sensor for this setting is shown in Fig. 2.12b. Due to the maximum frame rate of 3 Hz, when the distance to the target is below 5 m, the sensor frame rate cannot be increased anymore and the number of points starts to increase again. After downsampling with a voxel grid size of 2 cm, the number of points in each scan is between 4500 and 8000 (Fig. 2.12b).

If both settings are available, an adaptive frame rate is preferable, since this setting is more flexible: it allows capturing point clouds with a higher frequency in close range, when more frequent pose updates might be necessary due to higher requirements on the navigation precision. However, the fixed frame rate setting is also tested in the experiments, to illustrate settings that might be observed with different sensors such as flash lidars.

Integration in the GNC system

The proposed tracking method was implemented in C++ and integrated in the rendezvous-GNC system developed by DLR's OOS group [72]. This means that during experiments at EPOS, the lidar tracking is performed in closed loop: The controller of the chaser spacecraft adapts the control to the current navigation information, which is based on the filtered result of the lidar tracking. The lidar tracking used in closed loop for all experiments is the smoothed NDT, with an additional filtering and deblurring logic which will be presented in Chapter 3. In this chapter however, this additional logic is not added yet in the offline evaluations of the recorded datasets.

The algorithms compared in this chapter are fine registration algorithms, they require an initial guess to converge. Methods for providing such an initial estimate will be discussed in Chapter 4. However, for the tracking experiments in this Section, we assume that for the first point cloud of the recording trajectory, the pose is known, it is set to the ground truth value. For all subsequent scans of the sequence, the previous result of the pose estimation is used as an initial estimate for the refinement algorithm. This simple feedback logic is illustrated in Fig. 2.13. Accounting for the past motion in order to have a more precise initial estimate, which could for example be the result of the prediction step of a navigation filter, will be discussed in the next Chapter 3. In this Chapter, the focus lies on the comparison of the core of the point cloud processing algorithms.

Figure 2.13: Schema of the feedback loop for pose tracking. The previous result of the tracking algorithm (here smoothed NDT) is used as an initial guess for registration of the new collected point cloud.

Compared algorithms

Following algorithms are compared:

- **ICP:** An own version of ICP is implemented, following the logic of Section 2.1.2. For the nearest neighbor search, the source point cloud is stored in a k-d tree. Instead of an exact nearest neighbor search, an approximate neighbor search is performed for efficiency, similarly to the NDT implementation (see Section 2.2.3). The approximate search consists in directly selecting the k-d tree cell to which the query point belongs, and finding amongst the points of this cell the one closest to the query point. In an exact nearest neighbor search, other surrounding k-d tree cells should also be considered.
- **Smoothed NDT:** The implementation of the smoothed NDT method follows the description given in Section 2.2.
- **NDT:** As for ICP, multiple variants of the NDT algorithm are possible. In these experiments, to be able to specifically isolate the effect of the smoothing step on the NDT map, the “classical” NDT will be implemented in the same way as the smoothed NDT version, with the only difference that the smoothing step is not performed during the map construction.

Both ICP and (smoothed) NDT rely on matching a model of the target point cloud with the source point clouds. In the case of satellite pose tracking studied in this work, it is assumed that the target point cloud is known in the beforehand (see Fig. 2.1a). Therefore, the tree structures used for the registration algorithms are built offline, prior to the evaluation of the source point clouds. For ICP, this consists only in sorting the target point cloud in a k-d tree structure. For NDT, the distributions must be additionally computed, and eventually the smoothing step is performed.

To compare the three methods, the tuning parameters of Table 2.3 are used. These parameters are the result of individual tuning of each algorithm: For each method, the parameters yielding the best results (lowest pose tracking error) are selected, which is why the parameters differ from one method to the other. For ICP, it is chosen to have an approximate number of points per k-d tree bin of 20, which is empirically found to be a good number for an efficient nearest neighbor search [220]. For (smoothed) NDT, the cell size is it a trade-off between runtime, robustness (a bigger cell size leads to faster and more reliable convergence) and precision

(a smaller cell size leads to better precision). An approximate cell size of 10 cm is selected for classical NDT, since a lower cell size leads to high tracking errors during the experiments. On the contrary, for smoothed NDT, it is found that reducing the cell size to 7.5 cm increases the accuracy.

Table 2.3: Tuning parameters of ICP, NDT and smoothed NDT chosen for these experiments. The tree cell size refers to the resolution of the k-d tree used for creating the ICP and NDT search structures, while the downsampling grid size corresponds to the resolution of the voxel grid used to downsample incoming source point clouds.

method	approx. tree cell size	max pt-to-pt/ pt-to-cell dist.	downsampling grid size	termination criteria		
				max iter.	ang thresh.	pos thresh.
ICP	20 points	10 cm	2 cm	80	0.01 deg	0.5 mm
NDT	10 cm	10 cm	2 cm	30	0.01 deg	0.5 mm
smoothed NDT	7.5 cm	7.5 cm	2 cm	30	0.01 deg	0.5 mm

The maximum point-to-point distance for the ICP nearest neighbor association, which is the equivalent of the maximum point-to-cell distance for NDT, is also tuned accordingly. It is not identical for the different algorithms, since a maximum distance of 10 cm is found to yield the best results for ICP and NDT, while a point-to-cell distance of 7.5 cm yields the best results for smoothed NDT. Additionally, downsampling of all source point clouds is performed before the registration step, see previously in Fig. 2.12. This enables more robust and faster registration. For all algorithms, the source point clouds are downsampled in a pre-processing step with an octree, using a voxel grid size of 2 cm. Last, the termination criteria is similar for all algorithms, with the difference that the maximum permissible number of iterations is higher for ICP. The reason for not choosing the same termination criteria is that (smoothed) NDT converges faster towards the solution, so that less iterations are needed in average. Thus, the iterations are stopped earlier. On the contrary, if ICP is stopped after 30 iterations, the solution might not be reached and the algorithm will fail at tracking the target over consecutive point clouds.

The runtime of the tree construction step for the different algorithms is presented in Table 2.4. The same k-d tree is used for all algorithms. Therefore, the runtime is determined by the granularity of the k-d tree: 20 points per cell for ICP, approximately 10 cm for NDT, and 7.5 cm for smoothed NDT. Constructing the NDT map is faster in this case than constructing the ICP tree structure, but this is not a general result, and due to the different granularity of the trees. The tree construction step has the same complexity and should lead to a similar runtime for all algorithms. The additional smoothing step for smoothed NDT does not add significant runtime compared to the classical NDT map, and the runtime difference is mostly due to the different cell size. In the runtime evaluations of the next section, this tree construction step will not be included, as for a known target satellite this step is performed offline, prior to the registration of the source point clouds.

Table 2.4: Runtime of the tree/map construction step for the different algorithms, when evaluated on an Intel Xeon W-2135 Central Processing Unit (CPU).

	ICP search tree (approx. 20 points per cell)	classical NDT map (approx. cell size 10 cm)	smoothed NDT map (approx. cell size 7.5 cm)
construction time [ms]	29	20	22

2.5 Results

This section presents experiment campaigns for lidar tracking recorded at EPOS, and the results of the different tracking algorithms when evaluated on the test data.

2.5.1 Tracking of a slowly tumbling target

For the first experiment, an inspection and rendezvous flight towards a slowly tumbling satellite is simulated at EPOS. The target satellite is simulated to be on a near-circular polar orbit at an altitude of 500 km. The body frame of the target satellite is defined in Fig. 2.14. The initial inertia matrix of the target satellite is set to $I_{Tar} = \text{diag}(600, 500, 500)$ kg·m². It has a relatively slow tumbling motion directed mainly around its axis x_{Tar} . The tumbling motion is achieved by setting the initial angular velocity of the target with respect to the RTN frame expressed in the target coordinate frame to $\omega = (2, 0.2, 0)^T$ deg/s. The target satellite is oriented towards the positive normal direction (outwards the Earth), as shown in Fig. 2.15a.

Figure 2.14: Definition of the target satellite coordinate frame.

The trajectory of the chaser relatively to the target is presented in Fig. 2.15. The whole experiment lasts around 26 min. The experiment starts at a relative position of 17 m along the normal direction (z_{RTN}). During the first two minutes, an initial approach is performed until a distance of 15 m with 3 cm/s. After the second minute and until the 8th minute, the chaser

performs a partial fly-around maneuver of the target to inspect it from different angles. During this inspection phase, the chaser stays at a relative position of 15 m to the target, but with a different relative attitude. After the end of the fly-around, the approach is divided in three phases, as is observed in Fig. 2.15b: Until minute 15, the chaser approaches the target with a relative velocity of 2 cm/s, until a first hold point is reached at a relative distance of 8 m. From then onwards, an approach towards a relative distance of 4 m is performed with a relative velocity of 1 cm/s until minute 23. Finally, an approach up to 3 m distance is performed with the same velocity. Such a trajectory corresponds to a typical rendezvous scenario divided in fly-around for inspection, and approach, as presented in Section 1.2. It contains several hold points where it is chosen whether to continue the approach or not. For this experiment, it is not needed to perform a complete fly-around of the target, since with its tumbling motion, it will already be observed from different sides even if the chaser remains passive.

For visualization purposes of the attitude only, Euler angles are used. A common set of Euler angles are roll-pitch-yaw angles. However, they are not adapted here, because the pitch angle around 90 deg is located at the singularity for this convention. In this case, the tumbling motion is best described by another set of Euler angles: The evolution of the attitude of the target R in the RTN frame is decomposed in precession ϕ , nutation θ and spin (or intrinsic rotation) ψ . These angles are linked to the rotation matrix by:

$$R = R_Z(\psi)R_X(\theta)R_Z(\phi). \quad (2.66)$$

The evolution of these angles over time is presented on Fig. 2.15c. Two motions are identified: A spinning motion with a velocity of 2 deg/s, and a low frequency base oscillation of the two other angles. This corresponds to the precession component of the tumbling motion with a velocity of 0.2 deg/s.

For this experiment, the frame rate of the lidar is dynamically adapted, corresponding to the setting presented in Fig. 2.12b. Therefore, the frame rate of the lidar is below 1 Hz at larger distances, and increases to 3 Hz in close range. The raw point clouds contain more points, but after downsampling, the number of points per scan is approximately between 4500 and 8000 points. The experiment lasts around 24 min, during which 2602 point clouds are collected. Figs. 2.16a and 2.16c show a point cloud collected during the fly-around, and Figs. 2.16b and 2.16d one collected during the approach. On these point clouds, the rosette scan pattern of the Livox Mid-40 is clearly identifiable.

The point clouds contain a lot of erroneous measurements. For example, due to reflections of the laser ray on the golden MLI sheets covering the satellite (see Fig. 2.6), some parts of the front plate of the satellite disappear on the point cloud displayed in Fig. 2.16a. On the opposite, some blue points in Fig. 2.16c represent points that are “inside” the body of the satellite. These are erroneous measurements, and correspond to cases where the laser ray was reflected multiple times before reaching the emitter again. Another type of noise arises from the laser’s beam divergence. The laser being not perfectly directive, the measurements at surface edges are not necessarily “crisp”. This is observed in Fig. 2.16d. Due to the beam divergence, nearly all measurement points between the first yellow surface and the following blue surface are erroneous measurements: The real cylinder of the target satellite is much smaller in diameter than the measured points (see Fig. 2.6).

Figure 2.15: (a) Schematic representation of the fly-around and approach trajectory. (b) Position of the chaser relative to the target in RTN. (c) Attitude of the target in RTN, expressed as precession-nutation-spin angles.

An observation is also made concerning the appearance of the point clouds collected during the approach phase (Figs. 2.16b and 2.16d). Due to the target being observed frontally, the sides of the target such as the solar panels cannot be seen on the point clouds. Therefore, the point cloud lacks some 3D information: It mostly consists of two 2D planes (the yellow points forming the first plane, and the light blue points forming the second plane). Because they contain less 3D information than point clouds collected from the side, such point clouds are more difficult to register for the different tracking algorithms.

To evaluate the tracking error, the position and angular error of the pose estimation are analyzed. If $\bar{\rho}$ is the true relative position of the target and ρ the position estimated by the registration algorithm, the position error is the norm of the distance: $\|\bar{\rho} - \rho\|$. Likewise, we write \bar{R} for the real attitude of the target, and R the estimated attitude. The angular error is

Figure 2.16: Point clouds registered during the experiment, after background removal: (a) Front view and (c) side view of a point cloud collected during the fly-around phase. (b) Front view and (d) side view of a point cloud collected during the approach phase.

defined as the usual angular distance function between two rotations, and is defined by:

$$d(R, \bar{R}) = \arccos \left(\frac{\text{trace}(R^T \bar{R}) - 1}{2} \right). \quad (2.67)$$

Remark: From (2.36), we observe that this definition is equivalent to $d(R, \bar{R}) = \|R \ominus \bar{R}\|$.

The compared angular error of the three tracking algorithms is shown in Fig. 2.17a, and the position error in Fig. 2.17b. All trackers are able to keep track of the target's pose over the full rendezvous scenario. The smoothed NDT tracker has a maximal angular error of 3.11 deg and an average error of 1.48 deg. It is more precise than ICP and classical NDT, which have a maximum error of 7.33 deg and 4.52 deg, and an average angular error of 2.26 deg and 1.74 deg, respectively. In particular, around minute 20, the ICP tracker presents a spike in the attitude error, before this error is corrected in the following time steps.

The position error is also smaller in average for smoothed NDT compared to the two other methods. The maximum position error is reached around minute 1 for all algorithm, due to a relatively abrupt re-orientation of the satellite when starting the approach. This maximum error is of 10.5 cm for ICP, 13.4 cm for classical NDT, and 10.8 cm for smoothed NDT. During the approach, for all methods, the position error then decreases from around 6 cm to nearly

Figure 2.17: Compared results of ICP, NDT and smoothed NDT for tracking a slowly tumbling target satellite: (a) Absolute angular error of the tracking; (b) Absolute position error; (c) Runtimes (on an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU), including downsampling step; (d) Number of iterations.

1 cm, until it increases again around a 3 cm in the end, when the chaser is at 3 m distance to the target. At the end of the approach, the lidar sensor is at less than 1 m from the closest surface of the target satellite, so that the target is only partially in the lidar’s field-of-view. This might explain that the position error slightly increases. Overall, smoothed NDT also has the lowest average position error: it is of 2.45 cm, while it is of 3.01 cm for ICP, and 3.13 cm for classical NDT.

Figs. 2.17c and 2.17d present the distribution of the runtime and number of iterations of all algorithms. The runtime includes the pre-processing step consisting in downsampling the source point cloud with a voxel grid. On these boxplots, the boxes filled with color represent the data within the first and third quartile of the distribution, while the whiskers extend between the 5th and 95th percentiles. Outliers outside these percentiles are marked with crosses. Finally, the orange line inside each box represents the median value.

When evaluated on the Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU, ICP has a median runtime of 47 ms (Fig. 2.17c). Both NDT variants are significantly faster. Classical NDT has a median runtime of 20 ms, and smoothed NDT of 18 ms. This difference in runtime is partly due to the fact that ICP requires more iterations than NDT to converge. The median number of iterations for ICP is of 39, while it is of 18 for classical, and 17 for smoothed NDT (Fig. 2.17d). The distribution of the number of iterations also justifies the setting for the termination criteria to maximum 80 iterations for ICP and 30 for both NDT variants.

2.5.2 Tracking of a fast tumbling target

For this second experiment, we consider a similar fly-around and approach trajectory as in the previous experiment, but with a faster tumbling motion of the target satellite. For space objects, a “fast” tumbling motion corresponds to angular rates of several degrees per second. While this might appear slow, such an angular rate is challenging if it is needed to perform de-tumbling, or other robotic operations to service the target spacecraft. For example, after a failure of its attitude control, the Earth observation satellite ENVISAT had an angular rate increasing up to 3 deg/s over the years, before decreasing again [221]. In this experiment, the angular rate of the target satellite will be around 5 deg/s.

The initial inertia matrix of the target satellite is again set to $I_{Tar} = \text{diag}(600, 500, 500)$ kg·m², but the initial angular velocity of the target with respect to the RTN frame expressed in the target coordinate frame is $\omega = (5, 1, 0)^T$ deg/s. This leads to a tumbling motion of the target in the RTN frame, as schematically represented in Fig. 2.18a.

The overall trajectory, presented on Fig. 2.19a starts directly at a relative distance of 15 m: Between minutes 2.5 and 7, a fly-around at a steady distance of 15 m to the target is performed. Starting from minute 8, the approach is started with 2 cm/s first towards the intermediate hold point at 8 m, then with 1 cm/s towards the rendezvous point at 3 m.

The evolution of the precession, nutation and rotation angles defined in (2.66) over time is presented on Fig. 2.19b. On this plot, two motions are identified. The first is a clear spinning motion of the target around its axis x_{RTN} with a rate of 5 deg/s. The second is the ground frequency of the precession and nutation angles after ignoring the high frequency periodic motion. This frequency of 1 deg/s corresponds to a precession movement of the target around the axis z_{RTN} .

Figure 2.18: (a) Schema of the target attitude and its tumbling motion for this experiment, expressed relatively to the RTN frame. (b) Point cloud collected during the approach phase.

Figure 2.19: (a) Position of the chaser relative to the target in RTN. (b) Attitude of the target in RTN, expressed as precession-nutation-spin angles.

This time, the lidar is configured with a constant frame rate of 1 Hz. This enables to analyze the effect of a fast tumbling motion coupled with a low framerate of the sensor. This effect is relevant in practice if considering a space-grade lidar sensor with a lower framerate than the automotive sensor used for the tests. The point cloud density for this setting was presented in Fig. 2.12a. After downsampling, each point cloud contains between 5000 and 15 000 points. Because of the relative motion of the target during the scan time, the point clouds are blurred, as shown in Fig. 2.18b. This dataset contains 1390 point clouds, recorded over approximately 23 minutes. Due to the faster motion between two point clouds, all three methods require more iterations to converge. Therefore, for this experiment, the maximum number of iterations for ICP is set to 120, while it is increased to 40 for both NDT versions. The other tuning parameters are identical to the ones presented in Table 2.3.

The results of the tracking are presented on Fig. 2.20. Compared to the previous experiment,

the angular error of the tracking algorithms is higher, due to the faster tumbling movement of the target. From Fig. 2.20a, it is seen that ICP has a mean angular error of 3.88 deg over the experiment, but with high errors towards the end of the experiment, when both satellites are close to each other. The maximum angular error of ICP tracking reaches 10.50 deg. Likewise, classical NDT leads to a mean angular error of 3.86 deg, with a peak at 14.67 deg at the end of the experiment. For both methods, the tracking algorithm recovers from these errors and converges towards a better estimate in the next steps. On the contrary, smoothed NDT shows to be a more consistent estimator of the target attitude, with a mean angular error of 3.50 deg and a maximum angular error of 5.56 deg.

The difference in the attitude estimation error compared to previous experiment are explained by two factors: First, the relative rotational motion being faster, the difference between the attitude at the previous scan and at the current scan is more important (around 5 deg due to the frame rate of 1 Hz). Therefore, the initial guess for both tracking algorithms, which is the previous estimate, is further away from the optimal solution than in the previous experiment. In addition, the point clouds are blurred, and while the point cloud contains information about the state that the target satellite had during the whole duration of the scan, the ground truth with which the algorithm is compared is the ground truth at the end of the scan time. Taking into account the relative motion during the scan and these timing factors will be studied in detail in the next Chapter 3.

The average position error is lowest for smoothed NDT, with an average error of 1.87 cm. On the contrary, the average position error for classical NDT is 2.83 cm, and it is 2.76 cm for ICP. The position error of smoothed NDT is always below 4 cm, and decreases to around 1 cm when approaching the target, before increasing again in close range, when the satellite is not fully in the lidar's field-of-view anymore. The position error for ICP shows higher variations and less stability. In particular, around the 20th minute of the experiment, the position error increases shortly to above 8 cm, before the tracker recovers.

Both the average runtime and number of iterations increases compared to previous experiment, mostly because the initial guess is further away from the previous solution and more iterations are needed to converge. In particular, the median and maximum execution times for ICP are of 124 ms and 387 ms respectively (Fig. 2.20c). The runtimes are lower for both classical and smoothed NDT, with median values of 44 ms and 40 ms, and maximum values of 117 ms and 118 ms, respectively. The number of iterations strongly increases, see Fig. 2.20d. The median number of iterations for ICP is of 78, justifying the need to increase the maximum number of iterations to 120. For both NDT variants, new termination criteria is set at 40 iterations. Classical NDT requires more iterations than smoothed NDT to converge in average, with a median value of 33 iterations for the first, and of 28 iterations for the latter.

2.5.3 Runtime evaluation on a Zynq 7000

An answer to the first research question, RQ1 (Section 1.6), should show how a point cloud tracking method is adapted for onboard implementation. Due to multiple factors (Section 1.4) onboard computers qualified for space usually have limited processing power. Therefore, we seek to evaluate the different algorithms on onboard representative hardware, to assess the implementability of these methods for space missions.

Figure 2.20: Compared results of ICP, NDT and smoothed NDT for tracking a fast tumbling target satellite: (a) Absolute angular error of the tracking; (b) Absolute position error; (c) Runtimes (on an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU), including downsampling step; (d) Number of iterations.

Various onboard computers exist for space, each with very different processing power [66, 67]. For more computationally intense tasks such as image or point cloud processing, Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) components and in particular System-On-Chips (SoCs) are becoming increasingly popular for space applications [67]. To increase the reliability of these SoCs, onboard computing concepts relying on hybrid and distributed computing have been developed [222, 223]. DLR is developing such an onboard computer, based on distributed computing with several AMD Zynq™ 7000 SoCs [223]. This onboard computer is a candidate computing platform for future DLR rendezvous missions. Therefore, the Zynq 7000 is used as a representative platform for runtime evaluations in this work. It comprises a CPU and an FPGA, but only one core of the CPU is used for pose tracking. While the FPGA could provide runtime acceleration, the CPU is preferred for its implementation ease and flexibility, leading to faster development iterations. For this evaluation, the C++ implementations of ICP and smoothed NDT are compiled for the ARM v7 architecture, and executed on the board illustrated in Fig. 2.21. The CPU installed on the Zynq SoC is a dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 MPCore.

Figure 2.21: AMD Zynq™ 7000 used as a representative onboard computing platform for runtime evaluations.

The runtime comparison is performed on the dataset of the first experiment, presented in Section 2.5.1. Due to the limited memory on the device, only a subset of 250 point clouds from the full trajectory is loaded, but this is sufficient to evaluate the runtime. The results of the runtime evaluation are presented in Table 2.5. The runtime is broken down in pre-processing time (downsampling) and registration time, which is the actual runtime of each method.

Compared to the runtime evaluation on a desktop computer equipped with an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU, both ICP and (smoothed) NDT are 20 to 30 times slower when evaluated on the onboard representative computing hardware. The difference in runtime between both methods is the same as previously observed: because it requires fewer iterations, smoothed NDT is faster than classical NDT, with an average total runtime including pre-processing of 391 ms for the first, and 416 ms for the second. This is significantly faster than ICP, which requires a total average runtime of 1200 ms. The voxel grid downsampling is identical for all methods, and has an average runtime of 30 ms, which is not preponderant for the total runtime.

Table 2.5: Runtime comparison of ICP, NDT and smoothed NDT when evaluated on the Zynq 7000 CPU for tracking a slowly tumbling target. Values are shown as mean $\pm 1\sigma$, where σ is the standard deviation.

algorithm	downsampling [ms]	registration [ms]	total [ms]
ICP	30 ± 1	1170 ± 574	1200 ± 574
classical NDT	30 ± 1	386 ± 156	416 ± 156
smoothed NDT	30 ± 1	361 ± 117	391 ± 117

2.5.4 Robustness evaluation

The robustness of a tracking algorithm is defined in various ways: Robustness to noise, to different scenarios, to varying sensors... Here, we are interested in the robustness of a tracking algorithm with respect to the precision of the initial estimate. The trackers evaluated being local optimization methods, an important property to measure their effectiveness is to quantify how close to the solution the initial estimate is required to be for the algorithm to converge towards the global optimum.

The region for which an algorithm converges is also called its “convergence basin”. In this case, the convergence basin is parametrized by two variables, the angular error and the position error of the initial estimate with respect to the solution. Characterizing the convergence basin of the methods will consist in determining the envelope of initial position and attitude errors which are acceptable, i.e, for which the tracking algorithm is able to recover the correct solution. Not only is this useful to better understand and compare the different trackers, it will also enable to determine how good an initial estimate is required to be when designing a pose initialization method in Chapter 4.

The envelope of initial errors for which each tracking algorithm cannot be known exactly, but a Monte-Carlo simulation enables to get a sense of the convergence properties of each algorithm. For this statistical evaluation, the 2602 point clouds from the dataset collected in the first experiment (Section 2.5.1) are used. The idea is to view the space of possible initialization errors as a 2D space, with x-axis representing the norm of the initial rotation error (2.67), and the y-axis the norm of the initial position error. This 2D space is then discretized in bins (θ_i, δ_j) with $i, j = 1, \dots, 10$ for this evaluation.

The procedure for the Monte-Carlo evaluation is the following: For each bin (θ_i, δ_j) , a certain number N_{mc} of point clouds are chosen at random from the dataset (here $N_{mc} = 100$). For each of these point clouds, the ground truth pose is $\bar{T} = (\bar{R}, \bar{\rho})$. A random pose $T_{init} = (R_{init}, \rho_{init})$ is generated such that $d(R, R_{init}) = \theta_i$ and $\|\bar{\rho} - \rho_{init}\| = \delta_j$. This means that an initial pose is generated, which has an attitude error of θ_i and a position error of δ_j compared to the ground truth. This initial pose is used as a guess for the registration algorithm, which then produces a refined pose $T_{res} = (R_{res}, \rho_{res})$. Finally, the result provided by the algorithm is considered as successful if the result pose is close enough to the ground truth, i.e., if the error is below an angular threshold θ_{max} and a position threshold δ_{max} :

- $d(R, R_{res}) \leq \theta_{max}$;

- and $\|\bar{\rho} - \rho_{res}\| \leq \delta_{max}$.

Based on the results of the tracking experiment in Section 2.5.1, a simple success criteria is defined: The registration is considered successful if the result has a position error below $\delta_{max} = 10$ cm, and an angular error below $\theta_{max} = 5$ deg.

For the Monte-Carlo evaluation, the maximum possible value set for the initial pose error is of 75 cm and 40 deg. Because of the high initial pose errors, the maximum number of iterations was set to 200 for all algorithms. The other tuning parameters are identical to Table 2.3. Following this procedure, the success rate of each algorithm (ICP, classical NDT and smoothed NDT) is evaluated for each bin, producing the heatmaps presented in Fig. 2.22. On these heatmaps, a green color represents a success rate close to 100%, while a red color indicates a success rate close to 0%. Thus, the convergence basin is interpreted as the green region on these plots: The wider the green region spreads, the more an algorithm is considered robust to errors in the initial pose estimate.

As expected, when both the initial position error and initial angular error is low (bottom left corner of the heatmaps), the success rate is high, and oppositely. For NDT, a larger cell size increases the robustness and convergence properties. In spite of classical NDT being tuned with a cell size of 10 cm compared to the cell size of 7.5 cm for smoothed NDT, the smoothed version has a larger convergence basin, as shown in Figs. 2.23a and 2.22c. Using the smoothed version instead of the classical version enables to effectively increase the robustness of the registration. In comparison, the heatmap of ICP (Fig. 2.22a) is similar to the one of smoothed NDT.

The heatmaps contain 100 bins, each of them corresponding to the evaluation of 100 point clouds. The detailed results of the Monte-Carlo evaluation are presented in Table 2.6. Because a fraction of the evaluations is unsuccessful, the mean errors are less representative, and the median values are used for presenting the errors in the table. Overall, smoothed NDT show to be the more precise algorithm, with a success rate of 67.12%, compared to 63.74% for ICP and 47.05% for classical NDT.

Table 2.6: Compared results of ICP, classical and smoothed NDT for the Monte-Carlo evaluation, when the maximum number of iterations is set to 200 for each algorithm.

method	median pos. error	median att. error	success rate (< 5 deg & 10 cm)	median num. iterations	median runtime
ICP	3.41 cm	2.36 deg	63.74%	170	157 ms
classical NDT	6.92 cm	3.85 deg	47.05%	61	49 ms
smoothed NDT	3.50 cm	2.21 deg	67.12%	65	52 ms

Still, it is observed that the required number of iterations for ICP to converge, with a median number of 170, is high, and close to the maximum number of iterations of 200. If the maximum number of iterations is further increased to 300, ICP is successful in 71.33% of the cases, while the success rate for smoothed NDT remains similar. The number of iterations is not the limiting factor for smoothed NDT. However, it is possible to adjust other tuning parameters for NDT, such as the cell size: Increasing the cell size leads to an increased robustness of the algorithm,

Figure 2.22: Robustness evaluation on the slow tumbling dataset. Heatmap representations of the convergence basins for: (a) ICP; (b) Classical NDT; (c) Smoothed NDT.

The maximum number of iterations is set to 200 for every algorithm, and a registration is considered successful if the result has a position error below 10 cm, and an attitude error below 5 deg.

but at the expense of precision. For example, if the cell size is increased from 7.5 cm, as it is the case for all experiments, to 10 cm, smoothed NDT will have a success rate of 73.66% for the Monte-Carlo evaluation. If high initial errors in the pose estimate are expected, such a tuning is to be preferred.

2.5.5 Discussion

For the two tracking experiments, all three algorithms have shown to be able to track the target over time. However, smoothed NDT is more precise in the evaluations, with lower average position and angular errors than classical NDT and ICP. It is also faster than ICP, and more robust than classical NDT. Compared to classical NDT, for which the cell size has to be chosen

sufficiently large for the algorithm to converge, the smoothing operation allows to reduce the cell size of smoothed NDT, while keeping better convergence properties than classical NDT. This leads to a better precision of smoothed NDT compared to classical NDT, and similar convergence properties as ICP, see Section 2.5.4.

The precision requirements formulated in the beginning for pose estimation during close range rendezvous, listed in Table 1.1, were of a maximum error of 5 deg and 1% of the distance. During proximity operations (grasping, docking), this lowers to 2 deg and 5 cm. For the attitude error, the requirement of 5 deg in close range is held for the smoothed NDT tracker for the first experiment (Fig. 2.17a), and only exceeded during one timestamp in the second experiment (Fig. 2.20a), when the tumbling motion of the target is faster. On the opposite, the ICP tracking exceed this requirement in both experiments, and classical NDT in the second experiment. The requirement of a position error below 1% of the relative range in close range, and then 5 cm, translates to the position error having to be lower than 5 cm when the inter-satellite distance is below 5 m, and below 1% of the range when the distance is higher. This requirement is fulfilled for classical and smoothed NDT in both tracking experiments (Fig. 2.17b and 2.20b), but not for ICP. In both experiments, the position error of ICP shows spikes above 5 cm in close range.

The main advantage of (smoothed) NDT compare to ICP is its significantly lower runtime. In all experiments, both the median and maximum runtime of the NDT variants are approximately three times lower than for ICP. When evaluated on possible onboard computing hardware in Section 2.5.3, this trend is confirmed. The smoothed NDT tracker finds a solution within approximately 390 ms, while ICP requires 1.2s to converge in average. In Section 1.4, we stated that an order of magnitude of the processing time available for finding a relative navigation solution is 1 s. While this requirements might be adapted depending on the mission scenario, the results indicate that NDT is adapted for real-time onboard processing, while the suggested ICP implementation might be problematic in this regard, for this computing hardware.

Compared to other applications of point cloud registration algorithms such as robotic or automotive applications, the point clouds collected during a rendezvous are smaller and more compact. On the one hand, the target point cloud is known in advance and the object of interest is naturally free of any disturbing background, making it more straightforward to get a rough estimate of the position, for example. On the other hand, with less context and background also comes less information. In particular, due to the point cloud being compact, estimating the attitude with precision becomes challenging. Some point clouds for example lack some 3D information (Fig. 2.16b). Also, the shape of the target satellite used in this work is mostly hexagonal, i.e., symmetrical: If the initial pose estimate is far away from the correct pose, the chances of converging towards a wrong local optimum (for example a rotation of around ± 60 deg due to the hexagonal shape) are high.

Both ICP and NDT require a certain number of tuning parameters to work adequately for this type of scenario, see Table 2.3. For all methods, down-sampling the point cloud with a voxel grid prior to the registration is essential. Additionally, the maximum point-to-point or point-to-cell distance enables to discard potential association mismatches, and had to be tuned for all three methods. For ICP, setting a high number of iterations was important to avoid too early stopping. On the contrary, even when the initial pose estimate error is high, (smoothed) NDT requires much less iterations to converge (Table 2.6).

Finally, compared to ICP, NDT has an additional parameter, the cell size, which has to

be tuned according to a trade-off: A higher cell size leads to a higher robustness and a wider convergence basin. This is illustrated in Fig. 2.23: If the cell size of smoothed NDT is decreased to 5 cm, the convergence basin is smaller (Fig. 2.23a), but it increases if the cell size is set to 10 cm (Fig. 2.23b). However, due to the loss in granularity when increasing the cell size, the precision of the registration result diminishes. When this parameter is tuned properly, smoothed NDT shows to be both a fast, precise and robust registration algorithm compared to classical NDT and ICP (Table 2.6).

Figure 2.23: Parameter variation for the robustness evaluation: Heatmap representations of the convergence basins for smoothed NDT with a different cell size compared to the initial tuning. (a) Cell size of 5 cm; (b) Cell size of 10 cm.

The maximum number of iterations is set to 20, and a registration is considered successful if the result has a position error below 10 cm, and an attitude error below 5 deg.

2.6 Chapter conclusions

This chapter introduced a new formulation of the NDT point cloud registration algorithm. A smoothing method is applied to the NDT voxel grid, which contains the parameters (mean and covariance) of the distribution of the target points within this voxel. This smoothing enables to effectively increase the algorithm’s convergence basin, i.e., the optimization process converges even when the initial estimate is further away from the correct solution. Interestingly, this smoothing operation comes at the cost of negligible processing time and is performed offline, so that the runtime during online registration is not increased.

A k-d tree representation of the NDT map is suggested, allowing for more flexibility in the implementation. While in classical NDT, the point cloud matching task is formulated as a likelihood maximization problem, we suggest a relaxed formulation of the cost function. This is coupled with an efficient formulation of the optimization problem, in the manifold of the rigid transformation group. The formulation allows for fast convergence within few iterations.

Smoothed NDT is applied to lidar based satellite pose tracking during rendezvous experiments performed at the EPOS facility. The experiments demonstrate the precision, robustness and efficiency of the proposed method, especially when compared to ICP and classical NDT. In particular, smoothed NDT shows to be approximately three times faster than ICP and able to track the target's satellite pose reliably, making it suitable for onboard implementation. A runtime evaluation on potential space computing hardware confirms the method's applicability to real-time onboard pose estimation. Classical NDT is fast, but requires a good initial estimate to converge. On the contrary, ICP is robust and precise, but usually slower than NDT.

We recall RQ1: *How are lidar-based tracking methods enhanced to achieve efficient, robust and precise pose tracking of a spacecraft in non-cooperative rendezvous scenarios ?* For this task, the smoothed NDT formulation shows to be suited, enabling simultaneously fast and reliable point cloud registration.

This chapter focused on the core of the registration algorithms themselves, showing that smoothed NDT is applicable to lidar based satellite pose tracking. The tracking method is able to follow the evolution of the relative pose over consecutive point clouds even when the target tumbles with an angular rate of 5 deg/s for a lidar frame rate of 1 Hz. However, in these cases, the point clouds are blurred, and the precision decreases. To meet all GNC precision requirements for close range operations, and further increase the precision of the navigation solution, a possibility is to filter the measurements over time instead of taking the raw results. Additionally, the motion induced blur of the point clouds can be accounted for. These improvements will be considered in Chapter 3.

Finally, the tracking algorithm is a local optimization method, which requires an initial estimate to converge. The task of pose initialization, i.e., finding an initial pose estimate, will be studied in Chapter 4.

Chapter 3

Invariant Extended Kalman Filter for motion estimation and compensation

Lidar tracking methods, such as the smoothed NDT algorithm, enable to efficiently and precisely track the pose of a spacecraft during rendezvous. However, scanning lidars have a relatively low frame rate. If the relative motion, and in particular the tumbling motion of the target satellite, is high, the point clouds will appear blurred. This leads to a loss in accuracy and reliability of the tracking, and to following research question:

RQ2: How is the robustness and precision of a lidar-based navigation system ensured in the case of a rapidly tumbling target spacecraft ?

The first solution is to consider the tracking algorithm not in isolation, but in combination with a navigation filter. To formulate an adequate filter for estimating the target's attitude, we suggest expanding the Invariant Extended Kalman Filter formalism to our use case. In addition, two strategies are investigated to compensate the motion blur: The first one relies in correcting the point clouds in a pre-processing step, based on the velocity estimates of the navigation filter. The second is a continuous-time formulation of the NDT algorithm. The use of both the filter and the motion compensation strategies enables to guarantee a reliable and accurate navigation solution even for rapidly tumbling targets. This is demonstrated in hardware-in-the-loop experiments at EPOS.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 3.1 details the model of relative spacecraft dynamics used for navigation. The linear and extended Kalman filter are presented in 3.2, before introducing the Invariant Extended Kalman Filter (IEKF) formalism and its extension to the case where the measurement is also in a Lie group. This leads to a formulation of a pose filter for relative spacecraft navigation presented in 3.3. In the following Section 3.4, the effect of motion blur is modeled, and two strategies introduced to compensate it and increase the tracking precision. This is validated by experiments performed at EPOS described in Section 3.5, before 3.6 concludes this chapter.

3.1 Relative spacecraft dynamics

For precise relative navigation, the dynamics of the relative motion must be modeled. This section describes the modeling for both the translational and rotational dynamics during space rendezvous. In this chapter, for conciseness of the notation, the coordinate frame associated with the target spacecraft is denoted by \mathcal{T} , and the one of the chaser by \mathcal{C} .

3.1.1 Position dynamics

For circular or near-circular orbits, a common formulation of the position dynamics are the so-called Hill equations [224]. If dealing with orbits with high eccentricities, other models should be considered [22], such as the Tschauner-Hempel equations [225].

During the far range phase of a rendezvous, an accurate model of the relative motion is needed, because measurements might be sparse and have a high uncertainty. On the contrary, during the close range phase, the relative position dynamic is slow compared to the expected precision and update rate of the navigation measurements, originating for example from the lidar. Therefore, in close range, it is less important to model the evolution of the relative dynamics with high precision [22].

The Hill equations [224] are here used to describe the evolution of the relative position during the rendezvous phase. We assume that the target is passive, i.e., that it does not perform maneuvers, while the chaser is subject to some control force (thrust) \mathbf{T}_C . The chaser mass is m_C . The position of the chaser relative to the target is denoted by $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{C/\mathcal{T}} = \boldsymbol{\rho}_C - \boldsymbol{\rho}_\mathcal{T}$. When expressed in the RTN frame, the evolution of the components x, y and z of this relative position is given by [20, 22]

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{x} - 2n\dot{y} - 3n^2x &= \frac{T_{C_x}}{m_C}, \\ \ddot{y} + 2n\dot{x} &= \frac{T_{C_y}}{m_C}, \\ \ddot{z} + n^2z &= \frac{T_{C_z}}{m_C},\end{aligned}\tag{3.1}$$

where $T_{C_x}, T_{C_y}, T_{C_z}$ are the components of the thrust applied to the chaser satellite in the RTN frame. The symbol $\dot{\square}$ represents the derivative with respect to time, and n is the mean motion of the orbit. The mean motion is the orbit's angular velocity. If T is the orbital period, the

mean motion is

$$n = \frac{2\pi}{T}. \quad (3.2)$$

A closed-form solution of these equations exists, called the Clohessy-Wiltshire equations [226]. Assuming that the control force \mathbf{T}_C is constant over a time interval Δt , the Clohessy-Wiltshire equations are, in matrix form [18, 22]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\rho}_{C/\mathcal{T}}(t + \Delta t) \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_{C/\mathcal{T}}(t + \Delta t) \end{pmatrix} = F_{CW}(\Delta t) \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\rho}_{C/\mathcal{T}}(t) \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_{C/\mathcal{T}}(t) \end{pmatrix} + G_{CW}(\Delta t) \mathbf{T}_C(t), \quad (3.3)$$

where

$$F_{CW}(\Delta t) = \begin{pmatrix} 4 - 3c & 0 & 0 & s/n & 2(1 - c)/n & 0 \\ 6(s - n\Delta t) & 1 & 0 & -2(1 - c)/n & (4s - 3n\Delta t)/n & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c & 0 & 0 & s/n \\ 3ns & 0 & 0 & c & 2s & 0 \\ 6n(c - 1) & 0 & 0 & -2s & -3 + 4c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -ns & 0 & 0 & c \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.4)$$

with $c = \cos(n\Delta t)$ and $s = \sin(n\Delta t)$, and

$$G_{CW}(\Delta t) = \frac{1}{mc} \begin{pmatrix} (1 - c)/n^2 & 2(n\Delta t - s)/n^2 & 0 \\ 2(s - n\Delta t)/n^2 & 4(1 - c)/n^2 - 3\Delta t^2/2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1 - c)/n^2 \\ s/n & 2(1 - c)/n & 0 \\ -2(1 - c)/n & 4s/n - 3\Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s/n \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.5)$$

3.1.2 Absolute attitude dynamics

To parametrize the attitude dynamics, the precise definition of coordinate frames is important. For $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}$ three coordinate frames, the angular velocity of frame \mathcal{A} with respect to frame \mathcal{B} , expressed in frame \mathcal{C} , is denoted $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}}^{\mathcal{C}}$. The corresponding cross-product matrix (see (2.28)) is

$$\Omega_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}}^{\mathcal{C}} = (\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}}^{\mathcal{C}})^\times. \quad (3.6)$$

We recall that the rotation matrix from \mathcal{A} to \mathcal{B} , i.e., which transforms a vector expressed in frame \mathcal{A} into a vector expressed in frame \mathcal{B} , is written as $R_{\mathcal{A}}^{\mathcal{B}}$.

Euler's equation

We assume a rigid satellite, and consider a fix inertial frame \mathcal{I} with respect to which the attitude of the satellite is described. For satellites in Earth orbit, this inertial frame is typically the Earth-centered inertial (ECI) frame. The coordinate frame of the satellite (either the chaser

or the target) is \mathcal{S} . The angular velocity of the satellite with respect to the inertial frame, expressed in the satellite's frame is $\omega_{\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{S}}$. The inertia matrix of the satellite expressed in the satellite frame is $J_{\mathcal{S}}$.

The evolution of the angular velocity is more easily described in the non-inertial satellite body frame. We write $\tau_{\mathcal{S}}$ the control torque applied to the satellite in the satellite body frame. Euler's equation for describing the undisturbed rigid body dynamics is [18]:

$$J_{\mathcal{S}}\dot{\omega}_{\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{S}} + \omega_{\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{S}} \times (J_{\mathcal{S}}\omega_{\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{S}}) = \tau_{\mathcal{S}}. \quad (3.7)$$

Dynamical system using attitude matrices

The evolution of the angular rate is dictated by equation (3.7). To represent the governing equations for the attitude dynamics, one has to choose a representation of the attitude. In this section, we will use the attitude matrix $R_{\mathcal{S}}^{\mathcal{I}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ to represent the attitude of the spacecraft respectively to the inertial frame.

The time derivative of the attitude matrix $R_{\mathcal{S}}^{\mathcal{I}}$ is obtained equivalently by:

$$\frac{dR_{\mathcal{S}}^{\mathcal{I}}}{dt} = \Omega_{\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{I}} R_{\mathcal{S}}^{\mathcal{I}} = R_{\mathcal{S}}^{\mathcal{I}} \Omega_{\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{S}}, \quad (3.8)$$

whether the angular velocity is applied in the origin or destination frame. Together, (3.7) and (3.8) form a dynamical system representing the absolute evolution of the attitude.

3.1.3 Relative attitude dynamics

Euler's equation is a model of the absolute rotational dynamics of each satellite. The relative attitude of the target with respect to the chaser is $R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{C}}$, and the angular velocity of the target with respect to the chaser, expressed in the chaser frame, is $\omega_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{C}}$. They are obtained from the absolute values by

$$R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{C}} = (R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{I}})^{-1} R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{I}}, \quad (3.9)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{C}} &= \omega_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{C}} + \omega_{\mathcal{I}/\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{C}} \\ &= R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{C}} \omega_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{T}} - \omega_{\mathcal{C}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{C}}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

During a rendezvous, it is assumed that the chaser's attitude and angular velocity ($R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{I}}, \omega_{\mathcal{C}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{C}}$) are known. These values originate from the satellite's Attitude and Orbit Control System (AOCS). Similarly to the position case, the chaser is controlled while the target is freely tumbling. The chaser's control torque is $\tau_{\mathcal{C}}$, while the target's control torques are zero: $\tau_{\mathcal{T}} = \mathbf{0}$. There are two common possibilities when modeling the attitude dynamics for space rendezvous. The first possibility consists in only estimating the absolute attitude and angular velocity of the target ($R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{I}}, \omega_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{T}}$) using (3.7) and (3.8). The absolute rotational dynamics of the chaser is either known [70, 120, 71, 72], or estimated as well [227–229], in which case two filters are combined. Afterwards, the relative dynamics are retrieved via (3.9) and (3.10).

The second possibility is to directly estimate the relative attitude and angular velocity. The model for the relative angular kinematics is derived from the absolute models (3.8) and (3.10), and is found in [230–232]. This enables to directly model the effect of a control torque applied on the chaser satellite. This relative attitude model is used for a pose estimation filter for relative navigation in [233]. However, the linearization of the relative angular velocity model is complex, and the torque is already accounted for in the chaser’s absolute navigation filter (which is part of the chaser’s AOCS), which is why relative navigation filters usually estimate the target’s absolute attitude [43], before retrieving the relative kinematics with (3.9) and (3.10). The same strategy will be applied in this chapter.

3.2 Kalman filtering

Filtering methods enable to estimate the state of a system under the presence of noise in the measurements, and in the propagation model. This section provides an overview of usual filtering techniques from the family of Kalman filters, serving as a basis to introduce a formulation of the Invariant Extended Kalman Filter (IEKF) for attitude estimation.

3.2.1 Linear Kalman filter

The Kalman filter [124] is a probabilistic estimator, accounting for noise in a system. The state is assumed to be an n -dimensional vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the control term $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^p$. The state is measured by an observable $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m$. The discrete-time Kalman filter supposes a linear model for the dynamics and the observation, sampled at discrete time steps denoted by subscript k , separated by a time Δt :

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_k = F_k \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + G_k \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{n}_k \\ \mathbf{y}_k = H_k \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{w}_k \end{cases}, \quad (3.11)$$

with $F_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $G_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$, and $H_k \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$. The state noise is represented by $\mathbf{n}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and the measurement noise $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$. These are modelled by centered Gaussian random variables with covariance matrices Q_d and R_d respectively, i.e., $\mathbf{n}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q_d)$ and $\mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R_d)$. The subscript d emphasizes the fact that these are discrete noise models.

Details on the noise modelling

The continuous-time state-noise is modelled by a centered Gaussian white noise \mathbf{n} with Power Spectral Density (PSD) Q . In discrete-time, \mathbf{n}_k is the integrated white noise over the period Δt , which is modelled by a centered Gaussian random variable with a covariance matrix $Q_d \approx Q \Delta t$ [125]. Likewise, the continuous-time model for the measurement noise \mathbf{w} is a white noise defined by its PSD R . The discrete noise is not the result of the integrated noise over the time period, but only of the noise sampling with a period Δt . This is why in discrete time, \mathbf{w}_k is modelled by a centered Gaussian random variable with a covariance matrix $R_d = R / \Delta t$ [125].

Prediction

The Kalman filter provides a state estimate denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$, and the covariance matrix of this estimate given by P_k . The procedure for the filter is commonly divided into two steps: Prediction and update. The result of the first step, before the update refinement, will be denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}$ for the state and $P_{k|k-1}$ for the covariance. The prediction is simply based on the model of the dynamics

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} = F_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1} + G_k \mathbf{u}_k \\ P_{k|k-1} = F_k P_k F_k^T + Q_d \end{cases} . \quad (3.12)$$

Update

The difference between the measure and the expected measurement is the innovation $\boldsymbol{\nu}_k$, given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_k = \mathbf{y}_k - H_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} . \quad (3.13)$$

This leads to a correction of the prediction according to

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + K_k \boldsymbol{\nu}_k \\ P_k = (I - K_k H_k) P_{k|k-1} \end{cases} , \quad (3.14)$$

where the K_k is the Kalman gain defined by

$$K_k = P_{k|k-1} H_k^T (H_k P_{k|k-1} H_k^T + R_d)^{-1} . \quad (3.15)$$

In the linear case, the Kalman filter is optimal in the sense that it minimizes the variance of the state estimation error [234, 125].

3.2.2 Extended Kalman filter

The EKF generalizes the Kalman filter (Section 3.2.1) to the case where the model for the dynamics and the observation is non-linear. The evolution model (3.11) becomes

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_k = f(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k) + \mathbf{n}_k \\ \mathbf{y}_k = h(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{w}_k \end{cases} , \quad (3.16)$$

where f, h are potentially non-linear functions. The Jacobians with respect to the state are denoted by

$$F_k = \frac{\partial f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k)}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}} , \quad H_k = \frac{\partial h(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1})}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}} . \quad (3.17)$$

The prediction and update steps make use of these Jacobians to reproduce the same steps as in the linear Kalman filter. The only two differences are that the prediction of the state (3.12) is based on the non-linear function

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} = f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k) , \quad (3.18)$$

and that the innovation term is computed by following expression instead of (3.13):

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_k = \mathbf{y}_k - h(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}). \quad (3.19)$$

While the original Kalman filter is the linear estimator that minimizes the mean-square error, the EKF is a linearization based on the computation of the Jacobians, and has mathematical optimality properties only in limited special cases [131]. Alternative methods such as the unscented Kalman filter [235] or the iterated Kalman filter [236] have been developed in order to achieve optimality or better robustness in case of high non-linearities. Yet, the EKF remains a widely used standard for state estimation in mobile robotics [126].

3.2.3 Invariant Extended Kalman Filter

The linear and extended Kalman filters assume that the state and observable are in a vector space. For attitude estimation however, the state and observable are in the rotation group $SO(3)$, which is a Lie group but not a vector space. As discussed in Section 1.5.1, a natural extension to the EKF in Lie groups is the Invariant Extended Kalman Filter (IEKF) [131, 132].

The original version of the IEKF assumes that the state vector \mathbf{x} is in a Lie group, and the measurement \mathbf{y} is in a vector group. For relative pose estimation, the measurements consist of a relative pose, i.e., a position and an attitude measurement. If considering the attitude dynamics separately, the attitude measurement is also in a Lie group, like the attitude state. Thus, the contribution of this section consists in extending the IEKF formulation to the case where the measurement is also in a Lie group, and in applying this filter to the problem of relative attitude estimation for space rendezvous.

Depending on how the error state is defined, the IEKF is defined in two ways, either right-invariant or left-invariant [131]. We will present here the equations for the right-invariant EKF, which is found to be more robust to noise than the left-invariant version [133, 134]. Confusingly, the right-invariant EKF is associated with the left \oplus and \ominus operators defined in (2.39) and (2.40). From this perspective, the naming in the field is not homogeneous yet.

Evolution model of the right invariant EKF

Let \mathcal{F} be a Lie group with associate Lie algebra (tangent vector space) \mathbb{R}^n , and \mathcal{G} a second Lie group with associated Lie algebra \mathbb{R}^m . Let $x \in \mathcal{F}$ be the state, and $y \in \mathcal{G}$ be the observable. The control term is $u \in \mathcal{U}$. We consider the evolution model $f : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ and the observation function $h : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$.

We consider a random process noise $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ directly applied in the tangent space of the state. Likewise, the measurement noise $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is applied in the vector space of the observable. As previously, when expressed in discrete time, these random variables are assumed to follow a centered normal distribution, i.e., $\mathbf{n}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q_d)$ and $\mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R_d)$. The evolution model (3.16) becomes

$$\begin{cases} x_k = \mathbf{n}_k \oplus f(x_{k-1}, u_k) \\ y_k = \mathbf{w}_k \oplus h(x_k) \end{cases}. \quad (3.20)$$

We note here that both \oplus operators in (3.20) are not necessarily equivalent if \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are different. The first one is a function $\oplus : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$, and the second $\oplus : \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$.

However, to keep a light notation, we keep the same symbol for both operators, exactly like a “+” operator is used for additions in vector spaces of different dimensions.

Prediction

Having f and g operating on Lie groups, it is possible to define their (left) Jacobians on Lie groups according to (2.41):

$$F_k := \frac{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} f(\hat{x}_{k-1}, u_k)}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} \hat{x}_{k-1}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \quad (3.21)$$

and

$$H_k := \frac{\partial^{\mathcal{G}} h(\hat{x}_{k-1})}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} \hat{x}_{k-1}} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}. \quad (3.22)$$

The prediction step is identical to the EKF case (3.18), which we re-write for completeness:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{x}_{k|k-1} = f(\hat{x}_{k-1}, u_k) \\ P_{k|k-1} = F_k P_k F_k^T + Q_d \end{cases}. \quad (3.23)$$

Update

The innovation is an element of \mathbb{R}^m , obtained as

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_k = y_k \ominus h(\hat{x}_{k|k-1}). \quad (3.24)$$

The state and covariance are updated by

$$\begin{cases} \hat{x}_k = (K_k \boldsymbol{\nu}_k) \oplus \hat{x}_{k|k-1} \\ P_k = (I - K_k H_k) P_{k|k-1} \end{cases}, \quad (3.25)$$

where the Kalman gain K_k is obtained as in (3.15).

Overall, the IEKF resembles very much an EKF implementation (Section 3.2.2), with the difference that the innovation is computed via the logarithm map instead of a subtraction, and the estimation incremented via the exponential map instead of an addition. This IEKF will be used in the next section to formulate a pose estimation filter for relative navigation.

3.3 Relative navigation filter

This section details the implementation of the relative navigation filter. The measurements for the filter are pose estimates. Because the position and attitude dynamics are decoupled, two separate filters are used. The position filter is implemented as a linear Kalman filter, while the attitude filter is an IEKF.

3.3.1 Position filter

For the position filter, the translation part of the pose measurement is the observable $\mathbf{y} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_{C/\mathcal{T}}$, where $\bar{\square}$ stands for a measurement. The state for the position filter corresponds to the stacking of the position and velocity

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\rho}_{C/\mathcal{T}} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_{C/\mathcal{T}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{y} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_{C/\mathcal{T}}, \quad (3.26)$$

and the control term is the force applied on the chaser $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{T}_C$.

With the discrete time formulation (3.3), together with (3.4) and (3.5), the evolution of the relative position state vector is directly in the form of a linear Kalman filter (Section 3.2.1). In addition, the observation matrix linking the state to the observable is

$$H_{CW} = \begin{pmatrix} I_3 \\ 0_3 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 3}. \quad (3.27)$$

3.3.2 Attitude filter

Discrete time evolution model

The objective of the attitude filter is to estimate the target absolute attitude and angular velocity $(R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{I}}, \boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{T}})$, assuming that these values are known for the chaser. For conciseness of the notation in the filter equations, we simply write

$$R = R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{I}}, \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{I}}^{\mathcal{T}} \quad \Omega = \boldsymbol{\omega}^{\times}. \quad (3.28)$$

The state of the attitude is the concatenation of the target attitude and angular velocity, it is $x = (R, \boldsymbol{\omega}) \in SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3$. Contrarily to the position dynamics, Euler's equation (3.7) is not a linear differential equation. The target's attitude is assumed to be uncontrolled, so that the control torque is null. From (3.8) and (3.7), the continuous time dynamics of this state is

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dR}{dt} = R\boldsymbol{\omega}^{\times} = (R\boldsymbol{\omega})^{\times} R \\ \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}}{dt} = J_{\mathcal{T}}^{-1}(J_{\mathcal{T}}\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}) \end{cases}. \quad (3.29)$$

The dynamics for stepwise propagation are approximated by performing a linearization of the system. For discrete propagation steps $k, (k+1)$, spaced by a time step Δt , the linearization for the derivative of the attitude matrix would be

$$\frac{R_{k+1} - R_k}{\Delta t} = (R_k \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)^{\times} R_k + o(\Delta t). \quad (3.30)$$

However, writing this out leads to

$$R_{k+1} = (I_3 + \Delta t (R_k \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)^{\times}) R_k + o(\Delta t). \quad (3.31)$$

This expression, if propagated stewise, does not ensure that the rotation matrix R remains a valid rotation matrix over time when neglecting the higher order terms. Therefore, we will prefer

to express the time derivative of the attitude matrix as a derivative in the Lie group. With the definition (2.41), the derivative in the Lie group of R is

$$\frac{d^{SO(3)}R}{dt} = R\boldsymbol{\omega}. \quad (3.32)$$

Proof of (3.32). The derivative is identified using the Taylor expansion formula (2.43):

$$\begin{aligned} R(t + \Delta t) &= \left(\frac{d^{SO(3)}R(t)}{dt} \Delta t \right) \oplus R(t) + o(\Delta t) \\ &= \text{Exp}\left(\frac{d^{SO(3)}R(t)}{dt} \Delta t \right) R(t) + o(\Delta t). \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

With (3.31), we identify

$$\text{Exp}\left(\frac{d^{SO(3)}R(dt)}{dt} \Delta t \right) = I_3 + \Delta t (R(t)\boldsymbol{\omega}(t))^\times + o(\Delta t). \quad (3.34)$$

From the Taylor expansion of Exp (2.45), we thus identify

$$\frac{d^{SO(3)}R(t)}{dt} = R(t)\boldsymbol{\omega}(t). \quad (3.35)$$

□

The advantage of the formulation (3.32) is that the linearization writes

$$\begin{aligned} R_{k+1} &= \text{Exp}(\Delta t R_k \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) R_k + o(\Delta t) \\ &= R_k \text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) + o(\Delta t). \end{aligned} \quad (3.36)$$

The last line is obtained making use of following property, relying on the adjoint definition in Lie groups [209, 207].

Property 3 (Adjoint equality in $SO(3)$). *Let $R \in SO(3)$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, we have*

$$\text{Exp}(R\boldsymbol{\theta})R = R\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (3.37)$$

Right-multiplying this expression by R^T , and taking the logarithm, the adjoint equality is also useful under the following form:

$$R\boldsymbol{\theta} = \text{Log}(R\text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta})R^T). \quad (3.38)$$

We refer to [207] for a proof of (3.37). Now, if a linearization is performed, the stepwise propagation (3.36) will ensure a valid rotation matrix at every time step.

Likewise, the Taylor expansion of the angular acceleration yields

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_k + \Delta t J_{\mathcal{T}}^{-1}(J_{\mathcal{T}}\boldsymbol{\omega}_k \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) + o(\Delta t). \quad (3.39)$$

The evolution of the attitude discrete-time system will be approximated by neglecting the higher order terms of the expansions (3.36) and (3.39). Under this assumption, the discrete time model of the attitude dynamics is

$$\begin{cases} R_{k+1} = R_k \text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_k + \Delta t J_{\mathcal{T}}^{-1}(J_{\mathcal{T}}\boldsymbol{\omega}_k \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) \end{cases}. \quad (3.40)$$

IEKF formulation

The attitude filter is formulated as an IEKF. The state is $x = (R, \boldsymbol{\omega}) \in \mathcal{F}$, where $\mathcal{F} = SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3$ is a Lie group. Eq. (3.40) describes the discrete time evolution of the state in the absence of noise. As such, it defines the function $f : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ of the IEKF formalism (section 3.2.3):

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k). \quad (3.41)$$

The observable is the relative attitude, i.e., $y = R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{C}}$. Therefore, the measurements are also in a Lie group, which is $\mathcal{G} = SO(3)$. The observation function h links a measurement $y_k \in \mathcal{G}$ to the state x_k in the absence of noise. This function is expressed in terms of the absolute attitude R_k which composes the state x_k using (3.9):

$$\begin{aligned} y_k &= h(x_k) \\ &= (R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{C}})_k \\ &= (R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{T}})^{-1}_k R_k, \end{aligned} \quad (3.42)$$

where the attitude $R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{T}}$, which is the absolute attitude of the chaser, is known for each timestamp.

Jacobians of the IEKF

The Jacobian of the state evolution (3.21) is more conveniently expressed at the time step $(k+1)$ for simplifying index notations. It yields:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{k+1} &= \frac{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} f(x_k)}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} x_{k+1}} \\ &= \frac{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} (R_{k+1}, \boldsymbol{\omega}_{k+1})}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} (R_k, \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_{k+1}}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k} & \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_{k+1}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} \\ \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{k+1}}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k} & \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_{k+1}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.43)$$

Following property will be useful for computing the individual derivatives of this expression:

Property 4 (Useful derivatives in $SO(3)$). *For $R, Q \in SO(3)$ and $g : SO(3) \rightarrow SO(3)$, we have*

$$\frac{\partial^{SO(3)} g(R) Q}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} = \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} g(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R}, \quad (3.44)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial^{SO(3)} Q g(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} = Q \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} g(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R}. \quad (3.45)$$

Proof of Property 4. The first expression is directly obtained from the limit definition of the differential (2.41):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} g(R) Q}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} &= \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{Log} \left(g(\epsilon \oplus R) Q (g(R) Q)^T \right)}{\epsilon} \\ &= \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{Log} \left(g(\epsilon \oplus R) g(R)^T \right)}{\epsilon} \\ &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} g(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.46)$$

The second expression is derived from the adjoint equality. The limit definition is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} Q g(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} &= \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{Log} \left(Q g(\epsilon \oplus R) g(R)^T Q^T \right)}{\epsilon} \\ &= \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{Q \text{Log} \left(g(\epsilon \oplus R) g(R)^T \right)}{\epsilon} \quad (\text{using (3.38)}) \\ &= Q \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} g(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.47)$$

□

Coming back to the Jacobian F_{k+1} of (3.43), we now identify each component. The first term writes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_{k+1}}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k} &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k \text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k} \\ &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k} \quad (\text{using (3.44)}) \\ &= \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{Log}(\text{Exp}(\epsilon) R_k (R_k)^T)}{\epsilon} \\ &= I_3. \end{aligned} \quad (3.48)$$

The second term is obtained making use of the chain rule [207] for the derivative on Lie groups:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_{k+1}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k \text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} \\ &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} (R_k \text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k))}{\partial^{SO(3)} (\text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k))} \cdot \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} (\text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k))}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} \\ &= R_k \cdot \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} (\text{Exp}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k))}{\partial (\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)} \cdot \frac{\partial (\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} \quad (\text{using (3.45)}) \\ &= R_k D_{\text{Exp}}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) \Delta t. \end{aligned} \quad (3.49)$$

The notation D_{Exp} represents the derivative of the exponential map in $SO(3)$. This derivative has an analytical expression, which is derived in [209, 207]. For $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ with $\theta = \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$, the

expression of the derivative of the exponential map is

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{Exp}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) &:= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{Exp}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \\ &= I_3 + \frac{1 - \cos \theta}{\theta^2} \boldsymbol{\theta}^\times + \frac{\theta - \sin \theta}{\theta^3} (\boldsymbol{\theta}^\times)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3.50)$$

This is valid for $\theta \neq 0$. When $\theta = 0$, we have $D_{\text{Exp}}(\mathbf{0}) = I_3$.

The derivative of the second line of F_k in (3.43) are obtained by classical differentiation, so that the complete Jacobian is

$$F_{k+1} = \begin{pmatrix} I_3 & R_k D_{\text{Exp}}(\Delta t \boldsymbol{\omega}_k) \Delta t \\ 0_3 & I_3 + \Delta t J_{\mathcal{T}}^{-1} ((J_{\mathcal{T}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)^\times - (\boldsymbol{\omega}_k)^\times J_{\mathcal{T}}) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.51)$$

The Jacobian of the observation (3.22) is

$$\begin{aligned} H_k &= \frac{\partial^{\mathcal{G}} h(x_k)}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} x_k} \\ &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} (R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{I}})^{-1} R_k}{\partial^{\mathcal{F}} (R_k, \boldsymbol{\omega}_k)} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} (R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{I}})^{-1} R_k}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_k} & \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} (R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{I}})^{-1} R_k}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_k} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} (R_{\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{I}})^{-1} & 0_3 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.52)$$

With the propagation model (3.40) and the Jacobians (3.51) and (3.52), the equations of the attitude IEKF are complete. Once formalized, the formulation of the filter is relatively simple and compact, with the prediction and update steps being (3.23) and (3.25). Together, the position and attitude filters of this section form a complete pose estimation filter for relative spacecraft navigation.

3.4 Motion blur compensation

It was observed in the experiments of Section 2.5.2 that a fast relative motion leads to blurred point clouds, reducing the accuracy of point cloud registration. This section presents two different strategies to compensate motion blur when using a scanning lidar to approach a tumbling spacecraft. The first strategy consists in correcting the point cloud in a pre-processing step, based on the velocity estimates of the filter. The second strategy is a continuous-time formulation of the smoothed NDT algorithm, aiming at accounting for motion blur as part of the registration problem.

3.4.1 Motion blur model

A scanning lidar is subject to motion, blur, i.e., a deformation of the point cloud due to the motion of either the sensor or the scene during the duration of the scan. This effect becomes

particularly relevant when the relative motion between the sensor and the scene is important. In particular, the degradation of the quality of the tracking was observed for a fast tumbling target, with a rate of 5 deg/s, in Section 2.5.2.

We consider a point \mathbf{z} located on the structure of the target satellite, corresponding to an element of the spacecraft. We assume that the target satellite is rigid. The point, when expressed in the target coordinate frame, is constant over time and denoted by $\mathbf{z}^{\mathcal{T}}$. In the lidar coordinate frame \mathcal{L} , the point's coordinates are variable with time, and expressed as $\mathbf{z}^{\mathcal{L}}(t)$. Both representations are simply linked by a coordinate frame change

$$\mathbf{z}^{\mathcal{T}} = T_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t) \cdot \mathbf{z}^{\mathcal{L}}(t), \quad (3.53)$$

where $T_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}$ is the rigid transformation from the lidar to the target coordinate frame. Because this transformation changes over time, we explicitly marked the dependency of this transformation to the time t . Dividing into rotation and translation components, (3.53) becomes

$$\mathbf{z}^{\mathcal{T}} = R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t) \mathbf{z}^{\mathcal{L}}(t) + \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{L}/\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t), \quad (3.54)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{L}/\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{T}}$ is the position of the lidar with respect to the target, expressed in the target coordinate frame.

From (3.54), it is clear that depending on the time at which a point is scanned, its position in the lidar coordinate frame is different. Because during a scan, all points are captured by the sensor at a different time, the rigid point cloud representing the target when expressed in the target coordinate frame is distorted when expressed in the lidar coordinate frame, which is the frame in which the scan is received. Another way to express this is that strictly speaking, there is no rigid transformation $T_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}$ solution to the pose estimation problem, because this transformation varies during the duration of the scan.

3.4.2 Point cloud deblurring

Consider a point cloud that is registered in the time interval $[t^{k-1}, t^k]$. The point cloud is received in the lidar coordinate frame as a collection of 3D points $(\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}})_{1 \leq i \leq N_z}$. Additionally, each point has an individual timestamp $t_i \in [t^{k-1}, t^k]$. If all points were expressed at the same time, from (3.54), it could be assumed that a rigid transformation is solution to the point cloud registration problem.

The goal of point cloud deblurring is to transform the point cloud in a pre-processing step, in order to express all points at the same time. In this case, all points will be transformed to extrapolate their position at the end time of the scan, t^k . It is chosen to transform the points of the scan to the final time, and not the start time, so that the pose solution $T_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}$ corresponds to a more recent estimate, namely the estimate at t^k .

For $1 \leq i \leq N_z$, we define the time difference with respect to the end of the scan $\Delta t_i = t^k - t_i$. The position of $\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}$ at t^k is linked to its position at t_i by expressing (3.54) at these two different times, remarking that the left-hand side of the equation remains constant:

$$R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t^k) \mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) + \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{L}/\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t^k) = R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t_i) \mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) + \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{L}/\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t_i), \quad (3.55)$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) &= R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t^k)^{-1} \left(R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t_i) \mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) + \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{L}/\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t_i) - \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{L}/\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t^k) \right) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) + R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t^k)^{-1} R_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{T}}(t_i) \left(\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) - \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) \right) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) + R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) - \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.56)$$

We perform a first order approximation, i.e., assume a constant velocity and angular rate during the duration of the scan. From (3.36) we have

$$R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i)^{-1} \simeq \text{Exp}(\Delta t_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k)), \quad (3.57)$$

so that a linearization of (3.56) writes

$$\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) = \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k) + \text{Exp}(\Delta t_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k)) \left(\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) - \left(\boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) - \Delta t_i \mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i) \right) \right). \quad (3.58)$$

Here, $\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}}$ is the velocity of the target with respect to the lidar, expressed in the lidar coordinate frame.

To transform the point cloud according to (3.58), the relative position, velocity and angular velocity must be known. The true values are not known, but the estimates are provided by the filter. Therefore, the approximate transformation is performed using the filter predictions for the time stamp t_k , which are denoted by $(\hat{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}})_{k|k-1}$, $(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}})_{k|k-1}$ and $(\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{L}}^{\mathcal{L}})_{k|k-1}$.

The deblurring enables to transform the point cloud $(\mathbf{z}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t_i))_{1 \leq i \leq N_z}$ into the predicted point cloud $(\hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{\mathcal{L}}(t^k))_{1 \leq i \leq N_z}$, where all points are expressed at the same time. This is schematically represented in Figure 3.1.

Care has to be taken in the coordinate transformation to obtain these values. These values are first expressed in the chaser frame, before being transformed from the chaser to the lidar frame. This last transformation is trivial because it is constant. The relative angular velocity in the chaser frame is obtained from (3.10). The position filter delivers a position and velocity estimate expressed in the RTN frame. While the position is directly rotated in the chaser frame with the rotation matrix $R_{RTN}^{\mathcal{C}}$, which is assumed to be known, the velocity is transformed in the chaser frame according to

$$\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{C}} = R_{RTN}^{\mathcal{C}} \mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{C}}^{RTN} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_{RTN/\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{C}} \times \boldsymbol{\rho}_{\mathcal{T}/\mathcal{C}}^{\mathcal{C}}. \quad (3.59)$$

Tracking in combination with deblurring

The overall logic when combining the tracking algorithm with deblurring is presented in Figure 3.2. When a new point cloud is received, the filter estimates are used to perform motion correction of the point cloud according to (3.58). This corrected point cloud is then processed with a registration algorithm, for example the smoothed NDT. In Chapter 2, the previous result of the tracking algorithm was used to initialize the tracker for each new point cloud (see Figure 2.13). Instead, with a filter, the filter prediction is directly used as an initial estimate for the tracker. The prediction being, in general, closer to the real value than the previous result, this enables to shorten the number of iterations required for the tracker to converge.

Figure 3.1: Schema of the point cloud deblurring principle. The initial point cloud (left) was captured with a frame rate of 1 Hz, for a tumbling motion of 10 deg/s. After deblurring and expressing all points at the final time t^k , the point cloud is more crisp (right).

Figure 3.2: Schema of the feedback loop for point cloud deblurring. The filter estimate is used to correct the point cloud in a pre-processing step. Additionally, this estimate is used as an initial guess for the NDT registration.

3.4.3 Continuous-time NDT

With the deblurring logic of Figure 3.2, motion compensation is performed as a pre-processing step. An alternative discussed in the state-of-the art presentation (Section 1.5.1), is to perform motion compensation as part of the registration algorithm. In this case, the relative motion during the scan is estimated simultaneously to the relative pose of the target.

When deblurring is performed as a pre-processing step, the previous motion estimation is used to correct the motion blur observed in the current point cloud. However, the previous motion estimation might be outdated or not sufficiently precise. An advantage of estimating the motion as part of the registration algorithm is that information contained in the current scan is used to account for motion blur, and not information of the previous scans.

Objective function

The approach in this work for continuous-time registration is similar to the continuous-time ICP algorithm [113]. If a point cloud is collected during the time interval $[t^{k-1}, t^k]$, continuous-time ICP seeks to estimate two poses, T^{k-1} and T^k , which correspond to the poses at the initial and final time of the scan. However, from the result of the previous step which was incorporated in the filter, there is already a prediction for the pose at time t^{k-1} . This estimation is denoted by \hat{T}^{k-1} . To ensure consistency and help convergence, continuous-time ICP adds a penalty on the difference between \hat{T}^{k-1} and the pose T^{k-1} predicted for the current scan.

Differently from continuous-time ICP, we only estimate the final pose T^k , and assume that the pose at the beginning of the scan is \hat{T}^{k-1} . While fixing the initial pose is potentially less accurate in case of high-frequency movement, having to estimate only one pose instead of two is found to better converge in our use case. Additional differences compared to continuous-time ICP is that we use the smoothed NDT as underlying registration algorithm, and derive an explicit formula of the gradients for efficiently solving the optimization problem.

Identically to the assumption made for point cloud deblurring, it is assumed that the dynamics is linear, i.e., that the velocity and angular velocity during the duration of the scan are constant. The pose at a time $t_i \in [t^{k-1}, t^k]$ is linearly interpolated as

$$T_i = \text{interp}(\hat{T}^{k-1}, T^k, u_i), \quad (3.60)$$

where u_i is the interpolation coefficient

$$u_i = \frac{t_i - t^{k-1}}{t^k - t^{k-1}}. \quad (3.61)$$

We will define the function “interp” in the next paragraph. First, to motivate its use, we express the cost function of the continuous-time registration algorithm. The objective is similar to the smoothed NDT cost function defined in (2.24). The continuous-time registration seeks to find the final pose T^k that minimizes

$$s_{CT}(T^k) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} ((T_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)})^T C_{\eta(i)}^{-1} ((T_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)}). \quad (3.62)$$

This cost function is dependent of T^k , because T_i is a function of T^k in (3.60).

Interpolation in $SE(3)$

We will now define the function “interp”. We decompose the poses in attitude and translation components, and write $T_i = (R_i, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i)$ for the interpolated pose, $\hat{T}^{k-1} = (\hat{R}^{k-1}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\rho}}^{k-1})$ for the initial pose, and $T^k = (R^k, \boldsymbol{\rho}^k)$ for the final pose. The translation component of “interp” is obtained by linear interpolation as

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}_i = (1 - u_i)\hat{\boldsymbol{\rho}}^{k-1} + u_i\boldsymbol{\rho}^k. \quad (3.63)$$

The attitude component is obtained by Spherical Linear Interpolation (SLERP) interpolation, so that we write

$$R_i = \text{slerp}(\hat{R}^{k-1}, R^k, u_i). \quad (3.64)$$

For general rotation matrices R_0, R_1 and $u \in [0, 1]$, SLERP is expressed as follows using the \oplus (2.39) and \ominus (2.40) operators:

$$\text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u) = (u(R_1 \ominus R_0)) \oplus R_0. \quad (3.65)$$

Proof of (3.65). This exact expression of SLERP was not found elsewhere, which is why we provide a proof of the formula. However, a very similar formulation of SLERP is found in [128], for the right multiplication:

$$\text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u) = R_0 \text{Exp} \left(u \text{Log} \left((R_0)^T R_1 \right) \right). \quad (3.66)$$

We will proceed to show that this definition is identical to (3.65). Using the adjoint equality (3.37), the previous expression re-writes

$$\text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u) = \text{Exp} \left(u R_0 \text{Log} \left((R_0)^T R_1 \right) \right) R_0. \quad (3.67)$$

We apply (3.38) with $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \text{Log} \left((R_0)^T R_1 \right)$, and $R = R_0$. This writes:

$$\begin{aligned} R_0 \text{Log} \left((R_0)^T R_1 \right) &= \text{Log}(R_0 (R_0)^T R_1 (R_0)^T) \\ &= \text{Log}(R_1 (R_0)^T). \end{aligned} \quad (3.68)$$

Injecting this in (3.67), we finally get

$$\text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u) = \text{Exp} \left(u \text{Log}(R_1 (R_0)^T) \right) R_0, \quad (3.69)$$

which is identical to (3.64) when writing out the \oplus and \ominus operators. \square

Differentiation of the interpolation in $SO(3)$

We are interested in the differentiation of an interpolated rotation (3.64) with respect to the final rotation R_1 . To this aim, we will first introduce a helpful derivative, the derivative of the Log map in $SO(3)$. Take $R \in SO(3)$, and let $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \text{Log}(R)$ and $\theta = \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|$. The expression for the derivative of the Log map is given by [209]

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{Log}}(R) &:= \frac{\partial \text{Log}(R)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R} \\ &= I_3 - \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\theta}^\times + \frac{1 - \cos \theta - \frac{1}{2} \theta \sin \theta}{\theta^2 (1 - \cos \theta)} (\boldsymbol{\theta}^\times)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3.70)$$

We consider the derivative of $\text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u)$ with respect to R_1 . Writing $Q = R_1 (R_0)^T$, this derivative writes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1} &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{Exp} \left(u \text{Log}(Q) \right) R_0}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1} && \text{(from (3.69))} \\ &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{Exp} \left(u \text{Log}(Q) \right)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1}. && \text{(using (3.44))} \end{aligned} \quad (3.71)$$

We make use of the chain rule [207] for the derivative on Lie groups to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{slerp}(R_0, R_1, u)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1} &= \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{Exp}(u \text{Log}(Q))}{\partial^{SO(3)} u \text{Log}(Q)} \cdot \frac{\partial u \text{Log}(Q)}{\partial^{SO(3)} Q} \cdot \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} Q}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1} \\
&= D_{\text{Exp}}(u \text{Log}(Q)) u D_{\text{Log}}(Q) \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1(R_0)^T}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_1} \\
&= u D_{\text{Exp}}(u(R_1 \ominus R_0)) D_{\text{Log}}(R_1(R_0)^T).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.72}$$

Gradient based optimization

We will apply the same optimization procedure for the continuous-time NDT cost function (3.62) then we did for smoothed NDT in Section 2.3.4. The only difference in the cost function is that this time, the residuals depend on the interpolated rotation. For $i = 1, \dots, N_z$, they write

$$\mathbf{r}_i = (T_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i) - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\eta(i)}, \tag{3.73}$$

so that the Jacobian of the residuals becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_i &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}_i}{\partial^{SE(3)} T^k} \\
&= \frac{\partial (T_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)}{\partial^{SE(3)} T^k} \\
&= \left(\frac{\partial (T_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R^k} \quad \frac{\partial (T_i \cdot \mathbf{z}_i)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}^k} \right) \\
&= \left(\frac{\partial R_i \mathbf{z}_i}{\partial^{SO(3)} R^k} \quad \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}_i}{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}^k} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.74}$$

Using the chain rule, the first term expands to

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial R_i \mathbf{z}_i}{\partial^{SO(3)} R^k} &= \frac{\partial R_i \mathbf{z}_i}{\partial^{SO(3)} R_i} \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} R_i}{\partial^{SO(3)} R^k} \\
&= -(R_i \mathbf{z}_i)^\times \cdot \frac{\partial^{SO(3)} \text{slerp}(\hat{R}^{k-1}, R^k, u_i)}{\partial^{SO(3)} R^k} \\
&= -u_i (R_i \mathbf{z}_i)^\times D_{\text{Exp}}(u_i (R^k \ominus \hat{R}^{k-1})) D_{\text{Log}}(R^k (\hat{R}^{k-1})^T).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.75}$$

The second part of the Jacobian, corresponding to the translation, is simply

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}_i}{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}^k} = u_i I_3. \tag{3.76}$$

Following the Gauss-Newton procedure, the increment to perform to minimize the cost function s_{CT} is the same as (2.54), which we recall here:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = -\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} J_i^T W_i J_i \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} J_i^T W_i \mathbf{r}_i \right). \tag{3.77}$$

By iteratively updating the pose with

$$T^k \leftarrow \epsilon \oplus T^k, \quad (3.78)$$

a solution to the continuous-time NDT formulation is found, corresponding to a local optimum.

Continuous-time NDT is inherently different from the motion compensation logic presented in Fig. 3.2. It assumes that the pose at the beginning of the scan is known, it is \hat{T}^{k-1} , which is delivered by the navigation filter. The algorithm searches for the pose at the end of the scan T^k , accounting for the distortion of the scan as part of the registration algorithm. The logic of continuous-time NDT is summarized in Fig. 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Schema of the feedback loop for continuous-time NDT. The filter estimate is used to set the pose at the initial time of the scan, while the optimization searches for the pose at the end of the scan time.

3.5 Results

This section presents and compares the results of the tracking methods combined with the navigation filter, when evaluated on test datasets recorded at EPOS. In particular, the improvement compared to the results presented in Chapter 2 for test cases involving a rapidly tumbling target spacecraft is analyzed.

3.5.1 Experiment setup

Compared navigation methods

The different navigation methods presented in this chapter are evaluated in the same way as in Chapter 2. The EPOS facility is used to generate realistic rendezvous trajectories during which the lidar captures scans containing the target mock-up. The overall setup of the facility, as well as the lidar integration, calibration and configuration are identical to the description made in Section 2.4. The only difference lies in the nature of the compared methods.

Differently from the previous chapter, where we analyzed the raw errors of the pose tracking algorithms, we will now analyze the error coming from the navigation filter, i.e., the error of the filtered pose estimate. In the following, for all methods, the pose estimation error will be the error of the navigation filter. Three setups are compared:

- **NDT + filter:** For comparison, the smoothed NDT algorithm introduced in Chapter 2 is evaluated in combination with the navigation filter. The difference with the setup

presented in the previous chapter is that at each step, the filter prediction is used as an initial estimate by the registration algorithm.

- **NDT + deblurring:** This is also the smoothed NDT algorithm combined with the feedback from the navigation filter, but additionally, the deblurring step presented in Section 3.4.2 is added. This logic, where deblurring is added in a pre-processing step, was illustrated in Fig. 3.2.
- **Continuous-time NDT:** The continuous-time variant of the smoothed NDT algorithm, introduced in Section 3.4.3. This continuous-time registration algorithm is also used in combination with the navigation filter to provide an initial estimate. The logic for this case was illustrated in Fig 3.3.

For all methods, the mention “smoothed” is omitted for conciseness, but we underline that these methods use the smoothed NDT variant. Also, all three methods work in integration with the navigation filter.

Importantly, we keep the same tuning parameters for smoothed NDT as in Chapter 2 to ensure a fair comparison. For all three methods, the tuning parameters of smoothed NDT are identical to the ones presented in Table 2.3.

Filter noise tuning

The navigation filter is configured with values for the state noise and measurement noise models, as well as the value of the initial covariance matrix. First, the amplitude of the measurement noise is inferred from the results of the previous chapter (Section 2.5). It has to be noted that the measurement noise of the smoothed NDT algorithm has to be estimated only from the high-frequency oscillations of the measurements, without adding an eventual moving bias or low-frequency error. From the results presented in Fig. 2.17, we coarsely estimate the measurement noise to:

- Amplitude of the position measurement noise: $\sigma_{meas}^{pos} = 1 \text{ cm}\sqrt{\text{s}}$;
- Amplitude of the attitude measurement noise: $\sigma_{meas}^{att} = 1.0 \text{ deg}\sqrt{\text{s}}$.

The PSD of the position measurement noise is $R^{trsl} = (\sigma_{meas}^{pos})^2 I_3$, and the PSD of the attitude measurement noise is $R^{rot} = (\sigma_{meas}^{att})^2 I_3$. We recall (see Section 3.2.1) that the discrete time covariance matrix of the measurement noise is dependent on the sampling time Δt , and given by $R_d = R/\Delta t$. This also explains the unit of the amplitudes (containing a $\sqrt{\text{s}}$). Intuitively, the higher the frequency of the measurements, the higher the measurement noise is. This is also observed experimentally in the previous chapter, Fig. 2.17: With the adaptive frame rate, the frame rate of the lidar increases during the experiment (because the chaser comes closer to the target), and in consequence, the amplitude of the high frequency oscillations of the pose measurement error increases.

Next, we set the state noise for the position and attitude filters. The general rule we followed for tuning these values was to define physically realistic values, representative of the drift to be expected between the propagation models and the real dynamics over time. This drift also

incorporates potential unknowns in the system, such as errors in the calibration of the control forces, errors in the AOCS providing the chaser's absolute attitude estimation, or an inaccurate estimation of the target's inertia matrix. The state noise is set with following values:

- Amplitude of the position state error: $\sigma_{state}^{pos} = 2 \text{ mm}/\sqrt{\text{s}}$;
- Amplitude of the velocity state error: $\sigma_{state}^{vel} = 2 \text{ mm}/\text{s}^{3/2}$;
- Amplitude of the attitude state error: $\sigma_{state}^{att} = 0.2 \text{ deg}/\sqrt{\text{s}}$;
- Amplitude of the angular velocity state error: $\sigma_{state}^{angvel} = 0.2 \text{ deg}/\text{s}^{3/2}$.

The PSD for the state error of the translational and rotational filters is then defined by

$$Q^{trsl} = \begin{pmatrix} (\sigma_{state}^{pos})^2 I_3 & 0_3 \\ 0_3 & (\sigma_{state}^{vel})^2 I_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad Q^{rot} = \begin{pmatrix} (\sigma_{state}^{att})^2 I_3 & 0_3 \\ 0_3 & (\sigma_{state}^{angvel})^2 I_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.79)$$

Similarly to the measurement noise amplitudes, the state error amplitudes exhibit units containing divisions by $\sqrt{\text{s}}$. As explained in Section 3.2.1, this is due to the fact that the discrete covariance matrix of the state noise is obtained from the PSD by $Q_d = Q\Delta t$. Intuitively, the longer the propagation time is, the higher the error between the model and the real system is expected to be.

Finally, the initial covariance matrix of both filters has to be set. The initial position and attitude errors to be expected when starting the tracking will only be the result of the next chapter, Section 4.5.3, once a pose initialization method is implemented. However, we anticipate the result here to define a coarse value of the position and attitude initialization errors to be expected. In the filter, the initial velocity and angular velocity is set to zero, so that the initial uncertainty on these parameters is defined by the range of relative velocities and angular velocities that are expected from the target. With a conservative guess, we set these values to:

- Standard deviation of the initial position estimation: $\sigma_0^{pos} = 10 \text{ cm}$;
- Standard deviation of the initial position estimation: $\sigma_0^{vel} = 5 \text{ cm/s}$;
- Standard deviation of the initial attitude estimation: $\sigma_0^{att} = 1.5 \text{ deg}$;
- Standard deviation of the initial angular velocity estimation: $\sigma_0^{angvel} = 5 \text{ deg/s}$.

The initial covariance matrices of both filters are finally set to

$$P_0^{trsl} = \begin{pmatrix} (\sigma_0^{pos})^2 I_3 & 0_3 \\ 0_3 & (\sigma_0^{vel})^2 I_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad P_0^{rot} = \begin{pmatrix} (\sigma_0^{att})^2 I_3 & 0_3 \\ 0_3 & (\sigma_0^{angvel})^2 I_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.80)$$

Downsampling and motion compensation

As explained in Section 2.4.4, a pre-processing step before applying the smoothed NDT (or ICP) to the incoming point clouds consists in downsampling the point clouds with a voxel grid filter. This filter has a resolution of 2 cm in the experiments (see Table 2.3). The downsampling has two advantages: First, it increases the robustness of the registration, by mitigating for example the effect of the scanning pattern of the sensor, which leads to an inhomogeneous distribution of points in the cloud. Second, it ensures a faster runtime by reducing the number of points to be processed. The runtime is also more consistent from one scan to another, independently of the number of points.

The raw point cloud originating from the Livox Mid-40 lidar contains a list of 3D coordinates z_1, \dots, z_{N_z} . Each point additionally has an individual timestamp t_1, \dots, t_{N_z} . If no care is taken, then the timestamps are lost after downsampling with a voxel grid filter. When motion compensation is performed in the form of deblurring in a pre-processing step (“NDT + deblurring”), the solution is simple: Deblurring is first performed on the raw point cloud, using the individual timestamps, before the point cloud is downsampled with the voxel grid. After this step, the timestamps are not used anymore.

However, when using the “continuous-time NDT”, the timestamps are used as part of the registration algorithm. Thus, the voxel grid downsampling has to preserve the timestamps. After downsampling, each voxel will contain (at most) a single 3D point and timestamp. Different strategies are possible for setting the timestamp in a voxel: Taking the minimum of all timestamps of this voxel, or the maximum, the mean etc. In our experiments, setting the voxel timestamp to equal the mean of all timestamps of points falling into that voxel was found to give best results.

3.5.2 Tracking of a target tumbling with 2 deg/s

The first evaluation is performed on the same dataset used in Section 2.5.1. This lidar dataset is recorded during a fly-around and approach trajectory at EPOS, while the target is tumbling with an angular rate of approximately 2 deg/s. During this trajectory lasting 26 min, the lidar is set to have an adaptive frame rate, see Section 2.4.4. In the previous chapter, three tracking methods were compared, ICP, classical and smoothed NDT. Here, we evaluate the tracking in combination with the navigation filter, for the three possible setups listed in Section 3.5.1. The navigation filter estimate is compared to the ground truth of the facility. As in the previous chapter, the initial estimate for tracking the first point cloud of the dataset is given by the ground truth.

The navigation filter uses additional inputs compared to the point cloud tracking algorithm. First, the attitude filter uses the inertia matrix of the target to propagate the motion. For this experiment, we recall that the inertia matrix of the target was set to $I_{Tar} = \text{diag}(600, 500, 500)$ kg·m². It is assumed that this inertia matrix is known, or approximated: Like the geometrical model of the target, the inertial properties are either known before the flight, or the result of an inspection phase prior to the final approach [237, 232, 238]. For propagating the translational dynamics, the position filter uses the chaser mass and the control forces applied by the chaser at each timestamp. Thus, the control forces applied by the chaser during

the experiment are additionally provided as input to the filter.

The result of the evaluation of smoothed NDT in conjunction with the navigation filter, without and with deblurring, and the continuous-time version are presented in Fig. 3.4. The first observation is that the use of the navigation filter is beneficial. Compared to the previous chapter, where smoothed NDT was tested in isolation (see Fig. 2.17), the error of the navigation estimate when combining smoothed NDT with the navigation filter (light blue curve in Figs. 3.4a and 3.4b) is lower, and the error is smoother: Indeed, the error presented here is the error of the filtered navigation estimate, and not the raw error of the registration algorithm.

The second observation is that the prediction of both strategies using motion compensation (deblurring or continuous-time formulation) is very similar, and has a lower error than without motion compensation (Figs. 3.4a and 3.4b). Concerning the attitude prediction (Fig. 3.4a), the mean error of the filtered estimate for the “NDT + filter” strategy is of 1.39 deg, with a maximum at 2.73 deg. We recall that in the previous chapter, Section 2.5.1, the mean error when using the smoothed NDT in isolation without a filter was 1.48 deg with a maximum at 3.11 deg. Applying a motion compensation strategy in addition to the filter enables to further increase the precision. For both the “NDT + deblurring” and “continuous-time NDT” strategies, the errors are lower: The mean angular error is of 1.02 deg for both, with a peak error of 2.70 deg and 2.20 deg, respectively.

The position error is presented in Fig. 3.4b. All three methods exhibit a similar evolution of the error over time, with no significant differences. For this case, the motion compensation strategy mainly enables to improve the attitude prediction. Indeed, the attitude varies more rapidly than the position, so that taking into account timing effects improves mostly the prediction accuracy of the attitude. Still, in the previous chapter, when no filter was in the loop, a spike was observed in the position error at minute 1. This spike is still visible, but with a lower amplitude than previously, for the “NDT + filter” strategy. For the two other strategies, this abrupt movement which led to motion blur is compensated, and the spike is not observed anymore.

A second benefit of using the navigation filter is observed in the runtime and number of iterations, in Figs. 3.4c and 3.4d. When using the filter (“NDT + filter” strategy), the median runtime and number of iterations is significantly lower than in the previous chapter, when using only the tracking algorithm: The median runtime is of 10 ms while it was of 18 ms in Section 2.5.1, and the median number of iterations is of 8 while it was of 17. This is due to the fact that when using the navigation filter, the initial prediction delivered by the filter is closer to the current pose than when using the previous tracking result as an initial estimate. In consequence, fewer iterations are required to converge.

Like in Chapter 2, the boxplots 3.4c and 3.4d represent the distributions of runtimes and iterations such that the colored box extends to the first and third quartile, with the median being the middle line. The whiskers extend to the 5th and 95th percentiles, while outliers are shown as black crosses. Both “NDT + filter” and “NDT + deblurring” strategies show a similar distribution of number of iterations and runtimes. On the contrary, the number of iterations required by the “continuous-time NDT” is slightly higher, with a median number of 11 iterations. More significantly, the median runtime is twice as high: It is of 20 ms for the continuous-time formulation, while comprising 10 ms for the deblurring version. The reason is that the continuous-time formulation requires a higher runtime per iteration, due to the more

Figure 3.4: Compared results of different tracking methods in conjunction with the navigation filter, for a target tumbling with 2 deg/s. (a) Absolute angular error of the navigation filter; (b) Absolute position error of the navigation filter; (c) Distribution of runtimes (on an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU), including pre-processing; (d) Distribution of the number of iterations.

expensive computation of the gradient for each point in (3.74).

3.5.3 Tracking of a target tumbling with 5 deg/s

The second dataset used for this evaluation is the dataset which was recorded at EPOS for a fast tumbling target, with an approximate tumbling rate of 5 deg/s, and presented in Section 2.5.2. Compared to the previous chapter, we now evaluate the methods in conjunction with the navigation filter on this dataset. For this experiment, we recall that the lidar was set to have a fix framerate of 1 Hz. In consequence, due to the tumbling motion of 5 deg/s, motion blur effects become visible and are observed on the point clouds (see Fig. 2.18b in the previous chapter).

In contrast to the previous chapter, where the maximum number of iterations was increased for this experiment in order to enable both algorithms (ICP and NDT) to converge, this is not needed here, because the navigation filter helps to converge. The maximum number of iterations for the NDT algorithm is kept to 30, and all tuning parameters of NDT are identical to the previous experiment, and listed in Table 2.3 of the previous chapter.

The results when evaluating the three lidar navigation variants on this dataset are presented in Fig. 3.5. Due to the higher tumbling rate of the target satellite, the angular error of the “NDT + filter” strategy is higher than for both strategies accounting for motion blur (Fig. 3.5a). Compared to the results when no filter was in the loop (Section 2.5.2), using the filter in combination with smoothed NDT mostly leads to a smoother estimate. While the mean angular error is comparable (3.41 deg here vs. 3.50 deg without filter), the maximum error reduced (4.85 deg vs. 5.56 deg previously).

After the first steps, during which the navigation filter is initialized and converges to an angular velocity estimate, the angular error of both the “NDT + deblurring” and “continuous-time NDT” drop, see Fig. 3.5a. With a correct angular velocity estimate, the deblurring performed in the pre-processing enables to correctly relocate the points of the cloud. Likewise, a converged filter provides a good initial estimate for the continuous-time algorithm, which uses the individual timestamps of the points. As a consequence, the mean angular error over the experiment for the “NDT + deblurring” strategy is of 1.14 deg, and of 1.09 deg for the “continuous-time NDT”.

Like in the previous experiment, the position errors of all three algorithms are relatively similar in Fig. 3.5b. For all methods, the position error is below 4.1 cm for the complete experiment. The overall evolution of the position error is similar to the one observed in the previous chapter in Fig. 2.20b.

The same trend as in the previous experiment is observed concerning the algorithm’s runtime and number of iterations. The distribution of the number of iterations is similar for all three methods, see Fig. 3.5d. While “NDT + filter” and “NDT + deblurring” have a similar runtime distribution on Fig. 3.5c, with median runtimes of 12 ms, “continuous-time NDT” has approximately twice the runtime, with a median value of 25 ms. Again, the filter shows to have a very beneficial effect on the runtime, by providing a precise initial estimate leading to a reduction of the number of iterations. In the previous chapter, for the same experiment, the median runtime of smoothed NDT was 40 ms for a median of 28 iterations, while when using the filter prediction these median values drop to 12 ms and 9 iterations.

Figure 3.5: Compared results of different tracking methods in conjunction with the navigation filter, for a target tumbling with 5 deg/s. **(a)** Absolute angular error of the navigation filter; **(b)** Absolute position error of the navigation filter; **(c)** Distribution of runtimes (on an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU), including pre-processing; **(d)** Distribution of the number of iterations.

3.5.4 Tracking of a target tumbling with 10 deg/s

To further test the limits of the system, we perform a last experiment at EPOS, for a tumbling rate of approximately 10 deg/s. This experiment was not presented in Chapter 2: Without a navigation filter in the loop, for such a tumbling rate, both the ICP and (smoothed) NDT tracking diverge towards the end of the experiment.

The settings for this experiment are similar to the ones in the previous experiment, which was described more in detail in Section 2.5.2, with the main difference that the initial angular velocity is set to $\omega = (10, 1, 0)^T$ deg/s. The target's inertia matrix is kept identical to previously, $I_{Tar} = \text{diag}(600, 500, 500)$ kg·m². With these settings, the target has a tumbling motion and a spin rate of approximately 10 deg/s, as presented in Fig. 3.6b.

The position of the chaser respectively to the target during the rendezvous experiment is illustrated in Fig. 3.6a. Again, the experiment starts with a fly-around phase at a steady distance of 15 m, between the 2nd and 6th minute of the experiment. Afterwards, the approach is gradually performed, first from 15 m to 8 m with a velocity of 2 cm/s, then with a velocity of 1 cm/s until 3 m distance. In between, there is a short hold at 4 m distance, around the 19th minute.

Figure 3.6: (a) Position of the chaser relatively to the target in RTN. (b) Attitude of the target in RTN, expressed as precession-nutation-spin angles.

Similarly to the previous experiment, the lidar is set to have a constant frame rate of 1 Hz. Setting this low framerate, in combination with the fast tumbling motion, leads to a strong motion blur of the point clouds. In Fig. 3.1, we showed a point cloud recorded during this experiment: On the left, the raw point cloud appears blurred, while after motion compensation, the right point cloud has sharper edges.

The results of the navigation methods on this dataset are compared in Fig. 3.7. The first observation is that all three methods are able to track the pose of the target satellite over the whole experiment without diverging. Without the navigation filter in the loop, both ICP and (smoothed) NDT did not converge.

The angular errors between the navigation filter estimates and the ground truth for the three

Figure 3.7: Compared results of different tracking methods in conjunction with the navigation filter, for a target tumbling with 10 deg/s. **(a)** Absolute angular error of the navigation filter; **(b)** Absolute position error of the navigation filter; **(c)** Distribution of runtimes (on an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU), including pre-processing; **(d)** Distribution of the number of iterations.

methods are presented in Fig. 3.7a. Because it does not account for motion blur, the angular error of the “NDT + filter” method stays around its mean value of 6.10 deg throughout the whole approach, with a maximum error of 7.41 deg. The value of this mean error is understood intuitively: During the capture of one point cloud, which lasts 1 s, the target rotates by approximately 10 deg, so that the initial and final pose of the scan are 10 deg apart. If not considering the timestamps, the registration algorithm estimates a pose approximately in between the initial and final pose, which is roughly in the middle, so 5 deg away from the final pose. Adding some errors from the registration algorithm on top of this error, the mean error of 6.10 deg corresponds to the expectations.

For both methods accounting for motion blur, a similar attitude error profile is observed as in the previous experiment. After the first steps, during which the navigation filter converges, the angular errors drop and remain below 3 deg for the rest of the experiment, see Fig. 3.7a. Overall, the mean angular error of “NDT + deblurring” is of 1.42 deg, while it is of 1.40 deg for “continuous-time NDT”. We recall that in the previous experiment, where the target was tumbling with 5 deg/s, the mean angular error of these two methods was around 1.1 deg. Thus, for this experiment where the target is tumbling faster, the precision of the angular tracking slightly decreases.

The error of the position tracking, illustrated in Fig. 3.7b is relatively similar for all methods. The main difference is that “continuous-time NDT” has a higher position error in the beginning of the experiment, between minutes 2 and 5, reaching a maximum error of 4.30 cm. Otherwise, both “NDT + filter” and “NDT + deblurring” have a position error below 3.5 cm throughout the whole rendezvous.

Finally, the distribution of the runtimes and number of iterations are presented in Figs. 3.7c and 3.7d. For this experiment, “NDT + deblurring” requires the least number of iterations in average. While the median number of iterations is identical for “continuous-time NDT” and “NDT + filter”, the 3rd quartile is higher for the second. With blurred point clouds, the smoothed NDT method without motion compensation requires more iterations to converge. This also translates to the runtimes presented in Fig. 3.7c. Still, due to its more time expensive iterations, “continuous-time NDT” is the method with the highest runtime of the three.

3.5.5 Runtime evaluation on a Zynq 7000

Similarly to Section 2.5.3, we perform a runtime evaluation of the different methods when evaluated on the Zynq 7000 CPU. This computer is used as a representative onboard computing platform. To compare with the previous Chapter, we perform the runtime evaluation on the same sequence of point clouds as in Section 2.5.3. This corresponds to the tracking experiment of a slowly tumbling target presented in Section 3.5.2. The runtime results of the three methods when evaluated on the Zynq is presented in Table 3.1. The comparison of the runtimes of all three algorithms is similar to the results obtained on the desktop computer, with the difference that all runtimes are scaled by approximately a factor 25.

On this dataset, “NDT + filter” is the fastest method, with an average runtime of 217 ms. “NDT + deblurring” has a similar runtime, with the only difference that the pre-processing is longer in average. Indeed, in this case, the pre-processing does not only include voxel grid downsampling, but additionally point cloud deblurring. Finally, “continuous-time NDT” is the

Table 3.1: Runtime comparison of the three methods when evaluated on the Zynq 7000 CPU for tracking a slowly tumbling target. Values are shown as mean $\pm 1\sigma$, where σ is the standard deviation.

algorithm	pre-processing [ms]	registration [ms]	total [ms]
NDT + filter	30 ± 1	186 ± 100	217 ± 100
NDT + deblurring	42 ± 3	181 ± 102	223 ± 102
continuous-time NDT	47 ± 2	469 ± 224	516 ± 224

slowest method, in accordance to the previously obtained results. The registration is computationally more intensive, but also the pre-processing. This is due by the fact that the voxel grid downsampling for the continuous-time version is implemented less efficiently, since this downsampling also computes the average timestamp for each voxel, as explained in Section 3.5.1.

3.5.6 Discussion

The three experiments demonstrated, first, the improvement gained by associating the tracking method, here smoothed NDT, with the navigation filter. The proposed navigation filter, and in particular the attitude IEKF, shows to be suited for the task of relative spacecraft navigation, and simple to tune. Compared to the raw pose measurements of the tracking algorithm, the filtered estimates are smoother and more precise. In addition to better precision, using the filter prediction enables to improve the algorithm’s runtime: Because the filter prediction anticipates the probable pose of the target satellite, it is closer to the actual pose than was the previous measurement, and fewer iterations are needed for the tracker to converge.

The second benefit of the navigation filter is that its position and angular velocity predictions are used to motion compensate the point cloud in case the deblurring logic is applied. Accounting for motion blur in the point clouds leads to a significant increase in the precision of the pose estimation for rapidly tumbling targets, as could be observed for the experiments of Section 3.5.3 and 3.5.4.

The same gain of precision by accounting for motion blur is observed with the continuous-time NDT formulation. However, differently from the deblurring logic, the filter is not the main factor for the enhancement in this case. We also tested the continuous-time formulation without the navigation filter, i.e., the previous result is used as an initial estimate for the continuous-time tracking. In this case, the method also converges and is able to compensate motion blur. This is due to the fact that the continuous-time formulation performs the motion compensation as part of the registration process, not relying on the filter for this task. Yet, using the navigation filter to provide the initial estimate enables to further improve the precision, and mostly the number of iterations required to converge. Therefore, this version is preferred in the experiments.

Overall, the precision of smoothed NDT, whether associated with the deblurring logic or the continuous-time formulation, is very similar in all experiments. A possible explanation is that both methods rely on the same constant velocity assumption for motion compensation, so that the point clouds are undistorted in a similar way. Still, the deblurring logic relies on past measurements to estimate the current velocities and perform motion compensation, while the

continuous-time formulation uses the current point cloud data. Yet this conceptual advantage does not lead to a better precision of the estimation in practice, possibly because the relative dynamics, especially the rotational dynamics of the target, is very steady: The target satellite, in our experiments, is freely tumbling and not subject to any disturbance torque.

The major advantage of the deblurring logic compared to the continuous-time formulation is the faster runtime. Of the three navigation methods, smoothed NDT associated with deblurring is the fastest, while the continuous-time version is found to be more than two times slower. When evaluated on onboard representative computing hardware, both methods performing motion compensation have an average runtime below 0.6 s. An order of magnitude of the required execution time of the navigation being 1 s (Section 1.4), both are suitable for real-time implementation. Yet in addition to being faster, the simplicity of the deblurring logic compared to the continuous-time formulation is also appealing.

What is the maximum tumbling rate that is still tracked ?

The last experiment (Section 3.5.4) showed that with the motion compensation logic, it is possible to precisely track the considered target satellite's pose when it is tumbling with an angular rate of 10 deg/s. But what is the upper limit of the tumbling rate that the navigation still tracks ?

Such a limit is dependent on many parameters. The first one is the frame rate: The higher the frame rate, the higher also is the maximum permissible angular velocity of the target. The properties of the lidar sensor also influence this result. In particular, the point rate of the lidar as well as its scan pattern will influence the quality of the point clouds, and hence the precision of the tracking. Finally, the target's geometry is also important: A geometry with very distinguishable features will be easier to track than, in the worst case, a spherical object, for which it is not possible to determine the attitude.

Still, we are interested in an order of magnitude of the result in the case of our problem, i.e., for tracking the target satellite installed at EPOS, when flying a similar trajectory as in the experiments of this section. Due to the high tumbling rate, such trajectories could not be flown at the hardware-in-the-loop facility EPOS. However, we simulated trajectories with higher tumbling rates with a high-fidelity lidar simulator. This simulator will be described in detail in the next chapter, Section 4.1. Without going into the specifics of the simulator here, one important point is that the simulator also accounts for motion blur, so that the synthetic point clouds present a similar distortion to the real point clouds.

We simulate rendezvous trajectories with a similar profile as in the last experiment (Section 3.5.4). The lidar simulator uses a 3D model of the target satellite, the current pose and relative velocity and tumbling rate to synthesise a blurred point cloud. We record four synthetic datasets, with tumbling rates of the target satellite of 15, 20, 25 and 30 deg/s. Fig. 3.8 shows point clouds synthesized for this experiment. The higher the tumbling rate, the less the edges and features of the target satellite become recognizable.

For the synthetic datasets with a tumbling rate of 15 deg/s and 20 deg/s, all three methods presented in this section are able to keep track of the target's pose over time. In line with what was observed in this section, using a motion compensation strategy enables to greatly improve the accuracy of the tracking. On the contrary, for the datasets where the satellite tumbles with

Figure 3.8: Blurred point clouds obtained with the lidar simulator, recorded with a frame rate of 1 Hz, for different tumbling rates of the target satellite. (a) 15 deg/s; (b) 20 deg/s; (c) 25 deg/s; (d) 30 deg/s. Warm colors indicate points closer to the sensor.

25 deg/s and 30 deg/s, all tracking methods fail. By failing, we mean that the tracker is not able to catch up with the rotational speed of the target: The attitude error of the pose estimation steadily increases until 180 deg.

From the experiment on the synthetic point clouds, we conclude that for this target spacecraft shape, and with this lidar configured with a frame rate of 1 Hz, the maximum tumbling rate that is tracked by the lidar navigation system lies around 20 deg/s. In practice, for such high tumbling rates, it is very challenging to perform any type of satellite servicing or robotic operations. Catching the target implies to first synchronize with its rotational speed before de-tumbling. Still, if mission scenarios with very fast tumbling motions (in the order of 20 deg/s or above) are expected, a sensor setting with higher frame rates is to be considered for relative navigation and pose tracking.

3.6 Chapter conclusions

This chapter discussed how to combine a pose tracking algorithm, presented in Chapter 2, with a navigation filter. To design a navigation filter for tracking not only a position, but also an attitude, the filter is formulated as an IEKF, which is a natural extension of the EKF on Lie groups such as the attitude group. The IEKF formalism was extended to the case where measurements are also in the rotation group, and applied to the context of relative pose estimation during rendezvous.

The filter combined with a tracking method forms a complete navigation system, save for an initialization method. We recall RQ2: *How is the robustness and precision of a lidar-based navigation system ensured in the case of a rapidly tumbling target spacecraft?* The filter, which accurately predicts the target spacecraft's motion, is used to provide an initial estimate for the tracking algorithm. By doing so, the lidar navigation is able to track the target's pose even in case of a fast tumbling motion. This is demonstrated by hardware-in-the-loop experiments at EPOS in Section 3.5.

The use of a filter adds robustness to the tracking, enabling it to converge in spite of fast tumbling motions. However, due to motion blur effects, the precision of the tracking decreases

when the frame rate of the scanning lidar is low compared to the angular rate of the target spacecraft. To guarantee the precision of the tracking in such cases, two strategies were presented for motion compensation. The first strategy consists in relying on the filter to provide an estimate of the relative velocities, which are then used to correct motion blur in the point clouds as a pre-processing step. The second strategy is a continuous-time formulation of the NDT registration algorithm, which considers not only the position of the points during each iteration, but also their timestamp. Both versions perform a motion correction of the point cloud based on a linear velocity model.

The motion compensation strategies enable to greatly improve the precision when tracking targets tumbling with a high angular rate. This was verified during the experiments at EPOS, Section 3.5. Even when the target tumbles with 10 deg/s, the navigation errors after initialization are below 3 deg and 5 cm during the rendezvous experiment of Section 3.5.4. While both the deblurring and continuous-time strategy lead to a similar precision improvement, the first one is approximately twice faster than the second. Therefore, a recommendation is to choose the deblurring strategy, used as a pre-processing method before tracking. In all cases, performing deblurring enables to enhance both the precision and the runtime of the tracking, whether the target has a low or high tumbling motion.

In spite of these strategies, there is a limit on what angular rates are admissible for tracking. For example, for a scanning lidar with a frequency of 1 Hz, this limit was found in Section 3.5.6 to be around 20 deg/s. For higher tumbling motions, a sensor system which enables to acquire data with a higher frequency should be chosen. In the experiments of this section, the tracking was initialized with ground truth data. To complete the navigation system, a pose initialization method is required. This will be the subject of Chapter 4.

Chapter 4

Neural network based pose initialization

When an initial pose estimate is known, local point cloud matching methods such as smoothed NDT enable to precisely track the target satellite over consecutive point clouds. However, searching an initial estimate is a global optimization problem, for which finding a solution in real-time is challenging. In addition, many spacecraft present a symmetrical shape, so that the true attitude of the spacecraft is not uniquely defined from 3D data. This leads to following research question:

RQ3: How is a reliable pose initialization method designed for real-time onboard implementation, accounting for varying conditions, sensor noise, and potential symmetries in the shape of the target satellite ?

This chapter presents a pose initialization strategy relying on the use of a neural network. Two alternatives are explored, consisting in either projecting the point clouds to depth images for processing with a CNN, or direct processing with a point-based network. A custom rendezvous lidar simulator enables to generate a large and diversified synthetic training dataset. To handle the case of a symmetric spacecraft, an attitude classification logic is developed. Evaluations on data from the EPOS facility show that the method is reliable and precise. The pose initialization is optimized for runtime, and its real-time capability demonstrated on representative onboard computing hardware.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 4.1 describes the lidar simulator developed for generating synthetic training data. The attitude classification logic accounting for symmetries in the shape of the target satellite is presented in Section 4.2. Two neural network architectures are then explored for performing pose estimation with lidar point clouds. The CNN-based method is presented in Section 4.3, and the 3D network based method in Section 4.4. Finally, the pose initialization is evaluated on real EPOS data, and these results are presented in Section 4.5 alongside with the runtime evaluation. Section 4.6 concludes this chapter.

4.1 Rendezvous lidar simulator

The approach for developing a neural network based pose initialization method relies on training only with synthetic data, before evaluation and testing is performed on real data. There are two reasons for this strategy. First, neural networks require a substantial amount of data for proper training, and a lidar simulator enables to automate the quick generation of large datasets. Even with a facility such as EPOS, it is challenging to generate a very large and complete dataset, with a full coverage of the possible poses of the target spacecraft. In a mission scenario, if the 3D model of the target is only known after the inspection phase, a lidar simulator would enable to generate new data to re-train a model within hours, which would not be possible only with a hardware facility. Second, this approach allows to demonstrate the ability of the networks to generalize to different, unseen data. Indeed, if the method was trained for example on a mix of synthetic and real point clouds collected at EPOS, then the test data collected at the same facility would be very similar to the training data. In such a case, nothing would ensure that the method is able to generalize to different data, and in particular to the point clouds collected in space, which might differ from the point clouds collected at the facility.

This section describes the lidar simulator developed in this work, as well as the synthetic datasets used for training a pose estimation method. The simulator covers significant effects observed during space rendezvous scenarios.

4.1.1 Lidar simulator

To achieve Sim2Real, i.e., the successful transfer from learning on synthetic data to testing on real data, an accurate lidar simulator is needed, encompassing the most relevant effects observed in the space rendezvous context. While multiple lidar simulators are openly available, they are often meant for autonomous driving scenarios. For example, the Carla [239] and AirSim [240] simulators mostly support laser scanners with repetitive scan patterns such as Velodyne lidars. Frameworks used in multi-purpose robotics simulations such as Gazebo [241] or BlenSor [242] also provide range data simulators, but these are implemented as ray-casting, without directly available modeling of effects such as reflections or beam divergence. Woods and Christian [243] developed a lidar simulator with the application of space rendezvous in mind. Yet, the project was not continued, the simulator implements ray-casting but no additional disturbance effects apart from random noise. Therefore, a custom lidar simulator for space rendezvous applications was designed, and will be described in the following.

Ray casting and scan pattern

The simulator is built on top of a naive existing ray-tracer. In its initial version, the ray-tracer computes equally spaced rays coming from the source (assuming a grid scan pattern for the lidar). The 3D model of the target is saved as a triangle mesh. For each ray, it iterates through all triangles of a 3D mesh, finds the closest intersection and returns a point where the intersection was. While this ray-tracer “skeleton” was already existing, all the additional improvements that will be listed in the following were developed in the context of this work.

The first improvement is to accelerate the triangle search by using a k-d tree structure. At each layer of the tree, an efficient ray-box intersection is computed [244], and only nodes which intersect with the ray are further inspected. Whenever the node is a leaf node, i.e., containing a triangle, the intersection of the ray with the triangle is computed [245]. Next, the scanning pattern of the Mid-40 lidar used at EPOS is implemented. This is a non-repetitive rosette scan pattern (see Fig. 2.8a). Such a pattern is achieved by deflecting the ray by two inclined prisms rotating at different angular rates, and implemented following the modeling of Brazeal et al. [216].

Intensity modeling

A laser transmits a pulse with a certain power. The lidar measures the returned power over the area of its sensor, i.e., it measures an intensity. For simplification, we will only consider intensities and not power. It is assumed that the lidar emits a certain intensity I_0 , and only detects a return if the intensity is above a certain threshold I_{min} . When neglecting atmospheric effects, which are not relevant in space, the power attenuation of a signal with distance is proportional to the inverse squared distance [246, 247]. For an object located at a distance r to a lidar, Jutzi and Gross [246] consider that the returned signal has a distance attenuation in $1/r^2$, while the overall distance made by the ray is $2r$ (two ways). Using the same model, the attenuation of a ray after a distance r (one way) is

$$I(r) = \frac{I_0}{(r/2)^2} . \quad (4.1)$$

In addition, the intensity is modified when the ray is reflected by the surface it hits. An empirical model for surface properties in image simulation is the Phong model [248]. This model is adapted for modeling reflections in laser scanning by Jutzi and Gross [246]. For this model, a material is described by two parameters: A specular reflectance $k_s \in [0, 1]$, and a specular exponent $\eta > 0$. The diffuse reflectance is $k_d = 1 - k_s$. The diffuse reflectance indicates what fraction of the incoming light is reflected in all directions, while the specular reflectance determines what fraction is reflected only in the direction of the reflected ray. The specular exponent controls the width, or sharpness, of this reflection.

We consider the case illustrated in Fig. 4.1: A ray hits a (locally) planar surface with an incidence angle θ . The angle between the observer and the reflected ray is α . Let I_{in} be the intensity of the incident ray, and I_{out} the intensity of the ray viewed by the observer. In the adapted Phong model, these intensities are linked by [246]:

$$I_{out} = I_{in} (k_d \cos \theta + k_s \cos^\eta \alpha) . \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 4.1: Schematic representation of the incident ray, reflected ray and observer position.

When considering no multiple reflections on the surface, the emitter and receiver are located at the same place for a lidar, i.e., $\alpha = 2\theta$. Combining the distance attenuation (4.1) and the surface properties (4.2), the primary reflection on a surface located at a distance r from the sensor is perceived with an intensity

$$I_{primary} = \frac{I_0}{r^2} (k_d \cos \theta + k_s \cos^n 2\theta). \quad (4.3)$$

Double reflections

The point clouds captured in real conditions at EPOS contain some ghost points due to multiple reflections, sometimes in high quantities, see Section 2.5.1. To enable such effects in the simulator, additional reflections next to the primary return are modeled. To limit the computational load, the lidar simulator only models double reflections, i.e., a ray hits at most two surfaces before taking the same path back to the sensor. The logic for modelling double reflections is illustrated in Fig. 4.2.

The intensity for a double reflection is computed as follows: Let k_{s_1}, k_{d_1}, η_1 be the coefficients of the first surface, and k_{s_2}, k_{d_2}, η_2 the coefficients of the second surface. The path of the ray is illustrated in Fig. 4.2. It has an incidence angle θ_1 on the first surface, and is reflected with an angle α_1 with respect to the perfect reflection. It then hits the second surface with an angle θ_2 , before coming back the same way. Additionally, r is the distance between the lidar and the first surface, and d the distance between the two surfaces. The intensity of the secondary return coming from the double reflection is

$$I_{secondary} = \frac{I_0}{(r+d)^2} (k_{d_1} \cos \theta_1 + k_{s_1} \cos^{\eta_1} \alpha_1)^2 (k_{d_2} \cos \theta_2 + k_{s_2} \cos^{\eta_2} 2\theta_2). \quad (4.4)$$

Here, it was assumed that the intensity attenuation when the ray hits “surface 1” is identical on the outward and backward path, hence the square. While this does not hold in general, it is an approximation assuming that the angle α_1 is small compared to θ_1 .

How is the angle α_1 chosen? In principle, an infinite number of reflected rays with various angles α_1 could be computed. Again, to enable fast point cloud simulation on a CPU, a simpli-

Figure 4.2: Schematic representation of a secondary reflection. The ray takes the same path in both ways, before returning to the lidar.

fication is performed. A direction is chosen at random within a cone with a half cone aperture α_{max} , and only this ray is computed. This maximum half cone angle is defined as follows. It is assumed that double reflections are only relevant for highly reflective surfaces, i.e., when $\eta \gg 1$ and $k_s \approx 1$. In this case, the surface equation (4.2) becomes, for small angles α ,

$$\frac{I_{out}}{I_{in}} \approx 1 - \eta \frac{\alpha^2}{2}. \quad (4.5)$$

Under these assumptions, computing a reflected ray is only relevant for angles $\alpha < \alpha_{max} = \sqrt{2/\eta}$.

The primary or secondary reflections are only considered as a distance measurement by the lidar if their intensity is above I_{min} . If both returns have an intensity above this threshold, then the lidar receives two distance measurements: One at a distance r with an intensity $I_{primary}$, and a second at a distance $(r + d)$ with an intensity $I_{secondary}$. The distance measure is then a weighted average of these two distances:

$$d_{meas} = \frac{rI_{primary} + (r + d)I_{secondary}}{I_{primary} + I_{secondary}}. \quad (4.6)$$

Other effects

An additional effect observed with the Mid-40 lidar at the EPOS facility in Section 2.5.1 is the presence of artifacts, or wrong measurements, due to the laser's beam divergence. Indeed, the laser is not perfectly directional, and has a certain beam aperture. This beam aperture is defined as the full width at half maximum, i.e., the deviation angle from the ray's main direction for which the intensity only equals a fraction $1/e^2$ of the intensity in the middle of the ray. Formally, let β be the beam divergence angle. We consider a direction diverging from an angle γ from the

ray's main direction. Then the intensity in this direction is

$$I(\gamma) = I_0 \exp\left(-\frac{2\gamma^2}{\beta^2}\right), \quad (4.7)$$

while I_0 is the intensity along the main direction. This model is a simplified version of the beam divergence model found in [247].

To simulate the effects of beam divergence, Winiwarter et al. [247] suggest computing not only one ray, but several sub-rays having a slight divergence from the ideal ray direction. For each sub-ray, the intensity and the distance of the return is computed. This intensity accounts for the intensity loss of (4.7) due to the divergence. The final distance measure for the ray is an intensity weighted sum of the distances of all sub-rays. Our approach for simulating beam divergence is similar. The only difference is that we simulate less sub-rays, to maintain efficiency, but compensate this by randomizing the direction of each sub-ray. Thus, instead of a fix pattern for the distribution of the subrays, we select N_r sub-rays randomly. Each sub-ray diverges from the main ray direction with a random angle γ chosen uniformly in $[0, \beta]$. Empirically, we find that a number of sub-rays $N_r = 5$ is sufficient to produce realistic beam divergence artifacts, while keeping a low computational time.

Measurement errors are modeled by a random range error, following a normal distribution with a standard deviation usually provided in the sensor specifications. The final effect that is simulated is motion blur, which is observed in particular for fast tumbling targets, see Section 3.4. Motion blur is simulated according to the model presented in Section 3.4.1. As in Equation (3.58), it is assumed that the relative velocity and angular rate are constant for the duration of one scan. From an implementation perspective, the simplest is to shift the position and orientation of the sensor with respect to the 3D mesh after each scanned point according to the linear motion model.

A point cloud generated with these different effects is presented in Figs. 4.3a and 4.3c. It is compared with a point cloud taken at the EPOS facility for the same pose in Figs. 4.3b and Fig. 4.3d. Several effects are observed on both the simulated and real point clouds: The rosette scan pattern is recognizable, and the front MLI partly disappears due to its reflectivity. In addition, double reflections are observed at the basis of the satellite's tower, creating artifacts in the middle of the point clouds in Figs. 4.3a and 4.3b. Finally, the effect of the laser's beam divergence is best observed in Figs. 4.3c and 4.3d. The points between the tip of the satellite (in red) and the main hexagonal body (in green) are artifacts induced by the beam divergence.

4.1.2 Training and validation datasets

The lidar simulator is used to generate an extensive training and validation dataset. Since the objective is to train the network for close range pose estimation, the relative distances are chosen uniformly in the range 2.5 m to 20 m. Also, the relative attitude for each new point cloud is chosen at random, care being taken to have a uniform distribution in the attitude space. In addition, the target does not necessarily have to be in the center of the lidar's field-of-view: The angle of the direction from the lidar to the target with respect to the principal direction of the lidar is chosen according to a normal distribution centered around zero, with a 3σ value equal to the lidar's circular field-of-view angle. This way, cases where the target is centered in the

Figure 4.3: Comparison of simulated and real point clouds with the same pose: Front (a) and side (c) views of a point cloud generated with the lidar simulator. Front (b) and side (d) views of a point cloud collected at EPOS.

field-of-view are more likely, but cases where only a part of the target is visible are also in the dataset.

Next to the relative pose, the relative velocities, are also randomized. This is important to have cases with motion blur in the dataset (see Fig. 3.8 in Chapter 3). Both the velocity and angular rate are distributed uniformly, with a maximum velocity of 3 cm/s, and a maximum angular rate of 5 deg/s. To cover cases for different settings of the lidar, the frame rate is also randomized, so that the point clouds contain a variable number of points, including sparse and very dense point clouds. This framerate is chosen at random around a reference value depending on the distance to the target, so that the average number of points in the cloud is around 10 000.

The intrinsic lidar parameters such as range noise error and beam divergence angle are provided in the sensor specifications, see Table 2.2. In particular, the beam divergence angle for the Mid-40 is $\beta = 0.28$ deg, while the standard deviation of the distance error is 2 cm. However, the distance errors observed on real point clouds were observed to be significantly lower, so that this parameter was set to 0.5 cm for generating the synthetic dataset. A parameter of the

lidar is also the minimum intensity detection threshold I_{min} . In Table 2.2, it is specified that the maximum detectable distance for an object with 10% reflectivity is 90 m, while it is 130 m for 20% and 260 m for 80%. With the model for range attenuation (4.1), all these indications coincide approximately to define a minimum intensity detectability of $I_{min}/I_0 = 1.2e-5$.

Finally, the material properties, i.e., their specular and diffuse parameters, have to be chosen. Nakajima et al. [249] performed a characterization of the reflectivity properties of some materials constituting a satellite, such as MLI, foam and structure components. The experimental results indicate that the diffuse coefficient k_d of MLI lies between 1e-3 and 1e-2, while structural elements have a higher diffuse coefficient around 0.1. Since the exact material properties of the target satellite are unknown, we follow a domain randomization strategy similar to [171, 172]: The principle is to select the material properties at random within a pre-defined range covering the real properties. The training dataset will potentially be more general and cover more cases than the real data.

The random ranges for the material properties are presented in Table 4.1. Three different materials are distinguished: MLI, solar panels and structure. The selection of the range for the reflectivity and diffuse coefficients was aided by the experimental results of [249]. To illustrate the effect of different reflectivity values, Fig. 4.4 presents point clouds generated by the lidar simulator for a varying diffuse coefficient of the MLI: When the reflectivity is high (k_d close to 0), the MLI acts similarly to a mirror, and nearly disappears. In all cases, reflections of the front tower on the MLI are observed in the center of the point cloud, in blue on Figs. 4.4a - 4.4c.

Table 4.1: Randomization range of material properties for the lidar simulator.

material	k_d	η
structure	[0.1, 1]	[0.5, 5]
solar panel	[1e-2, 1e-1]	[5, 20]
MLI	[1e-3, 1e-2]	[25, 75]

With these settings, extensive datasets are generated for training and validation. Since it is observed that large datasets lead to a better generalization of the network and avoid overfitting, a dataset containing half a million point clouds is generated. This dataset is split as follows, where 80% of the point clouds are used for training, and 20% for validation:

- Synthetic training dataset: 400 000 point clouds;
- Synthetic validation dataset: 100 000 point clouds.

The training dataset is typically used to train the network, while the validation dataset is used as a reference to optimize the model and tune its hyperparameters. Finally, only once the model is set, evaluation is performed on a real lidar dataset.

Figure 4.4: Lidar point cloud simulated under the same conditions for different reflectivity values of the golden MLI covering the target satellite. Front view (a) and side view (d) for $k_d = 5e-3$. Front view (b) and side view (e) for $k_d = 1.1e-3$. Front view (c) and side view (f) for $k_d = 5e-4$.

4.2 Pose labeling of a symmetrical satellite

When designing a neural network for single-stage pose estimation from point clouds or depth images, an important point is to carefully design what the network has to learn. Obviously, for our problem, the network has to learn the relative pose of the target with respect to the spacecraft. The relative position consists of three continuous parameters, which are not a difficulty for a network to learn. However, finding a continuous encoding for the relative attitude is less trivial, especially in case of a symmetrical object [250, 251]. Many satellites, and in particular the satellite that we consider in our experiments at EPOS, present a symmetrical shape, which is why this problem is of practical relevance [174, 172]. This section describes a continuous attitude encoding for attitude estimation of symmetrical objects with neural networks.

4.2.1 Problem overview

Neural networks are universal approximators [252], yet, are much more easily trained and optimized to learn continuous functions. In particular, low-dimensional attitude representations have discontinuities: For example, the mapping from a rotation to Euler angles is discontinuous (if we gradually increase the first Euler angle θ above 2π , it switches back to $\theta = 0$). Likewise, the axis angle and quaternion representations are discontinuous [250]. On the contrary, representing a rotation with an attitude matrix is an over-parameterization, since two axes (6 parameters) of a rotated coordinate frame are sufficient to infer the last one. Zhou et al. [250]

show that a minimal continuous representation of a rotation has 5 parameters, and suggest using such a 5-dimensional representation for learning rotations with neural networks.

However, considering the attitude of a symmetrical object introduces additional discontinuities. We motivate our approach with a 2D example, illustrated in Fig. 4.5. In the absence of symmetries (left on the illustration), a rotation is represented by an angle $\alpha \in [0, 2\pi]$. To obtain a continuous representation of this rotation, one possibility is to take the first column of the 2D rotation matrix associated with the angle α . This means that the rotation is parametrized by the 2D vector $r_\alpha = (\cos \alpha \quad \sin \alpha)^T$, which is a continuous representation of the object's attitude. Next, we consider the case of an object with a planar symmetry (for example, this object is a rectangle in the middle of Fig. 4.5). Rotating this object by $\pm\pi$ leaves it unchanged from an observer point of view, so that parametrizing its attitude with an angle $\alpha \in [0, \pi]$ is sufficient to unambiguously describe its state for an observer.

Figure 4.5: Schematic representation of the attitude labeling in case of symmetries in a 2D case.

Now, if r_α is kept to describe the rotation in the symmetrical case, we observe that this parametrization becomes discontinuous when α switches between π and 0 : We have $r_0 = (1 \quad 0)^T$ and $r_\pi = (-1 \quad 0)^T$, while these two rotations are considered equivalent. A possibility, illustrated on the right in Fig. 4.5, is to define discrete attitude labels, associated with weights. For example, in the case illustrated on the image, the object is between labels “A” and “B” and could have interpolation weights of 0.1 for label “A”, and 0.9 for label “B”. Such a representation is continuous for all rotations, and is invariant by a rotation of the object of $\pm\pi$.

Remark: In this 2D case, there are simpler solutions to define a continuous attitude representation for the symmetrical object. For example, instead of choosing discrete labels, the function $\alpha \rightarrow (\cos(2\alpha) \quad \sin(2\alpha))^T$ is such a parametrization. However, such an approach does not directly translate to the 3D case, since Euler angles used to describe a 3D rotation are not only discontinuous, but also singular. This means that the Euler angles cannot be uniquely obtained given a certain rotation, so that an approach based on modifying these Euler angles is not directly applicable.

In 3D, finding a continuous representation of the attitude of a symmetrical object is not trivial. To perform pose estimation of symmetrical objects, Pitteri et al. [251] suggest training not one, but multiple neural networks, each of them for a fraction of the attitude space. A classifier network is used in a first step to determine which network should be chosen to estimate

the pose of a given object, thus avoiding the discontinuity. Differently, Hodan et al. [253] address this problem by dividing an object into labeled fragments. The pose estimation is tasked with estimating, for each pixel, to which fragment of the object it corresponds, but multiple correspondences are possible to account for symmetries. The final pose is retrieved with a modified PnP method. Our approach, schematically illustrated in Fig. 4.5, is very different: We suggest sampling the attitude space into discrete bins, and ensuring that this encoding remains continuous when object symmetries are introduced.

4.2.2 Uniform sampling of the attitude space

We first introduce the sampling and labeling strategy for a non-symmetrical spacecraft, which will serve as a basis when later considering the symmetrical case. Although they do not consider the case of a symmetrical spacecraft, dividing the attitude in several bins to train an attitude classifier is a principle that was applied to camera based spacecraft pose estimation by [173, 176]. When generating attitude samples, care has to be taken that the samples are uniformly distributed in the attitude space. Sharma and D’Amico [176] use a random bin generation approach: Random attitudes are generated, before only a well-spaced sub-sample of these attitudes is kept to define the bins. Differently, for a template matching algorithm, Guo et al. [146] also divide the attitude space, applying a triangular mesh sampling computed numerically.

We seek a simple and deterministic method for dividing the attitude space into uniform bins. To this aim, we first define the roll, pitch and yaw angles of the target, a usual convention of Euler angles for describing the attitude of a satellite. The roll angle is $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$, the pitch $\theta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ and the yaw $\psi \in [0, 2\pi]$ such that the attitude of the target in the lidar coordinate frame is

$$R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{L}} = R_Z(\psi)R_Y(\theta)R_X(\phi), \quad (4.8)$$

where $R_{\mathcal{T}}^{\mathcal{L}}$ is the rotation matrix from the target to the lidar coordinate frame, and R_X, R_Y, R_Z are rotation matrices of the given angle around the axes x, y, z respectively.

The uniform discretization of the attitude space should have a fix angular resolution $\Delta\alpha$. We consider first the yaw angle ψ and the roll angle θ . These two angles define the direction of the target’s x -axis in the reference frame. If we find a uniform discretization of these two angles, then the discrete values of the roll angle ϕ are simply

$$\phi_k = k\Delta\alpha, \quad k = 1, \dots, N_\phi, \quad (4.9)$$

where N_ϕ is the largest integer such that $N_\phi\Delta\alpha < 2\pi$. Denoting by $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ the integer part of a real number, it writes

$$N_\phi = \lfloor \frac{2\pi}{\Delta\alpha} \rfloor. \quad (4.10)$$

A naive approach would also be to choose ψ and θ equally spaced, but this would lead to a non-uniform distribution in the attitude space. Indeed, the position of the x axis of the target spacecraft would then be concentrated on the poles, as illustrated on Figure 4.6a.

To ensure a uniform distribution on the unit sphere, we use a uniform spiral sampling strategy as in Wong and Roos [254]. Given a desired number of samples on the sphere n_s , the discrete

Figure 4.6: Resulting orientations of the x -axis on the half unit sphere resulting from (a) the naive sampling approach and (b) the uniform spiral sampling approach. The sampling resolution $\Delta\alpha$ is chosen equal to 5° .

values for the yaw and pitch angles given by

$$\begin{cases} \psi_k = \sqrt{n_s\pi} \arcsin\left(\frac{2k - (n_s - 1)}{n_s}\right) \\ \theta_k = \arccos\left(\frac{2k - (n_s - 1)}{n_s}\right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \end{cases}, \quad k = 0, \dots, n_s - 1. \quad (4.11)$$

The number of samples n_s is chosen to match with the desired angular resolution $\Delta\alpha$. For this spiral path on the sphere, the distance between two adjacent points on the spiral is $\sqrt{4\pi/n_s}$ [254]. This distance corresponds to the desired angular resolution, so that the total number of sampled pitch and yaw angles is

$$n_s = \lfloor \frac{4\pi}{\Delta\alpha^2} \rfloor. \quad (4.12)$$

The result of this sampling strategy for the pitch and yaw angles is shown on Figure 4.6b. In summary, the attitude samples are parametrized by the roll-pitch-yaw angles $(\phi_i, \theta_j, \psi_j)$ for $i = 1, \dots, N_\phi$ and $j = 1, \dots, n_s$.

4.2.3 Attitude label weights for the non-symmetrical case

The attitude sampling strategy produces $N = N_\phi \times n_s$ attitude samples which we identify to their rotation matrices and denote R_1, \dots, R_N . Next, a rotation R needs to be assigned to each label with a certain weight. In case of a hard encoding, each attitude is associated with the closest attitude label R_i . However, such an encoding is both discontinuous, and is only as precise as the angular resolution of the sampling $\Delta\alpha$. Therefore, an attitude is assigned soft weights w_1, \dots, w_N corresponding to each sample. This is the encoding function L . The decoding is the

inverse operation Γ . The transformation chain is summarized as follows:

$$R \xrightarrow[\text{encoding}]{L} \begin{pmatrix} w_1 \\ \dots \\ w_N \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow[\text{decoding}]{\Gamma} R. \quad (4.13)$$

Because w_1, \dots, w_N are interpreted as interpolation weights, we additionally impose the constraint $w_i \geq 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$, and $\sum_i w_i = 1$.

Decoding

Our approach consists in first defining the decoding function Γ , before searching for an appropriate encoding function L . The reason is that the definition of Γ is more straightforward. Following [176, 173], the decoding function is defined such that

$$\Gamma(w_1, \dots, w_N) = \arg \min_{R \in SO(3)} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \|R - R_i\|^2, \quad (4.14)$$

where the matrix norm is the Frobenius norm.

Remark: Another possibility would be to consider the distance in the rotation group instead of the Frobenius norm, i.e., to define Γ as the rotation which minimizes $\sum_i w_i d(R, R_i)^2$. However, contrarily to (4.14), there is no known analytical solution to this minimization problem [255].

There is an explicit solution to the minimization problem (4.14). This solution is given by [255]

$$\Gamma(w_1, \dots, w_N) = \text{Proj}_{SO(3)} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N w_i R_i \right), \quad (4.15)$$

where $\text{Proj}_{SO(3)}$ is the orthogonal projection on the rotation group. The projection is obtained by decomposition with SVD. If a matrix M is decomposed via SVD in $M = U\Sigma V^T$, then the projection function is

$$\text{Proj}_{SO(3)}(M) = UV^T. \quad (4.16)$$

Encoding

Having defined the decoding function, we search for a suited encoding function L . Ideally, L would be an inverse of Γ , i.e., $L = \Gamma^{-1}$. However, such an inverse is not known analytically. Sharma and D'Amico [176] suggest using weights depending linearly on the angular distance of the attitude to each label. These weights are of the form $w_i \propto 1 - d(R, R_i)/\pi^2$. On the contrary, Proença and Gao [173] use exponential weights. However, the value of their smoothing factor is not specified. Similarly, we suggest using exponential weights to encode an attitude R into weights. For $i = 1, \dots, N$, the weights are

$$w_i = K \exp\left(-\frac{d(R, R_i)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad \text{where } K = \frac{1}{\sum_i \exp\left(-\frac{d(R, R_i)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)}. \quad (4.17)$$

The standard deviation σ is chosen proportional to the angular resolution of the attitude sampling $\Delta\alpha$. We set this value such that $3\sigma = 2\Delta\alpha$, and justify it in the following.

Justification of the encoding weights

The choice of the encoding weights in (4.17), and in particular of the value of the standard deviation σ , is justified experimentally. We seek to have L be approximately an inverse of Γ , i.e., the function $\Gamma \circ L$ should be as close as possible to the identity. Considering an attitude R encoded into label weights $L(R)$, it is decoded into $\tilde{R} = \Gamma(L(R))$. Thus, a good labeling function should minimize the error of the transformation chain

$$\epsilon_{\text{labeling}}(R) = d(R, \tilde{R}). \quad (4.18)$$

The “labeling error” $\epsilon_{\text{labeling}}$ is dependent on a given attitude R . To estimate the mean error of this function over the rotation group, we perform a Monte-Carlo evaluation. We generate 10 000 attitudes randomly, and for each attitude, compute the labeling error, before averaging these errors. We compare following labeling functions:

- The labeling function of [176], where $w_i \propto 1 - d(R, R_i)/\pi^2$;
- The labeling function (4.17), for different values of the standard deviation: $\sigma = \Delta\alpha/2$, $\sigma = 2\Delta\alpha/3$ and $\sigma = \Delta\alpha$.

The labeling functions are compared for different resolutions of the attitude sampling $\Delta\alpha$. The results of this statistical evaluation are presented in Fig. 4.7. They indicate that exponential weights lead to a lower error of the attitude labeling chain than linear weights (blue curve). Between the three possible choices for the standard deviation, $\sigma = 2\Delta\alpha/3$ seems to be the most appropriate one. For all the considered range of sampling resolutions $\Delta\alpha$, between 10 deg and 30 deg, it consistently leads to a low transformation error (green curve). The exponential labeling with a standard deviation $\sigma = \Delta\alpha/2$ (orange curve) has a higher average error for all the considered range. On the contrary, a standard deviation equal to $\Delta\alpha$ (red curve) gives a low transformation error for low values of $\Delta\alpha$, but an average transformation error above 3 deg when the attitude sampling resolution is of 30 deg.

4.2.4 Attitude label weights for a symmetrical spacecraft

Target spacecraft symmetries

The spacecraft considered as a use case for the development of the pose estimation, and for the experiments at EPOS, presents some symmetries. Views of a 3D model of this spacecraft are presented in Fig. 4.8. The coordinate frame of the target satellite is recalled in Fig. 4.8a. The satellite has a hexagonal shape, on top of which a tower is mounted. Without further details, it could be assumed that the target’s symmetry number is 6, i.e., all rotations of the hexagon by 60 deg lead to the same configuration. However, additional details on the satellite enable to discriminate between some configurations. In particular, the satellite has three small antennas (the axis y_{tar} is passing through one of them). Likewise, handlebars are mounted on the other corners of the hexagon. This enables to reduce the symmetry number of the satellite to 3. As illustrated on Fig. 4.8b, a rotation of ± 120 deg around the roll axis x_{tar} leaves the satellite’s configuration unchanged for an observer.

Figure 4.7: Statistical evaluation of the mean angular error of the labeling transformation for different labeling functions.

Figure 4.8: Symmetries of the target satellite (a) Coordinate frame definition; (b) Symmetry around the roll axis, target viewed from the front. The symmetry number is 3.

Formally, for a given attitude R of the spacecraft, we consider that three attitudes are equivalent, and write them $R^{(1)}, R^{(2)}, R^{(3)}$. One of them is equal to the original attitude R . These attitudes are called symmetrical equivalents of R , and we write

$$R \sim R^{(i)}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (4.19)$$

Similarly, we define a symmetrical distance function, so that symmetrical equivalents are equal (at a distance of 0) for this definition of the distance. The symmetrical angular distance function

of two possible attitudes of the spacecraft $R, Q \in SO(3)$ is defined by

$$d_{\text{sym}}(R, Q) = \min_{i=1,2,3} d(R^{(i)}, Q). \quad (4.20)$$

In this symmetrical case, the objective of the pose initialization changes. Instead of aiming at estimating the exact attitude of the spacecraft, the objective is to find this attitude modulo the given symmetries of the spacecraft. The goal is to minimize the symmetrical angular distance d_{sym} between the target's real, and estimated attitude.

Attitude encoding and decoding with symmetries

Due to the symmetries of the target satellite, some attitude samples R_1, \dots, R_N defined in Section 4.2.2 are redundant, or symmetrically equivalent, and should be removed. In particular, the roll samples $\phi_k = k\Delta\alpha$ defined in (4.9) are a uniform sampling of the interval $[0, 2\pi]$ with spacing $\Delta\alpha$. These samples are reduced to be taken only in the interval $[0, 2\pi/3]$ since a rotation with roll-pitch-yaw angles (ϕ, θ, ψ) is symmetrically equivalent to a rotation with angles $(\phi \pm 2\pi/3, \theta, \psi)$.

By removing all samples corresponding to a roll angle above $2\pi/3$, all symmetrical equivalents are removed. With this new sampling, the number of attitude samples is divided by 3 compared to sampling the full attitude space. The new attitude labels will be indexed by $M = N/3$ and denoted by R_1, \dots, R_M . The encoding and decoding are adapted to this new sampling and distance definition. The attitude encoding function in case of symmetries becomes L_{sym} . It is defined analogously to (4.17), with the only difference that the symmetrical angular distance function is used:

$$L_{\text{sym}}(R) = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 \\ \dots \\ l_M \end{pmatrix}, \quad l_i = K_{\text{sym}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_{\text{sym}}(R, R_i)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (4.21)$$

where K_{sym} is a normalization constant, such that $\sum_i l_i = 1$.

The definition of the symmetrical decoding function Γ_{sym} requires more modifications. First, it has to be noted that it is not possible to be ensured to retrieve the same attitude R after having embedded it into a symmetrical encoding $L_{\text{sym}}(R)$. The decoded attitude $\Gamma_{\text{sym}}(L_{\text{sym}}(R))$ will only be a symmetrical equivalent of the original attitude.

Since a decoded attitude is one of the three symmetrical equivalents, a choice has to be taken. Thus, given weights l_1, \dots, l_M , the first step of the decoding function is to set an attitude which will serve as a reference. This attitude corresponds to the sample with the maximum weight, denoted by $R_{i_{\text{max}}}$, with

$$i_{\text{max}} = \arg \max_{i=1, \dots, M} l_i. \quad (4.22)$$

Next, for each attitude sample R_i , out of its three symmetrical equivalents $R_i^{(1)}, R_i^{(2)}, R_i^{(3)}$, the one closest to $R_{i_{\text{max}}}$ is selected. This attitude is $R_i^{(k_i)}$, where the index k_i is defined by:

$$k_i = \arg \min_{k=1,2,3} d(R_i^{(k)}, R_{i_{\text{max}}}). \quad (4.23)$$

A final modification is made to the decoding function. Instead of considering all attitude samples for the projection, only the ones which are sufficiently close to the reference attitude are considered. By sufficiently close is meant that an angular threshold Δ_{max} is set, such that all attitude samples further away are discarded. Hence, the decoding function accounting for symmetries is

$$\Gamma_{\text{sym}}(l_1, \dots, l_M) = \text{Proj}_{SO(3)} \left(\sum_{\substack{i=1, \dots, M \\ d_{\text{sym}}(R_i, R_{i_{\text{max}}}) < \Delta_{max}}} l_i R_i^{(k_i)} \right). \quad (4.24)$$

For the target spacecraft considered in the experiments, the angular threshold is set to $\Delta_{max} = 50$ deg. This angular threshold enables to improve the precision of the attitude estimation when decoding the weights predicted by the neural network into an attitude. Indeed, due to the hexagonal shape of the satellite (Fig. 4.8), if a certain attitude is a likely estimate, the same attitude rotated around the roll axis by ± 60 deg is also a likely estimate, save for the antennas and handlebars which should help in the decision. Therefore, the network might predict high weights for both attitude classes. If a simple average of these rotations is performed, the final estimate will lie in between these two classes, which is certainly not the correct estimate. By setting the threshold Δ_{max} lower than 60 deg, only the one of these two candidates with the highest weight is considered for the weighted average (4.24). As such, the threshold helps to discriminate between several attitudes when the pose estimated by the network is ambiguous.

In summary, (4.21) is a continuous encoding of the attitude, transforming an attitude into a weights vector $L_{\text{sym}}(R)$. Most importantly, it remains continuous when the target symmetries are considered, i.e., if two attitudes are close for the symmetrical distance d_{sym} , their weights encoding are close for the Euclidean distance $\|\cdot\|$. The continuity of this attitude encoding when accounting for symmetries will be essential when training a neural network to learn the embedding. The other way around, the decoding function Γ_{sym} enables to find one of the symmetrical equivalents of the attitude predicted by the neural network. Interestingly, this function is discontinuous in the result space for the classical angular distance d , but not for the symmetrical distance d_{sym} .

Other types of symmetries

The attitude labeling accounting for symmetries presented in Section 4.2.4 will be used in the rest of this Chapter to design a pose estimation method for the satellite mock-up used at EPOS. However, this use case is only one special case of a symmetrical spacecraft, and many other configurations are possible. The proposed strategy is not specific to this spacecraft, and is applicable to other types of symmetries. In the following, we list examples of how the pose encoding is adapted for some other symmetrical configurations, illustrated in Fig. 4.9.

When considering these shapes, modifications to the attitude sampling strategy presented in Section 4.2.2 have to be applied. The original sampling generates discrete values for the roll $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$, the pitch $\theta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, and yaw $\psi \in [0, 2\pi]$. The symmetrical embedding for these cases is generated by removing samples corresponding to symmetric equivalents. This sub-sampling of the original sampling is achieved by only keeping attitudes corresponding to roll, pitch and yaw angles in the following range:

Figure 4.9: Example of symmetrical shapes for space objects: (a) rocket; (b) cylinder; (c) cube; (d) satellite with 4 solar panels; (e) satellite with 2 solar panels.

- **Rocket:** The attitude is described only by the pointing direction of the rocket. The most straightforward way is to parametrize this attitude with a normalized 3D vector defining this orientation. If using the attitude sampling, it is sufficient to parametrize the attitude only with two angles, pitch θ and yaw ψ .
- **Cylinder:** In addition to the previous case, the cylinder can be flipped upside down. Imposing an additional constraint on the pitch angle, for example $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$, enables to remove symmetrical equivalents.
- **Cube:** Three angles are needed to describe the attitude for this case. To remove all equivalent classes, it is sufficient to constraint all three angles such that $\phi, \theta, \psi \in [0, \pi/2]$.
- **Satellite with 4 solar panels:** This case is identical to a rectangular shape with two equal sides and one of different length ($a = b \neq c$). If the roll angle is defined as the rotation perpendicular to the solar panels, it has to be constrained such that $\phi \in [0, \pi/2]$. In addition, imposing for example a pitch $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$ enables to remove the last symmetry case, when the satellite is flipped and seen from “behind” compared to illustration in Fig. 4.9d.
- **Satellite with 2 solar panels:** This case is identical to a rectangular shape where all sides have different lengths ($a \neq b \neq c$). Similarly to previous case, the roll is to be constrained such that $\phi \in [0, \pi]$, and the pitch such that $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$.

4.3 CNN based pose initialization

After presenting the lidar simulator and an attitude encoding logic, the neural network for the pose initialization task is now introduced. In this Section, we investigate projecting the point cloud to a depth image to perform pose estimation using a CNN architecture. The approach of treating the point cloud as a 2D image is similar to [180–182]. The main difference is that we suggest a single-stage network design to directly retrieve pose estimates from a depth image, and select efficient CNN architectures in the prospect of onboard applicability.

An overview of the suggested CNN-based pose initialization pipeline is shown in Fig. 4.10. The first stage, illustrated on the left, is to extract the centroid of the point cloud, before projecting it to a normalized depth image. This image is then passed to a neural network with a CNN backbone, and producing two outputs to estimate the relative pose: On the one hand, the attitude weights enable to estimate the relative attitude, and on the other hand, the position of the satellite with respect to the point cloud’s centroid is estimated. This logic will be presented in detail in the following.

Figure 4.10: Overview of the CNN-based pose estimation pipeline.

4.3.1 Pre-processing

Trimmed centroid estimation

The 3D point cloud data already contains information about the target satellite’s position. However, the center of mass (or centroid) of the point cloud does not necessarily coincide with the position of the satellite’s center of mass $\boldsymbol{\rho}$, which is the position to be estimated. In general, the centroid of the point cloud is closer to the sensor than the satellite’s center of mass, since the lidar captures points on the satellite’s surface. Still, the centroid is a useful starting point to select the Region Of Interest (ROI) and normalize the depth image.

The first step of the pre-processing is to estimate the position of the centroid, which is denoted by \mathbf{c} . A regular centroid estimate consists in an average of the coordinates of all points. However, if not filtered out, outliers have a strong impact on such a mean. It was observed in the previous experiments at EPOS (Section 2.5.1) that the point clouds contain a high fraction

of outliers, due to sensor noise and the high reflectivity of the satellite materials, leading to multiple reflections. In particular, double reflections lead to “ghost reflections”, i.e., points in the cloud located at twice the distance at which they are in reality.

To filter out some of these artifacts, we suggest a simple but robust modification of the centroid computation: Instead of computing the mean of the points coordinates along each dimension, the trimmed centroid consists in computing the trimmed (or truncated) mean of the points for each dimension. The principle of a trimmed mean is to remove a pre-defined fraction of outliers, i.e., of the highest and lowest values in a dataset, before computing the mean. For example, when the trimming factor is 25 %, the lowest and highest 25 % of the values of the dataset are removed. This is also known as the interquartile mean, since it corresponds to computing the average of all data point belonging only to the second and third quartiles of the data.

Formally, let $(\mathbf{z}_i)_{1 \leq i \leq N_z}$ be the source point cloud. Each point has coordinates denoted by $\mathbf{z}_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i)^T$. There exists individual re-orderings $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$ of the range $1, \dots, N$ for each dimension such that the coordinates of the point cloud are sorted:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\sigma_x(1)} &\leq \dots \leq x_{\sigma_x(N_z)}, \\ y_{\sigma_y(1)} &\leq \dots \leq y_{\sigma_y(N_z)}, \\ z_{\sigma_z(1)} &\leq \dots \leq z_{\sigma_z(N_z)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.25)$$

Let $p \in [0, 0.5]$ be the trimming fraction. The trimmed centroid is obtained by:

$$\mathbf{c} = \frac{1}{n_{1-p} - n_p + 1} \sum_{i=n_p}^{n_{1-p}} \begin{pmatrix} x_{\sigma_x(i)} \\ y_{\sigma_y(i)} \\ z_{\sigma_z(i)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.26)$$

with $n_p = \lfloor pN_z \rfloor$ and $n_{(1-p)} = \lfloor (1-p)N_z \rfloor$. In particular, if $p = 0$, the trimmed centroid equals the classical centroid, and if $p = 0.5$, the trimmed centroid equals the median.

In our experiments, we will use a trimming fraction $p = 0.25$ (interquartile mean), but this parameter is adjustable depending on the quality of the point cloud data. Compared to a classical centroid, the trimmed centroid (4.26) leads to a more consistent estimate across point clouds with different noise and outlier values.

Projection to a depth image

If the full field-of-view of the lidar is projected to a depth image, only a sub-portion of the image, where the target is located, will contain relevant information. Therefore, only a selected Region Of Interest (ROI) of the scene will be projected to the depth image. This ROI is defined as a cubic bounding box. The cubic shape of the ROI will enable projection on a square image, and since there is no information about the attitude of the target at this time, there is no reason to have a different image width than height. This cube has a certain edge length l , which depends on the expected size of the target satellite. For the mock-up considered in this work and installed at EPOS, the length is set to $l = 4$ m.

The logic for the depth image projection is illustrated in Fig. 4.11. The ROI is selected by setting its center at the location of the trimmed centroid \mathbf{c} . Once this region is defined, all points

outside the box are removed from the point cloud, so that potential outliers are removed. This corresponds to keeping only points \mathbf{z}_i of the cloud satisfying $\|\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{c}\|_\infty < l/2$, where the infinity (or maximum) norm is used. Afterwards, the point cloud is normalized. For $i = 1, \dots, N_z$, the normalized coordinates of the point cloud are

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{c}}{l} + \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.5 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.27)$$

This ensures that each normalized $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_i$ has its three coordinates in the range $[0, 1]$.

Figure 4.11: Steps of the depth image projection: The point cloud is normalized around its centroid, before being projected to a 2D depth image.

The final step is to project the normalized point cloud to a depth image. This projection is not performed with a pinhole camera model, but with a weak perspective projection. The advantage of this projection is that for a same point cloud, if the lidar is placed at different positions (but with the same orientation), the final depth image will be identical. The weak perspective projection is independent of the lidar's relative translation. This enables to help decouple the position estimation problem from the attitude estimation.

Formally, the projection on a square image with $N_p \times N_p$ pixels is obtained as follows. Each pixel is denoted by $p_{i,j}$ with $1 \leq i, j \leq N_p$. For each pixel, the set of points in the cloud belonging to that pixel is

$$\mathcal{P}_{i,j} = \left\{ (\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_k)_{1 \leq k \leq N_z} \text{ such that } \tilde{x}_k \in \left[\frac{i-1}{N_p}, \frac{i}{N_p} \right], \text{ and } \tilde{y}_k \in \left[\frac{j-1}{N_p}, \frac{j}{N_p} \right] \right\}. \quad (4.28)$$

The depth value of pixel $p_{i,j}$ is then the average of the z coordinates of all points belonging to that pixel, and 1 if no point falls into that pixel:

$$p_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |\mathcal{P}_{i,j}| = 0 \\ \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}_{i,j}|} \sum_{\tilde{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathcal{P}_{i,j}} \tilde{z} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (4.29)$$

where $|\mathcal{P}_{i,j}|$ is the number of points in the set $\mathcal{P}_{i,j}$. In the depth image of Fig. 4.11, the background is black corresponding here to a depth value of 1, while closer points are brighter, corresponding to pixel values close to 0.

The normalized depth image contains information about the relative attitude of the target, independently of the relative position. Also, with the pixel depth values, the image contains information about the position of the satellite’s center of mass with respect to the centroid of the point cloud, i.e., with respect to the central point used for normalization. These are the two components that the neural network will try to estimate from the images.

4.3.2 Neural network design

CNN backbone

For processing the depth image, it is chosen to apply existing CNN models, without further modifications. The field of processing with CNNs is a mature field with multiple available architectures usable for various tasks, such as image classification, segmentation, object detection or face recognition [256]. Therefore, in this section, we focus less on the Artificial Intelligence (AI) models themselves than on the complete pipeline including pre-processing and post-processing with the encoding strategy. Particular focus is also put on the quality of the input data that is used to train the network. Such an approach is also referred to as data-centric AI [257], as opposed to model-centric AI which focuses on developing novel neural network architectures for a given task.

Many modern CNN architectures are available [256]. For the application considered in this work, the selection of a model is restricted to architectures with comparatively low runtimes when evaluated on a CPU. Also, preference is given to models already implemented in widespread AI libraries such as TensorFlow [258]. Among those models, a widespread alternative is the family of MobileNet models, the latest being MobileNetV3 [259]. The MobileNet models have been developed specifically for applications on edge devices. For camera-based pose estimation in space, Black et al. [168] suggested using a MobileNetV2 architecture [169].

Compared to a standard CNN with several convolutional layers, the main characteristics of the MobileNetv3 architecture are: The network uses depth-wise separable convolutions [260], which enable to achieve a similar result as a standard convolution with less multiplications, making the evaluations run faster. Other features include the use of residual connections [177], squeeze-and-excitation blocks [261], and a hard-swish activation function [259].

MobileNetV3 comes in two versions, a small and a large one, MobileNetV3-S and MobileNetV3-L, respectively. Alternatively, the class of EfficientNet models [179, 262] is also a popular choice for inference on edge devices. These models use similar principles as the MobileNet models. An EfficientNetV1 backbone was applied for camera pose estimation in space by Park and D’Amico [175]. The EfficientNet models are in general larger and slower than MobileNet models. EfficientNetV2 [262] comes in regular and “lite” versions, among which the smallest model is EfficientNetV2-B0. This last model will also be used for comparison.

Both MobileNetV3 and EfficientNetV2B0 architectures are designed for image sizes with a resolution of 224×224 . While this resolution could be modified, we keep this default resolution for the depth image projection, i.e., we set $N_p = 224$. The implementations of these backbones

in TensorFlow are openly available [258] and used without modifications.

Top layers

Neural network architectures typically produce a feature vector, i.e., the input image is transformed into a one-dimensional vector of a certain size. This feature vector is then processed by further fully connected layers to produce a classification result. This feature vector has a different size for the three considered models: It is of size 576 for MobileNetV3-S, 960 for MobileNetV3-L, and 1280 for EfficientNetV2B0.

The feature vector is directly passed to a double prediction head, as illustrated in Fig. 4.10. This means that the feature vector is independently processed by each prediction head, the first to estimate the attitude weights, and the second to estimate the position shift. For the attitude, a fully connected layer enables to reduce the size of the feature vector to M , the number of attitude classes accounting for symmetries. This attitude vector is formed of values $x_1^{att}, \dots, x_M^{att} \in \mathbb{R}$. To ensure attitude labels in $[0, 1]$ and with a normalized sum, softmax [263] is finally applied, so that the attitude weights vector predicted by the network is, for $i = 1, \dots, M$,

$$l_i = \frac{e^{x_i^{att}}}{\sum_{j=1}^M e^{x_j^{att}}}. \quad (4.30)$$

The estimated attitude is obtained from these weights by computing $\Gamma_{\text{sym}}(l_1, \dots, l_M)$ (Eq. (4.24)).

The second prediction head is tasked with obtaining the position. However, since the depth image was normalized around the point cloud centroid \mathbf{c} , the absolute position information was lost, and cannot be retrieved from the image. Thus, the position prediction head will not aim at estimating the position of the target with respect to the chaser, but only the position of the target with respect to the centroid \mathbf{c} which was used for normalization. This position is the position shift $\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}$. We have:

$$\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho} = \boldsymbol{\rho} - \mathbf{c}, \quad (4.31)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ is the position of the target's center of mass with respect to the chaser.

To estimate the position shift, the feature vector is processed by two consecutive fully connected layers. The intermediate layer is of size 128 with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation [263], and the final layer of size 3. The three position estimates $x_1^{pos}, x_2^{pos}, x_3^{pos} \in \mathbb{R}$ are then processed to ensure that they are within $[-l/2, l/2]$. Indeed, the ROI being a cube of side l centered around the centroid, we assume that the position of the target's center of mass must also be in this cube. This is achieved with the tanh activation function and additional scaling: The position shift estimates of the neural network are, for $i = 1, 2, 3$,

$$\Delta\rho_i = \frac{l}{2} \tanh(x_i^{pos}). \quad (4.32)$$

Finally, the relative position estimate is given by $\boldsymbol{\rho} = \mathbf{c} + \Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}$, as illustrated in Fig. 4.10.

4.3.3 Training

Loss and optimization

The neural network predicts attitude labels (l_1, \dots, l_M) , and a position shift $\Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}$. During training, it learns to minimize the difference between these predictions and both the ground truth labels $(\bar{l}_1, \dots, \bar{l}_M)$, and the ground truth position shift $\Delta\bar{\boldsymbol{\rho}}$. For classification tasks, cross-entropy is usually selected as a loss function. This is found in the implementation of widespread neural network architectures [259, 262]. For the position estimate, the objective is to minimize the distance between the estimated and real position, so that mean-squared-error is a natural choice. The overall loss function is a weighted sum of these two losses:

$$\text{loss} = - \sum_{i=1}^M \bar{l}_i \log l_i + \lambda \frac{\|\Delta\bar{\boldsymbol{\rho}} - \Delta\boldsymbol{\rho}\|^2}{3}, \quad (4.33)$$

where λ is the weighting parameter between the attitude and position loss.

The pose estimation method for the three different backbones (MobileNetV3-S, MobileNetV3-L, EfficientNetV2B0) is implemented in Python using the TensorFlow library [258]. An implementation of the backbones is already available, so that only the pre-processing and top layers have to be implemented. The backbones are trained starting from the weights optimized for the ImageNet [264] dataset. This is not a transfer learning approach, since most weights are re-optimized during the learning process, and the application (pose estimation on depth images) is very different from the ImageNet dataset (classification of RGB images). However, starting from the initialized weights helps to improve the learning time and final accuracy of the model. For the MobileNet backbones, the only layers that are not re-trained are the batch normalization layers. This follows the recommendation of Chollet [265]. Indeed, it is found that retraining the batch normalization layers leads to unstable training and poor final results. On the contrary, for the EfficientNet backbone, it is found to be beneficial to re-train the batch normalization layers. Therefore, the training process is different for each backbone.

Another difference in the training process between the two types of backbones concerns the dropout. During training, a dropout layer is added for regularization. This dropout layer is inserted before the two prediction heads, and has a dropout rate of 0.2 for the MobileNet models, as in the original training setup of MobileNetV3 [259]. For the EfficientNetV2 backbone, we find a dropout rate of 0.4 to lead to a lower final validation loss, which is why the rate is set differently. Data augmentation is also performed for all models, and will be detailed in the next subsection.

The models are trained on the synthetic training dataset containing 400 000 point clouds (Section 4.1.2). For minimizing the loss, the Adam optimizer [266] is used. An initial learning rate of 1e-4 is chosen. Higher learning rates are observed to make the training unstable, while lower learning rates lead to slow convergence, requiring many epochs to converge. The number of epochs, i.e., the number of times the entire dataset is seen by the network during the learning process, is set to 35. This number is chosen by observing the variation of the validation loss, i.e., the loss function (4.33) evaluated on the synthetic validation dataset, after each epoch. It is observed that after this number of epochs, the validation loss does not decrease anymore and enters a plateau, signifying that the optimization is finished. The batch size (number of images evaluated simultaneously for computing the gradients in the optimization) is set to 32.

Data augmentation

Data augmentation is a standard practice in machine learning to artificially enlarge a dataset [267, 177, 257]. It prevents overfitting, i.e., the specialization of the network on the test data and its inability to generalize to different data. Data augmentation consists in randomly modifying the inputs of the neural network to increase its robustness, and is applied only during training, not during inference. For the CNN model, we perform data augmentation on the 2D depth images, and not on the point clouds themselves.

Standard image augmentation techniques consists in randomly cropping, rotating, distorting or flipping the images. However, such augmentation is not necessarily adapted to the problem of pose estimation, since for example rotating or translating an image modifies the relative pose observed on the depth image, and makes learning of the relative pose impossible. Still, to make the network more robust to potential differences between the geometric model on which it was trained and the actual satellite, small deformations are performed, as illustrated on Fig. 4.12b. The input image is randomly zoomed in or out by a factor at most 15%. This is performed independently for the vertical and horizontal dimensions, resulting in a possible deformation of the image.

Figure 4.12: Image data augmentation: (a) Reference depth image; (b) Distorted image; (c) Addition of a black patch; (d) Addition of outliers; (e) Addition of a reflection patch; (f) Combination of all data augmentation layers.

In addition, custom data augmentation layers are developed specifically for this context of training on depth images originating from a lidar sensor. The first type of custom data augmentation layer is the addition of a random black patches, illustrated in Fig. 4.12c. Such

a patch masks a region of the depth image, replacing the pixels by black pixels. However, to mimic the behavior where a surface only partially disappears when scanned with a lidar because of its reflectivity, a patch is not fully black: It has an occupancy probability, set in this work to 95%: This means that 5% of the pixels within the patch keep their original value.

Instead of removing points, some artificial points are also added by data augmentation. This is the addition of noise, i.e., of some pixels with a random depth value at random locations, as illustrated in Fig. 4.12d. Finally, instead of single points, greater areas are added to mimic potential artifacts in the point cloud. This is illustrated in Fig. 4.12e. Such a reflection patch modifies the values of a certain region in the image to random depth values distributed uniformly around a certain mean, chosen at random as well. Similarly to the black patch, a reflection patch also has a 95% occupancy probability: 5% of the pixels within the patch are unchanged.

All these data augmentation layers are not applied to every image, they have a certain occurrence probability set to 50% for the black patches, outliers, and reflection patches, so that some images are left unchanged. The randomization of all possible properties of the data augmentation layers helps in improving the network's ability to generalize. In Fig. 4.12f, a depth image is shown after simultaneous application of all data augmentation layers.

4.3.4 Hyperparameter optimization

For fully defining the network, two parameters must additionally be selected: The angular resolution of the attitude sampling $\Delta\alpha$, and the weighting parameter λ of the loss function (4.33). These two parameters are not independent, since changing the angular resolution changes the number of attitude classes M , so that the loss (4.33) is also affected.

To select appropriate values for these parameters, a comparison criterion is to be defined. Since the neural network is used for pose estimation, two errors are used to quantify the quality of an estimate as in the previous chapters: The position and the attitude error of the estimate. For determining whether a pose initialization is successful or not, these two parameters are fused into a single success criteria. In the Introduction section 1.2.5, Table 1.1, we stated that the requirements for pose estimation in close range were of 5 deg for the relative attitude, and 1% of the relative distance. The relative distance when entering the close range phase and starting pose estimation is in the order of tens of meters. From the robustness analysis of Chapter 2, Fig. 2.22, we have also seen that for an initial position error below 10 cm and an attitude error below 5 deg, the pose refinement was successful in all tested cases.

Therefore, the success criterion is chosen identically to the robustness evaluation in Section 2.5.4, with the difference that the symmetrical angular distance function is used to account for symmetrical equivalents. If $(R, \boldsymbol{\rho})$ is the pose estimate from the initialization method, and $(\bar{R}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\rho}})$ are the ground truth values, the pose estimation is defined as successful if following criteria is met:

$$d_{\text{sym}}(R, \bar{R}) \leq \theta_{\text{max}} \quad \text{and} \quad \|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \bar{\boldsymbol{\rho}}\| \leq \delta_{\text{max}}, \quad (4.34)$$

with $\theta_{\text{max}} = 5$ deg and $\delta_{\text{max}} = 10$ cm.

A parameter search is performed to find an appropriate pair of parameters $(\Delta\alpha, \lambda)$, and presented in Fig. 4.13a. The angular resolution of the sampling is varied for five values between 15 deg and 30 deg, where each value is a divider of the total roll range, which is 120 deg when accounting for symmetries. For example, 120 deg corresponds to 8 times 15 deg, or 7 times

17.14 deg etc. Likewise, the weighting parameter λ is varied in the interval $[1, 100]$ with a logarithmic scale. The heatmap presents the success rate of the network trained without data augmentation for each pair of parameters $(\Delta\alpha, \lambda)$, when using a MobileNetV3-L backbone. In this parameter selection phase, data augmentation is not applied so that the training process is faster, enabling to quickly train multiple models for comparison. The evaluation is performed on the validation dataset, which is used to tune the model's parameters before deploying on the test dataset.

Figure 4.13: Hyperparameter optimization: (a) Success rate (<5 deg & <10 cm) on the validation dataset of the pose initialization trained with a MobileNetV3-L backbone without data augmentation. Outliers below 97% success rate are colored in black; (b) Number of attitude classes for each sampling resolution.

The best success rate for the hyperparameter variation is obtained for an angular resolution of $\Delta\alpha = 15$ deg and a weight $\lambda = 30$. On the validation dataset, this model achieves a 99.00% success rate. However, the training for a resolution of $\Delta\alpha = 15$ deg shows to be relatively unstable, with models trained for higher and lower λ values achieving comparatively poor results. In contrast, an angular resolution of $\Delta\alpha = 20$ deg paired with a weight $\lambda = 10$ leads to a slightly lower success rate of 98.83%, but with consistent results when varying the angular resolution or the weight around these values.

A finer angular resolution produces a higher number of attitude classes M , as illustrated in Fig. 4.13b. From (4.10) and (4.12), it follows that the number of attitude classes M varies proportionally to $1/\Delta\alpha^3$. For example, an angular resolution of 15 deg involves that the sampling produces a number $M = 1464$ attitude classes, while a resolution of 20 deg only produces $M = 618$ attitude classes. This also explains the results observed in Fig. 4.13a: a finer resolution involves more parameters in the network and sometimes a higher accuracy, but also leads to overfitting and potentially unstable training results for low angular resolutions.

In summary, while a finer angular resolution of for example 15 deg produces slightly better results in some cases, it also leads to a higher number of parameters in the network and potential overfitting. On the contrary, a low sampling resolution of 30 deg shows to achieve comparatively

poor results. In between, accuracies close to the best value are obtained for an angular resolution of 20 deg and a weight $\lambda = 10$, with more than twice less attitude classes than for a resolution of 15 deg. Therefore, the result of the tuning is to set the values to $\Delta\alpha = 20$ deg and $\lambda = 10$, which is a compromise between model accuracy and number of parameters.

4.4 3D neural network based pose initialization

In this section, we discuss the use of a 3D neural network for pose estimation. Compared to the previous section, a 3D or point-based network directly processes 3D point clouds, without the necessity for projection to a depth image. The overall logic of the architecture is presented in Fig. 4.14. The point cloud is pre-processed to find its centroid and downsample it to a fixed size, before it is passed to a point-based neural network. This network, similarly to the previous section, has two prediction heads, one for the attitude classification, and one for a position shift estimation.

Figure 4.14: Overview of the 3D neural network-based pose estimation pipeline.

While several components are identical to the CNN based pose estimation presented in Section 4.3, the pre-processing is specific to a point-based neural network and will be described in detail. In contrast to the previous section, we also suggest some modifications of the neural network backbone itself for optimizing the model runtime.

4.4.1 Pre-processing

Similarly to the CNN pre-processing, the first step of the pre-processing with a 3D neural network is usually to normalize the input point cloud [190–192]. To this aim, we compute the trimmed centroid \mathbf{c} of the point cloud with (4.26). Differently from Section 4.3.1, the point cloud is only centered and not additionally normalized. For $i = 1, \dots, N_z$, the coordinates of the centered point cloud $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_i$ are simply obtained from the original coordinates \mathbf{z}_i by:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_i = \mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{c}. \quad (4.35)$$

Point-based neural networks are, in principle, able to process point clouds with varying input sizes [190]. However, a standard practice is to set a fix input size, since it simplifies the implementation, and facilitates batch training [190–192, 195]. A common input size for small objects is 1024, which is for example used by several models [190–192, 195] when training on the ModelNet classification dataset [184]. We set the same input size for our evaluations. While point clouds collected at EPOS, depending on the lidar settings, contain approximately 10 000 points, space grade lidars might have lower scanning rates [60]. Still, while the number of points provided by a lidar is dependent on the sensor settings, it is realistic to expect a number of points in the order of at least 1000.

The neural network expects a point cloud with exactly 1024 points. If the input point cloud contains less points, points are duplicated at random to achieve 1024 points. On the contrary, if the point cloud contains too many points, it is downsampled to reduce the number of points to 1024. In the previous chapters, we used voxel grid downsampling to pre-process the point clouds before NDT or ICP refinement. However, such a downsampling does not produce a fixed size point cloud. A standard method for downsampling a point cloud to a pre-defined number of points is Farthest Point Sampling (FPS) [190–192, 195]. It produces a well-spaced point cloud and leads to better results than other downsampling strategies [268]. However, this pre-processing takes up a significant part of the total runtime, in particular if implemented on a CPU [268]. Therefore, we compare different downsampling strategies:

- Random downsampling: Points are randomly dropped until the correct number of points is reached;
- Voxel + random downsampling: The point cloud is first downsampled with a voxel grid, before points are randomly dropped or added to reach the desired size;
- QuickFPS [268]: A k-d tree based implementation of FPS, designed for accelerating the method when implemented on a CPU.

These different strategies for downsampling will be compared in terms of runtime and accuracy in Section 4.4.4.

QuickFPS

QuickFPS is not a contribution of this work and was developed by Han et al. [268]. Yet, for completeness, we provide an overview of this sampling method in the following, since it is an essential step in the pre-processing of the point clouds. Let (z_1, \dots, z_{N_z}) be the initial point cloud, from which it is desired to sample N_s points. Consider that s_1, \dots, s_k points have already been sampled from the cloud, with $k < N_s$. The distance of a point z_i to the already sampled point cloud is

$$d_i^{(k)} = \min_{l=1, \dots, k} \|s_l - z_i\|. \quad (4.36)$$

The logic of the classical FPS algorithm to select a new point s_{k+1} is then relatively simple: s_{k+1} is the point with the highest distance $d_i^{(k)}$, i.e., the farthest point to the already sampled point cloud. Following the selection of s_{k+1} , all distances are updated via (4.36) to define the

new distances $d_i^{(k+1)}$, for $i = 1, \dots, N_z$. Classical FPS involves to re-compute the minimum distances (4.36) for every new sampled point, leading to a complexity in $\mathcal{O}(N_z \cdot N_s)$.

The main idea of QuickFPS is to accelerate the computation of the distance updates $d_i^{(k+1)}$ by only performing those updates when necessary: In most cases, the value of $d_i^{(k+1)}$ is identical to the previous value $d_i^{(k)}$. This is achieved by splitting the original point cloud into buckets, for which a k-d tree is used. Let $\mathcal{B}_1, \dots, \mathcal{B}_{N_b}$ be the buckets (or cells) of the k-d tree. A bucket \mathcal{B}_j contains $N_{\mathcal{B}_j}$ points $z_{1,j}, \dots, z_{N_{\mathcal{B}_j},j}$. Therefore, the points of the cloud are now indexed by (i, j) , where j is the bucket index, and $i = 1, \dots, N_{\mathcal{B}_j}$ is the index of the point in this bucket. At the step k of the sampling process, each point (i, j) is associated with the distance $d_{i,j}^{(k)}$ defined analogously to (4.36). The bucket additionally stores two variables at step k : The farthest distance of all points in the bucket, which is

$$d_{max,j}^{(k)} = \max_{i=1, \dots, N_{\mathcal{B}_j}} d_{i,j}^{(k)}, \quad (4.37)$$

and the point of the bucket for which this distance is reached. This is the bucket farthest point $\mathbf{f}_j^{(k)}$.

We consider the last sampled point \mathbf{s}_k . The distance of this point to all points of a bucket is bounded from below by the distance between the cell \mathcal{B}_j and the point. This is the bucket distance $d_{bucket}(\mathbf{s}_k, \mathcal{B}_j)$, which is defined in Fig. 4.15. The distances and farthest point of \mathcal{B}_j are only updated if $d_{bucket}(\mathbf{s}_k, \mathcal{B}_j) < d_{max,j}^{(k-1)}$. After having updated all buckets, the new point to sample is selected among the bucket farthest points $\mathbf{f}_j^{(k)}$ for $j = 1, \dots, N_b$. Among those points, the new point to sample is the one with the farthest bucket distance $d_{max,j}^{(k)}$.

Figure 4.15: Schematic representation of the update step of QuickFPS [268]. The bucket is only updated if the distance between the cell and the sampled point is lower than the farthest distance held by the bucket.

By avoiding unnecessary updates, QuickFPS significantly reduces the number of distance updates performed, and thus the overall runtime of the algorithm. In addition, this method is exact, i.e., the final result is the same as the result for classical FPS.

4.4.2 Neural network design

The overall neural network architecture is similar to the architecture presented in the previous Section 4.3, the main difference being that a 3D neural network is used instead of a CNN. The first step is to process the downsampled point cloud containing, in this case, $N_s = 1024$ points, with a 3D network backbone. To this aim, four architectures are compared, which were introduced in Section 1.5.2: PointNet [190], PointNet++ [191], DGCNN [192] and PointTransformer [195]. These neural network architectures are re-implemented in Python using the TensorFlow library, following the descriptions and openly available implementations provided by the authors.

The PointNet, and DGCNN models additionally have spatial transformation layers, which aim at making the input rotation and translation invariant. Because such an invariance is not desirable for the pose estimation task, these layers are removed in our implementation. In detail, the models are implemented as follows: PointNet is implemented as the classification network presented in Fig. 2 of the publication by Qi et al. [190], with the only difference that the two spatial transformations (“input transform” and “feature transform”) are removed. PointNet++ follows the openly available author’s implementation for object classification [269]. The DGCNN implementation also corresponds the classifier introduced in Fig. 3 of the original paper by Wang et al. [192]. Again, the only difference is that the initial “spatial transform” is not applied to the point cloud. All these networks produce a feature layer of size 1024. On the contrary, PointTransformer is implemented as the classification network presented in Fig. 3 of the publication of Zhao et al. [195], and produces a feature vector of size only 512.

The only difference of the top network compared to the one used for CNN-based pose estimation (Section 4.3.2) is the addition of an intermediate layer between the feature vector and the two prediction heads. This addition will be experimentally justified in the results Section 4.5. From the four compared neural network backbones, only PointTransformer produces a feature vector of size 512, while the others output a feature vector of size 1024. This feature vector is then processed by an additional fully connected layer of size 512, which is the rightmost blue layer in Fig. 4.14. This fully connected layer is further processed by two prediction heads identical to the CNN case. The first prediction head is an attitude classifier with M output classes and softmax activation. The second one predicts the position shift through two fully connected layers of size 128, and 3.

4.4.3 Training

Data augmentation

Data augmentation is also a standard practice when training point-based neural networks [190–192], aiming to increase a network’s ability to generalize and prevent overfitting. For classification tasks with PointNet [190], the authors add random jitter to the point cloud, and randomly rotate it. For training PointNet++ [190], the point clouds are also randomly flipped and their coordinates scaled to deform the point cloud.

We apply similar data augmentation layers, except for point cloud flipping and random rotation, which would modify the aspect or pose of the point cloud. The different data augmentation layers are presented in Fig. 4.16. The first type of data augmentation consists in adding random errors (jitter) to the point cloud, and illustrated in Fig. 4.16b. The errors on the point

coordinates follow a normal distribution with a standard deviation of 1 cm, and are additionally clipped so that the maximum absolute error is of 3 cm. The next modification consists in randomly stretching or shrinking the point cloud along each coordinate axis with a dilatation factor of $\pm 15\%$, as shown in Fig. 4.16c.

Figure 4.16: Point cloud augmentation: (a) Reference point cloud; (b) With jitter; (c) Distorted point cloud; (d) With region dropout; (e) Addition of outliers; (f) Combination of all data augmentation layers.

Additional custom data augmentation layers are implemented. The first custom layer consists in simulating occlusions or missing information in the point cloud, similarly to the black patch for image augmentation in Section 4.3.3. The idea of a region dropout is to select one point at random in the point cloud, define a bounding box around this point with a randomized size, and remove all points within this box. This is illustrated in Fig. 4.16d. Because the input point cloud to the network always requires a fix number of points, it is not possible to simply remove points: other points must be added in replacement. This is achieved by duplicating at random some of the remaining points. The final type of data augmentation consists in the addition of outliers in the point cloud, as shown in Fig. 4.16e. A maximum of 50 outliers is added within a bounding box with 2 m side. Again, since the network expects a fix number of points and this augmentation adds new points, it is necessary to remove other points at random in the cloud to keep exactly 1024 points.

Data augmentation is applied to every point cloud of the training dataset, and never during validation or testing. While the addition of jitter and the deformation are performed for each point cloud, the region dropout and addition of outliers are only performed with a probability

of 50%, so that some point clouds present outliers, and others don't. An example of a point cloud obtained after applying all types of data augmentation is presented in Fig. 4.16f.

Training settings

The model is trained to optimize the loss (4.33). The parameters selected in Section 4.3.4 are kept, i.e., a weight $\lambda = 10$ for the loss function and an angular resolution $\Delta\alpha = 20$ deg. The weights of the 3D neural network implemented in Python with TensorFlow are initialized randomly. In between the last fully connected layer of size 512, and the two output heads, a dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 is applied during training for further regularization. This is similar to the original PointNet [190] implementation, where a dropout rate with this ratio is applied on the last fully connected layer, before the classification layer.

Similarly to the training process described in Section 4.3.3, the loss is optimized over 35 epochs, for a batch size of 32, on the 400 000 point clouds of the training dataset. The Adam optimizer [266] is used to minimize the loss. Differently to the CNN case, an initial learning rate of 1e-3 leads to a more effective minimization of the loss. However, the training process is relatively unstable, i.e., the same model trained multiple times will have a strongly varying validation loss each time. To stabilize the training, cosine decay is applied to the learning rate, i.e., the learning rate is reduced from its initial value of 1e-3 to a final value of 1e-5 at the end of the 35 epochs, following a cosine curve over a half period. This modification is found to greatly improve the result of the optimization. Interestingly, applying the same strategy to the CNN models presented in the previous section does not turn out to be beneficial.

4.4.4 Model selection

The design of the neural network is the result of an iterative process. Through comparisons and evaluations on the validation dataset, a model is selected and refined. This subsection serves as a justification for the choices made in the design of the neural network by presenting details and results of the different evaluated alternatives.

Choice of pre-processing

The first choice concerns the pre-processing. A standard pre-processing method is FPS, however, it is also computationally intensive. As presented in Section 4.4.1, we compare three alternatives: random downsampling, voxel downsampling followed by random downsampling, and QuickFPS, a k-d tree implementation of FPS. In all cases, if the initial point cloud size is smaller than the desired point cloud size $N_s = 1024$, the point cloud is upsampled by randomly duplicating points.

For comparison, the PointNet classification backbone is used to train and evaluate models for the different pre-processing strategies. The different options are compared with respect to two criteria, the runtime and the success rate, for a success criterion (error lower than 5 deg and 10 cm) defined in (4.34). Since the pre-processing and downsampling is meant to happen onboard, the runtime evaluation is performed on the representative computing hardware, the Zynq board CPU presented in Section 2.5.3. The results of the evaluation of the different pre-processing methods are presented in Table 4.2. The runtime only measures the pre-processing

time in this evaluation. For comparison with its k-d tree accelerated version, the runtime of classical FPS is also measured.

Table 4.2: Comparison of the different pre-processing strategies when using the PointNet backbone: pose estimation success rate (< 5 deg & < 10 cm) on the validation dataset, and pre-processing runtime on the Zynq CPU (shown as mean \pm standard deviation).

downsampling	model success rate [%]	pre-processing runtime [ms]
random	89.45	15 \pm 1
voxel (4 cm) + random	91.36	35 \pm 1
QuickFps [268]	93.06	118 \pm 6
FPS	93.06	1785 \pm 111

The type of pre-processing has a strong impact on the accuracy of each model. While random downsampling is the fastest method, it also leads to the lowest success rate of all models. Voxel grid downsampling with an octree leads to a slightly better success rate of 91.36%, with a still low average runtime of 35 ms. However, the best results are obtained using FPS (or equivalently its k-d tree version) for downsampling, with a 93.06% success rate. This justifies the selection of this downsampling strategy, even though the runtime of QuickFps is higher, with an average of 118 ms on the Zynq CPU. The k-d tree implementation is significantly faster than the classical implementation which has a mean runtime of 1785 ms, highlighting the importance of using an accelerated version for pre-processing. The difference in accuracy for a model trained with the different downsampling strategies is explained by the fact that FPS selects evenly spaced points and doesn't leave out key feature points, which is not guaranteed with random downsampling, even if preceded by a voxel grid downsampling.

Choice of backbone

Next, the four backbones presented in Section 4.4.2 are compared. These backbones are trained with the same parameters, using accelerated FPS for pre-processing. As for the pre-processing evaluation, the models are compared based on two criteria: The success rate on the validation dataset, and the model runtime on the Zynq CPU. This time, the runtime only corresponds to the neural network runtime, i.e., it is the time to obtain a pose estimate once the pre-processing has already been performed. While the training is performed in Python, using TensorFlow on a computer equipped with a GPU, the evaluation is performed on the Zynq CPU to measure the inference time. For efficiency and integration into the GNC flight software, the evaluation is implemented in C++, using the TensorFlow Lite library for neural network inference on edge devices. The results for PointNet, PointNet++, DGCNN and PointTransformer are presented in Table 4.3.

PointNet is the most efficient model, with an average runtime of 264 ms, but achieves the lowest accuracy by far. On the opposite, PointNet++ is the best performing model on the validation dataset, with 99% of correct pose estimates. This comes at the cost of an average runtime of around 1.7 s. DGCNN reaches the second best success rate, but for an average runtime

Table 4.3: Comparison of 3D network backbones: pose estimation success rate (< 5 deg & < 10 cm) on the validation dataset, and neural network runtime, without pre-processing, on the Zynq CPU (shown as mean \pm standard deviation).

backbone	model success rate [%]	neural network runtime [ms]
PointNet [190]	93.06	264 \pm 1
PointNet++ [191]	99.00	1719 \pm 1
DGCNN [192]	98.54	2455 \pm 0
PointTransformer [195]	97.97	676 \pm 0

of around 2.5 s which is higher than the one of PointNet++. With a runtime of 676 ms in average for a success rate of 97.97%, PointTransformer presents interesting results. Yet, the accuracy gap with PointNet++ is of more than 1 percentage point. We will show in the following that it is possible to modify PointNet++ to reduce its runtime below the one of PointTransformer, without such an accuracy loss. Therefore, PointNet++ is selected as a baseline backbone for the 3D neural network based pose estimation.

Model optimization of PointNet++

The baseline PointNet++ classification model is optimized for accuracy on benchmark datasets such as ModelNet [184], but not necessarily for runtime. To understand how it is possible to optimize the model for runtime, it is necessary to introduce the architecture of PointNet++ in detail. PointNet++ builds upon the PointNet architecture, presented in Section 1.5.2, Fig. 1.13. It uses multiple smaller PointNet models, i.e., with less layers and smaller layer size, to capture fine features of point clouds.

PointNet++ consists of several types of layers that are combined. These building blocks are:

- *Clustering*: A clustering operation takes as input a point cloud containing N_i points, and splits it into $N_e < N_i$ clusters containing each k points. These clusters can be partially overlapping. The clustering is achieved by first sampling the input point cloud with FPS to select N_e anchor points. For each of these anchor points, its k -nearest neighbors in the input point cloud are selected to form a cluster (or neighborhood) containing k points. The clustering step also modifies the features of each point: Let f be the number of features of the points, which is for example 3 for a 3D input point cloud. After the clustering, each point is transformed into a feature of dimension $(3 + f)$, which is the concatenation of the point’s relative position with respect to the center of the cluster to which it belongs, and of its features. In summary, the clustering operation takes as input a point cloud of dimension $N_i \times f$, and creates an output of dimension $N_e \times k \times (3 + f)$.
- *Shared MLP*: A standard MLP is the simplest form of a neural network. In 1D, it transforms an input vector with c channels into f features, by passing the input through several layers. Let $n \geq 0$ be the number of hidden layers, with dimensions h_1, \dots, h_n . These dimensions are summarized with the compact notation $\text{MLP}\{h_1, \dots, h_n, f\}$. A shared MLP is sim-

ilar to a standard MLP, with the difference that the input is not necessary 1-dimensional. Given an input of dimension $d_1 \times \dots \times d_n \times c$, it creates an output of dimension $d_1 \times \dots \times d_n \times f$ by applying the same MLP to each of the $d_1 \times \dots \times d_n$ data points. For PointNet++, all layers of a shared MLPs include batch normalization (normalization of the layer output) and ReLU activation [263].

- *Max pool*: This is a standard operation for neural networks which enables to reduce the dimension of input data. Max pooling consists in selecting the maximum in the data along the first before last dimension. For example, it transforms a matrix of size $a \times b$ into a vector of size b by selecting the maximum along the columns. Likewise, it reduces an input of dimension $a \times b \times c$ into an output of dimension $a \times c$.

For example, with these building blocks, the PointNet backbone illustrated in Fig. 1.13 is simply described as a shared MLP{64, 64, 64, 128, 1024} followed by max pooling. The layers of PointNet++ are summarized in Table 4.4. The input is a 3D point cloud with N_s points, and the output a feature vector of size 1024. In between, two clustering operations perform a sampling and grouping of the point cloud: the first clustering produces N_1 clusters of k_1 points each, and the second one N_2 clusters containing k_2 points each. In the baseline PointNet++ classification model [269], the sizes are $N_1 = 512$, $k_1 = 32$ for the first cluster, and $N_2 = 128$, $k_2 = 64$ for the second.

Table 4.4: Structure of the PointNet++ [191] classification model, without the top layers.

layer	output size
input	$N_s \times 3$
clustering	$N_1 \times k_1 \times (3 + 3)$
shared MLP{64, 64, 128}	$N_1 \times k_1 \times 128$
max pool	$N_1 \times 128$
clustering	$N_2 \times k_2 \times (3 + 128)$
shared MLP{128, 128, 256}	$N_2 \times k_2 \times 256$
max pool	$N_2 \times 256$
shared MLP{256, 512, 1024}	$N_2 \times 1024$
max pool	1024

The size of a cluster in a 3D network is similar to the size of the receptive field of a convolution, it is the dimension of the subregion of the point cloud that will be processed to identify features. With a smaller receptive field, smaller parts of the point cloud are processed to extract features. However, in the baseline configuration, there is an important overlap: for example, the initial point cloud containing 1024 points is split into 512 clusters of 32 points at the first step. Therefore, a first possibility to reduce the model's runtime is to reduce the dimensions of the clusters, defined by the sizes N_1, k_1, N_2, k_2 , to see if configurations with less and smaller clusters enable to reach a lower inference time while maintaining a similar performance.

The result of the variation of cluster number and sizes is presented in Fig. 4.17. As previously, the runtime of each model is evaluated on the Zynq CPU, and its success rate computed on the synthetic validation dataset, after the model was trained on the synthetic training data. The baseline model, on the top right in the Figure, achieves the best success rate, at the expense of the highest runtime. Reducing the cluster sizes k_1, k_2 by half (dark blue point in the Figure) already leads to a reduction of the runtime to approximately 1 s, for a success rate decreased by only 0.01 percentage points. We find that a reduction of the cluster sizes below 16 neighbors leads to a poor performance, so that the cluster sizes are kept to the minimum values $k_1, k_2 = 16$. The next step is to reduce the number of clusters N_1, N_2 . The variation of these cluster number is illustrated in the Figure, showing a clear trend and relation between the cluster sizes and the success rate. When reducing the cluster numbers up to a factor 4, i.e., to the point where $N_1 = 128, N_2 = 32$, the success rate drops steeply to a value of 98.52% (red point in Fig. 4.17).

Figure 4.17: Variation of the cluster number and sizes of PointNet++. The inference time is measured on the Zynq CPU and does not include pre-processing. The success rate (error below 5 deg and 10 cm) is measured on the validation dataset. The labels N_1, k_1 and N_2, k_2 indicate the cluster number and sizes of respectively the first and second clusters. The star represents the selected optimized PointNet++ model.

Choosing a model suited for onboard implementation is a trade-off between runtime and accuracy. In Section 1.4, we stated that a typical latency requirement for close range pose estimation is in the order of 1 s. Accounting for the additional pre-processing time and time to refine the initial estimate with NDT, we set here the requirement to have an inference time of the model below 0.5 s, so that the overall pose estimation pipeline runs within 1 s. This corresponds to selecting the model corresponding to the model identified by the brown star in Fig. 4.17. This model performs a first clustering with parameters $N_1 = 256, k_1 = 16$ and a second clustering

with parameters $N_2 = 64$, $k_2 = 16$. Its success rate on the validation dataset is 98.83%. It has to be noted that in case of different runtime requirements, or in case a different onboard computer is used, the selected model might be another one. In the following, we will distinguish between two models:

- PointNet++ baseline: the original classification model with sizes $N_1 = 512$, $k_1 = 32$, and $N_2 = 128$, $k_2 = 64$;
- PointNet++ optimized: the model with reduced sizes $N_1 = 256$, $k_1 = 16$, and $N_2 = 64$, $k_2 = 16$.

Starting from this model, we explore further optimization possibilities. Table 4.5 presents the success rate on the validation dataset, and runtime of models which all differ from the optimized PointNet++ model by one change. To quantify the efficiency of a modification of the model, the optimization score in the table presents the ratio between the runtime improvement (in seconds) and the number of percentage points lost in the accuracy through the modification. A higher optimization score corresponds to a modification which achieves a high runtime reduction for a comparatively low diminution of the accuracy.

A first approach is to reduce the number of parameters in each layer. For example, a shrinkage factor α_{MLP} is applied to all shared MLPs of the model. With a shrinkage factor $\alpha_{MLP} = 7/8$, the first MLP layer in Table 4.4 has layer sizes $\{56, 56, 112\}$, and this shrinkage is also applied to the following MLPs. The results of this model compared to the optimized model (for which $\alpha_{MLP} = 1$) are presented in the second line of Table 4.5. Another possibility is to reduce the number of layers, for example by removing the last fully connected layer before the prediction heads (rightmost blue layer in Fig. 4.14). The results for this model are presented in the third line of the table. Alternatively, it is tested to reduce the number of input points of the model, here by 25%. The results for a model with $N_s = 768$ input points are presented in line 4 of the table. Finally, the last line in the table corresponds to a model where the number of clusters in the first clustering operation has been divided by two, i.e., where $N_1 = 128$. This model is identical to the model corresponding to the orange data point in Fig. 4.17.

The results highlight that among the different optimization strategies, reducing the cluster sizes is the most effective. When being run on a CPU, the clustering operations take up a significant part of the runtime. In comparison, shrinking the size of the shared MLPs only slightly reduces the runtime. Removing one fully connected layer in the top layers of the network even has no measurable effect on the overall runtime. On the contrary, a reduction of the number of input points decreases the runtime, since the initial clustering step will run faster, but the model's accuracy also drops. The best ratio between runtime reduction and accuracy loss is obtained when reducing the number of clusters in the first clustering step. Therefore, this strategy is selected to optimize the model for runtime, leading to the optimized PointNet++ backbone with sizes $N_1 = 256$, $k_1 = 16$, and $N_2 = 64$, $k_2 = 16$.

4.5 Results

This section presents the results of the pose initialization methods when evaluated on real lidar data from the EPOS facility.

Table 4.5: Comparison of different optimization strategies: success rate (< 5 deg & < 10 cm) on the validation dataset, and runtime, without pre-processing, on the Zynq CPU (shown as mean \pm standard deviation). The optimization score is the ratio between the runtime improvement (in seconds) and the percentage points decrease of the validation score, compared to the reference optimized PointNet++ model.

model	success rate [%]	inference time [ms]	optimization score [s/%]
PointNet++ optimized	98.83	420 \pm 0	-
- shrinkage $\alpha_{MLP} = 7/8$	98.72	392 \pm 0	0.25
- one fully connected layer less	97.90	420 \pm 0	0
- input points $N_s = 768$	98.74	387 \pm 0	0.37
- cluster size $N_1 = 128$	98.71	338 \pm 0	0.68

4.5.1 EPOS test datasets

After training and validating models with the synthetic datasets, the pose initialization is tested on real lidar data. For pose tracking, realistic rendezvous trajectories were flown at EPOS, so that sequences of point clouds were recorded. However, such trajectories do not necessarily cover a wide range of relative poses of the target, since after an inspection phase the approach to the target is mainly performed along one direction in a straight-line approach. For example, for the tracking experiment presented in Section 2.5.1, the relative attitude to the target varies during the initial inspection phase at a distance of 15 m. However, during the approach phase from 15 m to 3 m, the chaser mainly approaches along the target’s x -axis, so that the relative attitudes observed during this phase are mostly rotations of the target around its roll axis, see Fig. 2.15.

To extensively test the pose initialization for a wide variety of relative poses to the target, new datasets are collected at EPOS. The objective of this data acquisition is to collect datasets for which the target is observed from various sides, for different distances to the target. To this aim, four datasets are collected, at discrete distances of 5 m, 10 m, 15 m and 20 m to the target. For each of these distances, the position of the chaser relative to the target is varied, leading to various relative attitudes, similarly to an inspection phase. For all these experiments, the target satellite is directed along the z -axis in the RTN frame, and spins around that axis with a rate of 1 deg/s, as illustrated in Fig. 4.18.

The four independent datasets collected at steady distances of 5 m, 10 m, 15 m and 20 m are named *epos_5m*, *epos_10m*, *epos_15m* and *epos_20m*, respectively. During each experiment, the lidar framerate is set to be adaptive as presented in Section 2.4.4, so that each point cloud contains approximately 10 000 points. At a distance of 5 m, this corresponds to a framerate of approximately 2.65 Hz, while the framerate drops to 0.7 Hz at 20 m distance. The chaser is commanded to perform a fly-around and inspection to observe the target from different sides, while staying at the same absolute relative distance for each dataset. The resulting relative trajectories in the RTN frame are presented in Fig. 4.19.

Figure 4.18: Spinning motion of the target satellite during the acquisition of the EPOS test datasets, expressed in the RTN frame.

The relative position to the target is varied to simulate a fly-around, but not all relative positions can be simulated at the EPOS facility for this target satellite and this configuration. In particular, it is not possible to see the target from “behind” (looking from the negative z_{RTN} direction in Fig. 4.18) since the robotic arm carrying the satellite would obstruct the field-of-view. Therefore, the datasets only contains a limited range of relative attitudes of the target. To measure what fraction of the attitude space is represented in the test data, the attitude space is divided in bins of 20 deg resolution identical to the attitude classification bins presented in Section 4.2.2. The attitude space coverage is then defined as the fraction of attitude bins which are represented in the test data. This measure, alongside with the number of point clouds contained in each dataset and the acquisition frequency of the lidar, is presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Overview of the EPOS test datasets for pose initialization.

name	target distance [m]	number of point clouds	lidar frequency [Hz]	attitude space coverage [%]
<i>epos_5m</i>	5	3976	2.7	10.8
<i>epos_10m</i>	10	1781	1.1	12.0
<i>epos_15m</i>	15	1253	0.9	9.9
<i>epos_20m</i>	20	1638	0.7	11.8
aggregated	5-20	8648	0.7-2.7	18.8

Figure 4.19: Position of the chaser relatively to the target in RTN for the four EPOS test datasets: (a) For *epos_5m*, at a steady distance of 5 m; (b) For *epos_10m*, at a steady distance of 10 m; (c) For *epos_15m*, at a steady distance of 15 m; (d) For *epos_20m*, at a steady distance of 20 m.

4.5.2 Methodology and compared models

Compared to pose tracking, the results of pose initialization are not evaluated on a sequence of consecutive point clouds, since the result of the pose initialization is not dependent on the previous point clouds. On the contrary, all point clouds of the test dataset are considered in isolation. Two types of pose initialization will be compared, CNN-based pose initialization as presented in Section 4.3, and 3D network based pose initialization as presented in Section 4.4. For pose initialization using a CNN, three different models will be compared, and identified by the backbone used: MobileNetV3S, MobileNetV3L, EfficientNetV2B0. When using 3D neural networks, two models will be compared, identified again by their backbones: PointNet++ baseline, and PointNet++ optimized. In total, five models will be compared, and identified by their respective backbones.

For both CNN and 3D network based processing, the pre-processing is performed with the same parameters: To compute the trimmed centroid, a trimming fraction $p = 0.25$ is selected, so

that the trimmed centroid corresponds to the interquartile mean. The target satellite mock-up installed at EPOS (Fig. 2.6) is approximately 1.8 m long, and has a hexagonal shape with a diameter of 1.6 m, so that it could fit in a bounding box of 2 m side. However, since the initial centroid estimation is only coarse, to avoid cropping out relevant parts of the point cloud, the ROI is selected as a bounding box with a side $l = 4$ m. For the point-based neural networks, an additional tuning parameter is the cell size of the k-d tree used for downsampling the point cloud using QuickFPS [268]. It is set such that the maximum number of points per k-d tree cell is 200, which is found to lead to the lowest runtime in average for point clouds containing approximately 10 000 points.

The CNNs use an input image with a resolution of 224×224 pixels, and the 3D networks a sampled point cloud containing $N_s = 1024$ points. The detailed training settings for both types of models were presented in Sections 4.3.3 and 4.4.3. Importantly, the models perform an attitude classification with a resolution for the attitude sampling $\Delta\alpha = 20$ deg, as a result of the trade-off presented in Section 4.3.4.

Finally, since pose initialization is designed to produce an initial estimate for a pose refinement, the overall pipeline will be completed by a pose refinement step using the smoothed NDT. For the refinement step, the smoothed NDT settings are identical to the ones used in the previous sections, which were summarized in Table 2.3. To analyze the results of the pose initialization when taken in isolation, or when combined with a pose refinement step, the results will be presented for both cases, with and without refinement.

4.5.3 Results on test datasets

Results before NDT refinement

First, the results of the pose initialization without the NDT refinement step are presented. The success rates of the five models evaluated on the EPOS test datasets are compared in Table 4.7, for the same success criteria as previously: an initial pose estimate with an angular error accounting for symmetries below 5 deg, and a position error below 10 cm. The CNN model using a MobileNetV3S backbone presents the worst results, with an overall accuracy on the four aggregated datasets of 79.34%. Switching to the large model, MobileNetV3L, leads to a significant increase in the precision, with an overall accuracy of 94.02%. On nearly all datasets, and for the overall accuracy, the CNN-based pose estimation relying on an EfficientNetV2B0 backbone has the highest accuracy, with 97.44% of successful initial pose estimates. In comparison, both point-based models, PointNet++ baseline and optimized, obtain a lower accuracy of 92.08% and 92.12%, respectively. Interestingly, the optimized model, using smaller and less point clusters than the baseline version, even achieves a slightly higher success rate than the baseline.

Another interesting trend is the difference in accuracy for all models for the four datasets: For all models, and in particular for the CNN-based models, the success rate for the *epos_5m* is comparatively low to the success rate at larger distance of 10 m or 15 m. The results drop again for *epos_20m*, recorded at a distance of 20 m.

The success rate is only one metric for measuring the precision of the pose initialization, but masks important aspects of the results, which are the distribution of position and attitude errors of the pose estimation. These distributions are presented in Fig. 4.20 for the attitude errors,

Table 4.7: Success rate (error below 5 deg and 10 cm) in %, of the pose initialization methods evaluated on the EPOS test datasets before NDT refinement.

dataset \ model	<i>epos_5m</i>	<i>epos_10m</i>	<i>epos_15m</i>	<i>epos_20m</i>	aggregated
MobileNetV3S	73.92	76.19	90.74	87.18	79.34
MobileNetV3L	90.32	95.96	98.24	97.68	94.02
EfficientNetV2B0	95.20	99.78	99.28	98.90	97.44
PointNet++ baseline	89.16	94.16	99.92	90.90	92.08
PointNet++ optimized	92.98	89.39	99.76	87.18	92.12

and Fig. 4.21 for the position errors. For all boxplots, the boxes extend between the first and last quartile, and the line within the box represents the median. The whiskers extend between the 5th and 95th percentiles, and outliers are not displayed.

Figure 4.20: Attitude errors before NDT refinement: Distribution of angular errors accounting for symmetries (d_{sym}) between the ground truth and pose initialization result for different models evaluated on the aggregated EPOS datasets.

From the distributions of the angular errors in Fig. 4.20, the first striking observation is a significantly better performance of the point-based models (PointNet++ baseline and optimized) compared to the CNN models. Apart from the CNN model using MobileNetV3S as a backbone, all models have a 95th percentile value lower or equal than 5 deg, so that the difference in the accuracy of the attitude estimation was not visible when considering a success threshold at 5 deg for the attitude estimation. In detail, all three CNN-based models have a median attitude error between 2 deg and 3 deg, while the median attitude error for the PointNet++ baseline and

Figure 4.21: Position errors before NDT refinement: Distribution of position errors between the ground truth and pose initialization result for different models evaluated on the aggregated EPOS datasets.

optimized models are of 1.53 deg and 1.60 deg, respectively. More importantly, the point-based models show to be consistent attitude estimators, with 95% of the estimates being below 3.01 deg for the baseline model, and below 3.05 deg for the runtime optimized model. In comparison, the EfficientNetV2B0 based model, which achieves the best overall success rate on the datasets, has a 95th percentile value for the attitude error of 4.30 deg.

The distribution of position errors presented in Fig. 4.21 shows fewer differences between the compared models. The median position error for all models is similar and lies between 5.9 cm, and 7 cm. More than the median error, the 95th percentile is again a good estimator of the robustness of the position estimation for each backbone. In this regard, the EfficientNet based CNN model achieves the best result, with 95% of the position estimations having an error below 8.9 cm. On the contrary, the two point-based models have a 95th percentile value slightly higher than 10 cm. Since the success criteria was set with a threshold for the maximum error of 10 cm, many of the pose estimates of the models based on PointNet++ appear as unsuccessful because of the higher position error.

When considering only the success rate, the two CNN models based on MobileNetV3L and EfficientNetV2B0 achieve a better performance than the PointNet++ models, while the CNN model relying on the MobileNetV3S backbone is by far the worst model. However, from Figs. 4.20 and 4.21, it is observed that the point-based models achieve a significantly lower attitude error, for a slightly higher position error than their CNN-based counterparts.

Results after NDT refinement

The pose initialization serves as an initial guess for the pose refinement. Therefore, this subsection presents the results of the pose estimation when the initialization method based on one of the five compared models is followed by a refinement step using the smoothed NDT. The

success rate for all models followed by NDT refinement on each of the EPOS test datasets is presented in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8: Success rate (error below 5 deg and 10 cm) in %, of the pose initialization methods evaluated on the EPOS test datasets after NDT refinement.

dataset \ model	<i>epos_5m</i>	<i>epos_10m</i>	<i>epos_15m</i>	<i>epos_20m</i>	aggregated
MobileNetV3S	89.41	92.36	96.73	96.28	92.38
MobileNetV3L	96.15	98.93	99.60	99.88	97.93
EfficientNetV2B0	98.49	99.89	100	99.94	99.27
PointNet++ baseline	99.62	100	100	99.94	99.81
PointNet++ optimized	99.55	100	100	99.94	99.78

Contrarily to the results before NDT refinement, when evaluating the success rate after the refinement step, the two point-based models achieve a higher accuracy than the CNN-based models. The overall success rate is of 99.81% for the baseline PointNet++ model, and very similar, of 99.78%, for the runtime optimized PointNet++ model. Amongst the different depth image based methods, the ranking of the models is the same as previously, with the EfficientNetV2B0 model achieving a higher accuracy (99.27%) than the large MobileNet version (97.93%), while the small MobileNet model has a markedly lower accuracy (92.38%). As for the previous case, it is observed that all models perform better at distance of 10 m to 15 m, compared to the two close and far datasets recorded at a distance of 5 m and 20 m, respectively.

The angular and position errors of the pose estimate after NDT refinement are presented in Figs. 4.22 and 4.23. For the angular errors 4.22, the MobileNetV3S model shows to have the highest errors, with many outliers leading to a 95th quartile at around 59 deg. The large version MobileNetV3L performs significantly better, with a median angular error around 0.74 deg and a 95th quartile value at 1.39 deg. The largest CNN model, EfficientNetV2B0, and the two point-based models PointNet++ baseline and optimized, achieve a similar distribution of angular errors after NDT refinement, with a median error around 0.72 deg and a 95% of the errors lying below 1.31 deg.

For all models, the distribution of position errors after the NDT refinement step is very similar, as shown in Fig. 4.23. Both the three CNN models and the two point-based models have a median position error of 6.6 cm, with 95% of the errors lying below 8.3 cm. The similarity in the distributions after the refinement step is explained by the fact that the same NDT algorithm is used for refinement for each method. If the initial estimate is sufficiently close to the correct pose, the same algorithm will lead to a similar final pose, even if initialized slightly differently.

More than the distribution of angular and position errors, after the NDT refinement step, the success rate is a good indicator of the performance of each model. Indeed, if the initial estimate was precise enough, than the refined pose estimate will be within the error threshold of 5 deg and 10 cm, while if not, the pose estimate will lay outside. With this measure, the two point-based models relying on the PointNet++ backbone show to have a very high accuracy.

Figure 4.22: Attitude errors after NDT refinement: Distribution of angular errors accounting for symmetries (d_{sym}) between the ground truth and pose estimation for different models evaluated on the aggregated EPOS datasets.

Figure 4.23: Position errors after NDT refinement: Distribution of position errors between the ground truth and pose estimation for different models evaluated on the aggregated EPOS datasets.

Runtime evaluation

The overall runtime is a critical point in the design of a pose estimation method, since the method has to be run onboard and in real-time. In particular, the computing hardware on which the runtime evaluation is performed, the CPU of Zynq 7000 SoC, is 20 to 30 times slower than, for example, a desktop computer equipped with an Intel Xeon W-2135 CPU. The detailed

runtimes of the different pose estimation methods on the onboard representative hardware are presented in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9: Decomposition of the pose estimation runtime when evaluated on the Zynq 7000 CPU. Runtimes are shown as mean \pm standard deviation.

model	pre-proc. [ms]	inference [ms]	refinement [ms]	total [ms]
MobileNetV3S	23 ± 1	248 ± 0	311 ± 82	582 ± 82
MobileNetV3L	24 ± 1	737 ± 0	347 ± 101	1108 ± 101
EfficientNetV2B0	24 ± 1	2232 ± 1	348 ± 110	2604 ± 110
PointNet++ baseline	118 ± 6	1719 ± 1	345 ± 114	2182 ± 114
PointNet++ optimized	118 ± 6	420 ± 0	341 ± 109	879 ± 109

Amongst the CNN models, there is a clear runtime difference between the small MobileNet model, with an inference time of 248 ms in average, the large MobileNet model (737 ms in average) and the EfficientNet model, which has an inference time above 2.2 s. These runtimes also correlate with the accuracies observed in Table 4.8, the more complex CNN models leading to a higher runtime but a better accuracy than lighter models. On the contrary, while the baseline PointNet++ model also presents a high inference time of around 1.7 s, the runtime for the optimized PointNet++ model drops to 420 ms in average, a runtime reduction by a more than a factor 4. This drastic runtime reduction does not lead to a significant accuracy drop, since both models have a similar accuracy on the test dataset, (Table 4.8), and outperform the CNN-based models.

The pre-processing step of the CNN-based models, consisting in a projection on a depth image, amounts for an average runtime of around 24 ms. In comparison, the FPS sampling for point-based networks is significantly slower with an average runtime of 118 ms, which is not negligible for the overall runtime. For all models, the NDT refinement is similar, but slightly lower for the MobileNetV3S model, because this model is smaller in size so that the overall processor load is lower. For the other models, the NDT refinement time amounts to approximately 350 ms in average. An advantage of the initialization step compared to the refinement step is its deterministic execution time, which varies only very slightly across different executions, as the standard deviation of the runtime is below 1 ms for all models. In contrast, the runtime of the refinement step, which consists in a variable number of iterations, has a high variability, with a standard deviation above 100 ms. Still, a maximum number of iterations is fixed, so that for a point cloud with a fixed size the maximum runtime of the tracking step is also bounded.

The runtime requirement for the complete pose estimation pipeline was set to approximately 1 s. This directly discards both the EfficientNetV2B0 and the PointNet++ baseline models, for which the overall runtime accounting for all steps is over 2 s. Amongst the remaining models, the MobileNetV3L model also slightly exceeds the 1 s mark, with an overall runtime of 1108 ms in average. Both the MobileNetV3S and optimized PointNet++ models have a total runtime below 1 s, with a clear advantage for the point-based model due to its accuracy on the test

datasets.

4.5.4 Ablation study

In the previous Section, Table 4.5, we have already analyzed the effect of various modifications of the optimized PointNet++ model. This evaluation was performed on the validation dataset, to refine the design of the model before tests on the EPOS datasets. However, some ablation studies only make sense on the test dataset. This is the case of the modifications or methods which were developed specifically to handle the specificities or real data compared to synthetic data. The first step that was developed to handle the noise and multiple reflections in the test data compared to synthetic data is the use of a trimmed centroiding approach in the pre-processing. A second step is the use of specific data augmentation layers, which aim at bridging the domain gap between synthetic and real point clouds by making the network robust to changes in the data.

The goal of an ablation study is to isolate the effect of a certain modification in a model or the training process, by removing it and comparing the results with the original version. To compare the effects of data augmentation for both the CNN-based models and the point-based models, two models are selected as reference. For depth image processing, the model relying on the MobileNetV3L backbone is selected as a reference, and for 3D point cloud processing, the model using the optimized PointNet++ backbone serves as a reference for the ablation study. The results of the ablation study for both models are presented in Tables 4.10 and 4.11.

Table 4.10: Ablation study for the CNN-based pose initialization: Success rate (error below 5 deg and 10 cm) on the aggregated EPOS test datasets after NDT refinement for a model trained without data augmentation, and a model using a standard centroid instead of a trimmed centroid.

model	success rate on test data [%]
MobileNetV3L	97.93
- no data augm.	91.56
- standard centroid	61.96

Table 4.11: Ablation study for the 3D network-based pose initialization: Success rate (error below 5 deg and 10 cm) on the aggregated EPOS test datasets after NDT refinement for a model trained without data augmentation, and a model using a standard centroid instead of a trimmed centroid.

model	success rate on test data [%]
PointNet++ optimized	99.78
- no data augm.	99.19
- standard centroid	82.71

We first analyze the effect of data augmentation on the overall model performance on test data. From Table 4.10, it is observed that the depth image augmentation presented in Section

4.3.3 greatly improves the overall accuracy for the CNN based model. The success rate drops from 97.93% when using data augmentation, to 91.56% without it. For the point-based network, the gap in performance between the model with the point cloud augmentation strategy presented in Section 4.4.3, and the model without, is less important. Still, without data augmentation, the success rate of the optimized PointNet++ model is of 99.19%, while it rises to 99.78% with augmentation. In this percentage range, when close to a 100% accuracy, an improvement of around 0.6 percentage points is significant, showing that data augmentation is also essential for point-based networks.

The second variation, presented in the last line of Tables 4.10 and 4.11, analyzes the impact of using a trimmed centroid for defining the initial ROI. Compared to the reference models, a model was trained for which the pre-processing is performed using a standard centroiding approach, corresponding to using a trimming fraction $p = 0$, both during training and testing. Using a standard centroid leads to a substantial performance in both cases: for the CNN-based pose estimation, the accuracy drops to 61.96%, and for the point-based network, it drops to 82.71%.

The magnitude of the performance drop between using a trimmed centroid and a standard centroid is explained by the fact that the point clouds collected at EPOS presents high levels of noise, and in particular, double reflection effects. Such a point cloud is presented in Fig. 4.24. Due to multiple reflections of the laser ray on the reflective materials of the satellite, and back to the chaser satellite, a “ghost” point cloud is observed behind the target satellite. These double reflections do not correspond to walls or other objects of the facility, and are not cropped out for maintaining a high level of realism in the experimental setup. If accounted for when computing the centroid, these points shift the centroid estimation away from the real position of the target’s center of mass, so that the ROI is wrongly selected and crops out relevant parts of the point cloud. In consequence, using a standard centroid for these noised point clouds leads to a significant accuracy drop of the pose estimation. On the contrary, the outliers corresponding to the “ghost” point cloud are removed in the computation of the centroid when using a sufficiently high trimming fraction, set here to $p = 0.25$. The trimmed centroid acts as a simple form of a clustering algorithm, which computes the centroid of the main point cluster observed in the cloud, discarding smaller clusters corresponding to outlier points.

Figure 4.24: Point cloud with reflections captured at a 10 m distance at the EPOS facility: the sensor is located at the origin of the coordinate system located on the right, and the main point cloud is in the middle. On the left, a double reflection leads to a second ghost point cloud, which does not correspond to an existing object.

4.5.5 Discussion

Comparison of image-based and point-based models

From the experiments of this Section, it is clear that the model using the most lightweight CNN backbone, MobileNetV3S, does not achieve a sufficient reliability for pose initialization, in comparison to the other methods. If runtime is not a requirement, the best performing CNN model is EfficientNetV2B0, and the best performing point-based network is the PointNet++ baseline model. Between the two models, which have a comparable runtime, the point-based model shows to be more robust for consistent pose initialization than its CNN counterpart. Indeed, after NDT refinement, 99.81% of the pose estimates coming from the point-based network meet the success criteria, while this number is of 99.27% for the CNN-based method.

In detail, the initial position error is slightly less accurate for PointNet++ compared to the EfficientNet based network. However, the attitude errors are significantly lower. During the refinement step, the initial position inaccuracy is corrected by the smoothed NDT tracking, while large initial attitude errors lead to a wrong final pose estimate. Interestingly, the loss function is identical for both types of networks (CNN and point-based), so that the fact that a network favors a better position estimation while the other one favors a better attitude estimation is only due to the type of data that the network receives. A hypothesis is that it is more difficult to estimate the attitude from a depth image, due to its pixel-wise projection and flattening of relevant 3D information, so that the CNN focuses more on optimizing the position estimation, achieving a better result in this task than the point-based network.

Adding the runtime as a requirement, the two large CNN and point-based models do not meet the real-time threshold of 1 s. Since the EfficientNetV2B0 is already a runtime optimized version of the EfficientNet models family, it was chosen not to further modify this backbone, but rather to select multiple candidates. A compromise between the runtime and accuracy for the image-based models is the MobileNetV3L backbone. Using this model enables to reach a total accuracy on the test dataset of 97.93% after NDT refinement, for a total runtime of approximately 1.1 s. Such a method is already considered highly reliable, and is close to meeting the real-time threshold for onboard implementation. In many cases, a runtime of 1.1 s for the initial pose estimation is sufficient during real-time operations.

For the point-based network, it is found that the PointNet++ baseline model is not yet optimized for runtime. A runtime reduction of the model by a factor approximately 4 is achieved, while maintaining nearly the same accuracy as the original model. The resulting optimized PointNet++ model, when used in combination with NDT refinement, correctly estimates the pose (error below 5 deg and 10 cm) in 99.78% of the test cases, for a total runtime of around 0.88 s. With these results, the point-based approach shows to outperform the depth-image based approach considering as well the runtime, as the reliability and accuracy of the method.

Achieving Sim2Real transfer

The ablation studies have shown the importance of both the data augmentation during training, and the use of a trimmed centroid for initially selecting the point cloud's ROI, when evaluating the method on real lidar data from the EPOS facility. To simplify the analysis of the difference in the results between evaluation on synthetic and real data, we present only the results for the

PointNet++ optimized model. This point-based model shows to produce the best compromise between runtime and accuracy. The results of this model when evaluated on the synthetic validation dataset, or on the aggregated EPOS datasets, are presented in Table 4.12.

Table 4.12: Comparison of pose estimation results on the synthetic validation dataset, and real test dataset, when using the optimized PointNet++ model.

dataset	initialization			refinement		
	median att.	median pos.	success	median att.	median pos.	success
	err. [deg]	err. [cm]	rate [%]	err. [deg]	err. [cm]	rate [%]
synthetic validation	1.85	2.61	98.83	1.78	2.22	98.97
EPOS test	1.60	6.67	92.12	0.73	6.63	99.78

The result of the pose initialization step, before refinement, shows a comparable median angular error, but higher position errors on real data. This is due to the fact that for real data, calibration errors of the sensor and mismatches between the point cloud model and the mock-up installed at the facility lead to errors in the estimated position of the target’s center-of-mass, which are not present in the simulated data. For this reason, the initial success rate is also lower on real data (92.12%) compared to simulated data (98.83%). For the real datasets, the refinement step enables to strongly reduce the initial pose error, leading to an overall success rate after NDT refinement of 99.78%. This success rate is even higher than on synthetic data (98.97%). Compared to the real data, the synthetic dataset contains more edge cases: target at the edge of the field-of-view, very close distance below 3 m, partial view of the target etc. It is meant to be more challenging than real conditions to enable successful Sim2Real transfer, which explains the overall lower accuracy on simulated compared to real data.

While the median position error is still lower on synthetic data due to the aforementioned reasons, the median attitude error after refinement is better on the real data compared to the synthetic data. One explanation resides in the fact that the synthetic point clouds are simulated with strong motion blur (angular velocity up to 5 deg/s) compared to the conditions for the EPOS datasets (spinning motion of 1 deg/s), so that attitude estimation is more difficult in the first case. Overall, the results show a successful Sim2Real transfer, and the ability of the method to close the domain gap between real and simulated data.

Applicability to onboard implementation

Amongst the models fulfilling the real-time requirements considered in this work, the optimized PointNet++ model leads to the best reliability, i.e., the highest accuracy of the pose estimate on the test dataset. Therefore, this model would be preferred compared to a CNN-based method or another point-based method in case of implementation on an onboard computer with similar characteristics as the Zynq 7000. As discussed in Section 4.4.4, the choice of a model is a trade-off between the runtime and precision requirements, so that different requirements might also lead to the choosing a different model. The proposed pose initialization method is flight-ready, implemented for inference in C++ and tested on a representative onboard computer. In total,

the optimized PointNet++ model has 1.7 million parameters, taking up 7.1 MB of space, which is not a problem for an onboard computer of this category.

The attitude classification logic, accounting for symmetries, only enables to find one of the symmetric equivalents of the actual target pose. Likewise, the NDT refinement step will converge towards a local estimate, but not enable to disambiguate between symmetric equivalents. In case of a perfectly symmetric target, unequivocal pose estimation is not possible, since one configuration cannot be distinguished from one of its symmetric equivalents by observation with optical sensors. In this case, unequivocal pose estimation is not needed, since the proximity operations with the satellite will be identical whether the satellite is in one configuration, or one of its symmetric equivalents. The satellite considered in this work presents a symmetry order of three. In case the satellite geometry contains additional details that would enable to disambiguate its initial pose estimate, strategies to resolve the symmetrical ambiguity in a second step could be investigated, but are not considered in this work.

In spite of its very high accuracy of 99.78% on the test datasets, the model still fails in some cases on the EPOS datasets. From Table 4.8, it is seen that most failures happen at close distances, for the dataset *epos_5m*. At larger distances, the pose estimation method only fails to find a solution within the success threshold once, for a point cloud at 20 m distance. However, looking further into this error case, it is found that this case is only marked as unsuccessful because the position error is of 10.1 cm, exceeding the 10 cm threshold. At further distances, it is normal that the position error increases, and such an error is still well below 1% of the relative distance. This error is not be problematic to initiate pose tracking.

On the contrary, at closer distances, the pose initialization fails to be within the success threshold for 18 point clouds, which still represents less than 0.5% of the point clouds of the *epos_5m* dataset. One explanation for the failures at lower distances is the adaptive lidar framerate setting. With this setting, the framerate at a distance of 5 m is of approximately 2.7 Hz, while it is around 0.7 Hz at a distance of 20 m, so that all point clouds contain approximately the same number of points. Due to the lidar's non-repetitive scan pattern, the distribution of points in the cloud is less homogeneous at shorter distance compared to larger distances, as is illustrated in Fig. 4.25. On the point cloud captured at 5 m distance (Fig. 4.25a), the 10 045 points are located along the scan lines, so that some regions are not scanned, and some details of the point clouds such as the small antennas are not captured by the lidar. On the contrary, on the point cloud captured at 20 m distance (Fig. 4.25b), an antenna is clearly visible (bottom of the scan) even though the point cloud contains only 7679 points. With sparser point clouds captured at short distances to the target, some features of the target are not present in the scan, and the pose estimation has more difficulties to find a correct estimate. Still, the success rate at 5 m is above 99.5%.

In an operational scenario, pose initialization is performed at the beginning of the close range phase, around distances to the target in the order of 15 m to 20 m. Therefore, a lower performance at very close range is not necessarily problematic. Still, it might be needed to reinitialize the pose tracking during the rendezvous, so that it is preferable to have a method able to initialize the pose at any distance to the target during the final approach.

Figure 4.25: Effect of variable lidar scanning frequency: (a) Point cloud captured with 2.7Hz at 5m to the target, containing 10 045 points; (b) Point cloud captured with 0.7Hz at 20m to the target, containing 7679 points.

Is pose tracking needed ?

The pose initialization is robust and directly delivers a pose estimate without an a priori knowledge of the current pose, so that it is asked if a pose tracking method is even needed. In terms of runtime, considering the point-based method using the optimized PointNet++ model, the pose initialization and pose refinement steps are comparable, see Table 4.9. However, the results presented in Section 4.5.3 indicate that the pose initialization delivers a coarser estimate than the smoothed NDT tracking, which effectively enables to refine the estimate. Still, we analyze the performance of the relative navigation when performing only neural network based pose initialization without a refinement step for every point cloud, and passing these pose estimates to a navigation filter.

The evaluation of this strategy is performed on the tracking dataset presented in Section 2.5.1. The chaser starts at a distance of 17m to the target, performs a fly-around of the target at 15m distance, before performing a final approach until a distance of 3m. During the whole experiment, the target tumbles with an angular velocity of 2 deg/s. Two tracking strategies are compared: The first one is the smoothed NDT tracking in combination with the navigation filter, for which the results are identical to the “NDT + filter” results presented in Section 3.5.2. The second strategy consists in performing the neural network-based pose estimation (relying on the optimized PointNet++ model) for each point cloud, without the NDT refinement step, and passing these measurements to the navigation filter. This method is referred to as “Neural-Net + filter”. The results of the navigation filter errors for each strategy are presented in Fig. 4.26.

The angular error of the tracking is presented in Fig. 4.26a. When integrating with the navigation filter, for the initialization estimate, the current attitude is always selected as the symmetrical equivalent closest to the previous attitude, since the initialization only estimates a possible symmetrical equivalent of the current pose. The attitude error is then shown as the symmetrical error d_{sym} . The first striking observation is that in the end of the experiment, below a distance of 4m (corresponding to approximately minute 23), the error coming from the neural network pose estimation increases. This is due to the target being only partially in the

Figure 4.26: Compared results of tracking with smoothed NDT compared to using only the neural network estimation, in conjunction with a navigation filter: (a) Angular error of the navigation filter; (b) Position error of the navigation filter.

sensor’s field-of-view at short distances. Without a priori information, the pose initialization struggles to precisely determine the correct pose of the target when only some parts of it are visible. This fact alone justifies the need for a pose tracking method in very close range. Still, it is possible to track the target using only the pose initialization result. However, even at larger distances, using only the pose initialization method in combination with a filter leads to a higher noise in the pose error, and less stability. Pose refinement with NDT leads to a lower error, and is able to continue to precisely track the target even in very close range, when the target is only partially in the field-of-view.

4.6 Chapter conclusions

This chapter introduced a method for finding an initial pose estimate of a spacecraft using lidar measurements in a non-cooperative rendezvous scenario. It is suggested to train a neural network to perform pose estimation using the lidar point clouds. To this aim, an advanced lidar simulator is developed, encompassing most relevant effects observed in real scenarios. This simulator is used to generate an extensive synthetic training dataset, relying on a 3D model of the target. The proposed strategy consists in training and refining the model only on synthetic data, enabling to quickly and extensively train or re-train a model in operational scenarios. To demonstrate successful Sim2Real transfer, the pose estimation is then tested on real lidar data from the EPOS rendezvous facility.

An important contribution of the presented pose estimation method is the handling of symmetries in the shape of the target spacecraft. This problem is of practical relevance, since many satellites present a symmetrical shape. Pose estimation of symmetrical objects with neural networks has to be carefully designed, to ensure that the network is able to correctly learn during the training phase. To represent a pose accounting for symmetries, it is suggested to classify the attitude in discrete classes, before removing the symmetrically redundant samples. A continuous

encoding, transforming an attitude into a labels vector representing the weight assigned to each attitude sample, is then introduced. The result is that in spite of discontinuities in the original attitude space, due to the object’s symmetries, the neural network is tasked with learning a continuous function, which facilitates the training.

Two types of neural networks are compared. The first strategy consists in projecting the point clouds to normalized depth images, before processing them with a CNN. The second approach relies on directly processing the point clouds with a point-based neural network. The importance of efficient and careful pre-processing, which is different for both methods, is also shown. The comparison indicates that for the same runtime, a point-based neural network achieves better robustness and precision than an image-based model.

We recall RQ3: *How is a reliable pose initialization method designed for real-time onboard implementation, accounting for varying conditions, sensor noise, and potential symmetries in the shape of the target satellite ?* The results of the evaluation on lidar data taken at the EPOS facility show that the pose estimation method optimized for runtime is precise and reliable. On the test data, 99.78% percent of the initial pose estimates have an angular and position error below 5 deg and 10 cm, enabling to start pose tracking. In this regard, even if trained on synthetic data, the pose estimation method is able to bridge the “domain gap”, and cope with the noise and varying conditions of real data.

The selected point-based neural network, PointNet++, is optimized for runtime by reducing the number and size of point clusters that it uses in each layer. These modifications enable to strongly reduce the model’s inference time, without a significant loss in accuracy compared to other model reduction strategies. To demonstrate real-time capability, the pose initialization method is evaluated on an onboard representative computing platform. Results indicate that the initial pose estimate, before refinement, is obtained within less than 0.6 s. When combined with smoothed NDT refinement, the final pose estimate is provided in less than 0.9 s, showing that the method is adapted for onboard implementation.

The pose initialization strategy presented in this chapter is developed in particular for the case of a symmetrical satellite. The attitude classification finds one of the symmetrical equivalents of the target spacecraft’s pose, and it is shown how it is adapted for various types of symmetries. It is also suited as it is for pose estimation of a non-symmetrical spacecraft. Nevertheless, the initialization method only provides a coarse estimate of the relative pose, so that refinement with a local matching method is needed to achieve precise pose estimation. Further, in very close range, if the target is only partially in the lidar’s field-of-view, it might not be possible to find the pose without an a priori estimate. Contrarily to the pose tracking, pose initialization is designed to be used to initiate the tracking during a final approach, but not to perform pose estimation continuously throughout the approach.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

The objective of this research was to design, implement and evaluate a complete lidar-based navigation system for non-cooperative space rendezvous scenarios. In particular, the focus laid on ensuring that the pose estimation is reliable, precise, and real-time capable for onboard implementation. The findings are supported by a series of experiments conducted at the EPOS facility, where a lidar sensor is mounted on a robot approaching a second robot carrying a satellite mock-up, mimicking a space rendezvous. Individual conclusions for each research question were provided at the end of each chapter. In the following, we first summarize the key contributions and findings of this dissertation with regard to the research objectives, before providing an outlook on future research and applications of this work.

5.1 Summary of contributions

A navigation system was developed for relative pose estimation in close proximity with a non-cooperative satellite. It consists of two components, a pose estimation method processing lidar point clouds, and a navigation filter for incorporating the pose measurements and providing a smooth estimate over time. The point cloud processing itself is also separated in two phases. First comes an initialization phase, corresponding to the initial acquisition of the relative pose, when starting the close range navigation for performing proximity operations. The second phase, after initialization, is the tracking, during which the previous pose estimate is used to find the relative pose on the current point cloud. During this phase, the point cloud processing and navigation filter closely interact to improve the precision and efficiency of the pose estimation.

Following this decomposition, the dissertation was structured around three blocks: pose initialization, pose tracking, and combination of a navigation filter with the pose tracking. This decomposition is also reflected in the chapter structure, although in a different order: Chapter 2 investigates a point cloud matching method for pose tracking, Chapter 3 introduces a formulation of the navigation filter and its interplay with pose tracking, while the topic of pose initialization is addressed in Chapter 4.

For lidar-based pose tracking, local point cloud matching methods are applied, which start from an initial estimate of the relative pose, and iteratively refine the pose estimate by minimizing a distance metric between the current point cloud, and a model or reference point cloud

of the target satellite. The challenges of pose tracking in the context of space rendezvous are summarized in the first research question:

RQ1: How are lidar-based tracking methods enhanced to achieve efficient, robust and precise pose tracking of a spacecraft in non-cooperative rendezvous scenarios ?

To answer this question, Chapter 2 introduced a new point cloud registration method, referred to as smoothed NDT. The idea is to start from the known NDT method, which is an efficient tracking algorithm suited for fast, real-time pose estimation. To improve the robustness of the original NDT algorithm, which only converges to a correct solution when the initial estimate is very close to the optimal pose, a smoothing method of the NDT map is introduced, which consists in performing applying a Gaussian kernel to the distributions of the NDT map. This simple and computationally inexpensive step greatly improve the method's robustness to initialization errors. For a flexible implementation of the algorithm, it is suggested to store the NDT map in a k-d tree. The optimization problem is relaxed and reformulated as a weighted least squares problem, and optimization is performed on the manifold of the rigid transformation group. The suitability of this method with regard to the first research question is demonstrated by evaluating and comparing smoothed NDT with state-of-the-art ICP on lidar datasets collected at the EPOS rendezvous facility. Smoothed NDT enables to precisely track the target's pose in the simulated rendezvous scenarios, even when the sensor framerate is low or the target only partially in the sensor's field-of-view. Compared to ICP, it is approximately three times faster, and evaluations on onboard computing hardware show that the method meets real-time requirements.

The key result of this chapter is that in the space rendezvous context, the common choice of selecting ICP as a point cloud tracking algorithm is not necessarily justified anymore. The presented NDT based algorithm largely outperforms ICP in terms of both precision and runtime, and provides a similar robustness as ICP, i.e., both methods converge to a correct solution for the same range of initial angular and position errors. Given its low runtime and high reliability observed during the rendezvous experiments, the smoothed NDT tracking is the preferred method for point cloud tracking implemented in the rendezvous GNC software developed at DLR. It should be considered as a candidate method in future rendezvous applications if a lidar sensor is used for relative navigation.

The pose tracking method alone is not sufficient to provide a precise pose estimate in case of rapid relative motion. In this case, the combination of a tracking method with a navigation filter is to be studied, as reflected in the second research question:

RQ2: How is the robustness and precision of a lidar-based navigation system ensured in the case of a rapidly tumbling target spacecraft ?

This question was answered in Chapter 3 by suggesting a close interplay between the navigation filter and the pose tracking: The navigation filter processes the pose estimates from the tracking method to provide a smooth estimate, and the tracking uses the estimates of the navigation filter to compensate motion blur and obtain a precise initial estimate of the current pose. The first major contribution of this chapter is a new formulation of a filter for relative navigation, resulting in a simple formulation, and enabling to reduce the pose estimation error

provided by the tracker. It consists in an adapting the IEKF formalism to the problem of pose estimation during spacecraft rendezvous, and is a natural extension of the widespread EKF to the task of state estimation in the rotation group.

The navigation filter is not only necessary to provide a smooth pose estimate to the spacecraft's guidance and control system, but also to support the pose registration in case of rapid dynamics. In particular, for of a fast tumbling motion combined with the low frame rate of a scanning lidar, the point clouds appear blurred. The second main contribution of this chapter are two strategies for compensating this effect: the first one relies on using the estimates of the navigation filter to correct the point cloud in a pre-processing step, and the second one is a continuous-time formulation of the smoothed NDT registration algorithm. The efficiency of these methods for motion compensation is demonstrated by tests at the EPOS facility with a target satellite tumbling with an angular rate up to 10 deg/s, for a lidar framerate of 1 Hz. In spite of the fast relative dynamics, these pose tracking methods combined with the navigation filter enable to provide a navigation solution which meets the typical precision requirements of a GNC system during proximity operations.

The final component for a complete lidar navigation system is a pose initialization method. Since there is no a priori estimate of the relative pose, the search space consists of all possible poses. The challenges of lidar pose initialization are summarized in the third research question:

RQ3: How is a reliable pose initialization method designed for real-time onboard implementation, accounting for varying conditions, sensor noise, and potential symmetries in the shape of the target satellite ?

To answer this question, Chapter 4 introduced a full workflow for neural network based pose initialization. This comprises a custom lidar simulator, developed to incorporate the main effects observed on point cloud data during rendezvous experiments. The simulator is used to generate large synthetic training and validation datasets. Two types of neural network architectures are compared, a CNN based approach which processes the point clouds after projection on a 2D depth image, and a 3D network based approach, which directly processes a point set. Through randomization of the synthetic dataset and custom data augmentation strategies, the pose initialization is robust to varying conditions and noise on real point clouds. This is confirmed by experiments performed at the EPOS rendezvous facility. To ensure real-time capability on onboard computing hardware, it is presented how to optimize the point-based neural network for runtime. Finally, an attitude classification logic enables to handle the case where the target satellite is symmetric, making an unambiguous attitude estimation impossible.

The main contribution of this chapter resides in the design of a complete pipeline for pose initialization, consisting of the lidar simulator, the point cloud pre-processing, the neural network architecture, and the training process. With these components, it is possible to re-train a network for a different target satellite within a short time, given only a 3D model of the satellite. It is demonstrated that with this pipeline, although training is performed on synthetic data, the Sim2Real transfer is successful when evaluating the method on real point clouds. Taken in isolation, a second key contribution of the chapter is the attitude classification logic accounting for symmetries, which is applicable for pose estimation of symmetrical objects in a more general context.

Regarding the complete pose estimation system, pose initialization and tracking complement each other. Even though it provides a pose estimate without relying on a previous estimate, pose initialization is not meant to replace the tracker. Indeed, the result of the neural network based initialization is coarse in comparison to the precision of the tracker. Thus, pose initialization is followed by a refinement step. The pose on the subsequent point clouds is best estimated using the NDT-based tracker aided with estimates from the navigation filter. These results also confirm that for point cloud matching, AI based methods and classical methods work hand-in-hand. Neural networks providing the ability to extrapolate, identify broad patterns and detect global correspondences, while classical methods enable precise final alignment.

5.2 Outlook

The navigation system presented in this dissertation is implemented in C++, and fully integrated in the rendezvous GNC flight software developed by DLR's OOS group. Apart from the results of the experiments presented in this work, the lidar pose estimation is routinely tested on a weekly basis during hardware-in-the-loop tests at EPOS, in the context of the RICADOS project [19]. It has proven to be highly reliable, with no failures observed during its many operational hours at the rendezvous facility. Given its reliability, precision, and real-time capability, the lidar navigation system is considered flight-ready.

However, the experiments were limited to one target satellite, constrained by the mock-up installed at the EPOS facility. While the shape of the considered mock-up is challenging for pose estimation tasks (symmetric, compact, and composed of reflective materials), satellites or space debris come in various shapes and sizes. In case of a rendezvous mission, the lidar pose estimation is to be adapted to the specificities of the considered spacecraft. This concerns the 3D model used for point cloud generation and matching, but also some tuning parameters of the methods (cell size, bounding box size, number of points etc.), and the type of symmetries considered, if any. Further, the case of deformable objects was not considered in this work, in which it was assumed that the target satellite is rigid. This might for example be relevant for satellites with orientable solar panels or antennas. In such cases, further research would be needed to investigate how to adapt the pose estimation.

The pose estimation methods also rely on the assumption that a 3D model of the target is known. This is a common assumption, since a non-cooperative rendezvous mission involving a close range approach and robotic operations is typically preceded by an inspection phase, during which information about the target satellite is gathered. However, the task of 3D reconstruction during an inspection phase is closely adjacent to this research, since it relies on similar methods for point cloud registration. Future studies might investigate the mapping or 3D reconstruction task from lidar data gathered in space, with challenges ahead in terms of computational complexity if this is to happen onboard.

The lidar navigation task is designed to be real-time capable, under the constraint of limited computational power. Much effort was put into reducing the computational time of both the pose initialization and tracking tasks, without compromising the precision of the navigation system. The exact runtime requirement is specified by the computing power of an onboard computer candidate considered for such applications by DLR. While this requirement will

be valid for upcoming rendezvous missions in the next few years, it is clear that it will soon become obsolete. The evolution of space computing closely follows the evolution of computing on ground, although with some delay. With the perspective of increased computational power and AI-specific computing architecture such as GPUs in space, the trade-offs between runtime and precision will be different, allowing for different processing methods or larger AI models. Nevertheless, the runtime optimizations presented in this research might still be found useful, since reducing the runtime on one end enables to increase it on another end, for example for processing larger point clouds.

A limitation of the results presented in this work also concerns the type of sensor used, since a lidar sensor from the automotive domain was used for the rendezvous experiments at EPOS. At the time of this research, due to the high cost of space-qualified lidars, no such sensor was available for the tests. While the settings of the automotive lidar were selected to approach the characteristics of space-grade sensors, future experiments at EPOS would be more representative if performed with a space lidar. In particular, in case a sensor is selected for a mission, tests should be performed with this lidar and the considered target mock-up prior to the mission, to analyze the effects arising by combining the laser and scanning properties of the sensor with the material properties of the target.

The evolution of space-qualified lidar sensors will probably follow the evolution of lidar sensors for terrestrial applications. Lidars in use for space applications are comparatively heavy, power intensive and costly. However, miniaturized sensors are arriving in the space market. Given the advantages of active 3D sensors compared for example to optical cameras for such applications, it is likely that navigation systems for future rendezvous missions will primarily rely on lidars, or similar ranging sensors. The automotive sensor used for experiments at EPOS has a high point rate, so that the recorded lidar point clouds are dense. Further analysis could be performed to study the case of pose estimation from sparse point clouds, which is challenging since fewer features are identifiable in the scans. However, following the evolution in the field of sensor development, it is more likely that the resolution of lidar sensors will increase in the future, leading to point clouds with higher density.

Even if the lidar navigation is robust, a failure is never excluded, and a GNC system should not rely on a single source of information for the safety of a rendezvous mission. When integrated in a complete GNC system, the lidar pose estimation has to be complemented with navigation information from different sources or different methods for consistency checks, and failure detection. This is the subfield of Fault Detection, Isolation and Recovery (FDIR), which is not in the scope of this dissertation. Future studies might analyze how consistency checks, or confidence scores, could be added to complement the methods developed in this work.

The goal of the research conducted in this dissertation is to enable precise relative navigation during space rendezvous. As such, the navigation system is designed to be ultimately applied in space. Its aim is to support future OOS and ADR missions, allowing for a both sustainable and ambitious use of space. Testing the lidar navigation system in its final environment, space, will also bring crucial insights and lessons.

Bibliography

- [1] Léo Renault, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Smoothed normal distribution transform for efficient point cloud registration during space rendezvous. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications*, volume 5, pages 919–930, 2023.
- [2] Léo Renault, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Lidar Pose Tracking of a Tumbling Spacecraft Using the Smoothed Normal Distribution Transform. *Remote Sensing*, 15(9):2286, 2023.
- [3] Léo Renault, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. LiDAR based pose tracking of an uncooperative spacecraft using the smoothed normal distribution transform. In *12th International Conference on Guidance, Navigation & Control Systems (ESA GNC and ICATT 2023). 12.-16. Jun. 2023, Sopot, Poland.*, 2023.
- [4] Léo Renault, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. CNN-based Pose Estimation of a Non-Cooperative Spacecraft with Symmetries from Lidar Point Clouds. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 2024. (in press).
- [5] Léo Renault, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Deep Learning on 3D Point Clouds for Fast Pose Estimation during Satellite Rendezvous. *Acta Astronautica*, 232:231–243, 2025.
- [6] Léo Renault, Heike Frei, and Andreas Nüchter. Invariant Extended Kalman Filtering for Relative Pose Estimation during Spacecraft Rendezvous. (in preparation).
- [7] ESA. Esa’s annual space environment report. https://www.sdo.esoc.esa.int/environment_report/Space_Environment_Report_latest.pdf, 2024. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [8] John L Goodman and Stephen R Walker. Hubble Servicing Challenges Drive Innovation of Shuttle Rendezvous Techniques. In *32nd Annual AAS Guidance and Control Conference*, 2009.
- [9] Robert B Friend. Orbital express program summary and mission overview. In *Sensors and Systems for space applications II*, volume 6958, pages 11–21. SPIE, 2008.
- [10] Matt Pyrak and Joseph Anderson. Performance of Northrop grumman’s mission extension vehicle (MEV) RPO imagers at GEO. In *Autonomous systems: Sensors, processing and*

- security for ground, air, sea and space vehicles and infrastructure 2022*, volume 12115, pages 64–82. SPIE, 2022.
- [11] Joshua P Davis, John P Mayberry, and Jay P Penn. On-orbit servicing: Inspection repair refuel upgrade and assembly of satellites in space. *The Aerospace Corporation, report*, page 25, 2019.
- [12] United States Space Force. Geosynchronous Space Situational Awareness Program. <https://www.spaceforce.mil/About-Us/Fact-Sheets/Article/2197772/geosynchronous-space-situational-awareness-program/>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [13] Donald J Kessler and Burton G Cour-Palais. Collision frequency of artificial satellites: The creation of a debris belt. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 83(A6):2637–2646, 1978.
- [14] Luisa Innocenti, Tiago Soares, Jessica Delaval, and Antonio Rinalducci. ESA clean space initiative. In *Safety is Not an Option, Proceedings of the 6th IAASS Conference*, volume 715, 2013.
- [15] Robin Biesbroek, Sarmad Aziz, Andrew Wolahan, Stefano Cipolla, Muriel Richard-Noca, and Luc Piguet. The clearspace-1 mission: ESA and clearspace team up to remove debris. In *Proc. 8th Eur. Conf. Sp. Debris*, pages 1–3, 2021.
- [16] Jason Forshaw, A Colebourn, C Walker, E Hutchinson, N Shave, S Iizuka, Y Seto, Y Ota, AA Lidtke, Y Kobayashi, et al. Operational progress update on the ELSA-d debris removal mission. In *Proceedings of the International Astronautical Congress, IAC*, 2022.
- [17] Alexandre Falcoz, Pierre Blanc-Paques, Keyvan Kanani, Jérémy Lesprier, Xavier Manuel-Juanpere, Benjamin Charbaut, Sophie Narbonne, Leila Lorenzoni, Paul Duteis, and Christoph Steiger. Guidance, Navigation & Control on-board architecture for Mars Sample Return Rendezvous & Capture. In *12th International Conference on Guidance, Navigation & Control Systems (ESA GNC and ICATT 2023). 12.-16. Jun. 2023, Sopot, Poland.*, 2023.
- [18] Wigbert Fehse. *Automated rendezvous and docking of spacecraft*, volume 16, pages 8–28, 41, 438, 441–445. Cambridge university press, 2003.
- [19] Heike Benninghoff, Florian Rems, Eicke-Alexander Risse, Patrick Irmisch, Ines Ernst, Bernhard Brunner, Martin Stelzer, Roberto Lampariello, Rainer Krenn, Matthias Reiner, et al. RICADOS-rendezvous, inspection, capturing and detumbling by orbital servicing. In *7th International Conference on Astrodynamics Tools and Techniques*, 2018.
- [20] Thomas A Lovell and David A Spencer. Relative orbital elements formulation based upon the clohessy-wiltshire equations. *The Journal of the Astronautical Sciences*, 61:341–366, 2014.
- [21] Gabriella Gaias, Simone D’Amico, and Jean-Sébastien Ardaens. Angles-only navigation to a noncooperative satellite using relative orbital elements. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 37(2):439–451, 2014.

-
- [22] Heike Frei, Léo Renaut, and Isabel Ibáñez Jiménez. A review on coordinate systems and orbit models for spacecraft rendezvous. *Advances in Space Research*, 2025. (Submitted).
- [23] Koji Yamanaka, Kiyomi Yokota, Katsuhiko Yamada, Hiroshi Koyama, Katsumi Tsukahara, Shoji Yoshikawa, and Taichi Nakamura. Guidance and navigation system design of R-bar approach for rendezvous and docking. In *17th AIAA International communications satellite systems conference and exhibit*, page 1299, 1998.
- [24] David C Woffinden and David K Geller. Navigating the Road to Autonomous Orbital Rendezvous. *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, 44(4):898–909, 2007.
- [25] David C Woffinden and David K Geller. Relative Angles-Only Navigation and Pose Estimation For Autonomous Orbital Rendezvous. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 30(5):1455–1469, 2007.
- [26] Yazhong Luo, Jin Zhang, and Guojin Tang. Survey of orbital dynamics and control of space rendezvous. *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 27(1):1–11, 2014.
- [27] Jean-Sébastien Ardaens and Gabriella Gaias. Angles-only relative orbit determination in low earth orbit. *Advances in Space Research*, 61(11):2740–2760, 2018.
- [28] Gabriella Gaias and Jean-Sébastien Ardaens. Flight demonstration of autonomous non-cooperative rendezvous in low earth orbit. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 41(6):1337–1354, 2018.
- [29] Justin Kruger and Simone D’Amico. Autonomous angles-only multitarget tracking for spacecraft swarms. *Acta Astronautica*, 189:514–529, 2021.
- [30] Joshua Sullivan and Simone D’Amico. Nonlinear Kalman filtering for improved angles-only navigation using relative orbital elements. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 40(9):2183–2200, 2017.
- [31] Jean-Sébastien Ardaens. *Angles-only Relative Navigation in Low Earth Orbit*. PhD thesis, TU Delft, 2020.
- [32] Simone D’Amico. Relative orbital elements as integration constants of Hill’s equations. *DLR, TN*, pages 05–08, 2005.
- [33] Simone D’Amico. *Autonomous formation flying in low earth orbit*. PhD thesis, TU Delft, 2010.
- [34] David C Woffinden and David K Geller. Observability criteria for angles-only navigation. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 45(3):1194–1208, 2009.
- [35] Matthew A Vavrina, C Eugene Skelton, Keith D DeWeese, Bo J Naasz, David E Gaylor, and Christopher D’souza. Safe rendezvous trajectory design for the restore-1 mission. *Advances in the Astronautical Sciences*, 168:3649–3668, 2019.

- [36] Chris Blackerby, Akira Okamoto, Seita Iizuka, Yusuke Kobayashi, Kohei Fujimoto, Yuki Seto, Sho Fujita, Takashi Iwai, Nobu Okada, Jason Forshaw, et al. The ELSA-d End-of-life Debris Removal Mission: Preparing for Launch. In *Proceedings of the International Astronautical Congress, IAC*, volume 8, 2019.
- [37] Takahiro Sasaki, Yu Nakajima, and Toru Yamamoto. Proximity Approaches and Design Strategies for Non-Cooperative Rendezvous V-bar Hopping vs. Spiral Approach. *Transactions of the Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences*, 64(3):136–146, 2021.
- [38] Frank Schnitzer, Klaus Janschek, and Georg Willich. Experimental results for image-based geometrical reconstruction for spacecraft rendezvous navigation with unknown and uncooperative target spacecraft. In *2012 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pages 5040–5045. IEEE, 2012.
- [39] Martin Dziura, Tim Wiese, and Jan Harder. 3D reconstruction in orbital proximity operations. In *2017 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, pages 1–10. IEEE, 2017.
- [40] Van Minh Nguyen, Emma Sandidge, Trupti Mahendrakar, and Ryan T White. Characterizing satellite geometry via accelerated 3D Gaussian splatting. *Aerospace*, 11(3):183, 2024.
- [41] Jürgen Telaar, Ingo Ahrns, Stéphane Estable, Wolfgang Rackl, Marco De Stefano, Roberto Lampariello, Nuno Santos, Pedro Serra, Marco Canetri, Finn Ankersen, et al. GNC architecture for the e. Deorbit mission. In *7th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences (EUCASS)*, pages 1–15. ESA Publications Division, ESTEC Noordwijk, The Netherlands, 2017.
- [42] Michael Hiltz, Craig Rice, Keith Boyle, and Ronald Allison. CANADARM: 20 Years of Mission Success Through Adaptation. In *International Symposium on Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and Automation*, 2001.
- [43] Lorenzo Pasqualetto Cassinis, Robert Fonod, and Eberhard Gill. Review of the robustness and applicability of monocular pose estimation systems for relative navigation with an uncooperative spacecraft. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, 110:100548, 2019.
- [44] Mate Kisantal, Sumant Sharma, Tae Ha Park, Dario Izzo, Marcus Märtens, and Simone D’Amico. Satellite pose estimation challenge: Dataset, competition design, and results. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 56(5):4083–4098, 2020.
- [45] Yinlin Hu, Sebastien Speierer, Wenzel Jakob, Pascal Fua, and Mathieu Salzmann. Wide-depth-range 6d object pose estimation in space. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 15870–15879, 2021.
- [46] Tae Ha Park, Marcus Märtens, Gurvan Lecuyer, Dario Izzo, and Simone D’Amico. SPEED+: Next-generation dataset for spacecraft pose estimation across domain gap. In *2022 IEEE Aerospace Conference (AERO)*, pages 1–15. IEEE, 2022.

- [47] Simone D’Amico, Mathias Benn, and John L Jørgensen. Pose estimation of an uncooperative spacecraft from actual space imagery. *International Journal of Space Science and Engineering* 5, 2(2):171–189, 2014.
- [48] Jian-Feng Shi, Steve Ulrich, Stephane Ruel, and Martin Anctil. Uncooperative spacecraft pose estimation using an infrared camera during proximity operations. In *AIAA SPACE 2015 conference and exposition*, page 4429, 2015.
- [49] Duarte Rondao, Nabil Aouf, and Mark A Richardson. Chinet: Deep recurrent convolutional learning for multimodal spacecraft pose estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 2022.
- [50] Mohsi Jawaid, Ethan Elms, Yasir Latif, and Tat-Jun Chin. Towards bridging the space domain gap for satellite pose estimation using event sensing. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 11866–11873. IEEE, 2023.
- [51] Guillermo Gallego, Tobi Delbrück, Garrick Orchard, Chiara Bartolozzi, Brian Taba, Andrea Censi, Stefan Leutenegger, Andrew J Davison, Jörg Conradt, Kostas Daniilidis, et al. Event-based vision: A survey. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 44(1):154–180, 2020.
- [52] Radu Horaud, Miles Hansard, Georgios Evangelidis, and Clément Ménéier. An overview of depth cameras and range scanners based on time-of-flight technologies. *Machine vision and applications*, 27(7):1005–1020, 2016.
- [53] Roberto Opromolla, Giancarmine Fasano, Giancarlo Rufino, and Michele Grassi. Characterization and testing of a high-resolution time-of-flight camera for autonomous navigation. In *2018 5th IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace (MetroAeroSpace)*, pages 380–385. IEEE, 2018.
- [54] Clemente Tecchia, Margherita Piccinin, Alessia Nocerino, Roberto Opromolla, and Ulrich Hillenbrand. Pose Acquisition of Non-Cooperative Spacecraft from LiDAR: Comparison of Methods Based on Point Correspondences. In *AIAA SciTech 2025 Forum*, page 1416, 2025.
- [55] Lujiang Liu, Gaopeng Zhao, and Yuming Bo. Point cloud based relative pose estimation of a satellite in close range. *Sensors*, 16(6):824, 2016.
- [56] Ksenia Klionovska and Matthias Burri. Hardware-in-the-loop simulations with umbra conditions for spacecraft rendezvous with PMD visual sensors. *Sensors*, 21(4):1455, 2021.
- [57] Dianqi Sun, Liang Hu, Huixian Duan, and Haodong Pei. Relative Pose Estimation of Non-Cooperative Space Targets Using a TOF Camera. *Remote Sensing*, 14(23):6100, 2022.
- [58] Farzin Amzajerjian, Vincent E Roback, Alexander Bulyshev, Paul F Brewster, and Glenn D Hines. Imaging Flash Lidar for Autonomous Safe Landing and Spacecraft Proximity Operation. In *AIAA SPACE 2016*, page 5591, 2016.

- [59] Ann B Dietrich and Jay W McMahon. Filter initialization with three-dimensional Lidar images in proximity to small bodies. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 43(2):310–318, 2020.
- [60] Jason M Leonard, Michael C Moreau, Peter G Antreasian, Kenneth M Getzandanner, Estelle Church, Curtis Miller, Michael G Daly, Olivier S Barnouin, and Dante S Lauretta. Cross-Calibration of GNC and OLA LIDAR Systems Onboard OSIRIS-REx. In *Proceedings of the 44th Annual American Astronautical Society Guidance, Navigation, and Control Conference, 2022*, pages 1585–1607. Springer, 2022.
- [61] ASC. GSFL-16KS Space 3D Flash LIDAR™. https://asc3d.com/gsf1_16ks/. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [62] Stéphane Ruel, Tim Luu, and Andrew Berube. Space shuttle testing of the TriDAR 3D rendezvous and docking sensor. *Journal of Field robotics*, 29(4):535–553, 2012.
- [63] Jena-Optronik. μ RVS The next generation LiDAR: Small, light and eye safe. <https://www.jena-optronik.de/products/rendezvous-sensors/mrvs.html>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [64] François Pomerleau, Francis Colas, Roland Siegwart, et al. A review of point cloud registration algorithms for mobile robotics. *Foundations and Trends® in Robotics*, 4(1):1–104, 2015.
- [65] Yipeng Li, Yunpeng Wang, and Yongchun Xie. Using consecutive point clouds for pose and motion estimation of tumbling non-cooperative target. *Advances in Space Research*, 63(5):1576–1587, 2019.
- [66] George Lentaris, Konstantinos Maragos, Ioannis Stratakos, Lazaros Papadopoulos, Odysseas Papanikolaou, Dimitrios Soudris, Manolis Lourakis, Xenophon Zabulis, David Gonzalez-Arjona, and Gianluca Furano. High-Performance Embedded Computing in Space: Evaluation of Platforms for Vision-Based Navigation. *Journal of Aerospace Information Systems*, 15(4):178–192, 2018.
- [67] Gianluca Furano, Gabriele Meoni, Aubrey Dunne, David Moloney, Veronique Ferlet-Cavrois, Antonis Tavoularis, Jonathan Byrne, Léonie Buckley, Mihalis Psarakis, Kay-Obbe Voss, et al. Towards the use of artificial intelligence on the edge in space systems: Challenges and opportunities. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, 35(12):44–56, 2020.
- [68] Bing Zhang, Yuanfeng Wu, Boya Zhao, Jocelyn Chanussot, Danfeng Hong, Jing Yao, and Lianru Gao. Progress and Challenges in Intelligent Remote Sensing Satellite Systems. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 15:1814–1822, 2022.
- [69] Tobias Herbst, Oleksii Balagurin, Tobias Greiner, Tobias Kaiser, Hakan Kayal, Andreas Maurer, and Tobias Schwarz. 6U+ CubeSat SONATE2: Operation of an Optical AI Payload in Low Earth Orbit. In *75th International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, 2024.

- [70] Nuno Filipe, Michail Kontitsis, and Panagiotis Tsiotras. Extended Kalman Filter for Spacecraft Pose Estimation Using Dual Quaternions. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 38(9):1625–1641, 2015.
- [71] Anthea Comellini, Davide Casu, Emmanuel Zenou, Vincent Dubanchet, and Christine Espinosa. Incorporating delayed and multirate measurements in navigation filter for autonomous space rendezvous. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 43(6):1164–1172, 2020.
- [72] Heike Frei, Matthias Burri, Florian Rems, and Eicke-Alexander Risse. A robust navigation filter fusing delayed measurements from multiple sensors and its application to spacecraft rendezvous. *Advances in Space Research*, 72(7):2874–2900, 2023.
- [73] Zhen Dong, Fuxun Liang, Bisheng Yang, Yusheng Xu, Yufu Zang, Jianping Li, Yuan Wang, Wenxia Dai, Hongchao Fan, Juha Hyypä, et al. Registration of large-scale terrestrial laser scanner point clouds: A review and benchmark. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 163:327–342, 2020.
- [74] Qin Zou, Qin Sun, Long Chen, Bu Nie, and Qingquan Li. A comparative analysis of LiDAR SLAM-based indoor navigation for autonomous vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 23(7):6907–6921, 2021.
- [75] Andreas Nüchter and Kai Lingemann. Robotic 3D scan repository. <http://kos.informatik.uni-osnabrueck.de/3Dscans/>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [76] Roberto Opromolla, Giancarmine Fasano, Giancarlo Rufino, and Michele Grassi. Pose estimation for spacecraft relative navigation using model-based algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 53(1):431–447, 2017.
- [77] PJ Besl and Neil D McKay. A method for registration of 3-D shapes. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis & Machine Intelligence*, 14(02):239–256, 1992.
- [78] K Somani Arun, Thomas S Huang, and Steven D Blostein. Least-Squares Fitting of Two 3-D Point Sets. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 9(5):698–700, 1987.
- [79] Yang Chen and Gérard Medioni. Object modelling by registration of multiple range images. *Image and vision computing*, 10(3):145–155, 1992.
- [80] Tomas Pajdla and Luc Van Gool. Matching of 3-D curves using semi-differential invariants. In *Proceedings of IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pages 390–395. IEEE, 1995.
- [81] Dmitry Chetverikov, Dmitry Svirko, Dmitry Stepanov, and Pavel Krsek. The trimmed iterative closest point algorithm. In *2002 International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, volume 3, pages 545–548. IEEE, 2002.
- [82] Aleksandr Segal, Dirk Haehnel, and Sebastian Thrun. Generalized-ICP. In *Robotics: science and systems*, volume 2(4), page 435. Seattle, WA, 2009.

- [83] Kenji Koide, Masashi Yokozuka, Shuji Oishi, and Atsuhiko Banno. Voxelized gicp for fast and accurate 3d point cloud registration. In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 11054–11059. IEEE, 2021.
- [84] Juyong Zhang, Yuxin Yao, and Bailin Deng. Fast and robust iterative closest point. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 44(7):3450–3466, 2021.
- [85] Michael Greenspan and Mike Yurick. Approximate kd tree search for efficient ICP. In *Fourth International Conference on 3-D Digital Imaging and Modeling, 2003. 3DIM 2003. Proceedings.*, pages 442–448. IEEE, 2003.
- [86] Andreas Nüchter, Kai Lingemann, and Joachim Hertzberg. Cached kd tree search for ICP algorithms. In *Sixth International Conference on 3-D Digital Imaging and Modeling (3DIM 2007)*, pages 419–426. IEEE, 2007.
- [87] Deyuan Qiu, Stefan May, and Andreas Nüchter. GPU-accelerated nearest neighbor search for 3D registration. In *Computer Vision Systems: 7th International Conference on Computer Vision Systems, ICVS 2009 Liège, Belgium, October 13-15, 2009. Proceedings 7*, pages 194–203. Springer, 2009.
- [88] Zi Jian Yew and Gim Hee Lee. Rpm-net: Robust point matching using learned features. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 11824–11833, 2020.
- [89] Peter Biber and Wolfgang Straßer. The normal distributions transform: A new approach to laser scan matching. In *Proceedings 2003 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS 2003)(Cat. No. 03CH37453)*, volume 3, pages 2743–2748. IEEE, 2003.
- [90] Martin Magnusson. *The three-dimensional normal-distributions transform: an efficient representation for registration, surface analysis, and loop detection*. PhD thesis, Örebro universitet, 2009.
- [91] Martin Magnusson, Andreas Nuchter, Christopher Lorken, Achim J Lilienthal, and Joachim Hertzberg. Evaluation of 3D registration reliability and speed-A comparison of ICP and NDT. In *2009 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, pages 3907–3912. IEEE, 2009.
- [92] Su Pang, Daniel Kent, Xi Cai, Hothaifa Al-Qassab, Daniel Morris, and Hayder Radha. 3d scan registration based localization for autonomous vehicles-a comparison of ndt and icp under realistic conditions. In *2018 IEEE 88th vehicular technology conference (VTC-Fall)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2018.
- [93] Martin Magnusson, Achim Lilienthal, and Tom Duckett. Scan registration for autonomous mining vehicles using 3D-NDT. *Journal of Field Robotics*, 24(10):803–827, 2007.
- [94] Cihan Ulaş and Hakan Temeltaş. 3D multi-layered normal distribution transform for fast and long range scan matching. *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems*, 71:85–108, 2013.

- [95] Eijiro Takeuchi and Takashi Tsubouchi. A 3-D scan matching using improved 3-D normal distributions transform for mobile robotic mapping. In *2006 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pages 3068–3073. IEEE, 2006.
- [96] David Droeschel, Jörg Stückler, and Sven Behnke. Local multi-resolution representation for 6D motion estimation and mapping with a continuously rotating 3D laser scanner. In *2014 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 5221–5226. IEEE, 2014.
- [97] Jan Quenzel and Sven Behnke. Real-time multi-adaptive-resolution-surfel 6D LiDAR odometry using continuous-time trajectory optimization. In *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pages 5499–5506. IEEE, 2021.
- [98] Arun Das and Steven L Waslander. Scan registration using segmented region growing NDT. *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, 33(13):1645–1663, 2014.
- [99] Todor Stoyanov, Martin Magnusson, and Achim J Lilienthal. Point set registration through minimization of the l 2 distance between 3d-ndt models. In *2012 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, pages 5196–5201. IEEE, 2012.
- [100] Andriy Myronenko and Xubo Song. Point set registration: Coherent point drift. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 32(12):2262–2275, 2010.
- [101] Hyunki Hong and Beom Hee Lee. Probabilistic normal distributions transform representation for accurate 3D point cloud registration. In *2017 IEEE/RSJ international conference on intelligent robots and systems (IROS)*, pages 3333–3338. IEEE, 2017.
- [102] Cornelia Schulz and Andreas Zell. Real-time graph-based SLAM with occupancy normal distributions transforms. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 3106–3111. IEEE, 2020.
- [103] Prasanta C. Mahalanobis. On the generalized distance in statistics. *Proceedings of the National Institute of Science of India*, 2(1):49–55, 1936.
- [104] Hyungtae Lim, Sungwon Hwang, Sungjae Shin, and Hyun Myung. Normal distributions transform is enough: Real-time 3D scan matching for pose correction of mobile robot under large odometry uncertainties. In *2020 20th International Conference on Control, Automation and Systems (ICCAS)*, pages 1155–1161. IEEE, 2020.
- [105] Cornelia Schulz, Richard Hantén, and Andreas Zell. Efficient map representations for multi-dimensional normal distributions transforms. In *2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pages 2679–2686. IEEE, 2018.
- [106] Jens Behley and Cyrill Stachniss. Efficient Surfel-Based SLAM using 3D Laser Range Data in Urban Environments. In *Robotics: Science and Systems*, volume 2018, page 59, 2018.
- [107] Frank Moosmann and Christoph Stiller. Velodyne SLAM. In *2011 IEEE intelligent vehicles symposium (iv)*, pages 393–398. IEEE, 2011.

- [108] Jean-Emmanuel Deschaud. IMLS-SLAM: Scan-to-model matching based on 3D data. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 2480–2485. IEEE, 2018.
- [109] Yue Pan, Pengchuan Xiao, Yujie He, Zhenlei Shao, and Zesong Li. MULLS: Versatile LiDAR SLAM via multi-metric linear least square. In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 11633–11640. IEEE, 2021.
- [110] Han Wang, Chen Wang, Chun-Lin Chen, and Lihua Xie. F-LOAM : Fast LiDAR Odometry and Mapping. In *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pages 4390–4396. IEEE, 2021.
- [111] Chanoh Park, Peyman Moghadam, Soohwan Kim, Alberto Elfes, Clinton Fookes, and Sridha Sridharan. Elastic lidar fusion: Dense map-centric continuous-time slam. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 1206–1213. IEEE, 2018.
- [112] David Droeschel and Sven Behnke. Efficient continuous-time SLAM for 3D lidar-based online mapping. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 5000–5007. IEEE, 2018.
- [113] Pierre Dellenbach, Jean-Emmanuel Deschaud, Bastien Jacquet, and François Goulette. CT-ICP: Real-time elastic LiDAR odometry with loop closure. In *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 5580–5586. IEEE, 2022.
- [114] Ji Zhang and Sanjiv Singh. LOAM: Lidar Odometry and Mapping in Real-time. In *Proceedings of the Robotics: Science and Systems Conference (RSS)*, pages 1–9. Berkeley, CA, 2014.
- [115] Andreas Nüchter, Michael Bleier, Johannes Schauer, and Peter Janotta. Improving Google’s Cartographer 3D mapping by continuous-time slam. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 42:543–549, 2017.
- [116] Gérard Blais and Martin D. Levine. Registering multiview range data to create 3D computer objects. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 17(8):820–824, 1995.
- [117] Jie Li, Yiqi Zhuang, Qi Peng, and Liang Zhao. Pose Estimation of Non-Cooperative Space Targets Based on Cross-Source Point Cloud Fusion. *Remote Sensing*, 13(21):4239, 2021.
- [118] Qishuai Wang, Ting Lei, Xiaofeng Liu, Guoping Cai, Yifeng Yang, Lihui Jiang, and Zhangwei Yu. Pose estimation of non-cooperative target coated with MLI. *IEEE Access*, 7:153958–153968, 2019.
- [119] Harvey Gómez Martínez, Gabriele Giorgi, and Bernd Eissfeller. Pose estimation and tracking of non-cooperative rocket bodies using time-of-flight cameras. *Acta Astronautica*, 139:165–175, 2017.

- [120] Roberto Opromolla and Alessia Nocerino. Uncooperative spacecraft relative navigation with LIDAR-based unscented Kalman filter. *IEEE Access*, 7:180012–180026, 2019.
- [121] Fang Yin, Wusheng Chou, Yun Wu, Guang Yang, and Song Xu. Sparse unorganized point cloud based relative pose estimation for uncooperative space target. *Sensors*, 18(4):1009, 2018.
- [122] Timothy D Barfoot. *State Estimation for Robotics*. Cambridge University Press, 2024.
- [123] Zhe Chen et al. Bayesian filtering: From Kalman filters to particle filters, and beyond. *Statistics*, 182(1):1–69, 2003.
- [124] Rudolph Emil Kalman. A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems. *ASME Journal of Basic Engineering*, 82(1):35–45, 1960.
- [125] Daniel Alazard. Introduction to Kalman filtering. *SUPAERO*, 2005.
- [126] François Auger, Mickael Hilaret, Josep M Guerrero, Eric Monmasson, Teresa Orłowska-Kowalska, and Seiichiro Katsura. Industrial Applications of the Kalman Filter: A Review. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 60(12):5458–5471, 2013.
- [127] Ern J Lefferts, F Landis Markley, and Malcolm D Shuster. Kalman Filtering for Spacecraft Attitude Estimation. *Journal of Guidance, control, and Dynamics*, 5(5):417–429, 1982.
- [128] Joan Sola. Quaternion kinematics for the error-state kalman filter. *Laboratoire d'Analyse et d'Architecture des Systemes-Centre national de la recherche scientifique (LAAS-CNRS), Toulouse, France, Tech. Rep*, page 35, 2012.
- [129] F Landis Markley. Multiplicative vs. Additive Filtering for Spacecraft Attitude Determination. In *Proceedings of the 6th Cranfield Conference on Dynamics and Control of Systems and Structures in Space*, pages 467–474. Citeseer, 2004.
- [130] Xiaojun Tang, Jie Yan, and Dudu Zhong. Square-root sigma-point Kalman filtering for spacecraft relative navigation. *Acta Astronautica*, 66(5-6):704–713, 2010.
- [131] Axel Barrau and Silvere Bonnabel. The Invariant Extended Kalman Filter as a Stable Observer. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 62(4):1797–1812, 2016.
- [132] Axel Barrau and Silvere Bonnabel. Invariant Kalman filtering. *Annual Review of Control, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems*, 1(1):237–257, 2018.
- [133] Haichao Gui and Anton HJ de Ruiter. Quaternion Invariant Extended Kalman Filtering for Spacecraft Attitude Estimation. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 41(4):863–878, 2018.
- [134] Yash Pandey, Rahul Bhattacharyya, and Yatindra Nath Singh. Adaptive invariant extended kalman filter with noise covariance tuning for attitude estimation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.01958*, 2024.

- [135] Wolfgang Hess, Damon Kohler, Holger Rapp, and Daniel Andor. Real-time loop closure in 2D LIDAR SLAM. In *2016 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation (ICRA)*, pages 1271–1278. IEEE, 2016.
- [136] Jiaolong Yang, Hongdong Li, Dylan Campbell, and Yunde Jia. Go-ICP: A globally optimal solution to 3D ICP point-set registration. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 38(11):2241–2254, 2015.
- [137] Dror Aiger, Niloy J Mitra, and Daniel Cohen-Or. 4-points congruent sets for robust pairwise surface registration. *ACM SIGGRAPH 2008 papers*, pages 1–10, 2008.
- [138] Nicolas Mellado, Dror Aiger, and Niloy J Mitra. Super 4pcs fast global pointcloud registration via smart indexing. In *Computer graphics forum*, volume 33(5), pages 205–215. Wiley Online Library, 2014.
- [139] Pascal Willy Theiler, Jan Dirk Wegner, and Konrad Schindler. Keypoint-based 4-points congruent sets—automated marker-less registration of laser scans. *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing*, 96:149–163, 2014.
- [140] Cedrique Fotsing, Nafissetou Nziengam, and Christophe Bobda. Large common plansets-4-points congruent sets for point cloud registration. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(11):647, 2020.
- [141] Ksenia Klionovska and Heike Benninghoff. Initial pose estimation using PMD sensor during the rendezvous phase in on-orbit servicing missions. In *27th AAS/AIAA Space Flight Mechanics Meeting*, 2017.
- [142] Bertram Drost, Markus Ulrich, Nassir Navab, and Slobodan Ilic. Model globally, match locally: Efficient and robust 3D object recognition. In *2010 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 998–1005. IEEE, 2010.
- [143] Christoph Schmitt, Michael Windmüller, Michael Schwarz, and Max Möller. RVS@ 3000-3D LiDAR—Next Stop: Gateway. In *Proceedings of the 44th Annual American Astronautical Society Guidance, Navigation, and Control Conference, 2022*, pages 489–496. Springer, 2024.
- [144] Christoph Schmitt, Johannes Both, and Florian Kolb. RVS3000-3D: LIDAR meets Neural Networks. In *International Symposium of Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and Automation in Space, (Jun. 4, 2018)*, pages 1–7, 2018.
- [145] Roberto Opromolla, Giancarmine Fasano, Giancarlo Rufino, and Michele Grassi. A model-based 3D template matching technique for pose acquisition of an uncooperative space object. *Sensors*, 15(3):6360–6382, 2015.
- [146] Wulong Guo, Weiduo Hu, Chang Liu, and Tingting Lu. Pose initialization of uncooperative spacecraft by template matching with sparse point cloud. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 44(9):1707–1720, 2021.

- [147] Yu Zhong. Intrinsic shape signatures: A shape descriptor for 3D object recognition. In *2009 IEEE 12th international conference on computer vision workshops, ICCV Workshops*, pages 689–696. IEEE, 2009.
- [148] Andrei Zaharescu, Edmond Boyer, Kiran Varanasi, and Radu Horaud. Surface feature detection and description with applications to mesh matching. In *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 373–380. IEEE, 2009.
- [149] Ivan Sipiran and Benjamin Bustos. Harris 3D: a robust extension of the Harris operator for interest point detection on 3D meshes. *The Visual Computer*, 27:963–976, 2011.
- [150] Yulan Guo, Mohammed Bennamoun, Ferdous Sohel, Min Lu, Jianwei Wan, and Ngai Ming Kwok. A comprehensive performance evaluation of 3D local feature descriptors. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 116:66–89, 2016.
- [151] Andrew E Johnson and Martial Hebert. Using spin images for efficient object recognition in cluttered 3D scenes. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 21(5):433–449, 1999.
- [152] Andrea Frome, Daniel Huber, Ravi Kolluri, Thomas Bülow, and Jitendra Malik. Recognizing objects in range data using regional point descriptors. In *Computer Vision-ECCV 2004: 8th European Conference on Computer Vision, Prague, Czech Republic, May 11-14, 2004. Proceedings, Part III 8*, pages 224–237. Springer, 2004.
- [153] Yulan Guo, Ferdous Sohel, Mohammed Bennamoun, Min Lu, and Jianwei Wan. Rotational projection statistics for 3D local surface description and object recognition. *International journal of computer vision*, 105:63–86, 2013.
- [154] Radu Bogdan Rusu, Nico Blodow, Zoltan Csaba Marton, and Michael Beetz. Aligning point cloud views using persistent feature histograms. In *2008 IEEE/RSJ international conference on intelligent robots and systems*, pages 3384–3391. IEEE, 2008.
- [155] Radu Bogdan Rusu, Nico Blodow, and Michael Beetz. Fast point feature histograms (FPFH) for 3D registration. In *2009 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation*, pages 3212–3217. IEEE, 2009.
- [156] Federico Tombari, Samuele Salti, and Luigi Di Stefano. Unique signatures of histograms for local surface description. In *Computer Vision-ECCV 2010: 11th European Conference on Computer Vision, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, September 5-11, 2010, Proceedings, Part III 11*, pages 356–369. Springer, 2010.
- [157] Martin A Fischler and Robert C Bolles. Random sample consensus: a paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography. *Communications of the ACM*, 24(6):381–395, 1981.
- [158] Qian-Yi Zhou, Jaesik Park, and Vladlen Koltun. Fast global registration. In *Computer Vision-ECCV 2016: 14th European Conference, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, October 11-14, 2016, Proceedings, Part II 14*, pages 766–782. Springer, 2016.

-
- [159] John O Woods and John A Christian. Lidar-based relative navigation with respect to non-cooperative objects. *Acta Astronautica*, 126:298–311, 2016.
- [160] Nathan Brightman, Lei Fan, and Yang Zhao. Point cloud registration: A mini-review of current state, challenging issues and future directions. *AIMS Geosci*, 9:68–85, 2023.
- [161] Sumant Sharma, Jacopo Ventura, and Simone D’Amico. Robust model-based monocular pose initialization for noncooperative spacecraft rendezvous. *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, 55(6):1414–1429, 2018.
- [162] Vincenzo Capuano, Shahrouz Ryan Alimo, Andrew Q Ho, and Soon-Jo Chung. Robust features extraction for on-board monocular-based spacecraft pose acquisition. In *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum*, page 2005, 2019.
- [163] Liang Hu, Dianqi Sun, Huixian Duan, An Shu, Shanshan Zhou, and Haodong Pei. Non-Cooperative Spacecraft Pose Measurement with Binocular Camera and TOF Camera Collaboration. *Applied Sciences*, 13(3):1420, 2023.
- [164] Leo Pauly, Wassim Rharbaoui, Carl Shneider, Arunkumar Rathinam, Vincent Gaudillière, and Djamila Aouada. A survey on deep learning-based monocular spacecraft pose estimation: Current state, limitations and prospects. *Acta Astronautica*, 2023.
- [165] Bo Chen, Jiewei Cao, Alvaro Parra, and Tat-Jun Chin. Satellite pose estimation with deep landmark regression and nonlinear pose refinement. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops*, pages 0–0, 2019.
- [166] Sumant Sharma and Simone D’Amico. Pose estimation for non-cooperative rendezvous using neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.09868*, 2019.
- [167] Kiruki Cosmas and Asami Kenichi. Utilization of FPGA for onboard inference of landmark localization in CNN-Based spacecraft pose estimation. *Aerospace*, 7(11):159, 2020.
- [168] Kevin Black, Shrivu Shankar, Daniel Fonseka, Jacob Deutsch, Abhimanyu Dhir, and Maruthi R Akella. Real-time, flight-ready, non-cooperative spacecraft pose estimation using monocular imagery. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2101.09553*, 2021.
- [169] Mark Sandler, Andrew Howard, Menglong Zhu, Andrey Zhmoginov, and Liang-Chieh Chen. Mobilenetv2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 4510–4520, 2018.
- [170] Maximilian Ulmer, Maximilian Durner, Martin Sundermeyer, Manuel Stoiber, and Rudolph Triebel. 6D Object Pose Estimation from Approximate 3D Models for Orbital Robotics. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.13241*, 2023.
- [171] Lorenzo Pasqualetto Cassinis, Alessandra Menicucci, Eberhard Gill, Ingo Ahrns, and Manuel Sanchez-Gestido. On-ground validation of a CNN-based monocular pose estimation system for uncooperative spacecraft: Bridging domain shift in rendezvous scenarios. *Acta Astronautica*, 196:123–138, 2022.
-

- [172] Karl Martin Kajak, Christie Maddock, Heike Frei, and Kurt Schwenk. Domain randomisation and CNN-based keypoint-regressing pose initialisation for relative navigation with uncooperative finite-symmetric spacecraft targets using monocular camera images. *Advances in Space Research*, 2023.
- [173] Pedro F Proença and Yang Gao. Deep learning for spacecraft pose estimation from photo-realistic rendering. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 6007–6013. IEEE, 2020.
- [174] Mohamed Adel Mohamed Ali, Arunkumar Rathinam, Vincent Gaudilliere, Miguel Ortiz Del Castillo, and Djamila Aouada. CubeSat-CDT: A Cross-Domain Dataset for 6-DoF Trajectory Estimation of a Symmetric Spacecraft. In *Proceedings of the 17th European Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ECCVW 2022)*, 2022.
- [175] Tae Ha Park and Simone D’Amico. Robust multi-task learning and online refinement for spacecraft pose estimation across domain gap. *Advances in Space Research*, 2023.
- [176] Sumant Sharma and Simone D’Amico. Neural Network-Based Pose Estimation for Non-cooperative Spacecraft Rendezvous. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 56(6):4638–4658, 2020.
- [177] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 770–778, 2016.
- [178] Mingxing Tan, Ruoming Pang, and Quoc V Le. EfficientDet: Scalable and Efficient Object Detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 10781–10790, 2020.
- [179] Mingxing Tan and Quoc Le. EfficientNet: Rethinking Model Scaling for Convolutional Neural Networks. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 6105–6114. PMLR, 2019.
- [180] Odysseas Kechagias-Stamatis, Nabil Aouf, Vincent Dubanchet, and Mark A Richardson. DeepLO: Multi-projection deep LIDAR odometry for space orbital robotics rendezvous relative navigation. *Acta Astronautica*, 177:270–285, 2020.
- [181] Zakaria Chekakta, Abdelhafid Zenati, Nabil Aouf, and Olivier Dubois-Matra. Robust deep learning LiDAR-based pose estimation for autonomous space landers. *Acta Astronautica*, 201:59–74, 2022.
- [182] Enrique Aldao Pensado, Luis Miguel González de Santos, Manuel Sanjurjo-Rivo, and Higinio González Jorge. Deep Learning Based Target Pose Estimation Using LiDAR Measurements in Active Debris Removal Operations. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 2023.
- [183] Yulan Guo, Hanyun Wang, Qingyong Hu, Hao Liu, Li Liu, and Mohammed Bennamoun. Deep Learning for 3D Point Clouds: A Survey. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 43(12):4338–4364, 2020.

-
- [184] Zhirong Wu, Shuran Song, Aditya Khosla, Fisher Yu, Linguang Zhang, Xiaoou Tang, and Jianxiong Xiao. 3D ShapeNets: A Deep Representation for Volumetric Shapes. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 1912–1920, 2015.
- [185] Daniel Maturana and Sebastian Scherer. VoxNet: A 3D Convolutional Neural Network for real-time object recognition. In *2015 IEEE/RSJ international conference on intelligent robots and systems (IROS)*, pages 922–928. IEEE, 2015.
- [186] Gernot Riegler, Ali Osman Ulusoy, and Andreas Geiger. OctNet: Learning Deep 3D Representations at High Resolutions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 3577–3586, 2017.
- [187] Roman Klokov and Victor Lempitsky. Escape from Cells: Deep Kd-Networks for the Recognition of 3D Point Cloud Models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pages 863–872, 2017.
- [188] Benjamin Graham, Martin Engelcke, and Laurens Van Der Maaten. 3D Semantic Segmentation with Submanifold Sparse Convolutional Networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 9224–9232, 2018.
- [189] Christopher Choy, JunYoung Gwak, and Silvio Savarese. 4D Spatio-Temporal ConvNets: Minkowski Convolutional Neural Networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 3075–3084, 2019.
- [190] Charles R Qi, Hao Su, Kaichun Mo, and Leonidas J Guibas. Pointnet: Deep learning on point sets for 3d classification and segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 652–660, 2017.
- [191] Charles Ruizhongtai Qi, Li Yi, Hao Su, and Leonidas J Guibas. Pointnet++: Deep hierarchical feature learning on point sets in a metric space. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30, 2017.
- [192] Yue Wang, Yongbin Sun, Ziwei Liu, Sanjay E Sarma, Michael M Bronstein, and Justin M Solomon. Dynamic graph cnn for learning on point clouds. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (tog)*, 38(5):1–12, 2019.
- [193] Yangyan Li, Rui Bu, Mingchao Sun, Wei Wu, Xinhan Di, and Baoquan Chen. PointCNN: Convolution On X-Transformed Points. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 31, 2018.
- [194] Hugues Thomas, Charles R Qi, Jean-Emmanuel Deschaud, Beatriz Marcotegui, François Goulette, and Leonidas J Guibas. KPConv: Flexible and Deformable Convolution for Point Clouds. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, pages 6411–6420, 2019.
- [195] Hengshuang Zhao, Li Jiang, Jiaya Jia, Philip HS Torr, and Vladlen Koltun. Point Transformer. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, pages 16259–16268, 2021.

- [196] Yasuhiro Aoki, Hunter Goforth, Rangaprasad Arun Srivatsan, and Simon Lucey. Pointnetlk: Robust & efficient point cloud registration using pointnet. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 7163–7172, 2019.
- [197] Bruce D Lucas and Takeo Kanade. An iterative image registration technique with an application to stereo vision. In *IJCAI'81: 7th international joint conference on Artificial intelligence*, volume 2, pages 674–679, 1981.
- [198] Yue Wang and Justin M Solomon. Deep closest point: Learning representations for point cloud registration. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, pages 3523–3532, 2019.
- [199] Shaodong Zhang, Weiduo Hu, and Wulong Guo. 6-DoF Pose Estimation of Uncooperative Space Object Using Deep Learning with Point Cloud. In *2022 IEEE Aerospace Conference (AERO)*, pages 1–7. IEEE, 2022.
- [200] Shaodong Zhang, Weiduo Hu, Wulong Guo, and Chang Liu. Neural-Network-Based Pose Estimation During Noncooperative Spacecraft Rendezvous Using Point Cloud. *Journal of Aerospace Information Systems*, 20(8):462–472, 2023.
- [201] Armin Hornung, Kai M Wurm, Maren Bennewitz, Cyrill Stachniss, and Wolfram Burgard. OctoMap: An efficient probabilistic 3D mapping framework based on octrees. *Autonomous robots*, 34:189–206, 2013.
- [202] Jon Louis Bentley. Multidimensional binary search trees used for associative searching. *Communications of the ACM*, 18(9):509–517, 1975.
- [203] Hang Su, Subhransu Maji, Evangelos Kalogerakis, and Erik Learned-Miller. Multi-view Convolutional Neural Networks for 3D Shape Recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pages 945–953, 2015.
- [204] David J Olive. Prediction and statistical learning. Unpublished notes available at <http://parker.ad.siu.edu/0live/slrn.pdf>, 2023.
- [205] Evan G Hemingway and Oliver M O'Reilly. Perspectives on Euler angle singularities, gimbal lock, and the orthogonality of applied forces and applied moments. *Multibody system dynamics*, 44:31–56, 2018.
- [206] Christoph Hertzberg, René Wagner, Udo Frese, and Lutz Schröder. Integrating generic sensor fusion algorithms with sound state representations through encapsulation of manifolds. *Information Fusion*, 14(1):57–77, 2013.
- [207] Joan Sola, Jeremie Deray, and Dinesh Atchuthan. A micro lie theory for state estimation in robotics. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.01537*, 2018.
- [208] Alexander A Kirillov. *An introduction to Lie groups and Lie algebras*, volume 113. Cambridge University Press, 2008.
- [209] Ethan Eade. Derivative of the exponential map. *Tech. Rep.*, 2018.

- [210] Heike Benninghoff, Florian Rems, Eicke-Alexander Risse, and Christian Mietner. European Proximity Operations Simulator 2.0 (EPOS) - A Robotic-Based Rendezvous and Docking Simulator. *Journal of large-scale research facilities JLSRF*, 2017.
- [211] Florian Rems, Heike Frei, Eicke-Alexander Risse, and Matthias Burri. 10-Year Anniversary of the European Proximity Operations Simulator 2.0—Looking Back at Test Campaigns, Rendezvous Research and Facility Improvements. *Aerospace*, 8(9):235, 2021.
- [212] Livox. Mid-40 specs. <https://www.livoxtech.com/mid-40-and-mid-100/specs>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [213] Ksenia Klionovska, Heike Benninghoff, and Klaus H Strobl. PMD Camera- and Hand-Eye-Calibration for On-Orbit Servicing Test Scenarios on the Ground. In *14th Symposium on Advanced Space Technologies in Robotics and Automation (ASTRA)*. ESA, 2017.
- [214] Rene Bergelt, Owes Khan, and Wolfram Hardt. Improving the Intrinsic Calibration of a Velodyne LiDAR Sensor. In *2017 IEEE SENSORS*, pages 1–3. IEEE, 2017.
- [215] CL Glennie and PJ Hartzell. Accuracy assessment and calibration of low-cost autonomous lidar sensors. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 43:371–376, 2020.
- [216] Ryan G Brazeal, Benjamin E Wilkinson, and Hartwig H Hochmair. A Rigorous Observation Model for the Risley Prism-Based Livox Mid-40 Lidar Sensor. *Sensors*, 21(14):4722, 2021.
- [217] Vincent Fremont, Philippe Bonnifait, et al. Extrinsic Calibration between a Multi-Layer Lidar and a Camera. In *2008 IEEE International Conference on Multisensor Fusion and Integration for Intelligent Systems*, pages 214–219. IEEE, 2008.
- [218] Ankit Dhall, Kunal Chelani, Vishnu Radhakrishnan, and K Madhava Krishna. LiDAR-Camera Calibration using 3D-3D Point correspondences. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.09785*, 2017.
- [219] Guohang Yan, Feiyu He, Chunlei Shi, Pengjin Wei, Xinyu Cai, and Yikang Li. Joint Camera Intrinsic and LiDAR-Camera Extrinsic Calibration. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 11446–11452. IEEE, 2023.
- [220] Michael Greenspan, Guy Godin, and Jimmy Talbot. Acceleration of binning nearest neighbor methods. *Proceedings of Vision Interface 2000*, pages 337–344, 2000.
- [221] Svenja Sommer, Jens Rosebrock, Delphine Cerutti-Maori, and Ludgar Leushacke. Temporal analysis of ENVISAT’s rotational motion. In *Proceedings of the 7th European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany*, pages 18–21, 2017.
- [222] Alan D George and Christopher M Wilson. Onboard Processing With Hybrid and Reconfigurable Computing on Small Satellites. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 106(3):458–470, 2018.

- [223] Daniel Lüdtkke, Thomas Firchau, Carlos Gonzalez Cortes, Andreas Lund, Ayush Mani Nepal, Mahmoud M Elbarrawy, Zain Haj Hammadeh, Jan-Gerd Meß, Patrick Kenny, Fiona Brömer, et al. ScOSA on the Way to Orbit: Reconfigurable High-Performance Computing for Spacecraft. In *2023 IEEE Space Computing Conference (SCC)*, pages 34–44. IEEE, 2023.
- [224] George William Hill. Researches in the lunar theory. *American journal of Mathematics*, 1(1):5–26, 1878.
- [225] J Tschauner and P Hempel. Rendezvous zu einem in elliptischer bahn umlaufenden ziel. *Astronautica Acta*, 11(2):104–+, 1965.
- [226] WH Clohessy and RS Wiltshire. Terminal guidance system for satellite rendezvous. *Journal of the aerospace sciences*, 27(9):653–658, 1960.
- [227] Son-Goo Kim, John L Crassidis, Yang Cheng, Adam M Fosbury, and John L Junkins. Kalman filtering for relative spacecraft attitude and position estimation. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 30(1):133–143, 2007.
- [228] S Mikael Persson and Inna Sharf. Invariant Trapezoidal Kalman Filter for Application to Attitude Estimation. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 36(3):721–733, 2013.
- [229] Lijun Zhang, Huabo Yang, Shifeng Zhang, Hong Cai, and Shan Qian. Kalman filtering for relative spacecraft attitude and position estimation: a revisit. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 37(5):1706–1711, 2014.
- [230] Shay Segal and Pini Gurfil. Effect of Kinematic Rotation-Translation Coupling on Relative Spacecraft Translational Dynamics. *Journal of Guidance, Control, and Dynamics*, 32(3):1045–1050, 2009.
- [231] Liang Sun and Wei Huo. Robust adaptive relative position tracking and attitude synchronization for spacecraft rendezvous. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 41:28–35, 2015.
- [232] Vincenzo Pesce, Michèle Lavagna, and Riccardo Bevilacqua. Stereovision-based pose and inertia estimation of unknown and uncooperative space objects. *Advances in Space Research*, 59(1):236–251, 2017.
- [233] Gabriella Gaias and Marco Lovera. Extended kalman filters for close-range navigation to noncooperative targets. *Advances in Space Research*, 73(11):5521–5544, 2024.
- [234] Brian D. O. Anderson and John B. Moore. *Optimal Filtering*, page 49. Prentice-Hall Information and System Sciences Series. Prentice-Hall, 1979.
- [235] Eric A Wan and Rudolph Van Der Merwe. The unscented Kalman filter for nonlinear estimation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE 2000 adaptive systems for signal processing, communications, and control symposium (Cat. No. 00EX373)*, pages 153–158. IEEE, 2000.
- [236] Bradley M Bell and Frederick W Cathey. The iterated Kalman filter update as a Gauss-Newton method. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 38(2):294–297, 1993.

- [237] Ulrich Hillenbrand and Roberto Lampariello. Motion and parameter estimation of a free-floating space object from range data for motion prediction. In *Proceedings of i-SAIRAS*, 2005.
- [238] Alessia Nocerino, Roberto Opromolla, Giancarmine Fasano, Michele Grassi, Pol Fontdegloria Balaguer, Spencer John, Hancheol Cho, and Riccardo Bevilacqua. Experimental validation of inertia parameters and attitude estimation of uncooperative space targets using solid state LIDAR. *Acta Astronautica*, 210:428–436, 2023.
- [239] Alexey Dosovitskiy, German Ros, Felipe Codevilla, Antonio Lopez, and Vladlen Koltun. CARLA: An Open Urban Driving Simulator. In *Conference on robot learning*, pages 1–16. PMLR, 2017.
- [240] Shital Shah, Debadeepta Dey, Chris Lovett, and Ashish Kapoor. Airsim: High-fidelity visual and physical simulation for autonomous vehicles. In *Field and Service Robotics: Results of the 11th International Conference*, pages 621–635. Springer, 2018.
- [241] Open Source Robotics Foundation. Gazebo documentation. <https://gazebo.org/docs/latest/getstarted/>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [242] Michael Gschwandtner, Roland Kwitt, Andreas Uhl, and Wolfgang Pree. BlenSor: Blender sensor simulation toolbox. In *Advances in Visual Computing: 7th International Symposium, ISVC 2011, Las Vegas, NV, USA, September 26-28, 2011. Proceedings, Part II 7*, pages 199–208. Springer, 2011.
- [243] John O Woods and John A Christian. Glidar: An OpenGL-based, Real-Time, and Open Source 3D Sensor Simulator for Testing Computer Vision Algorithms. *Journal of Imaging*, 2(1):5, 2016.
- [244] Amy Williams, Steve Barrus, R Keith Morley, and Peter Shirley. An efficient and robust ray-box intersection algorithm. In *Proc. ACM SIGGRAPH 2005 Courses*, volume 10, page 55–60, 2005.
- [245] Tomas Möller and Ben Trumbore. Fast, Minimum Storage Ray/Triangle Intersection. In *Proc. ACM SIGGRAPH 2005 Courses*, volume 2, pages 21–28, 2005.
- [246] Boris Jutzi and H Gross. Normalization of LiDAR intensity data based on range and surface incidence angle. *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spat. Inf. Sci.*, 38:213–218, 2009.
- [247] Lukas Winiwarter, Alberto Manuel Esmorís Pena, Hannah Weiser, Katharina Anders, Jorge Martínez Sánchez, Mark Searle, and Bernhard Höfle. Virtual laser scanning with helios++: A novel take on ray tracing-based simulation of topographic full-waveform 3d laser scanning. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 269:112772, 2022.
- [248] Bui Tuong Phong. Illumination for computer generated pictures. *Communications of the ACM*, 18(6):311–317, 1975.

- [249] Yu Nakajima, Takahiro Sasaki, Naoki Okada, and Toru Yamamoto. Development of LiDAR Measurement Simulator Considering Target Surface Reflection. In *Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany*, pages 20–23, 2021.
- [250] Yi Zhou, Connelly Barnes, Jingwan Lu, Jimei Yang, and Hao Li. On the Continuity of Rotation Representations in Neural Networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 5745–5753, 2019.
- [251] Giorgia Pitteri, Michaël Ramamonjisoa, Slobodan Ilic, and Vincent Lepetit. On Object Symmetries and 6D Pose Estimation from Images. In *2019 International conference on 3D vision (3DV)*, pages 614–622. IEEE, 2019.
- [252] Kurt Hornik, Maxwell Stinchcombe, and Halbert White. Multilayer feedforward networks are universal approximators. *Neural networks*, 2(5):359–366, 1989.
- [253] Tomas Hodan, Daniel Barath, and Jiri Matas. EPOS: Estimating 6D Pose of Objects With Symmetries. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 11703–11712, 2020.
- [254] Sam TS Wong and Mark S Roos. A strategy for sampling on a sphere applied to 3D selective RF pulse design. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, 32(6):778–784, 1994.
- [255] Maher Moakher. Means and Averaging in the Group of Rotations. *SIAM journal on matrix analysis and applications*, 24(1):1–16, 2002.
- [256] Zewen Li, Fan Liu, Wenjie Yang, Shouheng Peng, and Jun Zhou. A Survey of Convolutional Neural Networks: Analysis, Applications, and Prospects. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, 33(12):6999–7019, 2021.
- [257] Steven Euijong Whang, Yuji Roh, Hwanjun Song, and Jae-Gil Lee. Data collection and quality challenges in deep learning: A data-centric AI perspective. *The VLDB Journal*, 32(4):791–813, 2023.
- [258] Tensorflow library. <https://www.tensorflow.org/>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [259] Andrew Howard, Mark Sandler, Grace Chu, Liang-Chieh Chen, Bo Chen, Mingxing Tan, Weijun Wang, Yukun Zhu, Ruoming Pang, Vijay Vasudevan, et al. Searching for MobileNetV3. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, pages 1314–1324, 2019.
- [260] François Chollet. Xception: Deep learning with depthwise separable convolutions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 1251–1258, 2017.
- [261] Jie Hu, Li Shen, and Gang Sun. Squeeze-and-Excitation Networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 7132–7141, 2018.
- [262] Mingxing Tan and Quoc Le. EfficientNetV2: Smaller Models and Faster Training. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 10096–10106. PMLR, 2021.

-
- [263] Chigozie Enyinna Nwankpa, Winifred Ijomah, Anthony Gachagan, and Stephen Marshall. Activation Functions: Comparison of Trends in Practice and Research for Deep Learning. In *2nd International Conference on Computational Sciences and Technology*, 2021.
- [264] Jia Deng, Wei Dong, Richard Socher, Li-Jia Li, Kai Li, and Li Fei-Fei. ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database. In *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 248–255. IEEE, 2009.
- [265] François Chollet. Transfer learning & fine-tuning. https://keras.io/guides/transfer_learning/. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].
- [266] Diederik Kingma and Jimmy Ba. Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2015.
- [267] Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey E Hinton. ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 25, 2012.
- [268] Meng Han, Liang Wang, Limin Xiao, Hao Zhang, Chenhao Zhang, Xiangrong Xu, and Jianfeng Zhu. QuickFPS: Architecture and Algorithm Co-Design for Farthest Point Sampling in Large-Scale Point Clouds. *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, 42(11):4011–4024, 2023.
- [269] Charles Qi. PointNet++ GitHub repository. <https://github.com/charlesq34/pointnet2>. [last accessed: 16th March 2025].

Proclamation

I hereby confirm that I wrote this dissertation independently and that I have not made use of any other resources or means than those indicated.

Munich, April 2025

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